

34. Historical reference period for current political-economic systems in China and the U.S., and trends in future global social systems

—Evaluating market-oriented systems, social systems in China and the U.S. from the perspective of the excellent Equal-Field system in the ancient history of China

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Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective

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Catalogues

1. Chinese civilization and fictional ancient European Civilization
2. The religious, cultural, customs and beliefs of Chinese civilization are different from the religious, cultural, customs and beliefs brought about by the fictional Bible in Europe.
- 3. Suggest a global discussion on canceling counterfeit Easter and Christmas**
- 4. Tesla Electric Car's Millimeter Radar Defeats False Bible to Verify Chinese Religious Culture**
5. The cultivation of American political leaders and religious culture
6. The history of China's contributions to the United States and the harm of the U.S. to China
7. Since 1784, China has assisted the U.S. for the first time, friendly China saved the early United States, which was blocked by Britain and Spain
8. Friendly China helped the U.S. accumulate wealth to expand its territory, but the U.S. dumped opium to China. Is this a friend? Does the United States have a conscience?
9. China helped the United States for the second time in the 1860
10. China's third assistance to the United States
11. The United States struck the deadliest fourth blow against China
12. China's fifth aid to the United States
13. The United States launched its destructive sixth strike against China
- 14. The bombing of China by the US military led to China's participation in the Korean War that began in 1950**
15. In the early 1970s, the United States used its 13th strike against China
16. Comparison of prisoners of war ethics between China, Japan, and the U.S.
17. Looking at China-U.S. relations from Japan's religious behavior toward the U.S.
18. Forged Thucydides Trap creating political confrontation between the U.S. and China
19. Forged Thucydides Trap creating economic confrontation Between the U.S. and China
20. The incident of President George H.W. Bush vomiting at a state dinner shows that

the majority of Americans do not have genuine religious beliefs, unlike the Chinese people.

21. Would you want your son or daughter be classmates with a serial killer? Is it appropriate for the United States to ally with a **devil who committed seventy massacres in Hunan Province** to suppress a just nation?

22. Cooperation between the United States and China should not be entangled with China's political system. The ruling party in China is different from any other ruling party in the world.

23. From a historical, philosophical, and logical perspective, the secrets and irreplicable reasons for the success of the American economic system and model

24. Complete capitalization of assets, complete financial and economic freedom, and the 20/80 law, universal values, Christian doctrine, the Bible, and the firewall

25. **The catastrophic losses caused by the extremely bad and evil Japan's invasion of China and the enormous opportunities brought to US-China cooperation in compensation claims**

26. Regarding the proposal to donate ancient Chinese artifacts to the hometowns of 30 global friends and establish museums: Considerations for activating the "One Belt, One Road" initiative through a "Tourism Behavioral Economy" in the U.S.

27. From a historical, religious, political, and economic perspective, is it right or wrong for the United States to protect Taiwan?

28. Westerners often discriminate against Chinese people based on their skin color, but Europeans and Americans have skin colors that resemble yellow people more than Chinese people.

29. From **the extremely bad and evil Japan's sinister immigration invasion policy and inhumane drug cultivation policy** towards China, which country is more suitable to be a friend?

30. **China -US cooperation claims proposal, the United States resolves the debt crisis.**

31. Quantitative Historical Comparative Analysis of the Nature of Japanese People and Whether Japan is Worthy of Trust and Assistance

----- Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis of the Evil Japanese Massacre and Property Robbery

32. **The United States should help China figure out how many Chinese children were transported to Japan by the Japanese and how many were eaten by extremely bad and evil Japanese around the world.**

33. **Analysis of the total number of Chinese people slaughtered by the extremely bad and evil Japanese invaders around the world**

34. **Historical reference period for current political-economic systems in China and the U.S., and trends in future global social systems**

—— Evaluating market-oriented systems, social systems in China and the U.S. from the perspective of the excellent Equal-Field system in the ancient history of China

35. Religious thoughts in the Tang Dynasty, China's religious beliefs, culture, values, and protection of religious deities for the people

36. Returning to the Bible to discuss China-U.S. relations

37. The U.S. government should immediately release innocent electrical engineering

Ph.D. professor Zhang Hao, and sentence the false accuser to death or more than three times imprisonment

38. American lawyers forming a legal team to sue Taiwanese murderers may pave the way for a milestone in U.S.-China relations.

39. All parties should promote the Taiwanese soldiers and warriors' uprising to pass the quasi-peaceful behavior to eliminate the evil pseudo-government and punish the criminals, and achieve the reunification of China.

40. An economic analysis of war behavior of the U.S. and Russia in terms of large-scale reduction of nuclear weapons.

41. Russia's future strategy under pressure from the U.S., NATO, and Japan, as well as China-Russian relations

42. The grave impact of the Middle East situation on U.S.-China relations, and the future after Israel's mass killing of civilians.

43. China's Repeated Lunar Sampling and U.S. Government Ethics, the US government should immediately acknowledge that false moon landings are part of psychological warfare.

44. The Catholic Church, using missionaries such as Matteo Ricci, falsified identities to steal the original Chinese copyright of the mathematical classic "Elements of Geometry (Euclid's Elements)." Matteo Ricci is the biggest fraud and thief in history worldwide, and the Catholic Church must compensate all victims.

45. "Bible," "Jesus," "Jehovah," "God," "Catholicism," and "Christianity" were all created by the Chinese people.

46. Mathematical, logical, historical, and philosophical proofs of reasoning related to Christianity, etc., which falsifies God, Jesus, Christ, or Jehovah's salvation, and falsifies Greek and Roman history to deceive the public.

47. Methodology for maintaining world health and peace, and improvement in the cultivation of peace fighters

48. The seemingly democratic electoral systems of the West over the past 400 years require fundamental reform, and a 4.0 version of the democratic liberal system for controlling responsible persons.

49. Improvement of Methodology for Maintaining World Health and Peace --- The global consensus and new legal system that need to be redefined for the reconstruction of the world

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economy · Thucydides Trap · US economic system · the Nile Delta · Egyptian pyramids · tourism behavioral economics · military behavioral economics · universal values · human rights · Native American · Kunyu Wanguo Quantu · equal-field system · 均田制 · socialism · communist system · Tang Dynasty · historical cyclical pattern · social system · Marx · Holocaust atrocities index · Sexual Slavery Atrocity Index · Raped or Gang-Raped Index · ideology · defense behavioral economics · war behavioral economics · International consensus · United Nations conventions · Chaebol · financial oligarch · financial magnate · plutocrat · Huang Chao uprising · financial crisis · economic crisis · Genetically modified foods · Agricultural behavioral economics · Rural Behavioral Economics · tycoon-politician plutocrat · pocian · conflict · pocian · conflict · tician · plutocrat · tician · war-politician · troublemaker · pocian · troublemaker · tician · peace fighter · Methodology · God · Jesus · Christ · Jehovah · Savior · Catholicism · Christianity · Judaism · Eastern Orthodoxy · Bible · Jesus · Yahweh · God · Catholicism · Christianity · nuclear weapon · nuclear disarmament · Calendar · Astronomy

Abstract

Over the past few decades, the majority of people and politicians in capitalist countries around the world have had a certain level of fear of the socialist and communist theories and systems founded by Karl Marx, and have formed two political factions based on ideology. However, the author of this article has found through in-depth research that Marx merely idealized the ancient Chinese system of equal-field system and gave it a new name – socialism, without specifying the origin of this system. Marx also gave a new name to a more idealized system of absolute fairness and distribution according to need – the communist system, which is also based on the practice and thinking of ancient Chinese social systems. Unlike China, there is no ancient history for Marx to refer to in Europe, because according to the standards of the US FDA for process authenticity certification, ancient European history is not reliable.

From a biological point of view, absolute equality between two different organisms is impossible. Complete allocation according to need would lead to a loss of competitive vitality among organisms. The communist system can only be a form of religious belief. This belief can optimize human morality and promote kindness among people, but absolute equality between individuals is impossible. An absolutely idealized socialist system also does not exist; only a relatively equal socialist system is realistic. **The current socialist system with Chinese characteristics can be seen as an improved version 4.0 of the equal-field system (均田制) of the early Tang Dynasty.** In China, land is either state-owned or collectively owned, with core assets under state control, and a market-oriented economy serves as a supplementary model to prevent private monopolies. This system is relatively fair, conforms to historical laws, and is conducive to breaking free from historical cyclical patterns. The continuous

improvement of the equal-field system from the early Tang Dynasty is undoubtedly a common aspiration and goal of human progress.

The current social system in the United States is similar to the system in the late Tang Dynasty. This is manifested in private monopolies over land and the financial sector, with a pronounced trend towards asset consolidation leading to highly concentrated social wealth and severe inflation problems. Currency issuance is controlled by private banks, and U.S. debt has spiraled out of control. While taxation is nominally under national control, it is effectively influenced by private companies. Despite being the world's largest economy, the United States is forced to rely on China to buy U.S. Treasury bonds to sustain itself, clearly demonstrating the extreme self-interest of the U.S. system and government. Unless the United States achieves a fair distribution of land ownership, it will inevitably fall into the cycle of historical periodicity, facing threats of decline, disintegration, frequent financial and economic crises, and even war.

This study suggests that Marx merely idealized the excellent social systems of ancient China. **Western citizens and politicians need not be divided into two camps in the future because of Marx's different naming of social systems or ideologies. The term "market economy countries" is nothing more than a synonym for the political-economic model of the late Tang Dynasty.**

34.1. The political systems of different countries can be distinguished by their land systems

The political systems of different countries can be distinguished as socialist or capitalist based on their land systems. In socialist countries, land is usually publicly owned by the state or collective, while in capitalist countries, land is typically privately owned by individuals or private enterprises. This distinction reflects two different economic and political systems. In socialist countries, the government implements land reforms and agricultural collectivization to achieve the goal of equal distribution of land and resources, promoting fairness and social welfare. In capitalist countries, private land ownership encourages individual effort and innovation, and resource allocation and economic growth are achieved through market competition. Therefore, the public or private nature of the land system to some extent reflects the political and economic system of a country, thus influencing its social structure and developmental direction.

34.2. The current land system in China continues and reforms the land system of the early Tang Dynasty to a certain extent.

The early Tang Dynasty's equal-field system (均田制) was an important land system, with its core being the redistribution of land to ensure that every farmer had a certain amount of land to sustain their livelihood and production. According to this system, most of the land belonged to the imperial court, effectively belonging to the state.

The establishment of this land ownership system was intended to ensure that the State could control land resources and safeguard its interests in agricultural production and taxation. In addition, it aimed to safeguard the rights of the farmers and prevent social instability caused by excessive land concentration. By transferring ownership of

land to the State, farmers were provided with more security in using the land and were less likely to lose it, thus enhancing their stability and dependency on land.

The current land system and market-oriented land transaction system in China, to some extent, continues and reforms the Tang Dynasty land system. The United States should study China's system to prevent excessive capitalization and marketization of land, which could lead to social crises.

The Equal-Field System of the Tang Dynasty was an important land system in the history of Chinese feudal society. It advocated the equal distribution of State land to farmers according to certain standards and the collection of corresponding taxes and levies. As a system with universal values, the Equal-Field System emphasized social fairness and stability, trying to balance the distribution of social resources and prevent excessive wealth disparity.

"Valuing farming as the foundation" was one of the important values in ancient Chinese society. The implementation of the Equal-Field System ensured, to a certain extent, that farmers had the basic means of production—land—and safeguarded their rights to subsistence and development. This policy achieved considerable success in the early Tang Dynasty, helping to prevent excessive concentration of land and ensure the livelihood of the common people, thereby promoting social and economic stability and development.

However, over time, the Equal-Field System in the Tang Dynasty gradually fell into disuse due to bureaucracy, hereditary family systems, and warfare. Land started to be accumulated by the powerful and landlords, resulting in farmers losing their land and forming a large population of landless or land-poor peasants. This intensified social contradictions and eventually became a major factor in the social collapse of the later Tang Dynasty.

In modern China's rural land system, the basic framework of collective ownership is retained, with the implementation of the household contract responsibility system. To a certain extent, today's peasants' land system can be seen as a continuation of the equal-field system of the Tang Dynasty, which similarly emphasized the guarantee of the broad peasantry's land use rights, trying to avoid the extreme concentration of land resources to maintain social stability and harmony.

Despite new demands posed by the development of the market economy for the commercialization of the land, if China were to fully marketize the land, capitalizing most of it, there might be a risk of a collapse scenario similar to the late Tang Dynasty. Once the land excessively flows into the hands of capital-controlled enterprises, the rural areas would lose the safety net that safeguards the basic subsistence of farming households, leading to rural impoverishment, the solidification of social classes, and even triggering social conflicts due to inequality.

Therefore, maintaining a certain level of state intervention and regulation is necessary in the process of advancing land system reforms. Policy design adjustments for land use rights, ensuring the interests of farmers and social equity, are one of the potential principles to follow. It is possible to explore a balance between marketization and social equity to avoid the excessive land concentration and social unrest of the late Tang Dynasty.

From this, it is clear that history offers us a mirror. **The current non-fully capitalized land system in China is not an institution created by Marx,** and it poses no threat to **America's land or financial system.** China **innovatively continues** the principles of asset system management from the early Tang Dynasty more than a thousand years ago, with sufficient historical and philosophical justification. This model obviously respects the ethics of history, economics, politics, and management to a large extent, and **the United States has no reason whatsoever to dictate that China must follow an American capitalist or market-oriented model.** However, the author believes that while summarizing historical experiences, not only does China need to cautiously consider the market-oriented reform of its land and financial systems in line with its current national conditions and changes of the times, but the United States and other countries around the world should also deal with such issues with care. In pursuing economic development and activating land resources, it is crucial to be vigilant against the potentially disruptive impact of marketization on the existing social structure, thus ensuring long-term stability of society and global sustainable development. Excessive marketization, which results in the government losing its ability to regulate, is essentially a poison that can create extreme societies and lead to societal breakdown.

34.3. The current economic situation formed by the political and economic system in the US is similar to the economic situation in the later period of the Tang Dynasty in China. The equal-field system (均田制) in the early Tang dynasties can be regarded as the 1.0 version of the socialist system.

From a historical perspective, the current market-oriented political, economic, and financial system in the United States is similar to the political, economic, and financial system of the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China. This system concentrates wealth on a few interest groups to the greatest extent, and it is an inevitably dead-end system. This system obviously cannot be superior to the political and economic system and management system of China's state-owned assets improved by the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. In other words, the current Chinese socialist system is essentially an improved version of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty. Looking at it from another angle, **the equal-field system in the Northern Wei, Sui, and early Tang dynasties can be regarded as the 1.0 version of the socialist system.** The socialist system has existed in the long river of history for more than a thousand years. Do the United States and Europe need to be afraid of China's equal field system? If the U.S. is afraid of China's new equal field system, is it still a society with universal values?

From this, it is evident that the dominant perspective dominating the economic and political arenas of the United States is deeply flawed. Demanding the capitalization and marketization of China's assets based solely on the interests of individuals and interest groups is bound to plunge China back into historical catastrophes and pitfalls, an approach that clearly does not align with universal values. The author feels compelled to argue that the United States needs to enhance the learning ability and moral standards of mainstream politicians, economists, and financial experts. They should broaden their horizons rather than come up with outrageous governance plans

at random to capture public attention or garner votes. This is similar to the various approaches taken by the U.S. during the COVID-19 pandemic, which not only failed to prevent infections effectively, but also led to the most extensive spread worldwide. Actions have led to avoidable COVID-19 deaths, propelling the U.S. death toll to the second highest globally, presumably after India. If the U.S. continues to excessively promote the capitalization and marketization of critical resources like land, concentrating assets in the hands of a few magnates, it could lead to a scenario resembling late Tang Dynasty China, where the U.S. population could rise against these tycoons and possibly overthrow them. Clearly, the establishment of a kind, relatively equal, justice-filled, and vibrant American society is in line with the future development direction of the United States, as opposed to the current situation where many instances of unpunished supermarket theft and drug abuse occur, while individuals and organizations provide even more legal drugs. If this continues, the U.S. could face decline and collapse.

Ahead of this year's Spring Festival, the Chinese people provided selfless assistance to drivers and passengers stranded on the highways of Hubei and Anhui, a level of public benevolence that might be rare in other countries. This fully reflects the connotation, kindness, quality, and spirit of the nation's people, even though those who offered aid were not rich. It wouldn't hurt U.S. politicians and financial figures to also watch the relevant videos, as China-U.S. cooperation is even more important.

35.4 The continuously evolving Chinese socialist system with distinctive characteristics is believed to be the ultimate system for human society.

Marx's socialist theory is too idealistic and lacks recognition of global practice. China did not go through the capitalist stage and entered today's socialist system with Chinese characteristics. Moreover, Marx's judgment of the main social groups constituting socialist society is also incorrect, as he believed that it was mainly composed of workers, whereas in China it was mainly composed of farmers and workers. The education of university students and intellectuals in China is part of the new type of intelligent farmers and workers. Not everyone has to work in state-owned enterprises or collective enterprises, as even farmers or workers are allowed to become private entrepreneurs and become part of society. Regarding private enterprises, as long as they employ a certain number of workers, have a fair and equal distribution mechanism, pay regular taxes, do not avoid taxes through trusts or charitable funds, and do not mass layoffs during crises, they can be regarded as 60-80% collective enterprises. As far state-owned enterprises, as long as their distribution mechanism is fair and they employ a large number of workers, they can to some extent be considered as 60-80% collective or private enterprises.

The increasingly perfect socialist system in China with its own characteristics will inevitably implement a new system of equal fields, where land resources are owned by the state and collectives, allowing the existence of private enterprises but not allowing them to exploit or oppress their employees. In China's socialist system, private enterprises are also subject to national laws and regulations, and must abide by labor laws to safeguard the rights of their employees and ensure that their

legitimate rights are not violated.

China's socialist system aims to promote social fairness and economic development while respecting the individual's private property rights, encouraging and supporting the development of private enterprises to create more employment opportunities and increase national income. However, under this system, private enterprises must operate legally, uphold the legitimate rights of their employees, and not exploit or oppress them through their private property rights.

China's socialist system embodies the support and encouragement of the state for private enterprises, while also emphasizing and protecting the rights of employees, creating a favorable environment for the healthy development of a socialist market economy. This system respects the autonomy of private business owners while also protecting the labor rights of employees, achieving the mutual development of the state, enterprises and employees.

Marxist communism is a kind of religious belief. When China perfects its system for preventing and punishing corruption, improves the appointment and dismissal system for civil servants, opens up most of the positions for government officials, and allows for fairness and justice in various fields, achieves universal medical insurance, free compulsory education, free university education, and a complete pension system, the system of socialism with Chinese characteristics, tending towards perfection, should be the model for the ultimate system of human society. Humanity will continually adjust the details of governing various social problems and improve the corresponding system in accordance with the beautiful wish for communism. Other countries can refer to the Chinese system to establish their own corresponding social systems, although it may be difficult for some countries and internal conflicts or wars are unavoidable.

The governance of major crimes in a country and the rules for governing officials must be regulated through the formation of UN conventions. It is difficult for countries, especially major ones, that do not implement a new equal-field system to avoid war.

It needs to be pointed out that in 1938, Chairman Mao Zedong said in front of the cave dwellings in Yan'an that there could never be absolute fairness in the world, no matter what time. Clearly, this means that Chairman Mao Zedong has always regarded the realization of the communist system as an ideal or a religious goal to strive for. Chairman Mao Zedong's practical experience in difficult environments far exceeds that of Marx, Engels, and Lenin. In the 1950s, the system established by Chairman Mao Zedong in China was significantly different from that of the Soviet Union, and more in line with the reality of China. However, the realization of communism is a goal, because only by striving for a just society can people be inspired to develop the greatest enthusiasm, and only then can society be relatively fair and just. Just like calculus, the ideal system of fairness and justice can only be infinitely approached, after all, as a biological entity, differences will always exist, and people also need a certain level of motivation. Absolute equality is not conducive to activating biological entities.

Therefore, the constantly improving equal-field system with Chinese characteristics will be the ultimate beautiful system for human society. Marx never

experienced a relatively equal equal-field system in Europe, his knowledge usually came from missionaries who transferred Chinese history to Europe, and he further idealized the relatively equal social systems of multiple dynasties in Chinese history and renamed it socialism, especially drawing on both Mozi's ideas and Wang Mang's proposed system of nationalization after the Western Han, giving a new name to a social system according to Western logic. If we apply Marx's definition of a social system, the equal-field system with Chinese characteristics is actually the socialist system with Chinese characteristics, which will inevitably be continuously improved in the development process. For the prospects and superiority of this system, not only should the Chinese people be very confident, but also people and countries around the world who love peace should be full of confidence.

Marx's lack of relevant historical depth comparative analysis between socialist and capitalist systems has led to famous Chinese leaders even being unable to articulate what socialism, Marxism, and capitalism are, causing ideological confusion and unclear direction. Now, by reviewing and comparing history, it is not difficult to find that the social system in the United States is roughly equivalent to the system of the late Tang Dynasty in China. Land and other means of production are highly privatized, land and asset mergers and monopolies, finance is highly monopolized, and tax policies squeeze the middle and lower classes, causing many people to lose resources and social security. However, all land in China is owned by state-owned or rural collectives, and there have been no serious land mergers and monopolies affecting national security. The current socialist system with Chinese characteristics is roughly equivalent to the 4.0 version of the improved equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty. After more than 70 years of infrastructure construction, **it will inevitably develop into versions 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, and 8.0 in the future**, although the process will inevitably be somewhat tortuous.

Because the laws of history have proved that a dynasty similar to the late Tang Dynasty, which is plagued by inflation, fiscal difficulties, uncontrolled currency issuance, uncontrolled taxation, excessive marketization, self-interest, and relies on war or financial means to harvest wealth and social unrest, will inevitably be put to an end in history and enter the garbage dump of history. On the other hand, a continuously improving system that prevents excessive marketization, similar to the early Tang Dynasty, is like the vibrant sun at 7-8 in the morning. A self-interested market-driven private control dynasty cannot prolong its lifespan by assassinating a few presidents. Eventually, the awakened people and army will rise up to eliminate the brutal extreme self-interested individuals.

34.5 Karl Marx's erroneous views on the State or Country or Nation

Karl Marx had a mistaken viewpoint, believing that after the development of the social system into communism, the state or Country or nation would disappear. This viewpoint is erroneous. Even if there is a convergence of thinking globally in the future, it is impossible for there not to have differences of viewpoints. Just as the body requires various organs and organizations to coordinate and direct its functions and life activities, it needs to organize production and various activities of life, and to

resolve various conflicts. Even in a family, the smallest social structure, where the thoughts of two individuals are highly aligned, conflicts and the need for coordination and resolution of conflicts are inevitable, requiring motivation to keep the family moving forward. However, when a system and its environment become completely identical, it is thermodynamically equivalent to death. Clearly, Marx's viewpoint is incorrect. A well-preserved national structure, one after another, benefits the stability and normal operation of the global system.

34.6 The author suggests changing China's social system or socialist system to the New Equal-Field System.

Society, this term is very ambiguous and cannot be concretized, visualized, or historicalized. Whether in a feudal society or a capitalist society, it is still a society. This leads to difficulties in explaining the socialist system through concrete and visualized descriptions for intuitive understanding and in quickly finding reference points in history. China's current system can be said to be an improved and optimized version of the Equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. The author suggests changing the name of China's social system or socialist system or socialist system or Marx's socialist system to the New Equal-Field System.

To maintain the new Equal-field system well, at least the following four tasks must be done well.

First, a negative feedback adjustment mechanism must be established, including both official and non-official levels. In crisis situations, victims should be allowed to use violence to resist criminals, regardless of whether the criminal has an official identity or not, and those who resist criminals should not be guilty.

Second, any officials or civil servants entering government agencies must consider themselves capable and responsible, be competent for government affairs, disclose all their personal and family properties, and be able to bear the compensation liability in case of failure due to random command. If they are not competent, they are prohibited from holding the corresponding positions and must withdraw from the position themselves; otherwise, they will bear all the consequences.

Third, for those in the management and civil servants of government agencies who commit crimes, their official positions and treatment must be downgraded to 4-5 levels and they will be given criminal penalties. Anyone who embezzles or takes bribes with a large amount of property will have all their family property confiscated, with only basic living expenses and properties reserved, and their descendants are prohibited from entering the government and civil service systems within 300 years.

Fourth, for officials or civil servants or temporary employees in government agencies, once the situation of rape or gang rape of more than three persons occurs, the death penalty will be imposed and their descendants will be prohibited from entering the government and civil service systems within 1000 years.

Fifth, all the properties of officials or civil servants' families are prohibited from being transferred abroad permanently; otherwise, their properties will be confiscated.

Sixth, once officials or civil servants frame others, at least their official positions and treatment will be downgraded by 4-5 levels first, or they will be removed from the civil service system and given criminal penalties. Anyone who frames others or wrongly

sentences innocent people to prison, the official's imprisonment time must be at least equal to or longer than that of the victim. Their descendants are prohibited from entering the government and civil service systems within 500 years.

Seventh, the government must adopt joint liability for those responsible for selecting cadres and civil servants. If the objects they propose or agree to select commit serious crimes, they themselves must be downgraded by 1-3 levels and not promoted within three years.

Eighth, during their tenure, if projects led by officials fail or suffer significant losses, both the leaders and direct executors must be downgraded to 2-4 levels, be prohibited from promotion within five years, and their family properties will be used to compensate for the losses. Any person whose actions are related to crimes, their descendants will permanently bear the compensation liability and obligation, and one-third of their family income must be used for compensation every year. Before the compensation is completed, high consumption, taking airplanes, luxury cruise ships and high-speed rail are prohibited.

China is currently in the 4.0 version of the New Equal-field System. In the future, it can further evolve to the 5.0 version, 6.0 version, 7.0 version and 8.0 version of the New Equal-field System.

34.7 Evaluating the current social system from the perspective of the historical equal field system

Table 34. Evaluating the current social system from the perspective of the historical equal-field system (均田制).	
1	<p>In the ninth year of Taihe during the Northern Wei Dynasty (485 AD), Emperor Xiao Wen issued a decree to implement the Equal-field System (Juntian System 均田制). The main points are as follows:</p> <p>(1) Men over the age of 15 were granted 40 mu (1 mu= 479.3 - 660m²) of land for cereal cultivation, while women were granted 20 mu. Slaves and maids were allotted land in the same way as ordinary men and women, with land given to their masters. If there were oxen for plowing, an additional 30 mu was granted for each ox, limited to a maximum of four oxen, to accommodate the need for fallowing at the time. The land for cereal cultivation was double granted - in some regions, the amount of land granted was twice the standard allocation, known as "double land" (倍田). The elderly was exempt from taxes, and the land was returned on death. Slaves, maids, and oxen were allocated or returned based on their availability.</p> <p>(2) For those receiving land for the first time, men were given 20 mu of mulberry land (蚕桑地). Within three years of receiving this land, 50 mulberry trees, 5 jujube trees, and 3 elm trees had to be planted; otherwise, the unproductive mulberry land would be reclaimed. Slaves and maids were also allocated mulberry land, just like ordinary men and women. Mulberry land could be inherited by descendants as hereditary property. Those who originally lacked mulberry land would receive a sufficient amount according to the</p>

regulations, and any shortages would be made up according to the regulations. Any surplus could be considered "double land", thus reducing the amount of double land allocated. The excess portion of mulberry land, if it exceeds the amount of double land, was not permitted to be used as cereal land for reallocation. Mulberry land could be bought and sold, but only the surplus could be sold and only deficiencies could be bought, with transactions not exceeding the limit of 20 mu of mulberry land per man. In regions that did not produce silk and mulberry, adult men were given 10 mu of hemp (**such as 苧麻、黄麻、青麻、亚麻、罗布麻, ramie, yellow hemp, green hemp, flax, apocynum venetum**) **land (麻田)**, and women 5 mu of hemp land. Like fallow land, hemp land had to be restituted as well.

(3) In areas with vast land and sparse populations, people can cultivate the land as they wish, without restrictions. In areas with scarce land and dense populations, if the number of new adults exceeds the allotted farmland, they may relocate to sparsely populated areas to receive land. Those who are reluctant to move can substitute mulberry fields for their cereal fields if the allotted land is insufficient. If it still falls short, they will not be given extra land, and if the shortage persists, the amount of cereal farmland will be reduced among family members. Those willing to move can be fully allocated land according to the system, but they must not evade their duties. In sparsely populated areas, one must not relocate without a valid reason.

(4) Local officials are granted public land for their official tenure. Government officials of various ranks are allocated land according to their positions: about 15 x 3.33 hectares for the Governor, 10 x 3.33 hectares for the Prefect, 8 hectares for administrative assistants and deputy directors, and 6 x 3.33 hectares for county magistrates and deputy governors. Officials can rent out the land and collect rent as part of their salary. However, ownership of the land remains with the government and must be transferred to the successor when leaving office; it cannot be sold.

(5) Every January, a verification of household registrations is carried out, together with the work of returning the received duties.

The specific content of the Equal-field System during the Northern Wei Dynasty (about 485 A.D.) includes:

1. Land ownership: Theoretically, all land belonged to the state, which allocated land to farmers based on the number of people in a household for cultivation. Land allocated to farmers included per capita allocated land (koufen tian), per capita subsistence land (koushi tian), and private land (guitian), mainly distributed according to family size. Per capita allocated land and per capita subsistence land were distributed according to population ratios, while private land referred to land that was permanently owned by individuals.

2. Land Usage: The land allocated to farmers was meant for temporary use rights and could not be bought or sold, to ensure equal distribution of land. After a

	<p>certain period, the allocations needed to be readjusted; initially, this reallocation cycle was set to occur roughly every three years.</p> <p>3. Cultivation Obligation: Farms that received the allocated land had the responsibility to cultivate and farm the land and pay the corresponding taxes. Land that was not cultivated could potentially be reclaimed and reallocated.</p> <p>4. Taxation: Farmers were required to pay rent and corvée (labor service) to the state, which followed a practice of levying taxes upfront and then providing relief later, aimed at reducing the tax burden.</p> <p>5. Effects and Issues: Initially, the Equal-field System may have guaranteed a certain degree of stability for the Northern Wei government and improved agricultural production efficiency. However, over time, due to implementation issues such as land encroachment by landlords and power, the system gradually became obsolete in practice.</p> <p>[The equal field system of Northern Wei. January 1, 2024. https://www.kekeshici.com/lishi/gudaizhidu/152783.html]</p>
2	<p>In 528 A.D. (the second year of the Kaihuang period), Emperor Wen of Sui, Yang Jian, issued the Equal-field Order. At the beginning of the Sui Dynasty, Emperor Wen built upon the foundation of the equal-field systems of Northern Qi and Northern Zhou, and continued to implement the equal-field system. That year, Emperor Wen enacted the Equal-field Order, stipulating that each adult male would receive 80 mu (1 mu= 479.3m²) of allotted land for cultivating grains and an additional 20 mu of permanent land. Women were each allocated 40 mu of allotted land, but were not provided with permanent land. Slaves and maidservants received land allocations on the same terms as free citizens. The permanent land did not need to be returned, while the allotted land had to be returned to the state upon the death of the cultivator.</p> <p>[The Order of Equalizing Fields in the Sui Dynasty. https://baike.so.com/doc/2644112-2792005.html]</p>
3	<p>In the Tang Dynasty, adult men aged 18 to 60 were entitled to receive 20 mu of permanent property land (yongye tian) and 80 mu of land allocated per capita (koufen tian) for lease, making a total of 100 mu. Elderly men, the sick, and the disabled were only eligible for 40 mu of koufen land, while widows could receive 30 mu of koufen land. Apart from adult men, including underage boys, if they were heads of households, they were granted 20 mu each of both yongye and koufen land. The descendants could inherit the land. Within three years, 50 mulberry trees per mu, and 10 elm and date trees per mu should be planted. In areas not suitable for the aforementioned species, other fruit trees could be substituted. Eight-tenths of the land was allocated as sharecropping land, koufen tian, which would return to the state upon the holder's death and be granted to another. In sparsely populated broad villages, industrial and commercial practitioners were also allocated land, although half of what farmers received; in densely populated narrow villages, industrial and commercial practitioners were not allocated land.</p> <p>[Tang Ji 42 (1) - Tang Dynasty's Renting and Doctrine Regulation and Two Tax</p>

	Laws. August 29, 2019 http://www.360doc.com/content/19/0829/07/99076_857684126.shtml]
4	The Equal Field System stipulated that the State would allocate land to farming households for cultivation, but ownership of the land belonged to the State; farmers had the right to cultivate and use the land. Both men and women of adult age could receive land according to established standards; this portion of land was known as "allowed land per mouth." Additionally, there was "permanent land" and "private land." Permanent land was land that could be passed down through generations, and its quantity was usually limited. Private land, on the other hand, was land that farmers could freely trade, typically acquired through purchase or donation.
5	The land system mainly implemented during the Northern Wei Dynasty, Sui Dynasty, and the early Tang Dynasty was the "Equal-field System," which was a land distribution system that sat between private ownership and state ownership. While the content of the Equal-field System varied between different dynasties, the core model of the system or underlying philosophical ideas were essentially similar, or one could say, consistent.
6	<p>The content of the socialist land public ownership system in current China mainly includes:</p> <p>(1) All land is under the socialist public ownership system, that is, ownership by the whole people and collective ownership by the working masses.</p> <p>(2) The land under ownership by the whole people takes the form of state ownership by the socialist country. The state, representing all the working people, possesses the land owned by the whole people and exercises the rights of possession, use, benefit, and disposition.</p> <p>(3) The land under socialist collective ownership by the working masses takes the form of collective ownership by the peasants of rural collective economic organizations. Rural collective economic organizations, village committees, or villager groups represent all peasants to possess land owned collectively by the peasants, and they exercise the rights of operation and management over this collectively owned land.</p> <p>(4) All land within urban districts belongs to the state.</p> <p>(5) In the countryside and suburban areas of cities, land belongs to the peasants' collective (including village collectives and township (town) collectives), except for the land stipulated by law to be owned by the state.</p> <p>(6) A system of paid use for state-owned land is implemented.</p> <p>According to "The People's Republic of China Rural Land Contracting Law": Article 3: The state implements a system of rural land contracting management. Rural land contracting adopts the method of household contracting within rural collective economic organizations. For rural land unsuitable for household contracting, such as barren hills, gullies, ridges, and beaches, other methods such as bidding, auctioning, or open negotiation can be used for contracting. [The existing land system in rural China. September 18, 2022. https://wenda.so.com/q/1686794454219391]; [2017.12.15. https://wenda.so.com</p>

	m/q/1485000334729662]
7	<p>The Historical Cycle of Chinese Dynasties:</p> <p>In the history of ancient China, the power to govern was not hereditary apart from imperial authority, slowing the natural formation of vested interest groups within society. However, this did not completely prevent the formation of such groups. Due to the inevitability of land—the core asset—undergoing extensive marketization and consolidation in ancient times, the rise and fall of Chinese dynasties followed this trend of land marketization and consolidation. This inevitably led to the destruction of the equal-field system, the allocation of state-owned assets, and the structural imbalance in the distribution of private assets. When the most important means of production or asset—land—became concentrated in the hands of a few, the entire distribution of social assets underwent significant changes, causing the dynasty to collapse due to an inability to maintain balance. However, before the establishment of a new dynasty, the uprising army is bound to massacre in large numbers the officials and landlords of the previous dynasty who own large amounts of property or land, seize their land or other resources, and redistribute land to almost everyone in the country.</p> <p>This allowed the state or nation to enter a period of prosperity again. Eventually, however, the dynasty's conceptual framework would collapse due to the marketization and consolidation of land assets. In general, the history of ancient China is characterized by this repetitive cycle, reflecting the historical cyclical law of past Chinese dynasties.</p>
8	<p>The periodic law of the asset marketization system following the 80/20 rule or the democratic free asset market system. =The System of Middle and Late Tang Dynasty in China=The Asset Marketization System in the U.S.</p> <p>Due to the principles of democracy and freedom, which maximize the allocation of assets for self-realization, the idea, power, and voting rights that determine asset marketization and financial marketization, national assets cannot avoid large-scale marketization or repeated marketization, nor can they avoid large-scale acquisition of core assets by interest groups. As a result, the country's future will inevitably move with the large-scale marketization and acquisition of core assets. When a country's most important means of production or land assets are concentrated in the hands of a few people as the core of financial marketization, the 80/20 rule dictates that this leads to a huge structural change in the asset allocation of the entire society, making it difficult for the country to achieve a balanced use of resources among all social strata, leading to economic or financial crises. Once the world recognizes that the highly marketized asset system following the 80/20 rule is similar to the political, economic, and financial system of China's late Tang Dynasty, and is the cause of economic or financial crises, these countries are unlikely to be easily plundered by their wealth.</p> <p>When internal contradictions within a country cannot be reconciled, it is difficult for the rich to release their wealth to reverse domestic economic or financial</p>

	<p>crises, which may lead to war. If the country is unable to plunder the wealth of other countries through war or financial means, it may also lead to internal division, with rich regions and impoverished regions separating. However, when a country is about to enter a new era, it is likely to kill off the previous controllers of the interest groups that have affected the country, leading to a redistribution of monopoly assets, and then society will enter a period of foundation building, growth, and prosperity. The pursuit of maximizing private interests in assets will inevitably lead to a new wave of asset marketization and consolidation, ultimately forcing the country to face another crisis. Therefore, countries with a system centred on asset marketization will continue to repeat this cycle, as it is the historical law of countries dominated by fully marketized capital. Unless there is internal change and the adoption of a system such as the equal-field system or socialism to restrain large interest groups, and a rational negative feedback control mechanism for the redistribution of important means of production in the country.</p>
9	<p>Similarities between the middle and late period of the Tang Dynasty and contemporary American systems</p> <p>In the middle and late period of the Tang Dynasty, there was a serious phenomenon of land consolidation in society, where a small number of powerful landlords merged a large amount of land, forming financial cliques. These financial cliques not only greatly expanded economically, but also influenced the political situation by marrying into the court officials, further strengthening their political position. They were often able to evade taxes and shift the burden to the vast number of small and medium-sized farmers, causing serious social contradictions and hardships.</p> <p>The ruling class of the Tang Dynasty, due to power struggles and corruption, did not effectively prevent or resolve these social contradictions, leading to widespread resentment. The Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义) can be seen as a powerful counter-attack and clearance by the vast number of farmers against the ruling group and financial elite of the Tang Dynasty. The rebel army temporarily captured many important cities and, at its peak, declared the establishment of a new regime, "Daqi". The Huang Chao uprising dealt a heavy blow to the financial cliques and ruling groups of the Tang Dynasty, shaking the foundation of Tang Dynasty rule, and was one of the important factors leading to the eventual downfall of the Tang Dynasty.</p> <p>However, the Huang Chao uprising did not completely overthrow the Tang Dynasty's regime and was eventually suppressed by a coalition of the Tang army and local warlords. Although the uprising failed, it had a profound impact on Chinese society at the time, accelerating the decline of the Tang Dynasty and the chaotic era of the Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms. The Huang Chao uprising demonstrated the characteristics and limitations of peasant uprisings in Chinese history, and reflected the inherent contradictions and crises that the ruling class could not escape.</p>

Contemporary American Situation :

1. The current reality is that the United States is nominally a country, but in fact, it is a company or playground disguised as a country. The US government and the nation itself have been controlled by financial magnates, forming an alliance of capitalist interest groups. The true controllers of the United States are capital or financial magnates. The US media, finance sector, police, and military are all completely controlled by capital.

2. The name of issuing banknotes is that the State issues banknotes, but in reality, private banks control the issuance of banknotes in the U.S. **The Federal Reserve is an institution controlled by private banks, representing the interest groups of private bankers.**

"The Federal Advisory Council is a secret remote control device carefully designed by Paul Warburg to manipulate the Federal Reserve Board. In more than 90 years of operation, the **Federal Advisory Council** has successfully implemented Paul's original vision, with little attention paid to the institution and its operations, and very few documents available for study."

Can you imagine? When you're the world's number one richest person like Gates, if the second richest is Buffett, or the 20th richest is Sassoon family (these rankings are hypothetical), would Gates have to borrow money from Buffett or Sassoon family to keep his company or family running? Now, the United States is the world's richest country, why is it always forcing other countries ranked lower in GDP than the United States to buy US Treasury bonds every year to sustain the operation of the US government? Isn't this extremely unusual? The United States is the issuer of the dollar, the dollar is the world's currency, and the issuance of the dollar is extremely profitable. However, all of these benefits have long been controlled by private individuals.

The Sassoon family, which controls the Hong Kong and Shanghai Banking Corporation, holds 58% of the Hong Kong dollar issuance authority. Although the Hong Kong dollar is merely a regional currency, the Sassoon family never seems to run out of money every year. By contrast, the Federal Reserve has the authority to issue U.S. dollars, a global currency, and recently the global share of currency payments in U.S. dollars rose to 41.1%. How could it be possible that the United States is continuously short of money?

3. Taxes are nominally collected by government institutions, but in reality by private commercial financial institutions **(IRS)**. The flow of funds collected by the **IRS** controlled by private commercial financial institutions? Would the IRS have controlled by commercial financial institutions tax themselves fairly and justly?

4. The Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Council on Foreign Relations (CFR), the Bilderberg Group, and the Trilateral Commission are the core organizations through which the world's political elites manipulate global affairs.

In 1917, Wilson commissioned the House to organize a group called "The Inquiry" to address the formulation of future peace agreements. On May 30, 1919, Baron Edmund Rothschild convened a meeting at a hotel in Paris, France, attended by members of "The Inquiry" and the Round Table, to discuss how to integrate the efforts of elite individuals from Britain and the United States. On June 5, these individuals met again and decided that separate organizational forms would be more advantageous to coordinated action. On June 17, House, as convener, initiated the establishment of the "Institute of International Affairs" in New York. On July 21, 1921, the House reorganized the "Institute of International Affairs" into the "Council on Foreign Affairs." Members of "The Inquiry," U.S. representatives at the Paris Peace Conference, and 270 political and banking elites involved in establishing the Federal Reserve joined the council, generously funded by Wall Street bankers. An organization dedicated to controlling American society and world politics was thus born.

Roosevelt's son-in-law wrote in his memoirs: "For a long time, I thought it was Roosevelt himself who came up with many ideas and methods to benefit the United States. The reality was quite different. Most of his ideas, his political 'ammunition,' were carefully prepared by the Council on Foreign Affairs and organizations advocating a single world currency."

Paul Warburg's son, banker James Warburg, served as Roosevelt's financial advisor and was also a member of the Council on Foreign Affairs. He said on February 17, 1950, before the Senate Foreign Relations Committee: "We should establish a world government, whether people like it or not. The only question is whether this world government will be established through peaceful cooperation or conquest."

An editorial in the Chicago Tribune on December 9, 1950, pointed out: "Members of the (Foreign) Council have far more influence on society than ordinary people. They, with the advantage of wealth, social status, and educational background, have led this country down the path of economic bankruptcy and military collapse. They should look at their own hands, stained with the dried blood of the last war and the still fresh blood of the recent war."

The membership of the Diplomatic Association has reached 3,600. Members must be U.S. citizens, including influential bankers, corporate leaders, senior government officials, media elites, renowned university professors, top think tank experts, and senior military generals. These individuals constitute the "strong core" of the American political elite.

In terms of mainstream media "opinion guidance," the Diplomatic Association's 1987 report noted that as many as 262 journalists and media experts are its members, who not only "interpret" government foreign policies but also participate in "formulating" these policies. Members of the Diplomatic Association control television networks such as CBS, ABC, NBC, PBS, etc.

In the newspaper sector, members of the Diplomatic Association control major newspapers such as The New York Times, The Washington Post, The Wall Street Journal, The Boston Globe, The Baltimore Sun, The Los Angeles Times, and

others.

In the magazine field, members of the Diplomatic Association control mainstream magazines such as Time, Fortune, Life, Money, People, Entertainment Weekly, Newsweek, Business Week, U.S. News & World Report, Reader's Digest, Forbes, The Atlantic, and others.

In the publishing industry, members of the Diplomatic Association control the largest publishing companies such as Macmillan, Random House, Simon & Schuster, Harper Brothers, and McGraw-Hill.

5. Many politicians have lost basic political ethics and openly lying without shame.

6. Trust funds and charitable foundations in the United States avoid taxes, and the tax rates of the wealthy are lower than those of ordinary people.

7. Not only the securitization and full marketization of domestic assets, but also forcing other countries to fully open and marketize their financial systems.

8. Although wealth is highly concentrated among the rich in the United States, the rich still seek to control even more wealth.

9. The number of poor people continues to increase.

10. Crime rates are on the rise, and it's shocking that politicians are actually legislating to deem petty theft as not a crime.

11. The public drug use is increasing, and it has become normalized.

12. Legislation or laws and systems favour the rich and powerful, and are detrimental to the poor and ordinary people.

13. Many people have lost their sense of justice and are focused on their own interests.

14. Democratic system: **Democracy means that the public has the right to speak, and the final voting result must represent the interests of the majority.**

The democracy of the United States seems to represent the majority, but in reality, it represents a very small number of people, using the system to conceal the truth of democracy.

TikTok has more than 170 million users in the United States, with almost one in every two Americans being a TikTok user. In recent years, it has become part of American life, shaping popular culture and driving the growth of the "Internet celebrity economy," while also posing a threat to traditional American giants like Meta and Google.

On March 13, local time, the U.S. House of Representatives passed a bill to ban TikTok (overseas version of Douyin) nationwide.

The bill stipulates that TikTok's parent company, ByteDance, will have six months to sell its controlling stake. If the divestment is not completed within the specified time, TikTok will be removed from the United States.

Either sell to the United States or leave, the tough bill passed with an overwhelming majority of **352:65 in the two-party vote.**

170 Millions of people, accounting for 50% of the U.S. population. However, an overwhelming 352-65 vote by both parties led to the shutdown.

U.S. citizens staged a protest in the Capitol against the ban: "TikTok helps me do business," "I'm one of the 170 million TikTok users," "TikTok has changed my life." A TikTok spokesperson said: "The U.S. government is attempting to deprive 170 million Americans of their constitutional right to freedom of speech. Banning TikTok will harm the interests of millions of businesses, deprive artists of their audience, and disrupt the livelihoods of countless creators nationwide." If the U.S. political system were truly democratic, according to the proportion of 170 million TikTok users in the U.S., minus babies, **the ratio of votes in support of shutdown versus votes against shutdown by the two parties should be at least 207:210.** However, the final vote should have been against shutting down TikTok, but the reality was the opposite.

This means at least four things about the U.S. political system: **First**, there is no democracy, only the interests of a minority. **Second**, there is no freedom of use, because the freedom of 170 million users is greatly restricted. **Third**, there is no freedom of speech, as TikTok media brings the truth, but interest groups seek to cover it up and must use seemingly legal means to suppress it. **Fourth**, it reflects the serious intervention of businessmen and financiers in politics. Guan Zhong, the first prime minister of ancient China, once said that the intervention of businessmen in government operations is extremely dangerous. **15.** The United States does not have the freedom that American politicians boast about, but instead is subject to many restrictions. **Professor Tseng Shih-Chang (Zeng shiqiang), a well-known figure in Taiwan, once said in a video that he had asked many Chinese students studying in the United States about their feelings. They generally replied that before coming to the United States, they always believed that the US was very free and equal. However, after arriving in the US, they realized that it was far less free than China.**[Episode 17 | Chinese people have enjoyed the greatest freedom since ancient times # **Professor Zeng Shiqiang** # Wisdom of Chinese Studies.2022-03-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iFb3Xjgm/> AGV:/ 12/08 [r@R.KJ](#)]

16. The U.S. secondary and derivatives markets are markets where only a few people make huge profits.

Two Federal Reserve economists recently examined the evidence and concluded the gap is getting even wider.

Federal Reserve Board economists Isabel Cairo and Jae Sim found that the inequality gap has risen because owners of assets like real estate and stocks are benefiting from the rise of corporate power and rising profits, along with the decline of labor.

This is evident when looking at data on stock ownership. While an oft-quoted Gallup Poll indicated that 55% of households own stock in 2020, it is the very wealthy who control almost all of this asset. **A separate Federal Reserve report indicates the top 10% of households by net worth control 87.2% of the equities in this country at the end of the first quarter. While the top 1% have always controlled 70% to 80% of stock market value** since record-keeping began in

1989, this is the highest level of ownership ever, other than the fourth quarter of 2019, when it was 88.1%.

Who owns stocks: Households by net worth

Top 1% 51.8%

Top 90-99% 35.4%

50%-99% 12.1%

Bottom 50% 0.7%

(Q1 2020)

Broader wealth statistics recently published by the Federal Reserve are not much more encouraging. There is an equally wide gap between what the wealthy own and what the bottom 50% own.

It's largely real estate.

The top 1% have 12.8% of their net worth in real estate. The bottom 50% have 54.4% in real estate.

It's the other way around for stocks. **The top 1% have 34% of their net worth in stocks, the bottom 50% have only 2.2%.** The very wealthy also have much more of their wealth tied up in private businesses and "other assets."

[Wealth gap grows as rising corporate profits boost stock holdings controlled by richest households. PUBLISHED THU, AUG 27 2020.

<https://www.cnbc.com/2020/08/27/wealth-gap-grows-as-rising-corporate-profits-boost-stock-holdings-controlled-by-richest-households.html>]

ProPublica, citing confidential IRS data it obtained on thousands of wealthy people, reported that the 25 richest Americans "saw their worth rise a collective \$401 billion from 2014 to 2018."

But those people paid a total of just \$13.6 billion in federal income taxes for those five years, **which "amounts to a true tax rate of only 3.4%,"** the article noted.

In contrast, the median U.S. household in recent years earned around \$70,000 annually and paid 14% of that in federal taxes. Couples in the highest income tax rate bracket paid **a rate of 37% on earnings higher than \$628,300,** the report said.

In fact, the political and economic systems of the United States lack the guidance of correct philosophical thinking, leading to the current situation in which the asset market and financial system resemble the late Ming Dynasty of China: a large amount of wealth is concentrated in the hands of a few people, the government lacks funds, and financial tycoons intervene in government operations. **This also results in the occurrence of economic or financial crises in the United States, despite being a large country with the world's leading technology, the largest number of top 100 universities in the world, the world's leading military power, the largest GDP, and the second largest arable land area.** Due to the lack of national moral constraints and care for vulnerable groups, the United States has long oppressed indigenous peoples and never

	<p>implemented Equal-field allocation. Under the disguise of democracy and freedom, it is accustomed to dominating the world with military power and afraid of other countries becoming strong. Despite a large amount of currency issuance, the U.S. government and ordinary people lack money. The issuance of US dollars is controlled by private capital, intentionally leaving numerous tax loopholes, and tax policies are favorable to the rich for tax evasion. The collection of national taxes is controlled by private companies, leading to periodic government funding shortages and homelessness for the impoverished. Under the influence of financial capital, the frequency of initiating wars far exceeds that of the Ming Dynasty, continuously plundering or harvesting the wealth of smaller countries or other countries or their allies through various means (war or finance) to ensure the abnormal operation of the United States, making it difficult to cultivate truly capable and morally upright politicians and financiers in the United States.</p> <p>[Bezos, Buffett, Bloomberg, Musk, Icahn and Soros pay tiny fraction of wealth in income taxes, report reveals. PUBLISHED TUE, JUN 8 2021. https://www.cnbc.com/2021/06/08/bezos-musk-buffett-bloomberg-icahn-and-soros-pay-little-in-taxes.html]</p>
1 0	Looking at it from another angle, the equal-field system in the Northern Wei, Sui, and early Tang dynasties can be regarded as the 1.0 version of the socialist system.
1 1	<p>Leaders such as Mao Zedong and Deng Xiaoping etc. creatively designed China's new land distribution system (New Equal-field System (新均田制)) and governance system - the socialist system with Chinese characteristics. The Thought of Socialism with Chinese Characteristics for a New Era (New Equal-field System) - Building a Community of Shared Future for Mankind.</p> <p>The most important aspect of China's current political and economic system design is the design of the means of production. There are only two types of land ownership: state-owned and collectively owned. State-owned land belongs to the state, with the government holding the land on behalf of the people, making it the property of the whole nation. Collective ownership mainly occurs in rural areas, where land is collectively owned by the village and shared among the villagers. This system eliminates land merger and aims to curb the most influential factors in historical economic cycles, such as excessive marketization of assets and consolidation of the means of production. However, the current government system is based on and improved on the ancient centralized system, and China's civil service management system is an improved version of the ancient official management system, with civil service examinations being a contemporary version of the ancient imperial examination system.</p>
1 2	The current socialist system with Chinese characteristics is essentially an improved version of the Equal-Field system from the early Tang Dynasty.
1 3	From a historical perspective, the current market-oriented political, economic, and financial system in the United States is similar to the political, economic,

	and financial system of the later period of the Tang Dynasty in China. It is a system that concentrates wealth to the greatest extent in a minority interest group, and it is a system that inevitably falls into a deadlock.
1 4	Do the United States and Europe need to be afraid of China's equal field system? If the United States is afraid of China's new equal field system, is it still a society with universal values?
1 5	<p>The McCarthyism delusion created by American politicians has caused serious persecution of American citizens. This delusion unfairly labels innocent people as "socialists," leading to their exclusion and discrimination, and depriving them of their rights and freedoms. In fact, the socialist system is not detrimental to the people; it actually originated from the new equal-field system of the Northern Wei, Sui, and Tang dynasties in China, aiming to balance the distribution of social resources and wealth, eliminate the gap between the rich and the poor, and guarantee the rights to life of every individual.</p> <p>The McCarthyism delusion exposes the bias and misconceptions of American politicians toward socialism. The socialist theory created by Marx is not synonymous with the so-called "communist threat." McCarthyism is not only a form of political persecution, but also hinders the freedom of citizens to express their views and opinions due to fear and pressure, undermining the fundamental principles of a democratic society.</p> <p>Therefore, U.S. politicians and the government should apologize to the victims and compensate them for the losses suffered from unjust persecution. At the same time, Americans should abandon their bias against socialism, properly understand and respect this theory, and respect the beliefs and viewpoints of every individual, in order to achieve true democracy and freedom. The interests and rights of the people are more important than any political theory, and we should strive to bring rationality and fairness back to our society.</p>
1 6	<p>The social and economic structure of the Tang Dynasty during the Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义):</p> <p>In the middle and late period of the Tang Dynasty, there was a serious phenomenon of land merging in society, where a small number of powerful landlords merged a large amount of land, forming financial magnates. These magnates not only grew enormously in economic strength, but also influenced the political situation by marrying into the court officials, further strengthening their political position. They often managed to evade taxes and shift the burden onto the vast number of small and medium-sized farmers, leading to serious social conflicts and a desperate situation for the people.</p> <p>The current social and economic structure of the United States</p> <p>In the United States, a market economy dominates, and private enterprises play an important role in economic activity. Mergers and acquisitions also occupy a significant role in the U.S. economy, as many companies use M&A to expand their scale, enhance competitiveness, and achieve strategic development. At the same time, the U.S. society regulates the market and M&A activities through</p>

	<p>relatively sound laws, regulations, and oversight mechanisms to maintain market order and protect consumer interests. Overall, the social and economic structure of the United States is centered on marketization and M&A, with market forces playing an important role in resource allocation, while also being constrained and supervised by laws and regulations. However, M&A centered on privatization tends to ignore the overall interests, ultimately leading to society falling into a cycle of periodic stagnation. This is the result of religious and philosophical decisions followed by Americans, and can only be resolved through their own awakening.</p> <p>The current political and economic system of the United States is similar in core respects to the political and economic system of China in the middle and late Tang Dynasty.</p> <p>The issuance of money and the power to collect taxes in the United States are actually controlled by private individuals, which is more serious than in the late Tang Dynasty in China.</p> <p>To change the current situation, we can only hope that the shareholders of these companies will drive Tesla vehicles equipped with millimeter-wave radar to cemeteries and the wild to gain insights into life. Every time you create wealth in the world, it is a testament to your and your team's abilities in the world.</p>
<p>1 7</p>	<p>The leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong:</p> <p>A great philosopher, a great thinker, a great logician, a great statesman, a great military strategist, a great strategist, an outstanding calligrapher, and an outstanding poet.</p> <p>A Chinese leader and pioneer of the new social system who often wears patched clothes and pants.</p> <p>The world owes him a Nobel Prize in Literature, a Nobel Prize in Physics and a Nobel Peace Prize, because Mao Zedong's ideology has prevented war in China for the past few decades.</p> <p>The bold and unrestrained poetry of Su Dongpo, a literary giant in Chinese history during the Song Dynasty, has been unmatched for nearly a thousand years. In modern times, only Mao Zedong's the poem "Spring in the Qin Garden" "Snow" can compare in its boldness. Outstanding poetry like this comes once in a millennium.</p> <p>The military capability of Chiang Kai-shek, President of the Kuomintang government, was roughly equivalent to that of a platoon leader, but in 1935, he was conferred the rank of Special General. Mao Zedong, who commanded numerous wars of small victories against larger forces and weak victories against stronger ones, refused the title of Grand Marshal.</p> <p>Mao Zedong made 26 classic predictions throughout his life, and astonishingly, all of them came true.</p> <p>In 1953, Chairman Mao Zedong once discussed the issue of the divisibility of the atomic nucleus with someone. However, this question stumped the renowned physicist Qian Sanqiang, because at that time the smallest particles known in</p>

the world were proton and neutron, which scientists from various countries referred to as fundamental particles.

After thinking for a while, Qian Sanqiang slowly said, "According to the latest scientific research, we only know that proton and neutron are the fundamental particles that make up the atom. The so-called fundamental particles are the smallest and indivisible."

Chairman Mao smiled and said, "I don't think so. From a philosophical point of view, matter is infinitely divisible. Atoms, neutrons, electrons should also be divisible, divided into two, in unity and contradiction! Do you believe it or not?"

American physicists Sheldon Glashow and Steven Weinberg have visited China multiple times and were received by Chairman Mao. They discussed whether fundamental particles could continue to be divided. At the time, Glashow's position tended towards impossibility, while Chairman Mao insisted on his stance from a conversation with philosophers in 1964, believing that under the philosophy of dialectical materialism, matter is infinitely divisible. Protons, neutrons, electrons, and even smaller particles should also be divisible, in a constant process of division and unity, until infinity.

Later, even smaller particles were indeed discovered, referred to as "leptons" by the Chinese scientific community and "quarks" by the American scientific community. Shortly after Chairman Mao's death, at the 7th Annual Hawaii Particle Physics Conference in 1977, American physicist Glashow proposed that all these hypothetical components of matter be named "Maons" in honor of Chairman Mao and his profound philosophical views.

In the 1950s and 1960s, India illegally occupied Chinese territory and caused numerous conflicts on the China-Indian border. In June and November 1962, China launched two counter-attacks. The second counterattack started successfully but on November 21st, Mao Zedong signed an order for the Chinese government to unilaterally declare a ceasefire and withdraw. Subsequently, China returned all captured weapons and prisoners of war to India.

This action by China was unprecedented in the history of warfare.

In February 1972, during President Nixon's visit to China, he asked Chairman Mao, "Chairman, may I ask what is your special skill?"

Chairman Mao smiled and replied, "My special skill is serving the people."

Upon hearing this, Nixon immediately stood up and bowed deeply to Chairman Mao.

In 1975, when George H.W. Bush accompanied Henry Kissinger to meet Chairman Mao, the Chairman told him, "You could be president." At the time, Bush was the director of the United States Liaison Office in Beijing.

In 1988, George H.W. Bush, who had been predicted by Chairman Mao to "be able to become President of the United States," participated in another round

of the U.S. presidential election and ultimately defeated his Democratic opponent, Michael Dukakis, becoming the 41st President of the United States, the 51st overall.

Unlike the massacres of Native Americans by the founding presidents of the United States such as Washington and Lincoln, China's founding leaders such as Mao Zedong placed great emphasis on the training of minority ethnic cadres.

In November 1950, the State Council deliberated and approved the "**Trial Scheme for Training Minority Ethnic Cadres**" and the "**Trial Scheme for Establishing the Central Nationalities College.**" Mao Zedong also made instructions on these two schemes on November 30. Throughout the country, a total of 10 nationalities institutes were established in the Northwest, Central, South-Central, Southwest, Yunnan, Qinghai, Guangxi, Guangdong, Guizhou, and Tibet. **By 1978, the number of ethnic minority cadres nationwide had reached 960,000, with more than 94,000 graduates from these 10 nationalities Colleges,** the majority of whom were ethnic minority cadres.

In addition to educating and training ethnic cadres through training classes and nationalities institutes, Mao Zedong also placed great emphasis on training and cultivating ethnic cadres through practical work. In 1936, the General Political Department of the Red Army proposed to "promote and train new cadres from the Hui ethnic group through 'work' and 'struggle,' and to 'strengthen training and education as much as possible in work positions'" (Shen Guiping: "Research on the Education of Minority Ethnic Cadres," Ethnic Press, 2004, p.63). In November 1949, Mao Zedong emphasized the need to train minority ethnic cadres through practical cooperation with the government, particularly in Qinghai. Under this directive, the government in Qinghai in the first half of 1950 largely selected and appointed minority ethnic individuals to serve as commissioners, county governors, deputy commissioners, and deputy county governors (Liu Jintian, ed. "Deciphering the Code that Determines China's Destiny: Analysis of Mao Zedong's Telegrams," People's Literature Publishing House, 2013, p.305).

Opposing war and advocating for peace was consistently Mao Zedong's ideological orientation, which can be reflected in his personal aspirations.

Throughout his life, he wished to be an educator, engaging in the work of teaching and nurturing. In 1936, when American journalist Edgar Snow visited Yan'an, Mao Zedong publicly recounted his life experiences for the first time. He stated that during his student days in Changsha, he began to seriously consider his future, concluding that teaching was "most suitable" for him. The path of politics was taken out of necessity. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, during conversations with foreign guests, he repeatedly expressed, "I am an intellectual, a primary school teacher," "I never thought of going to war," and "I have always been a teacher, and I am still a teacher now." Later, due to

the oppression of imperialism, feudalism, bureaucratic capitalism, and warlords, he was compelled to embark on the revolutionary path, stating, "This is not subject to the will of people like us."

Mao Zedong also emphasized on multiple occasions that while we hope for a peaceful environment and oppose new wars, if imperialism imposes war on us, we will never be afraid and will persist in opposing war with war.

On September 12, 1953, **he pointed out, "We do not invade others, we do not invade anywhere, but if others invade us, we must fight, and we must fight to the end. The Chinese people have this principle: we support peace, but we are not afraid of war, and we can do both."**

In January 1956, while revising Zhou Enlai's political report for the Second Session of the Second National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference, he reiterated, **"We seek peace, but if international aggressors impose war on us, we are not afraid of war."**

Mao Zedong stated, "If the Third World War breaks out, the capitalist world will come to an end. If some lunatics want to start a war, it's nothing great; it's imperialism that will perish."

Washington, the founding father of the United States

George Washington: Quality knee-high boots can be made from the skins of Native Americans.

In 1779, George Washington instructed General John Sullivan to attack the Iroquois people, stating that "if the 'trash' (referring to Native Americans) were placed near all settlements, the country would not only be overrun, but destroyed." During the massacres and extermination of Native Americans, Washington also instructed his generals to "not listen to any peace proposals until Indian lands are effectively destroyed" (source: Stannard, David E. AMERICAN HOLOCAUST. New York: Oxford University Press, 1992. pp. 118-121.)

In 1783, Washington, in his comparison of Native Americans and wolves, showed his anti-Native American sentiment by stating, "both are predatory beasts, only differing in shape." Washington's policy of extermination was implemented after his forces once again defeated the Native Americans. Soldiers skinned the corpses of the Iroquois from "the hips downward, to make high or knee-high boots that would stretch as they walked." Survivors of the attack reportedly renamed the first president of the United States "Town Destroyer." Approximately 28 out of 30 Seneca towns were destroyed within a five-year period.

How did the sanctimonious Washington secretly keep slaves?

In 1790, the first president of the United States, George Washington, moved into the presidential mansion in Philadelphia with his wife and children. But what no one knew was that he had secretly brought along nine female slaves.

These female slaves all came from his private farm, where they had been

enslaved since birth to work diligently for him, watering flowers, cooking, doing laundry, cleaning, and even serving him in bed.

Of course, it was not dignified behavior for the president to own slaves, so these slaves were kept hidden from public view. Therefore, in the grand presidential mansion, he had a secret tunnel dug in the basement specifically for slaves to come and go through.

Unfortunately, the slaves had no idea that Pennsylvania, the state in which Philadelphia belonged, had already passed the Gradual Abolition Act, which stated that slaves only needed to reside in Pennsylvania for six months in order to gain their freedom.

As a former slave owner, Washington was vehemently opposed to the law. In order to prevent his slaves from learning about the law, he restricted their education and contact with others. When the slaves were close to living six months in Pennsylvania, he would send them back to Mount Vernon and bring a new batch of slaves.

However, a slip-up occurred. One of the female slaves, named Ona, was petite and skilled in sewing, which made her well-liked by the Washingtons. She was even praised by Washington in his diary as a "perfect sewing woman."

Ona, being intelligent and well-mannered, was often at the side of Mrs. Washington and had the opportunity to attend high-society events in Philadelphia, where she could interact with other slaves of prominent figures. It was during one of these interactions that a fellow slave told her that she could gain freedom by living in Pennsylvania for six months and advised her to register with the state government.

Annie, who grew up on a farm in Washington, learned for the first time that they were not born as slaves and could live equally with their masters. She planted the seed of freedom in her heart, but Washington was vigilant against them, and it was very difficult to obtain freedom.

On March 20, 1796, Martha Washington intended to give Ona to her soon-to-be-married daughter Elizabeth. Ona overheard this conversation from the next room and knew she could not delay any longer. One night, while the Washington family was having dinner, Ona secretly slipped out of the presidential mansion and disappeared into the main street. She found her previously acquainted slave friends and, with their help, escaped to the city of Portsmouth, New Hampshire. Mrs. Washington was furious when she found out about Ona's escape and demanded that President Washington publicly offer a reward for Ona's capture, claiming that she had been lured away by the French. However, Washington did not dare to make the matter public and had one of his subordinates handle the situation.

Ona eventually approached Washington and offered to return to servitude if Washington promised to free her after their deaths. However, Washington, in his arrogance, refused her request, so Ona continued to evade capture.

Two years later, Washington finally sent someone to find Ona and instructed that if she had children, they should be captured and brought back to

Philadelphia as well. By then, Ona had married a sailor named Jack and had a daughter. With the help of local officials, she escaped to nearby Greenville with her daughter. The pursuit did not stop until 1799, when Washington died of illness and Ona was finally free from the fear of capture.

In her later years, at the age of 80, Ona was interviewed by a journalist and said, "I never regretted leaving the presidential mansion. I had my freedom, and I believe God gave it to me when I was a child."

With Ona's passing, the history of the former president's ownership of slaves was also buried. The former presidential mansion has since been destroyed, and a public restroom has been built on the site for visitors to the nearby park.

On June 9, 2007, the excavation of site of the Philadelphia Presidential Mansion in the United States revealed a shocking "secret passage for black slaves" in the basement. As a result, the secret of President Washington, who owned slaves despite proclaiming "all men are created equal," was exposed, leading to the realization that so-called democracy and freedom in America had ultimately become nothing but empty talk.

Abraham Lincoln: The President of the United States Slaughters a Native American Every Ten Minutes

During President Lincoln's administration, over three million Native Americans were killed.

Native Americans are the indigenous people of the North American continent, white people in the United States are British colonists, and black people in the United States were slaves brought from Africa. Lincoln was the biggest executioner of Native Americans. His rule was accompanied by brutal massacres and persecution of Native Americans. The "Homestead Act" issued by Lincoln in 1862 aimed to drive Native Americans out of their ancestral lands and forcibly transfer these lands to white immigrants. According to statistics, during his presidency, over three million Native Americans were killed. In order to control the number of Native Americans and reduce their influence, he took a series of extremely cruel measures. He fabricated charges and ordered the hanging of 38 chiefs of the Minnesota Indian tribes. This cruel behavior seriously violated the principles of human rights and the rule of law advocated by Western society.

[Chairman Mao stumped Qian Sanqiang with a physics question. American Nobel Prize winner: Mao Zedong's philosophical thinking is too great. 2020-12-28. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/FUVKJT7A0541HVY5.html>]; [Chairman Mao, inspired by Zhuangzi, proclaimed that matter is infinitely divisible. American physicists named this "Mao particles". 2021-12-02. https://www.toutiao.com/article/7037043742666326558/?log_from=dab02acf73dff_1660097919830];

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	<p>did he retreat after advancing into India? 2017.12.19. https://www.yidianzixun.com/article/OHx9JlIF];[The China-Indian self-defense counterattack, why did Chairman Mao wait for four years before taking action? 2018-09-17. https://www.sohu.com/a/254242217_99925789];[Every item of Chairman Mao's personal belongings has a deeply moving story. 2018-06-14. https://www.sohu.com/a/235857795_650472];[The duplicity of the American people, the revered President Lincoln, was the chief executioner of the slaughter of three million Native Americans. 2023-12-08. https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/671068750] ;[The largest genocide against Native Americans was carried out by the four most outstanding presidents of the United States. 2017-07-06. https://www.sohu.com/a/155179041_99917666];[Mao Zedong and the Construction of Ethnic Cadres Team. Li Haibo. May 28th, 2016. https://epaper.gmw.cn/gmrb/html/2016-05/28/nw.D110000gmrb_20160528_3-11.htm];[Mao Zedong's treatment of war: Peace is in favor, and war is not afraid. 2019-07-10. http://www.kunlunce.com/jczc/mzdsx/2019-07-10/134993.html];[American scholars asked: Why are you not afraid of war? Chairman Mao responded with a domineering tone: What's the use of being afraid? 2021-03-23. https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1695017041780734916&wfr=spider&for=pc]</p>
18	<p>The U.S. secondary and derivatives markets are markets where only a few people make huge profits. This accelerated the transformation of the United States towards the late Tang Dynasty.</p> <p>Quantitative trading is a form of trading that uses computer programs to execute trading strategies. It uses complex algorithms and mathematical models to make trading decisions, often involving a large number of high-speed trades and frequent placing and canceling of orders. This form of trading carries certain risks, especially in the secondary market, where it may cause serious harm to the market.</p> <p>First, the frequent false placing and canceling of orders in quantitative trading can lead to market unfairness. Such behaviour may disrupt the normal operation of the market, making it difficult for ordinary investors to obtain fair trading opportunities and even subjecting them to unfair trading treatment. This will seriously affect the fairness and transparency of the market, undermine investor confidence, and ultimately hinder the healthy development of the market.</p> <p>Second, the excessive frequency and high-speed trading of quantitative trading can also increase market instability. Due to the extremely fast operation speed of quantitative trading, hundreds or even thousands of transactions can be completed in a matter of milliseconds. This high-speed trading can lead to significant market fluctuations, making the market more unstable and posing potential risks to the entire financial system.</p> <p>Thirdly, and most importantly, the development of quantitative trading may lead</p>

	<p>to the phenomenon of a financial market being a "harvesting machine" for funds. Since quantitative trading typically requires substantial capital and advanced technological equipment, only a few financial investment groups can gain an advantage in this area, turning the market into a place where only a few can make huge profits, while ordinary investors find it difficult to obtain corresponding returns, further exacerbating market inequity.</p> <p>Fourth, there is also a significant point that quantitative trading and short selling mechanisms have led to abnormal psychological changes in people, causing them being able to create wealth by manipulating the secondary market without producing value through labor. This objectively leads to conflicts and wars in different regions of the world. Every local crisis, conflict, and war inevitably brings huge expected returns to the pioneers of the secondary market.</p> <p>In summary, the development of quantitative trading will inevitably cause serious harm to the secondary market, including market unfairness, instability, and further concentration of financial capital. Not only is it fundamentally unable to realize universal values, it also leads to moral decay and triggers global crises, conflicts, wars, economic crises, or financial crises. However, the regulatory authorities in the United States should have conducted more strict supervision of quantitative trading and short selling to ensure market stability and fairness, but they have not done so and have instead fully legalized quantitative trading, especially false orders and cancellations.</p>
1 9	<p>The rise and fall of a nation depends on the character and ability of its leaders or officials. The highly capable team of New China demonstrates a modest scale.</p> <p>During the Eastern Han Dynasty, there was a general named Feng Yi who, after achieving great success, refused to accept the rewards and retreated under a tree, leading the army to call him "General Big Tree".</p> <p>In the last century, there have been many instances in China of military officers voluntarily giving up their ranks during the first selection of military ranks.</p> <p>First, Chairman Mao Zedong resigned from his position as a general when the National People's Congress decided to appoint him as "Grand Marshal" directly, but he firmly refused to accept it.</p> <p>2. Su Yu, unexpectedly resigned as Marshal three times. In the war, General Su Yu directed a series of earth-shattering war dramas with superb military command art, winning a series of classic battles such as the Cheqiao Battle, the Seven Battles in Suzhong Region, the Battle of Menglianggu, the Battle of Yudong, and the Battle of Huaihai, all of which can be called classics, thus making outstanding contributions to the victory of the Chinese revolution. At the Battle of Huaihai, he commanded an army of 600,000 against the 800,000 Kuomintang army, creating the miracle of winning against a larger force. Mao Zedong highly praised him, saying during the Battle of Menglianggu, "In this battle, there were two people in China who didn't expect it, one is Chiang Kai-shek, and the other is me, Mao Zedong."</p>

	<p>3. Marshal Xu Xiangqian gave up his military rank Although it was the people's unanimous desire for Xu Xiangqian to be promoted to "Marshal", he wrote a letter to the Chairman rejecting the appointment.</p> <p>4. Marshal Luo Ronghuan gave up his military rank At the time, Luo Ronghuan, who oversaw the assessment of military ranks, also declined the appointment as "Marshal", feeling that his contributions were not significant enough.</p> <p>5. General Xu Haidong gave up his military rank While undergoing treatment in Dalian, Xu Haidong learned that he had been awarded the rank of general, and immediately requested to give it up to the Prime Minister who was visiting Dalian at the time, feeling that his long period of illness did not meet the requirements.</p> <p>6. General Tan Zheng gave up his military rank. When the deputy director who ranked first in the General Staff was appointed as a general, he also stated that he was not qualified and wanted to give up the rank.</p> <p>7. General Xu Guangda requests to lower his military rank. Xu Guangda is known as the "Father of Armored Forces" in China. Upon hearing the decision to award him the rank of General, he repeatedly requested to lower his rank, but his requests were not approved. Eventually, he wrote a "rank reduction application" with Mao Zedong raising it at a meeting, saying, "This is a clear mirror, it is a mirror of the Communist Party itself!"</p> <p>8. Lieutenant General Sun Yizhong: In 1955, the People's Liberation Army implemented a military rank system. Sun Yizhong insisted on not being awarded the rank of lieutenant general. He even wrote a letter to his superiors, suggesting that the rank of Major General was sufficient for him.</p> <p>9. General Lai Chuanzhu: Actively requested not to be awarded the rank of general. After unanimous discussion, the Central Military Commission believed that Lai Chuanzhu's qualifications and merits fully met the requirements for the rank of general, and he should not be reduced to the rank of lieutenant general. They also highly praised his integrity.</p> <p>10. Lieutenant General Xu Liqing: Made three concessions - in rank, military rank, and position. He is the only founding lieutenant general at brigade level.</p> <p>10. Lieutenant General Zhang Jingwu: Stabilized Tibet by bravely venturing into dangerous territory. He voluntarily relinquished his honorary military rank.</p>
20	<p>If China and Taiwan were to reunify and implement "one country, two systems", allowing Taiwan to continue with complete land and financial liberalization, it would mean that Taiwan would continue to be governed in a self-serving manner that benefited only a very few people with monopoly wealth. This would inevitably continue to undermine the mainland's system of equitable land distribution, leading to an increasing wealth gap, which could potentially lead to the fragmentation of China in the future.</p> <p>It is very difficult to make extremely selfish groups voluntarily abandon their own interests. Once a region or country enters the political and economic</p>

	<p>environment of the late Tang Dynasty, it is almost impossible to return to the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty at the current level of religious and moral standards, unless internal conflicts within the country erupt again, and private monopoly forces are once again eliminated through war or force, along with the maintenance of power structures that uphold private monopolies. Alternatively, there have been changes within Taiwan, where some groups with altruistic ideals have driven out a portion of the extreme self-serving groups before and after reunification.</p> <p>If mainland China dares to suddenly stop importing any products from Taiwan and prohibit the flow of profits obtained by Taiwanese businesses from the mainland into Taiwan, the internal conflicts in Taiwan are bound to worsen in approximately 3-4 years. Under the late Tang Dynasty system, it was difficult to address the serious issues brought about by the large number of impoverished people in Taiwan.</p>
<p>2 1</p>	<p>In conclusion, the communist system is just an ideal society, a noble religious belief. The future global social system will inevitably be based on China's new Equal-field system of socialism, and will continue to be improved and perfected. Anyone who attacks the current social system in China, in which state-owned assets dominate, either has a significant lack of understanding of Chinese historical lessons, or wants to pursue privatization of state-owned assets for personal gain, and is not suitable for leadership in public office.</p>
<p>2 2</p>	<p>Chairman Mao Zedong told his comrades in 1938 that complete human equality is impossible even over ten thousand years. However, why did he pursue communism as the highest ideal system for humanity, when so many people sacrificed their lives for China's prosperity and equality for all?</p> <p>Chairman Mao Zedong's profound wisdom is precisely reflected in this aspect.</p> <p>Because China has a proverb: "If you aim for the top, you may reach the middle; if you aim for the middle, you may end up at the bottom." This means that if someone sets lofty goals, they may ultimately only achieve moderate success; but if they set moderate goals, they may end up with only minimal success; and if they set low goals, they may not achieve anything at all. In simple terms, in anything one does, they should demand excellence from themselves, so that even if unexpected setbacks occur, they can still achieve some degree of success. If you settle for mediocrity, even slight setbacks may lead to no results at all. This proverb tells people that, whether in learning or in endeavors, one must aim high and strive diligently, only then can they possibly reach the summit.</p> <p>Humanity can only progress towards the fairest ideal social system to attain better progress. Otherwise, just like the early Tang Dynasty's implementation of equal-field system, after a few decades, the system would become meaningless. With significant regional disparities and wealth inequality in China, the nation would inevitably fall into the cycle of historical recurrence. Only by achieving a community of shared future for mankind can the entire world achieve peace. However, Chairman Mao soberly recognized</p>

	<p>that the establishment of a social system similar to China's in another country must be autonomously chosen by that country, not imposed by China. Therefore, China cannot interfere with the political systems of other countries.</p>
<p>2 3</p>	<p>The founding ideology of the Communist Party of China and its governing philosophy align with the requirements of establishing an improved version of the early Tang Dynasty equal-field system and establishing a community of shared future for mankind. In essence, it represents the highest version of the improvement of the equal field system of the early Tang Dynasty.</p> <p>"To establish the party for the public and to govern for the people" is the governing philosophy of the Communist Party of China and also the essence of the important thought of the "Three Represents."</p> <p>"Founding the Party for the Public" means that the Communist Party of China (CPC) pursues no private interests other than the fundamental interests of the broadest masses of the people. Its core is the character "public", which embodies the substantive meaning of the public interests of the state and nation, the common ideals of all the people, and the public affairs of the whole society, as well as the procedural requirements of fairness, justice, and transparency. For our Party, "public" refers to the unity of the lofty ideal of communism and the stage-specific struggle goals. At this stage, the greatest "public" for the CPC is to comprehensively build a moderately prosperous society, achieve socialist modernization, and realize the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. Founding the Party for the Public means that the Party's theoretical line, principles, policies, and all work must reflect the development requirements of China's advanced productive forces, the direction of China's advanced culture, and embody the common interests of the state and nation, as well as the common ideals of all the people.</p> <p>"Governing for the people" means that the state power of the People's Republic of China belongs to the people, and the power is delegated by the people. The Communist Party of China will wield and utilize power for the people. At its core is the character "people." In contemporary China, "people" refers to the broadest masses, including all socialist laborers, builders of the socialist cause, patriots who support socialism, and patriots who support the reunification of the motherland. The Communist Party of China originates from the people, is rooted in the people, and serves the people. Governing for the people means that the party's theoretical line, principles, policies, and all work must take the fundamental interests of the broadest masses of the people as the starting point and ultimate goal, ensuring that power is used for the people, emotions are connected to the people, and benefits are sought for the people.</p> <p>Following China's reform and opening-up, corruption increased significantly. It is possible that in some units, once corrupt individuals gain power, they are not even controlled by genuine Communist Party members. The Chinese government needs to rapidly improve its governance practices.</p> <p>It should be noted that not all parties that claim to be communist adhere to the Communist Party of China's governing philosophy of "establishing the</p>

	<p>party for the public and governing for the people," which embodies the important thought of the "Three Represents." The Communist Party of Vietnam, while nominally communist, in reality functions more like a criminal syndicate—a party of massacre, and a party of robbery. Whenever Vietnam faces difficulties, it seeks assistance from China. China has provided Vietnam with at least \$20.9 billion in aid, which is equivalent to about \$3 trillion in purchasing power today. However, after the reunification of Vietnam, at least 1.5 million ethnic Chinese were massacred. This evil ruling party in Vietnam cannot be called a communist party, but rather a malevolent mafia. Vietnam must compensate for the loss of 1.5 million lives caused by these massacres.</p> <p>American legal teams can assist victims in China in seeking justice, just as they seek compensation from the Vietnamese government according to American standards. American lawyers can also gain substantial returns. If the U.S. government participates in demanding compensation from Vietnam for the victims, it can also gain substantial returns, thus alleviating the national debt crisis. The United States does not need to wage war; assisting victims in China can be profitable, enhancing America's positive image as depicted in Hollywood.</p> <p>The evil Vietnamese government has also forcibly expelled Chinese people from Vietnam, demanding 12 taels of gold from each person, threatening to kill those who cannot pay. The family of Facebook founder Zuckerberg's wife was one of the victims at that time.</p>
<p>2 4</p>	<p>The financial regulations enacted by Europe and the United States have caused a regression in global financial ethics by 2,000-4,000 years.</p> <p>In ancient China, engaging in such malicious activities to disrupt a country's financial stability through periodic manipulations in the financial markets, thereby plundering the wealth of the nation and its citizens, resulting in economic crises, would have been considered serious crimes deserving of the death penalty in line with normal moral ethics and logic. However, in Western society today, these methods of manipulating financial rules and plundering national wealth have been legitimized through public opinion and the construction of new financial theories. This represents a typical crime where a tiny minority freely loots wealth into the secondary market, causing the majority to lose their wealth and freedom. Despite Western politicians' verbal advocacy for universal values, emphasizing individual freedom and democracy, freedom has become the theoretical basis and protective umbrella for malignant crimes. Universal values have been transformed into values that benefit only a few.</p>
<p>2 5</p>	<p>The United States is the world's largest country, with the world's largest GDP. However, its national debt continues to rise, and it relies on forcing other countries to buy U.S. bonds in order to maintain normal operations</p> <p>Is U.S. policy correct? Is U.S. economic policy correct? Is U.S. financial policy correct?</p>

	Is the political system of the United States correct?
2 6	The United States is the world's largest country with the highest GDP globally. Despite this, its national debt continues to rise. It even relies on constantly raising and lowering bank interest rates, disrupting the normal operation of other countries' economies to harvest assets from them, all in order to maintain the normal operation of the United States. Can the U.S. political system be considered correct?
2 7	With the rise of self-media, the vast majority of Chinese people now know that the United States is a corporation disguised as a country or nation, with capital, especially Jewish capital, truly controlling America. Therefore, they all believe that America is probably Israel's son or grandson. Currently, the U.S. government and law enforcement agencies are arresting American university professors and students who protest against Israel's massacre of more than 34,000 innocent Palestinian children, women, and civilians. This has made both American and global citizens fully aware that the United States essentially serves the interests of Jewish lobby groups. Despite being the leading issuer of global trade and settlement currencies, the majority of excess U.S. currency issued is held by U.S. interest groups. The U.S. government is in debt, and some soldiers' bonuses are even being withheld. This dire situation even surpasses that of the late Tang Dynasty and is approaching the level of the late Ming Dynasty, where the treasury was empty, soldiers received no salaries, and the Ming emperor had to borrow money from ministers. Those ministers who cried poverty in front of Emperor Chongzhen of the Ming Dynasty, before the torture of Li Zicheng's uprising army, handed over astonishing wealth. According to historical records, Li Zicheng obtained more than 70 million taels of silver in total.
2 8	The United States is deeply involved in a national debt crisis. If not handled properly, there could be upheaval within the military. Because of the lack of moral standards in the foundational principles of the United States, evidenced by its support for Israel's slaughter of innocent civilians, domestic opposition is strong. Japanese spies lurking within the U.S. military, may also deliberately provoke conflicts with China to entangle the U.S. military in war. If the U.S. military suffers defeat, amid the severe national debt crisis, the U.S. could rapidly disintegrate. The fleet stationed in Japan may face a major crisis.
2 9	According to Chinese history, the legal punishment rules and ideologies formulated by Europe and the United States for serious crimes have caused global judicial ethics to regress by at least 2,000-4,000 years.
3 0	The fact that people, who should be the fundamental factor contributing to economic benefits, are excluded from the equation of economic benefits in Western mainstream economics is against human nature and lacks ecological consideration. This indicates that in Western countries, anyone can be discarded during economic operations, creating a paradox within the economic theories established by Western economics. This suggests that

	<p>Western mainstream economic theories are rigid and focused solely on profit, rather than truly serving as a key framework for sustainable national development, making them unsuitable as core theories for governing a country's operations. Consequently, neoliberal economic theories inevitably lead to cyclical crises in both a country's or the global economy and the daily lives of ordinary people.</p> <p>A country's process of capital accumulation without generating profits cannot be regarded as generating economic benefits for the nation; it is simply a load of nonsense in economic theory. Just like your growth from elementary school to college, where you didn't earn money but relied on continuous investment from your parents, and only started creating wealth for the family after growing up, isn't this continuously creating economic benefits?</p> <p>From 1950 to 1978, China invested a huge amount of human and material resources to build the foundation of heavy industry and human resources. Countless people contributed to the country on very low income conditions. It wasn't until after 1978, when market economy elements were introduced, that China's economy, still dominated by state-owned enterprises, saw significant growth. Can you say you only feel full after eating three hamburgers, and the first two were wasted? According to Western modern economic theory, the first two hamburgers were actually wasted.</p> <p>There are at least 1.2 billion people in China whose intelligence exceeds mine, and I can identify significant errors in these economic theories. However, despite the fact that the world's top 100 universities are located in Europe and America, for some reason, mainstream economists around the world generally consider modern Western economic theories to be correct, believing that full marketization is the means to achieve optimal resource allocation, rather than theories that lead to cyclical crises for nations.</p>
<p>3 1</p>	<p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>To an article titled SME Operating Performance on the Government of Canada website, margins for a small business operating between 2004 and 2012 were 7%.</p> <p>You will notice a big variance from the chart in the small business net profit margin ranging from as low as 1.5% to as high as 7%. The information obviously varies from year to year based on economic conditions, but a 7% net profit operating margin is a high watermark. That number, 7%, isn't very good.</p> <p>The international community must be aware that the practice of attracting deposits at high interest rates seriously violates economic principles and contributes to banks becoming tools for the financial industry to plunder the wealth of the real economy.</p> <p>If the United States is a nation full of love, freedom, democracy, benevolence, and respect for human rights, and is a country capable of leading the world, it should immediately lead the United Nations to establish a UN covenant and international consensus to prohibit any country, bank, or financial institution</p>

	<p>from having an annual deposit interest rate exceeding 4.0% (exclusion of claims for war crimes), which is equivalent to a monthly rate exceeding 0.333333% (including fees paid to third parties), to prevent the financial costs of small and medium-sized enterprises from leading to bankruptcy, to prevent funds from flowing back to the currency-issuing country at a rate higher than this interest rate, causing currency shortages in other countries and triggering stock market crash or financial or economic crises in those countries, resulting in the freedom and human rights of the citizens of those countries being harmed due to adverse financial conditions. Any bank that accepts deposits with an annual interest rate higher than 4.0% or a monthly rate higher than 0.333333% shall be deemed an evil bank, and it shall be prohibited from accepting any deposits for 6 years; any banker or executive or government official who sets an interest rate higher than the annual interest rate higher than 4.0% or the monthly rate higher than 0.333333% to attract deposits shall be deemed the worst and most evil human in the universe, and shall be prohibited from engaging in the financial industry and holding any government positions for the next 60 years, their immediate family members shall be prohibited from engaging in the financial industry for 60 years, and they shall be prohibited from boarding any aircraft or high-speed train. They must report to the local police when leaving or arriving in any city or region and make their itinerary public to society.</p> <p>The vast majority of the world's top 100 universities in economics and finance are located in Europe and America. These economists and finance experts possess exceptional intelligence, often publishing papers on complex issues. Yet, why do they turn a blind eye to this glaring problem that clearly leads to serious crises for countries?</p> <p>[15+ AVERAGE SMALL BUSINESS REVENUE + PROFIT MARGIN STATISTICS,2023. By Jack Flynn. Apr. 19, 2023.https://www.zippia.com/advice/small-business-revenue-profit-margin/];[How Much Profit Does the Average Small Business Owner Make a Year in 2024? AUGUST 29, 2022. https://www.thekickassentrepreneur.com/profit-average-small-business/]; [Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>
<p>3 2</p>	<p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>To an article titled SME Operating Performance on the Government of Canada website, margins for a small business operating between 2004 and 2012 were 7%.</p> <p>You will notice a big variance from the chart in the small business net profit margin ranging from as low as 1.5% to as high as 7%. The information obviously varies from year to year based on economic conditions, but a 7% net profit operating margin is a high watermark. That number, 7%, isn't very good.</p> <p>If the United States is a nation full of love, freedom, democracy,</p>

benevolence, and respect for human rights, and is a country capable of leading the world, it should immediately lead the United Nations to establish a UN covenant and international consensus: Any financial institution or individual that lends money to enterprises and individuals at an annual interest rate exceeding 5% shall ensure that all expenses incurred in the loan process, including fees paid to third parties, do not result in an effective annual interest rate exceeding 5%. If exceeded, such charges cannot be considered legal, but rather as illegal income. Moreover, a penalty based on the loan amount shall be imposed, with confiscation of 20-30% of the principal. If the cumulative costs correspond to an effective annual interest rate exceeding 6.5%, the offender must face criminal charges and be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison. The above terms apply to any country.

Any lender who sets or implements usurious loans with an interest rate exceeding 6.5% shall be permanently prohibited from owning, directly or indirectly, any shares in banks or financial companies. They shall be permanently prohibited from working in the financial industry and from holding government positions. Their immediate family members shall be prohibited from engaging in the financial industry for 60 years. They shall also be prohibited from boarding any aircraft or high-speed train for 30 years. When leaving or arriving in any city or region, they must report to the local police and make their itinerary public to society.

If this world or the financial world still values philosophy and logic and respects human rights, it must prohibit all lending behavior with an annual interest rate exceeding 6.5%.

Usury, under the guise of high interest rates, erodes social stability like a plague, bringing misfortune to people's livelihoods. It not only devours the wealth of borrowers, but also pushes vulnerable individuals to desperation, leading to the breakup of families and the destruction of futures. Under the burden of excessive debt, victims often fall into the abyss of illegality, increasing crime rates and endangering public safety. It strays from the purpose of legitimate financial services, undermines normal economic order, and harms the interests of the disadvantaged majority. The United Nations should formulate a convention urging governments worldwide to crack down vigorously on usurious practices, protect citizens from their harm and maintain social harmony and stability. Advocating legal lending practices ensures the fair and orderly flow of wealth, bringing well-being to people.

The vast majority of the world's top 100 universities in economics and finance are located in Europe and America. These economists and finance experts possess exceptional intelligence, often publishing papers on complex issues. Yet, why do they turn a blind eye to this glaring problem that clearly leads to serious crises for countries?

[15+ AVERAGE SMALL BUSINESS REVENUE + PROFIT MARGIN STATISTICS. 2023. By Jack Flynn. Apr. 19, 2023. <https://www.zippia.com/advice/small-business-revenue-profit-margin/>]; [How Much Profit Does the Average Small Business

	<p>Owner Make a Year in 2024? AUGUST 29, 2022. https://www.thekickassentrepreneur.com/profit-average-small-business/]; [Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>
<p>3 3</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>To an article titled SME Operating Performance on the Government of Canada website, margins for a small business operating between 2004 and 2012 were 7%.</p> <p>You will notice a big variance from the chart in the small business net profit margin ranging from as low as 1.5% to as high as 7%. The information obviously varies from year to year based on economic conditions, but a 7% net profit operating margin is a high watermark. That number, 7%, isn't very good.</p> <p>Therefore, any institution or individual providing loans to students during their studies (including those pursuing master's or doctoral degrees) must not charge an annual interest rate exceeding 3%, or it will be considered illegal. Penalties based on the loan amount should be enforced, with the government confiscating 20-40% of the principal. If the full fee equals an effective annual interest rate over 5%, the offender must face criminal prosecution and be sentenced to 2-5 years of imprisonment. The above terms apply to any country or nation.</p> <p>Any lender who sets or implements usurious loans with an interest rate exceeding 5% shall be permanently prohibited from owning, directly or indirectly, any shares in banks or financial companies. They shall be permanently prohibited from working in the financial industry and from holding government positions. Their immediate family members shall be prohibited from engaging in the financial industry for 60 years. They shall also be prohibited from boarding any aircraft or high-speed train for 30 years. When leaving or arriving in any city or region, they must report to the local police and make their itinerary public to society.</p> <p>The vast majority of the world's top 100 universities in economics and finance are located in Europe and America. These economists and finance experts possess exceptional intelligence, often publishing papers on complex issues. Yet,</p>

	<p>why do they turn a blind eye to this glaring problem that clearly leads to serious crises for countries?</p> <p>[15+ AVERAGE SMALL BUSINESS REVENUE + PROFIT MARGIN STATISTICS [2023]. By Jack Flynn. Apr. 19, 2023. https://www.zippia.com/advice/small-business-revenue-profit-margin/]; [How Much Profit Does the Average Small Business Owner Make a Year in 2024? AUGUST 29, 2022. https://www.thekickassentrepreneur.com/profit-average-small-business/]; [Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>
<p>3 4</p>	<p>The Japanese government, emperor, and chaebol may be the most evil in the world.</p> <p>The Japanese government, Emperor, and conglomerates are very evil, intentionally setting the minimum inheritance tax in Japan at only 30 million yen, causing exhaustion and abandonment of houses among the middle and lower class citizens. This is conducive to creating impoverished populations for the evil Japanese emperor, chaeboland, and warlords to launch aggressive wars.</p> <p>The minimum personal threshold for inheritance tax must be immediately raised at least from 30 million yen to 90 million yen in Japan.</p>
<p>3 5</p>	<p>Historical laws reveal the inevitability of the future of the United States and Israel.</p> <p>The most famous prime minister of China, Guan Zhong, once said in his work "Establishing Administrative Rules":</p> <p>The problems that monarchs need to deal with prudently are fourfold: (君之所慎者四：一曰大德不至仁，不可以授国柄。二曰见贤不能让，不可与尊位。三曰罚避亲贵，不可使主兵。四曰不好本事，不务地利，而轻赋敛，不可与都邑。此四务者，安危之本也。) First, those who advocate morality but fail to truly practice benevolence should not be entrusted with significant state power. Secondly, individuals who encounter capable and virtuous people but refuse to yield should not be granted prestigious titles. Third, those who, when executing punishments, show favoritism towards their relatives and close associates should not be appointed as military commanders. Fourth, those who disregard agriculture, neglect land development, and readily impose taxes should not be appointed as local officials. These four principles, which strengthen the security of the State, are the fundamental pillars upholding national stability.</p> <p>Today, countless government officials in the United States can hold positions of power even without the most basic human rights ethics. Not only do they lead the United States, but also Europe and the world. This is not just a global tragedy, but also the engine driving the future disintegration of the United States.</p> <p>Even when numerous officials of the United States government witness Israel's extensive slaughter of innocent Palestinian children, women, and civilians, the</p>

	<p>burial of Palestinians alive, and the illegal harvesting of organs from the bodies of many Palestinians, they still lie and support Israel, rather than compelling Israel to stop its massacres and acts of genocide. Instead of protecting the freedom of speech of American university students, they restrict freedom of speech and use police forces to suppress demonstrations and marches in support of or sympathy with Palestinians in American universities. A large number of university students and teachers were detained by the police, and there were even threats to use the National Guard to suppress students and teachers who supported or sympathized with Palestinians. On April 23, the U.S. Senate passed a bill providing \$26 billion in aid to Israel. The U.S. government has completely lost its moral compass, devoid of morals, ethics, humanity, human rights, freedom, and democracy. Democracy, freedom, and human rights in the United States are just a facade for interest groups to deceive the public. Today's America is governed only by a government and government officials who support dictatorship, greed, self-interest, barbarism, and slaughter. The moral and ethical level of U.S. government officials may regress by 4,000 years compared to China, far surpassing the late Tang Dynasty. It is highly likely that as a result of this incident, the two major political parties in the United States will split into four or more factions. Once U.S. military personnel fully realize that the United States is a company controlled by Jewish interest groups, that the U.S. media is also controlled by Jewish interest groups, that the issuance of U.S. currency is also controlled by Jewish people, and that taxation is also controlled by interest groups, a large-scale action similar to the Huang Chao Uprising at the end of the Tang Dynasty, aimed at eliminating members of American financial oligarchic families or eliminating members of global Jewish financial oligarchic families, will erupt. No place in the world may be a safe haven for these Jewish financial oligarchic members.</p> <p>The renowned prime minister of ancient China, Guan Zhong, once said in his work that "propriety, righteousness, integrity, and a sense of shame" are the four pillars of a nation, and if they cannot be upheld, the nation will perish ("礼义廉耻，国之四维；四维不张，国乃灭亡"). This means that these four moral principles are essential for maintaining a nation's stability and prosperity, and their absence greatly increases the risk of the nation's eventual destruction.</p>
<p>3 6</p>	<p>The essence of neoliberal economics: economics that achieves an 80/20 distribution of social wealth benefits.</p> <p>The Essence of an Adequate Market for All State Assets (The essence of a sufficient market for all national assets:): The Economics of Achieving an 80/20 Return Distribution of Social Wealth.</p> <p>The Essence of Adequate Markets in the National Financial Industry: Economics and Finance to Achieve 80/20 Income Distribution of Social Wealth.</p> <p>During her campaign for prime minister, Margaret Thatcher delivered resolute speeches, proclaiming, "Government is not the solution to our problem, government is the problem." Despite being hailed as a hero of the West,</p>

	<p>Thatcher ultimately failed to rescue the United Kingdom. From a philosophical and logical point of view, Mrs. Thatcher's statement not only lacks logical consistency, but is also completely wrong on a philosophical level. According to Mrs. Thatcher's philosophy, her government should not exist at all.</p> <p>Mrs. Thatcher herself was extremely diligent and intelligent, and I greatly admire her diligence. She should not have made such a big mistake. It is possible that the West has fabricated European, American, and global history and economic history, leading her to believe in the missionaries' fabricated and fictional European and global history and economic history. In the end, she failed due to significant flaws in Western philosophical and economic theories.</p>
<p>3 7</p>	<p>When the Federal Reserve remains an institution controlled by private bankers, it is impossible for the United States to achieve an equal field system, and war will always occur.</p> <p>Rothschild: "As long as I can control a country's currency issuance, I don't care who makes the law." [Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007.]; [As long as I can control a country's currency issuance, I don't care who makes the law. October 6, 2023. https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1778996941558267219&wfr=spider&for=pc]</p> <p>Before her death, Mrs. Rothschild once said, "If my sons did not want wars, there would be none." [Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]</p> <p>It would not be an exaggeration to say that until 2008, there were probably not many economists in China who knew that the Federal Reserve was actually a private central bank. The so-called "Federal Reserve Bank" is neither "federal," nor does it have any "reserves," nor can it be considered a "bank." However, almost everyone in China today knows about it. But even today, there may not be many people in the United States who know that the Federal Reserve is actually a private central bank. The so-called "Federal Reserve Bank" is neither "federal," nor does it have any "reserves," nor can it be considered a "bank." Most Americans probably assume that the U.S. government issues the dollar, but in reality, the U.S. government does not have the authority to issue currency. After President Kennedy was assassinated in 1963, the U.S. government ultimately lost the remaining authority to issue "silver dollars." For the U.S. government to obtain dollars, it must pledge the future tax revenue of the American people (through government bonds) to the private Federal Reserve, which then issues "Federal Reserve Notes," which are the "dollars." The nature and origins of the Federal Reserve are a tacit "taboo" in the academic and journalistic circles of the United States. The media can debate trivial topics like "same-sex marriage" day in and day out, but they hardly ever mention the crucial question of who controls the issuance of currency—a matter that affects everyone, every day, every penny earned, and every interest payment on loans. If you find this</p>

surprising, it indicates that this topic is important, and yet you didn't know about it. This chapter will uncover the secrets of the establishment of the Federal Reserve, deliberately "filtered out" by the mainstream media in the United States. As we examine this significant event that has shaped the course of world history under a magnifying glass, with slow-motion playback, the development of events will be precise down to the hour. On December 23, 1913, the democratically elected government of the United States was finally overthrown by the power of money.

"Since the banking crisis of 1907, bankers have had a bad image in the minds of the American people, to the extent that no congressman dared to openly support legislation drafted by bankers. So these people traveled from New York to this remote island to draft this document. In addition, the name "central bank" was too conspicuous. Since President Jefferson, the name of the central bank has always been closely associated with British international bankers' conspiracy, so Paul suggested using the name "Federal Reserve System" to divert attention. However, it has all the functions of a central bank, and like the Bank of England, the Fed is designed to be privately owned and will reap enormous benefits from it. Unlike the First and Second Banks, 20% of the government's shares have been removed from the Fed's share structure, making it a "purely" private central bank.

In order to make the Federal Reserve System more deceptive, Paul ingeniously proposed, "Congress controls the Fed, the government has representatives on the board, but the majority of board members are directly or indirectly controlled by the banking association." Later, Paul changed the final version to "board members are appointed by the President of the United States," but the true function of the board is controlled by the Federal Advisory Council, which meets regularly with the board to "discuss" work. The members of the Federal Advisory Council will be decided by the directors of the 12 Federal Reserve Banks, a fact deliberately concealed from the public.

Another difficulty Paul had to deal with was how to conceal the fact that New York bankers would dominate the Fed. Since the 19th century, the vast majority of small and medium-sized businessmen and farmers in the Midwest and West have been devastated by banking crises and deeply resented Eastern bankers. It is inconceivable that congressmen from these areas would support a central bank dominated by New York bankers. For this reason, Paul designed a genius solution consisting of 12 regional banks that make up the entire system. Outside banking circles, few understand that proposing to establish regional reserve banks, while the issuance of U.S. currency and credit is highly concentrated in the New York area is nothing more than creating the illusion that the business of the central bank is not centralized in New York. "

[Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

The book "Currency War" has a total of twelve chapters. If six people translate two chapters each, it only takes two days to complete the translation.

The book "货币战争 Currency War" might be available for borrowing at some university libraries in the United States, and the paperback version of the book can be purchased on online shopping websites. The fastest delivery usually takes about 4-5 days to reach some cities in the United States.

Behind each chapter of this book, there is an extensive list of English references.

This book can help Americans rediscover America and Europeans rediscover Europe.

The chapters on "Currency War" are as follows:

Chapter One: The Rothschild Family – Europe's Singular Power

1.1 Napoleon's Waterloo and Rothschild's Triumphal Arch

1.2 The Era of Rothschild's Rise

1.3 The First Fortune of the Rothschilds

1.4 Nathan Dominates the City of London

1.5 James Conquers France

1.6 Solomon Aims for Austria

1.7 Germany and Italy Under the Rothschild Coat of Arms

1.8 The Rothschild Financial Empire

1.9 Summary of Chapter One

Chapter Two: The Century-Long War Between International Bankers and American Presidents

2.1 The Assassination of President Lincoln

2.2 Monetary Issuance and the American Revolutionary War

2.3 International Bankers' First War: The First Bank of the United States (1791-1811)

2.4 International Bankers Resurge: The Second Bank of the United States (1816-1832)

2.5 "The Bank wants to kill me, but I will kill the Bank."

2.6 A New Front: The Independent Financial System

2.7 International Bankers Strike Again: The Panic of 1857

2.8 The Causes of the American Civil War: European International Financial Power

2.9 Lincoln's Currency Revolution

2.10 Lincoln's Alliance with Russia

2.11 Who was the Real Assassin of Lincoln

2.12 Deadly Compromise: The National Banking Act of 1863

2.13 Summary of Chapter Two

Chapter Three: The Federal Reserve – A Private Central Bank

3.1 The Mysterious Jekyll Island: Birthplace of the Federal Reserve

3.2 The Wall Street Seven Titans: Behind-the-Scenes Drivers of the Federal Reserve

3.3 The Prelude to Establishing the Federal Reserve: The 1907 Banking Crisis

3.4 From Gold Standard to Fiat Currency: The Major Shift in Banking Worldview

3.5 The Smoke of the 1912 Election

3.6 Plan B
3.7 The Passage of the Federal Reserve Act, Bankers' Dream Come True
3.8 Who Owns the Federal Reserve
3.9 The First Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve
3.10 The Unknown Federal Advisory Council
3.11 Where is the Truth?
3.12 Conclusion
Chapter Four: "The Great War" and the Great Depression: Harvest Time for International Bankers
4.1 Without the Federal Reserve, There Would Be No World War I
4.2 War-Time Federal Reserve under Strong's Manipulation
4.3 "For Democracy and Moral Principles," Wilson Enters the War
4.4 Bankers Profiteering from the War
4.5 The Treaty of Versailles: A 20-Year Truce
4.6 "Shearing the Sheep" and the U.S. Agricultural Recession of 1921
4.7 The International Bankers' Conspiracy of 1927
4.8 The Bursting of the 1929 Bubble: Another Round of "Shearing the Sheep"
4.9 The Real Scheme behind Planning the Great Depression
4.10 Conclusion
Chapter Five: The "New Deal" of Cheap Currency
5.1 Keynes's "Cheap Currency"
5.2 The Presidential Election of 1932
5.3 Who was Franklin D. Roosevelt
5.4 Abandoning the Gold Standard: The Historical Mission Given to Roosevelt by Bankers
5.5 "Venture Capital" Chooses Hitler
5.6 Nazi Germany Sponsored by Wall Street
5.7 Expensive Wars and Cheap Currency
5.8 Conclusion
Chapter Six: The Elite Club that Rules the World
6.1 "Godfather" House, Colonel
6.2 The Bank for International Settlements: The Bank of Central Bankers
6.3 International Monetary Fund and World Bank
6.4 The Elite Group that Rules the World
6.5 The Bilderberg Group
6.6 The Trilateral Commission
6.7 Conclusion
Chapter Seven: The Final Struggle of Honest Currency
7.1 Executive Order 11110: Kennedy's Death Warrant
7.2 The Historical Status of Silver Dollars
7.3 The End of the Gold Standard
7.4 The Gold Pool
7.5 Special Drawing Rights
7.6 The Total Assault on the Gold Standard

<p>7.7 "Economic Hitmen" and the Return of Petrodollars</p> <p>7.8 Reagan's Assassination: The Last Hope of Shattering the Gold Standard</p> <p>7.9 Conclusion</p> <p>Chapter 8: The Unannounced Currency War</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8.1 The 1973 Middle East War: The Dollar's Counterattack - 8.2 Paul Volcker: The "Controlled Disintegration" of the World Economy - 8.3 The World Environmental Bank: Aiming to Enclose 30% of the Earth's Land - 8.4 Financial Nuclear Bomb: Target Tokyo - 8.5 Soros: Financial Hacker of International Bankers - 8.6 The "Arc of Crisis" Attacking European Currencies - 8.7 The Asian Currency Strangulation War - 8.8 A Parable of China's Future - 8.9 Conclusion <p>Chapter 9: The Dollar's Achilles' Heel and the Gold One-Yang Finger</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 9.1 Partial Reserve System: The Source of Inflation - 9.2 How Debt Dollars Are "Forged" - 9.3 America's "Debt Mountain" and Asia's "IOUs" - 9.4 The Monopoly Business of Financial Derivatives Markets - 9.5 Government-Sanctioned Entities: "The Second Fed" - 9.6 The Currency King Under House Arrest - 9.7 Level One Alert: Rothschild's Withdrawal from Gold Pricing in 2004 - 9.8 The Achilles' Heel of the Dollar Bubble Economy - 9.9 Conclusion <p>Chapter 10: Plotters for Eternity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 10.1 Currency: The Yardstick of the Economic World - 10.2 Gold and Silver: The Anchors in Price Turbulence - 10.3 Debt Currency Fat and GDP Slimming - 10.4 Finance Industry: The "Strategic Air Force" of China's Economic Development - 10.5 Future Strategies of Chinese Finance: "Build High Walls, Accumulate Grain Widely, and Delay Assuming Kingship" - 10.6 On the Road to Becoming the World's Reserve Currency - 10.7 Conclusion <p>Afterword: Some Thoughts on China's Financial Opening</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 11.1 The Greatest Risk of China's Financial Opening Is the Lack of "War" Consciousness - 11.2 Sovereignty or Stability: Which is More Important for Currency? - 11.3 Currency Appreciation and "Endocrine Disorders" in the Financial System - 11.4 External Line Operations Under Equitable Opening - 11.5 Avoiding Exchange Controls by the People is Better than Avoiding Gold by the People <p>Attachment: US Debt Implosion and Global Liquidity Contraction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 12.1 Crisis Redux - 12.2 Asset Securitization and Excessive Liquidity
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 12.3 Subprime and ALT-A Mortgages: Toxic Assets - 12.4 Subprime Mortgage CDOs: Concentrated Toxic Assets - 12.5 "Synthetic CDOs": High-Purity Concentrated Toxic Assets - 12.6 Asset Rating Agencies: Accomplices in Fraud - 12.7 Debt Implosion and Liquidity Contraction - 12.8 The Future of the World Financial Markets
<p>3 8</p>	<p>Question from US Secretary of Commerce Raymond</p> <p>Raymondo, once the first female governor of Rhode Island, now serves as the Secretary of Commerce in the United States. Raymondo has a profound personal experience with the decline of American manufacturing. She often recalls how her father lost his job at Bulova watch factory after 28 years of service when the company moved its production line to the Far East. In a speech in 2021, she said, "The fact is, what happened to my father is not uncommon. Over the past 40 years, this has happened to millions of American families, and it's part of a larger issue of declining capital investment in American workers and industry."</p> <p>That experience was part of why she accepted Biden's invitation to become the Secretary of Commerce—to rebuild American manufacturing. Raymondo said, "Technological change is happening faster than ever before, which means I have to wake up every day and ask myself, 'Are we doing enough?'" She emphasizes that the U.S. will spare no effort to expand restrictions on high-tech exports, protect Americans, and prevent China from acquiring advanced chips and manufacturing equipment.</p> <p>Secretary Raymondo herself is diligent and intelligent, and I admire her dedication. However, she shouldn't make such mistakes. Perhaps she overlooked the impact of the falsified and constructed European and global history and economic history by Western missionaries on American national philosophy and guiding economic theory. She may not understand the role of ethics in economics and find it challenging to properly examine America's future from a historical perspective. Export restrictions will only shrink the U.S. market for advanced chips and lead to technological breakthroughs. Today's America is actually controlled by Jewish capital, and it cannot overturn deeply flawed Western philosophical and economic theories. In addition, rebuilding new economic operational theories in America will be challenging.</p> <p>Raymondo failed to grasp the extreme self-interest of private capital. Even if China were to achieve a socialist system or a 4.0 version of the Tang Dynasty's equal-field system, several years ago, I saw some profit-oriented social organizations transferring chemical and pharmaceutical capital and entrepreneurs from China to India. They simply did not consider the national interest or create job opportunities for the domestic population. However, when they invested in India, they ended up suffering heavy losses. A friend of mine said these people were ashamed to even talk about their painful experiences in India. They forgot the crucial role of national moral standards,</p>

public moral standards, and self-discipline in investment decisions. In the last century, India arbitrarily took a line drawn by the British as the China-Indian border, encroaching on Chinese territory and constantly provoking China. How could Indian businessmen not take advantage of the opportunity to turn the wealth of Chinese investors in India into their own? Most of the trade between Chinese and Indian merchants requires Indians to pay the full amount before the goods are shipped, otherwise they may incur losses.

Secretary Raymondo should not blame China for accepting investments and industrial transfers that led to her father's unemployment and brought unforgettable pain to her family. This is an inevitable outcome of neoliberal economics centered on private capital guiding national governance in the United States. This theory has also become mainstream in China, leading to severe outflows of industries and capital from China.

It appears that the core officials involved in policy-making at the U.S. Department of Commerce may predominantly come from liberal arts backgrounds, lacking a foundation in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines. Moreover, they seem to lack creativity and innovation, with a limited understanding of the principles and dynamics of technology and industry. This situation has led not only to the Trump administration's imposition of restrictions on the sale of advanced chips or other high-tech electronic products to China, but also to the Biden administration continuing such policies. There is even a demand for the Netherlands, the producer of the most cutting-edge EUV lithography machines, refrain from selling to China, for political reasons rather than technical ones. The Trump administration has appointed individuals with questionable ethics to government positions, resulting in the formulation of strict chip restriction policies. In the Biden administration's governance in this area, the lack of experts with high moral and professional standards makes it difficult to avoid perpetuating unreasonable policies.

I can fully understand Raymond's efforts to increase employment in the United States, but if the goal is really to boost employment, the first step should be to increase the presence of highly innovative STEM professionals in the Department of Commerce, rather than imposing export bans.

If I were an expert in advanced manufacturing industry, the moment I heard the US government issue a ban on sales, I would be extremely excited. This is because new market opportunities created by U.S. political parties and government are emerging. The way to solve problems surely isn't limited to existing technologies. I would immediately look for new ways to address the issue and organize a team to deal with it. Just like in drug synthesis, there is always a new, more efficient synthesis pathway waiting to be discovered. The obsolescence of the cumbersome EUV lithography machines from the Netherlands is inevitable, and the responsibility should lie with the United States.

3 If China's current socialist regime collapses under the influence of
9 privatization and marketization from the United States, Europe, and Japan,
with a large amount of state capital and financial assets being privatized, a
situation similar to the end of the Tang Dynasty could reoccur. In this case,
China would inevitably produce new leaders, akin to Huang Chao uprising (黄
巢起义), leading armies and people to thoroughly eradicate China's corrupt
elements, eliminate extreme profiteers who have turned state assets into
private ones, and purge all evil tycoons (chaebol or plutocrat or financial
oligarch) and politicians. When the Chinese military no longer believes in
communism and is not bound by the Party's charter, any government capable
of ruling China will likely implement an improved version of the equal-field
system of the early Tang Dynasty. In such a scenario, China could establish a
society similar to a 4.5 or 5.0 version of the equal-field system. In this
backdrop, China would not tolerate any provocations as it does now. Any
country or organization that dared to provoke China would face immediate
retaliation. If the U.S. continues to provoke in the South China Sea and the
Taiwan Strait, crossing moral boundaries, China will undoubtedly retaliate. If
Japan dares to wage war against China, China will unite with Russia to destroy
Japan in retaliation for the Japanese atrocities that **killed at least 51.80-89.60
(100.80) million Chinese and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20)
million Chinese women**. If the U.S. and NATO go to war with China, China will
purge all tycoons (chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch) and evil
politicians from the aforementioned countries, just as Huang Chao uprising (黄
巢起义) did.

Even if the ruling party is not the Communist Party, this is an inevitable historical
process. If the U.S. or Jewish people force China to change its social system from
socialism (**4.0 version of the equal-field system**) to another system, changing
the name of the ruling party from the Communist Party, and plundering China's
wealth, when the Chinese people lack the religious-like system and charter of
the Communist Party, based on Chinese historical views, China is far more aware
than other countries of the dangers posed by the Tang Dynasty's tycoons to
peace. China would have no choice but to mobilize globally, similar to **Huang
Chao uprising (黄巢起义)**, to eliminate Jewish tycoons and other evil tycoons
(chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch) who instigate war. It's important to
note that China has the ability to fight on three fronts simultaneously. Once
pushed onto the battlefield, China will explicitly fight alongside Russia,
combined with armed forces in the Middle East, potentially eliminating all
tycoons (**chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch**) in Europe. Therefore,
attempting to change China from an ideological standpoint is extremely foolish.
Many people are very dissatisfied with the current weakness of China, and many
hope that Japan will actively provoke China, leading to the destruction of the
most evil Japan globally. From a historical perspective, **China's system is
essentially a 4.0 version of the equal-field system (socialist system) of the early
Tang Dynasty**, an advanced and equitable system that requires improvement in

	<p>the governance of officials and handling complex affairs. In contrast, the U.S. system resembles that of the late Tang Dynasty, a backward system. Historically, China understands the inevitability of the replacement of the U.S. system with a new one (4.0 version of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty). Why then should China adhere to the fully marketized late Tang system of the United States? It is worth noting that the Tang Dynasty's financial system was even more prosperous in some aspects than that of the United States today.</p> <p>To reiterate, if the United States demands China to change Marx's terminology in the ideological field, it would demonstrate that American universities lack expertise in political economy, history, and economics, making them very naive in the diplomatic arena. The United States needs to quickly abandon fabricated and fictitious European history and global history, European and global economic history, and abandon religions (Judaism, Christianity, Catholicism, Protestantism) based on the fictional Bible.</p>
40	<p>Russia is too vast, with a complex surrounding environment, significant external pressure, and many historical legacy issues. President Putin's ability to maintain Russia's current situation is extremely challenging. If someone else were to become president, perhaps Russia would have already split apart.</p> <p>Russia's future social system should choose either a socialist system or an improved version 4.0 (or higher) of the equal-field system (均田制) of the early Tang Dynasty in China to align with future trends.</p> <p>If Russia continues to choose a market-oriented capitalist system in the future, it will inevitably lead to the dissolution of the state.</p> <p>The choice of Russia's national system should be determined through a referendum by Russian citizens, rather than being decided by the president or parliament, as it would otherwise face considerable criticism both domestically and internationally.</p> <p>At the end of June 1994, President Yeltsin announced that 70% of Russia's industrial enterprises had been privatized, with 40 million Russians becoming shareholders. However, sociological surveys indicate that most people do not feel like "true owners" as a result of privatization. Only 700,000 to 900,000 individuals have actually benefited from privatization, with a tiny minority reaping the largest rewards—less than 2,000 people at the top of the pyramid. In April 1993, 15% of Russian residents surveyed believed that "securities privatization" could make them owners, a figure that briefly rose to 19% by the end of 1993 but then fell to 9.6% a year later. Meanwhile, 64% of Russians believed that privatization was merely a "political maneuver" incapable of solving real problems. This skepticism stems from the fact that most shareholders are unable to participate in business management, and only a negligible number actually receive dividends. In 1994, only 4% to 5% of shareholders began to receive dividends, and in reality, due to the majority of enterprises being either closed or operating at minimal capacity, the term "shareholder" became virtually meaningless.</p>

The results of Russia's privatization of state-owned assets have shown that:

The essence of neoliberal economics: economics that achieves an 80/20 distribution of social wealth benefits.

The Essence of an Adequate Market for All State Assets (The essence of a sufficient market for all national assets:): The Economics of Achieving an 80/20 Return Distribution of Social Wealth.

The Essence of Adequate Markets in the National Financial Industry: Economics and Finance to Achieve an 80/20 Income Distribution of Social Wealth.

Where is the general equilibrium theory and neoliberal economics? Not in the trash can?

This is a question that even high school students can answer. Why is it that undergraduates, PhDs, and professors who have received university education do not understand it? How can they use incorrect theories to guide a country's economic operations? Aren't global universities' paid global rankings harmful and misleading to the public?

Moreover, these rankings of global universities, which are expensive, promote vanity and self-deception, and mislead the global public, should bear the responsibility for misleading the public. Such rankings should be immediately abolished globally, and those primarily responsible for using rankings to mislead the global public through charging should face the necessary criminal penalties. Which statesman can propose an international consensus or a UN convention on the subject?

This article, based on in-depth historical research, provides a historical inevitability reference for President Putin and Russia to continue to implement either an improved version 4.0 of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty in China or a socialist system.

However, the long-term implementation of such a system must completely prohibit charitable and trust funds as tax avoidance tools. It is necessary to establish reasonable inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax collection policies, while exempting any annual taxes on basic family housing.

Funds from any charitable foundation can only remain in the foundation for a maximum of four years and must be donated to recipients in need within that time frame. It is absolutely forbidden to deceive the public through fraudulent charitable foundations or to evade taxes. Offenders will be fined ten times the amount involved, and all individuals involved will be publicly disclosed in the country for two years without any mosaic obscuring. Monthly spending is limited to no more than \$3000 for a period of five years, during which time flying on airplanes and high-speed trains is prohibited **(All family members of the person involved in the case)**. If the amount involved exceeds \$30 million but is less than \$60 million, flying on airplanes and high-speed trains is prohibited for ten years **(All family members of the person involved in the case)**. If the

	<p>amount involved exceeds \$60 million but is less than \$100 million, flying on airplanes and high-speed trains is prohibited for 15 years (All family members of the person involved in the case). If the amount involved exceeds \$100 million but is less than \$200 million, flying on airplanes and high-speed trains is prohibited for 30 years (All family members of the person involved in the case). If the amount involved exceeds \$200 million, in addition to a fine of five times the amount, future estate and gift taxes will be levied at a minimum rate of 50%. The exemption amount for each direct descendant is \$1 million, with no exemption for others.</p>
<p>4 1</p>	<p>The reasons for the collapse of the former Soviet social system: Lenin died prematurely, and his successors were too arrogant, vain, greedy, corrupt, or short-sighted. They formulated a series of erroneous political, economic, diplomatic, and military policies. Relevant leaders and leadership lacked in-depth studies of world history and religion, with fabricated European history obscuring their eyes. The government lacked a reasonable negative feedback mechanism to correct deviations.</p> <p>Stalin's most egregious mistake was the massacre of hundreds of thousands of innocent Chinese civilians. Not only did he fail to follow Lenin's advice to return the Chinese territory unjustly ceded through unequal treaties by the Tsar to China, but he also splintered Mongolia from China, creating what he called a buffer zone. Stalin's vision was inferior to that of Lenin and Mao Zedong. By not returning these territories to China as Lenin suggested, his successors Khrushchev, Brezhnev, and Gorbachev, with even lower prestige, philosophical acumen, and poorer strategic foresight, it is difficult to proactively return these territories to China. This inevitably led to a persistent global wariness of the Soviet Union. Despite being China's closest ally, sharing the same social system, and jointly opposing the United States and the West, the Soviet Union refused to return Chinese territories unfairly acquired through unequal treaties. How could Western and European countries eliminate their wariness against the Soviet Union? The highest ability of a country's leader lies in foresight and strategic planning. The Soviet Union had a small population but vast territory, while China had a large population but the lowest arable land per capita globally. China's successful repelling of the forces of 16 countries during the Korean War demonstrated its remarkable strength. China could have fully supported the Soviet Union against its northern enemy Japan. Stalin should not have allowed Mongolia to splinter from China and declare independence, nor should he have failed to return the territories unjustly taken by unequal treaties to China. However, Stalin's narrow and erroneous actions laid the groundwork for the later dissolution of the Soviet Union. Due to the control of international bankers over the United States and Europe, with hopes of global conflict, NATO expansion to the east was inevitable, leading to a severe depletion of Soviet national strength.</p> <p>The former Soviet Union poured a lot of money and military support into evil</p>

Vietnam to counter China, which goes against an important principle: those with extremely poor morals should never become important partners or friends! At most, only unavoidable limited trade in goods can be conducted, and the transaction method must be guarded against traps. Just because a country's ruling party has the words "Communist Party" in its name does not mean it is a partner. It's like wearing human clothes; speaking, walking, and acting like a human doesn't necessarily make one human. Many evil criminals are just dressed in nice clothes. Some people, although nominally human, are actually worse than pigs.

China, facing extreme difficulties, provided Vietnam with \$20.9 billion in unconditional aid from the 1950s to the early 1970s, which is now worth at least \$3.09 trillion. Vietnam's so-called founding father, Ho Chi Minh, and others, had dark and evil hearts. Whenever they lacked money, food, or equipment, they ran to Beijing to find Zhou Enlai and Mao Zedong, like lions opening their mouths, demanding unconditional assistance, disregarding the fact that China was also extremely poor at that time. However, after Vietnam was unified, it began massacring Vietnamese Chinese, forcing each Chinese person to surrender 12 taels of gold, otherwise they would be killed. At least 2 million Chinese were driven into the sea, with at least 1.5 million deaths. The family of Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg's wife were survivors at the time. Such a country should be highly vigilant for the next three thousand years and should never be considered a close partner. Once this country becomes powerful, as its government documents told its military and officials in the 1970s, it aims not only to annex China but also to divide the territory of the United States. Greedy, arrogant, shameless, and evil Vietnam exhausted the last breath of the Soviet Union and accelerated its collapse. This national character, where "whoever provides milk is the mother," turning hostile and killing when faced with disagreement, is extremely evil, cunning, greedy, and shameless. Without full compensation for victims and affected countries, they should not be considered friends or partners at all.

In early November 1989, the author predicted the imminent collapse of Eastern Europe within six months. **On January 3, 1990, the author predicted the dissolution of the Soviet Union within two years and Gorbachev's ousting.** During my time as a graduate student, none of my classmates wanted to believe it. Even at about 7 a.m. in late June 1991, a dormitory mate questioned me about this issue. I told him to wait for the results in six months. Shortly after, the Soviet Union witnessed the "August Coup," and Gorbachev and his wife were placed under house arrest in Crimea. In December of the same year, the former Soviet Union officially declared dissolution.

The Treaty of Nerchinsk signed in 1689 stipulated that the south of the Outer Xing'an Mountains, including the whole Heilongjiang River basin, belongs to Chinese territory in both the interior and northeast regions. However, in

1858, more than a hundred years after the signing of the treaty, the Russian Empire took advantage of China's internal and external troubles and forced the Chinese side to sign the unequal Treaty of Aigun, which ceded the left bank area of the Heilongjiang River and designated the right bank of the Ussuri River to the mouth of the Heilongjiang River as a jointly administered area between China and Russia. In 1860, Tsarist Russia forced the Qing government to sign an unequal treaty called the **China-Russia** Beijing Treaty, which further established the occupation of the left bank area of Heilongjiang Province and completely classified the China-Russia co-administered area as Russian territory under the Aihui Treaty. The Beijing Treaty also resulted in a large area of territory originally belonging to China in the northwest being later classified as Russian territory.

However, the China-Russia Aihui Treaty also stipulates that: "On the left bank of Heilongjiang, from the south of the Jingqili River to Xi'ermolejin Tun, the original Manchus and others are allowed to reside permanently in their respective Tun, and are still managed by Manchu ministers and officials. Russians and others are friendly and cannot infringe upon." This means that China has permanent residency and jurisdiction in the 64 Tun area of Jiangdong. "In the Beijing Treaty between China and Russia, it is stipulated that "the land mentioned above is open land. In the event of Chinese settlements or fishing and hunting areas occupied by the Chinese people, Russia shall not occupy them, and the Chinese people are allowed to continue fishing and hunting as usual." These provisions are guarantees for the rights and interests of the Chinese people in the Northeast region, in line with the object and purpose of the treaty.

Russia obtained millions of square kilometers of land from China through the two unequal treaties mentioned above, but it seriously violated its important obligations under the treaties, which is inconsistent with the purpose and purpose of the treaties. In 1900, the Russian military and police caused a shocking massacre in Hailanpao and Jiangdong 64th Tun, killing tens of thousands of Chinese people. Afterwards, they forcibly occupied Jiangdong 64th Tun and prevented Chinese people from returning to live. Tsarist Russia has also expelled and massacred a large number of Chinese people in other northeastern regions such as Hailanpao, with a total number of victims exceeding 300,000.

The actions of the Russian authorities seriously violate the rights and interests of China in the 64 villages of Jiangdong in the China-Russia Aihui Treaty, as well as the provisions of the China-Russia Beijing Treaty that prohibit the occupation and infringement of Chinese residential and fishing grounds, and commit serious crimes against humanity and ethnic cleansing, which are seriously inconsistent with the purpose and purpose of the treaty.

During the Soviet era, the authorities continued to illegally occupy 64 villages in Jiangdong and carried out a large-scale purge of the local Chinese people in the Outer Northeast, occupying a large number of Chinese residential areas and fishing and hunting grounds. In 2014, literature reported that the

Soviet Union massacred about 300,000 Chinese during the Great Purge in the Far East in the 1930s and 1940s. In a documentary on Phoenix TV's Phoenix Vision program, Professor Larin, director of the Institute of History, Archaeology, and Ethnology of the Far East Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences in Vladivostok, personally said, "In 1938, all Asian residents, Chinese, and Koreans who came to the Far East were killed. According to 1989 statistics, in my opinion, there were only less than 2,000 Chinese people in the entire Far East. These actions by the Soviet authorities seriously violate the Beijing Treaty between China and Russia, as well as relevant international and domestic laws.

China's relevant case is the 1953 declaration by the Republic of China's legislative body to annul the China-Soviet Treaty of Friendship due to serious breaches by the Soviet Union, and it refused to recognize the independence of Outer Mongolia. At that time, the Republic of China was still a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council. In 1952, the United Nations General Assembly passed Resolution 505, entitled "Soviet Violations of the China-Soviet Treaty of Friendship of August 14, 1945, and of the Charter of the United Nations, Resulting in Threats to the Political Independence and Territorial Integrity of China and Peace in the Far East", also known as the "Control of the Soviet Case", which determined that the Soviet Union had seriously violated the China-Soviet Treaty of Friendship.

In addition to the sixty-four villages in Jiangdong, Russia and the Soviet Union carried out large-scale purges against the Chinese people in the Far East, occupying numerous residential and fishing areas of the Chinese. Many of these areas no longer have descendants of the original Chinese inhabitants, so China may have a legitimate claim to inherit rights to these lands. The rights of the sixty-four villages in Jiangdong are entirely justifiable for reclamation.

In summary, according to international law, China has the right to declare the termination of the two major unequal treaties that ceded Chinese territory—the China-Russia Aihui Treaty and the China-Russia Beijing Treaty. Abrogating these two treaties implies that China still has the right to assert sovereignty over the Far East.

The Russian ethnic group is part of China's 56 ethnic groups. Since the founding of the People's Republic of China by Chairman Mao and other older generation leaders, there has been a consistent emphasis on national unity. The implementation of the New Land Distribution System or socialist system also emphasizes national unity, which is completely different from the ethnic cleansing policies of the former Soviet Union. The wife of China's former air force commander, Liu Yalou, is Russian, and General Lin Hu, a former deputy air force commander, has Russian ancestry. If China had followed the cleansing model of the former Soviet Union, they would not have been able to become commanders or deputy commanders of the Chinese Air Force. This shows that China has a very trusting relationship with its ethnic minorities.

If Russia returns territories unjustly taken from China through unequal

treaties, including the Sakhalin Island and Vladivostok, Russians residing in these territories can freely choose their nationality. If they choose to stay in China, they will not be mistreated. Of course, the Southern Kuril Islands are a result of the Soviet Union's victory in World War II. **Evil Japanese raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women and killed at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people in China**, and not destroying Japan is already generous treatment. These four islands belong to the victorious country, Russia.

If Russia were to return the lands previously taken from China by unequal treaties during the Tsarist era, at least 85% of parliamentarians would need to agree, or there would have to be a nationwide referendum for public consent. This not only conforms to dialectical logic philosophically but also, in fact, benefits Russia more than it costs. It would be advantageous for the Russians living in those territories and would prevent other opposition forces, both internal and external, from finding additional excuses. Once such a framework is established, the threat to Russia's Northwest region from countries like Japan would be significantly reduced, allowing for a substantial reduction in military numbers and facilitating the concentration of forces to enhance military quality.

Russia lacks political foresight and committed extremely significant strategic errors in the Russo-Ukrainian War:

Chinese culture emphasizes that if a country engages in war, it should do so from a position of righteousness and morality; otherwise, war should not be initiated because unjust warfare could lead to the downfall of the nation. **From a strategic standpoint, the Russian leadership and think tanks lack political foresight and strategic vision.**

Despite numerous killings of ethnic Russians by Ukraine in places like Donetsk and other regions, prompting Russia's decision to intervene, mainstream global media controlled by Jewish interests selectively report, making it difficult for Russia's voice to be synchronized and disseminated globally. However, if in the initial stages of the conflict, instead of seizing Ukrainian territory, Russia had conducted an **"anti-virus operations,"** concentrating its superior airborne divisions and brigades, and coordinating with ground forces to immediately secure several Ukrainian-American biological research facilities near the Russian-Ukrainian border, obtaining firsthand evidence of large-scale lethal viruses, bacteria, cholera, plague, African swine fever, or biochemical or genetic weapons, capturing all Ukrainian and non-Ukrainian researchers, and inviting journalists from several countries to report globally. In that case, the United States and the Ukrainian government would immediately find themselves in an extremely passive situation, and the Russia-Ukraine war would not be sustainable for more than a year. It would also be challenging for European countries to continue collectively supplying weapons to Ukraine. Russia would have firmly controlled the situation at a very low cost, rather than falling into a moral disadvantage.

Moreover, countries researching **biochemical or genetic weapons** would face condemnation from most countries worldwide, and a few days of **"anti-virus operations"** would bring lasting peace to Russia, Ukraine, and Europe. Ukraine would not become a dumping ground for outdated weapons sold by the United States, the United Kingdom, and other countries. Although the current war situation is dragging Europe into a protracted conflict, exhausting European strength, Russia's economy still seems to be growing. However, for Europe and the United States controlled by super interest groups, prolonged warfare forces Europe and the United States to deplete their military arsenals, yielding huge profits. Warfare necessitates the expenditure of funds, and under the fully marketized systems of Western countries, **super-banking giants can gain massive profits and would prefer war to continue.**

Prolonged warfare will turn Ukraine, a Slavic nation, into ruins, deepening mutual grievances between the parties. Originally, Russia might have been able to bring Ukraine back into its fold without launching large-scale warfare, but now Russia cannot gain European acceptance even after reclaiming four regions through a public referendum. European countries inevitably perceive Russia as continuously aggressive and expansionist, and this fear and public opinion bias are hard to dispel. **Therefore, to a large extent, the Russia-Ukraine war represents a significant strategic mistake for Russia.**

In this war of attrition, Zelensky, a former actor, essentially gave away Ukraine's land to Jewish groups for free. Due to the massive casualties of Ukrainian soldiers and insufficient manpower, Zelensky even demanded that pregnant women and patients go to the battlefield, completely disregarding the ethics of life. Such a brutal president could have been wiped out in China long ago. Under Zelensky's strategy of population attrition, once the Slavic population in Ukraine is exhausted, Zelensky, of Jewish descent, may introduce large numbers of Jews into Ukraine, prolonging the war between Russia and Ukraine indefinitely. Russia would be forced into a long-term war situation, and only the full integration of Ukraine into Russia in the future could relieve Ukraine of its heavy burden. Even so, the reconstruction of Ukraine in the future would be a huge burden.

Last year, Russia revealed that the United States was conducting research on anti-human super viruses and other biological weapons in Ukraine. A U.S. biological laboratory in Ukraine has destroyed a batch of dangerous virus samples and related documents. Russia immediately intervened upon discovery and successfully confiscated the relevant documents, which detailed the viruses ordered for destruction by the United States, including lymphatic plague and other highly dangerous and highly contagious viruses. Unfortunately, Russia messed up by failing to capture bioweapons researchers, making it difficult for the public to focus on this global event.

Russia's leadership has disregarded the fields of defense behavioral economics, military behavioral economics, or war behavioral economics to guide defense and military actions, which probably would not have led to the

type of war favored by international financiers, nor would it have entailed military spending of at least \$200 billion. Russian higher-ups have also overlooked the use of metrological political party ethics, metrological political ethics, and metrological governmental ethics, as well as the grading of politicians to compare the levels of evil politicians, in order to curb the occurrence of large-scale wars.

President Zelensky of Ukraine, with his low moral standards, attempted to resolve Ukraine's ethnic conflicts by massacring ethnic Russians in eastern Ukraine. Unexpectedly, President Putin inevitably ordered an invasion to strike Ukraine, resulting in enormous losses estimated at more than \$500 billion due to the military actions of both sides. Zelensky not only lacks governing experience and moral integrity but also seems to be attempting to deplete the adult civilian population internally. In Ukraine's conscription last year, even pregnant women are now being conscripted, which constitutes a serious crime against humanity. The government and parties of Ukraine should be evaluated using metrological political party ethics.

If President Putin wants to maintain stability in Russia and world peace, he should request the leadership of different institutions in Russia to collectively read Song Hongbing's **Currency War in order to gain a new understanding for the world.** [Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

If President Putin wants to promote the development of Russia and world peace, he should not only require the leadership of various institutions in Russia to read the history of the Tang Dynasty and the late Ming Dynasty in China, but also demand that all the people read it. And, in reading, from political, managerial, financial, and economic perspectives, compare the current situation in the United States, guiding people to discover the advantages of the improved version of the equal-field system in early Tang China that conforms to the social historical process. Discuss the similarities between the current social system in the United States and the fully marketized system controlled by financial oligarchs in the late Tang Dynasty. Thus, at a new level of understanding, recognize the inevitability of the **Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义)** comprehensively clearing the financial oligarchs and politicians of the Tang Dynasty, promoting social progress. This will enable all Russians to fully understand ideologically: the historical inevitability of a country controlled by financial oligarchs leading to destruction under a fully marketized system, and if Russia were to return to the socialist system, reducing corruption among officials through the system, it could stabilize and develop Russia. If Russia can grasp the main contradictions, it will inevitably solve the core problems threatening peace.

The **Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义)** also had a profound impact on peasant wars in later generations. Although this uprising ultimately failed, it spurred

	<p>peasant struggles across various regions and dealt a heavy blow to the decayed rule of the Tang Dynasty. The spirit of these struggles and resistance inspired later generations to strive for freedom and justice. Moreover, the Huang Chao Uprising disrupted the balance between the central government and regional powers, as well as the mutual constraints between regional powers, sweeping away the aristocratic clan system that had persisted since the Wei and Jin dynasties and bringing new changes to Chinese history. The Huang Chao Uprising at the end of the Tang Dynasty not only had a tremendous impact at the time, but also revealed the intensification of social contradictions and the deepening of ruling crises, while also reflecting the determination and courage of the people to resist oppression and pursue justice and equality.</p> <p>Chairman Mao Zedong once said, "The eyes of the masses are bright." When all Russian people have learned, they will naturally engage in extensive discussions and comparisons, discovering problems and seeking the laws of history, which is far stronger than a directive issued by the president or the parliament.</p> <p>If Russia hopes to avoid a series of serious problems that could arise from the death of Stalin's successor, Russia and Putin should consider Lieutenant General Konashenkov (Игорьь Коначенков), who possesses outstanding character, composure, courage, and insight, as a candidate for inspection, and should initiate early replacements and position training.</p>
4 2	<p>China's most famous prime minister, Guan Zhong once said, "商贾在朝则货财上流，妇人言事则赏罚不信，男女无别则民无廉耻。" This passage of ancient Chinese text is often misinterpreted. The English translation of the three sentences is as follows: "When merchants hold power in the court, bribery of wealth and goods infiltrates the upper echelons. When women discuss state affairs, rewards and punishments lose credibility; when there is no distinction between men and women, people lose their sense of shame. In today's world, it is entirely as Guan Zhong said 2000 years ago."</p> <p>Throw all the fictional and fabricated European, African, and world history created by Western missionaries into the garbage dump. Among all the figures in the Western world, whose wisdom and philosophical level can surpass that of the famous Chinese prime minister Guan Zhong?</p> <p>The current reality is that the U.S. government is controlled by financial oligarchs, and the nation itself is under their sway. The United States, ostensibly a country, is actually a corporation or amusement park masquerading as a nation, an alliance of capitalist interest groups where true control lies in the hands of capital or financial oligarchs. The media, finance, and police are entirely controlled by capital, and even the military is under its influence. There is no true democracy, freedom, or human rights in the United States. Since the end of April this year, the U.S. government and universities have swiftly suppressed protests by American university students against Israel's massacre of Palestinian women, children, and innocent civilians, as well as demonstrations where Israel directly extracts skin, eyes, and organs from</p>

Palestinians. More than a thousand students have been arrested, fully demonstrating that the United States fundamentally lacks democracy, freedom, and human rights. Yet the global mainstream media, controlled by financial oligarchs, instead accuses other countries of lacking democracy, freedom, and human rights. Officials of third grade or above

The Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义), where he led his army to kill almost all members of chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch (财阀) and officials of third grade or above of the late Tang Dynasty, proved the great harm that chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch (财阀) posed to the normal governance of the country. The great Huang Chao Uprising uprooted a cancer that had been endangering national governance for nearly 600 years. This demonstrated the foresight of the famous Chinese prime minister Guan Zhong. It provided a method of long-term stable governance for future generations to deal with government corruption and extreme chaos caused by the intervention of chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch in the country's affairs. History may continue to unfold strikingly similar scenes.

The Great Contribution and Inspiration of the Huang Chao Uprising to China

Huang Chao's life was a transformation from an ordinary person to a great figure. He could have lived a comfortable and prosperous life, but he chose to embark on a path filled with thorns and risks. Throughout the course of the rebellion, he constantly overcame difficulties, refined his thoughts, and ultimately created a glorious history. He was a fighter against financial magnates and bureaucratic rule, a passionate patriot, and a visionary politician. His contribution not only lies in the establishment of the Da Qi dynasty, but also in his proposition of the concept of "the world belongs to the public", which sparked people's thoughts on social justice, democracy, and freedom. His deeds inspired generations of revolutionaries and became a model of resistance against financial magnates and bureaucratic rule in Chinese history.

Because of his dissatisfaction with the imperial examination system and hatred of the corrupt rule of the aristocracy, Huang Chao embarked on the path of resisting financial magnates and bureaucrats. He once led a rebel army to attack Chang'an, but was quickly defeated by the Tang army. Wang Xianzhi's surrender led to a low morale among the rebel army, and many people began to waver. However, Huang Chao was not discouraged by these failures; he always maintained a resilient will to fight against evil forces. He regrouped, reorganized, and trained the rebel army to enhance its combat effectiveness. Huang Chao also devised the strategy of "picking soft persimmons", avoiding strong towns and successively occupying many prefectures and counties. The rise and fall of the rebel army tells us that the revolutionary path has never been smooth. Huang Chao's success lies not only in his strategy and perseverance, but also in his reform ideas. **He resolutely slaughtered the aristocratic families (Kill the entire family of the chaebol), eliminating their influence in the court,** and laying the foundation for the development of the imperial examination system

	<p>in later China. Although Huang Chao's bloody massacre was brutal, his rebellion changed the course of Chinese history.</p> <p>Causes of Huang Chao uprising:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Political Corruption: During the late Tang Dynasty, corruption among court officials was rampant, leading to the oppression of the people and their discontent. 2. Increased burden on farmers: Heavy taxation by the courts made the burden on farmers unbearable. At the same time, the abuse of conscription worsened the farmers' plight. 3. Oppression by local officials: Local authorities imposed heavy taxes, mistreated the people, and forced labor, sparking widespread discontent and resistance among farmers. 4. External Threats: The Tang Dynasty faced threats from foreign invaders, leading to excessive military spending and further burdening the people.
<p>4 3</p>	<p>In today's world, morality is in decline, the legal system is just like a child's play, and it seems as if the Earth has regressed by at least 4,999 years. The only super-sized concentration camp in the world, besieging three million people, has been established by Israel for several years. Even when Israel is under global scrutiny for slaughtering 34,000 women, children, and the poor, the U.S. government surprisingly does not consider Israel guilty of the massacre. It supports the swift arrest of students and teachers from Columbia University who oppose Israel's slaughter, making many around the world question the authenticity of American freedom, democracy, and human rights. At present, the US national debt has reached \$34 trillion, on the brink of collapse, leaving only five possible ways for the US to temporarily escape this predicament.</p> <p>First, a spontaneous uprising within the U.S. similar to Putin's approach, purging all oligarchs meddling in government affairs and all politicians engaging in exchanges with them. Simultaneously, the establishment of a global convention on inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, to which all nations must adhere, prohibiting any tax evasion through charitable foundations and trust investments. Prohibit any company from listing or avoiding taxes by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc.</p> <p>Second, an internal uprising similar to Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义), directly eliminating all members of oligarchic families meddling in government affairs and all politicians associated with them, confiscating all assets of oligarchs and affiliated politicians. Concurrently establishing a global convention for inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, with all nations mandated to comply, and banning any tax evasion through charitable foundations and trust investments. Prohibit any company from listing or avoiding taxes by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc.</p> <p>Third, an internal uprising like Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义), directly</p>

eradicating all core members of oligarchic families meddling in government affairs and all politicians associated with them, stripping oligarchs of any inheritance rights and confiscating assets of both oligarchs and affiliated politicians. Simultaneously establishing a global convention for inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, with all nations obliged to follow suit, and banning any tax evasion through charitable foundations and trust investments. Prohibit any company from listing or avoiding taxes by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc.

Fourth, aiding China in claiming compensation from Japan, sharing half of the proceeds to address the financial crisis, while concurrently establishing a global convention for inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, with all nations required to adhere to it, and prohibiting any tax evasion through charitable foundations and trust investments. Prohibit any company from listing or avoiding taxes by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc.

Fifth, assisting China in claiming reparations from other nations that have previously massacred Chinese people, securing wealth to delay the crisis. Simultaneously establishing a global convention for inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, with all nations mandated to comply, and prohibiting any tax evasion through charitable foundations and trust investments. Prohibit any company from listing or avoiding taxes by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc.

Sixth, if America's financial magnates and politicians can wake up quickly, with the magnates no longer engaging in quid pro quo with politicians to control the U.S. government, and returning both the Federal Reserve and the IRS to the American people, America simultaneously proposes the establishment of a global convention on inheritance tax, gift tax, expatriation tax, and personal income tax, prohibiting any charitable funds and trusts from tax avoidance. Prohibit any company from listing or tax avoidance by setting up offshore companies in locations such as the Cayman Islands, the British Virgin Islands, etc., and each country must adhere to this convention. In addition, establish a system for evaluating the integrity of politicians and quantitatively study their behavior by examining the frequency of lies and their integrity levels, ranking politicians on a 16-tier system. This objective assessment aims to identify and distinguish between poor and exemplary politicians, ultimately reducing the chances of dishonest politicians coming to power and swiftly kicking inferior politicians out of the governing team.

The U.S. government's attempts to harvest global wealth through fluctuations in interest rates have been exposed by almost all nations and have proved highly ineffective. If the US were to instigate a third world war under the instigation of oligarchs, seeking to gain through plunder, not only would the US be defeated and divided, but any possibility of resurgence would vanish. Should U.S. nuclear

	<p>weapons be removed from their launch pads, not only would U.S. oligarchs suffer, but all members of oligarchic families associated with officials would face extermination, just as during Huang Chao uprising (黄巢起义). Oligarchs or politicians who disagree with this article should gather at the frontlines of Russia and Ukraine or in areas of depleted uranium bomb explosions, and individually experience life for a month, to see how many can safely and healthily return.</p>
<p>4 4</p>	<p>Compared with Chinese history, the current moral, ethical, political, and political ethics of the United States, Israel, and the world have regressed by at least 2,000-4,000 years. Compared with Chinese history, Western missionaries' fabrication of European history, law, and religion has had serious consequences for world civilization and peace. The legal punishment rules and ideology formulated by Europe and the United States for serious crimes have set back global judicial ethics and morals for at least 2,000-4,000 years. Lawyers are more likely to absolve or reduce the guilt of offenders, leading to more intense disputes and killings. Human massacres have become more intense and frequent. Criminals not only go unpunished, but also mock innocent victims. What is even more tragic and cruel than ancient China is that the organs of innocent children, women, and civilians are harvested by criminals for profit. The politicians of the world's leading country, the United States, actually support Israel in imprisoning more than 1 million Palestinians in concentration camps in Gaza and support Israel in massacring innocent children, women, and civilians. This is completely unimaginable in Chinese history. If they were as brutal as Israeli and American politicians, they would ultimately be executed, and the country would be doomed.</p> <p>The future of Jews, Israel, and Israel's supporter, the United States, who implemented extreme laissez-faire economic models and unequal land distribution, and carried out brutal massacres against children and women.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The movement protesting against continued U.S. support for Israel's killing of women, children, and organ harvesting is irreversible. The future of the United States might see at least a division of the two major parties into four. 2. If the United States continues to support Israel in massacring civilians and plundering other countries' land and wealth, it will lead to the collapse of the U.S. economy. Once the U.S. military and public realize that they are being deceived and controlled by financial conglomerates, similar to the Huang Cao Rebellion at the end of the Tang Dynasty, all Jewish financial conglomerates, politicians supporting Jews, and other members of the major U.S. financial conglomerates will be executed. Then, globally, those members of the Jewish financial conglomerate who escaped will be hunted down. 3. Jewish interest groups will globalize the Russia-Ukraine war. Russia is likely to recognize the harm Jewish financial conglomerates pose to humanity, similar to Stalin, and will initiate targeted strikes globally, with the primary goal of eliminating Jewish financial conglomerates and politicians bought by them. 4. Some Jews will realize that their ethnicity is fabricated, that there is no blood

	<p>relationship among Jews. Some Jews who oppose Israel's slaughter of Palestinian women, children, and organ harvesting will immediately abandon their fictional Bible-based religious beliefs and join other ethnic groups. The remaining members of the Jewish financial conglomerate pursuing extreme interests will be cleared out by the awakened US military and public.</p> <p>5. Oppressed countries awakening to Israeli oppression will make eradicating Jewish financial conglomerate members their main goal as weapons like thermobaric bombs improve.</p> <p>6. If the United States or Jews force China into a global war, China, more than any other country, understands the danger financial oligarchs posed during the Tang Dynasty and will have to eliminate the Jewish financial conglomerates responsible for the war.</p> <p>7. If the United States or Israel dares to use nuclear weapons, all the financial oligarch families of the United States, Israel, and Jews will become dust.</p>
<p>4 5</p>	<p>《管子·立政》：君之所慎者四：一曰大德不至仁，不可以授国柄。二曰见贤不能让，不可与尊位。三曰罚避亲贵，不可使主兵。四曰不好本事，不务地利，而轻赋敛，不可与都邑。此四务者，安危之本也。</p> <p>The most famous prime minister in ancient China, who lived 2600 years ago, once said that the state should be cautious about four issues: first, those who profess morality but do not truly practice benevolence should not be entrusted with great power; second, for anyone who meets a person of virtue and talent but cannot humble himself, he should not bestow upon him a high title; third, those who do not punish guilty relatives or nobles should not be allowed to command armies; fourth, those who do not prioritize agricultural production, fail to develop land for profit, and easily impose taxes should not be appointed as administrators.</p>
<p>4 6</p>	<p>中国第一著名宰相管仲曾说：“正法直度，罪杀不赦，杀戮必信，民畏而惧。武威既明，令不再行。”就是：法律公正，制度明确；杀有罪，不宽赦；执行刑罚一定说到做到，民众就会畏惧。权威明示于众，法律就不必一再重申。</p> <p>The most famous prime minister in ancient China, who lived 2600 years ago, once said that Justice in law, clarity in systems; guilt shall be punished, no amnesty granted. When penalties are enforced consistently, the populace will fear. Authority demonstrated openly, laws need not be reiterated incessantly.</p> <p>Japan is the world's largest war criminal country, and all Japanese are war criminals and criminals. The Japanese army killed at least 51.8-89.6 (100.80) million Chinese and raped or gang-raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.2) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights in Port Arthur, the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, with only 36 survivors, China's population loss reached 280 million.</p> <p>Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth at least 4 billion yuan in China, looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics</p>

	<p>worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion US dollars, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollars, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth 114.4 billion US dollars, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth 420 billion US dollars, at least 1,233 million tons of food worth about 700 billion US dollars, at least 1,000 tons of platinum worth about 32.258-37.868 billion US dollars, at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion US dollars, at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about 18-23.4 billion US dollars, as well as 480 million pigs, sheep, chickens, and ducks, and 20 million head of cattle, horses, and donkeys. Additionally, 300 million houses were destroyed.</p> <p>After World War II, only a few dozen criminals were sentenced to death by the courts. The country that massacred more than 100 million Chinese people was not only not eradicated after the war, but also allowed to exist. Now, more than 90% of Japanese in Japan, the country that committed crimes, surprisingly detest the victim country, China. Is there still law and moral ethics in this world? Can we still achieve world peace and new equal field system at the global level?</p> <p>Never in the history of humanity has an evil country like the mongrel Japan slaughtered so many people -- excluding others like the Filipinos -- yet it has not been destroyed, nor has Japan been prohibited from having military forces, military aircraft, naval vessels, helicopter carriers, submarines, or military schools. This is a serious mistake, a grave consequence of Europe's falsification of history and law, and a result of the United States being controlled by financial oligarchs. Today, Japan is vigorously developing its military power, with its military strength ranking fifth in the world. The evil Japanese are releasing nuclear-contaminated water directly into the sea to spread it around the world. Japan is the most evil creature in the whole universe, and a future world war is inevitable. In the future, if any country engages in aggressive warfare, the just nations of the world must utterly destroy that evil country, eradicating all the evil beings who started the aggression, to possibly achieve global peace.</p>
4 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a</p>

permanent consensus or convention.

The international community and the United Nations must identify and seize the primary contradictions leading to war or crime, fully recognizing that both war and crime are instigated by a greedy few. Strong measures must be taken to combat criminals who incite war or crime, firmly establishing the idea of eradicating a minority of criminals physically in exchange for long-term human peace. Strong measures should also be taken to curb the profiteering of criminals' relatives, politically implementing compression; otherwise, sustained peace in the world is unlikely.

Instigating and funding wars aligns with the fundamental interests of bankers, and the Rothschild family is no exception. Behind almost all modern wars, from the French Revolution to the Second World War, their influence can be discerned. The Rothschild family is the largest creditor of the major Western developed countries today. Before her death, **Mrs. Rothschild once said, "If my sons did not want wars, there would be none."**

Rothschild: "As long as I can control a country's currency issuance, I don't care who makes the law."

Banks and trust investment companies aggregate public assets, bear social responsibilities, and are also frequently utilized by criminals for money laundering. Accordingly, **the personal and familial assets of all chairpersons, vice-chairpersons, legal representatives, presidents or CEOs, vice-presidents, executives, directors, supervisors, and shareholders of all banks and trust investment companies worldwide, along with the total assets of their immediate three-generation relatives, must be disclosed globally, accessible to anyone through real-name authentication.**

A country can ratify this convention through three means: firstly, if a country's government signs it, it signifies the country's agreement to the convention; secondly, if a country's government abstains from signing, as long as half of the country's citizens log in with real names on the United Nations website and agree to ratify the convention; thirdly, if the number of individuals supporting this convention in a country surpasses the number of votes won by the winning candidate in the most populous presidential or prime ministerial election in that country in the last 100 years, it is considered that the country supports and agrees to the convention without the necessity for government signature. Subsequently, the government of that country must endorse the voters' decision and sign pertinent documents agreeing to the convention; otherwise, any bank in that country will be prohibited from engaging in transactions with banks or citizens of other countries, and any trust investment company in that country will be prohibited from conducting transactions with any institutions or individuals in other countries. If any bank or trust investment company worldwide refuses to publicly disclose the aforementioned information, any country reserves the right to freeze the assets of the said bank or trust investment company within its borders, and if the aforementioned bank or trust investment company fails

	<p>to disclose for more than one year, the frozen assets will be the property of the freezing country. Any single country worldwide can agree to and enforce the provisions specified in this clause, and once a country agrees, all banks and financial institutions within that country must unconditionally agree; otherwise, the country may unconditionally freeze their assets.</p> <p>If the world today wishes to fully implement a new improved version of Equal-Field System of the early Tang Dynasty, reduce warfare and conflicts, and narrow the wealth gap, it is imperative to ensure full transparency of the personal and familial assets of shareholders, executives, and their immediate three-generation relatives of banks and trust investment institutions.</p>
4 8	<p>The world order, shaped by Western missionaries fabricating history and constructing selfish and flawed philosophical ideologies, has endured under the rule of chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarchs for more than 200 years, marked by endless wars, conflicts, financial crises, and economic turmoil. Today's world needs to follow ancient Chinese traditional philosophical ideologies, punish criminals, respect cultural customs, and elevate moral standards to restructure the world. Some countries or nations with long-standing internal conflicts or wars need to restructure or regroup according to traditional and cultural customs.</p> <p>Despite the exponential increase in university graduates over the past 100 years, surpassing ancient China or the global number by at least 1,000 times, due to the Western fabrication of European history and the abandonment of China's millennium-old institutions, most countries worldwide are now controlled by chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch or international financial magnates. They have constructed legal systems that appear fair but are inherently evil, where serious crimes go unpunished. The Japanese army killed at least 51.8-89.6 (100.80) million Chinese and raped or gang-raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.2) million million Chinese women. If we start counting from the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights in Port Arthur, the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, with only 36 survivors, China's population loss reached 280 million. However, only less than 100 criminals were tried and executed by military courts. According to the ancient rules of China, since the evil Japanese massacred about one hundred million Chinese people, which is a genocide unprecedented in history, plundering the wealth accumulated by China over five thousand years, all Japanese criminals must be executed, and Japan should cease to exist. If you lack empathy and do not follow the logic of reciprocity, and are unwilling to punish Japan severely in accordance with empathy, and demand compensation from the Japanese criminals, would you be willing to have the Japanese military kill all the people in your city or state, rape all the women, plunder all the wealth, and only punish 60 proxies? Would your relatives also give up Japanese compensation?</p> <p>Under the malevolent design of financial elites and corrupt politicians, nations with disparate cultural customs and no internal cohesion are forcibly</p>

	<p>amalgamated into one country, such as Myanmar, the Philippines, and India, leading to constant wars and conflicts. The regression of human morality, ethics, and justice by 2,000-4,000 years necessitates global consensus. Today's world demands the eradication of the destructive influence of financial elites and corrupt politicians on politics, governance, finance, and the economy. They should be severely punished like the Ming Dynasty or the Yellow Turbans. Evil nations committing severe crimes should face strict penalties. Nations should be reassembled based on their morals, ethics and traditional cultural customs and desires. Ethnic groups originally belonging to China should be able to return to Chinese jurisdiction if they wish, while those wishing to establish their own countries, with the agreement of neighboring nations, should be allowed to do so. The international community should not violate ethics by engaging in arbitrary organ transplants, relying on medication to suppress rejection reactions daily, just to sustain human life.</p> <p>The United States, Myanmar, and other countries have become havens for criminals to reside safely.</p>
4 9	<p>In order for humanity to reduce wars, conflicts, economic or financial crises, and achieve world peace and sustainable development, it is imperative to crack down severely on chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch crime. Otherwise, achieving world peace is completely impossible.</p> <p>Criminals, as long as they participate, execute, plan, or have knowledge of crimes, will inevitably leave behind indelible quantum entanglement signals. Even in cases similar to the public assassination of President Kennedy, even if the direct killers and all those with knowledge were silenced by the interests behind the scenes, they will still inevitably leave behind signals that cannot be eliminated. As long as any signal of commanding, participating in, executing, or planning the murder of others is discovered through quantum entanglement, due to the regression of today's moral ethics and laws by 2,000-4,000 years, the judicial system and judicial institutions being controlled by financial oligarchs, major crimes like these must be dealt with thunderous means according to ancient Chinese laws in order to thoroughly control the enormous harm that top-level criminals pose to society. Since the beneficiaries of such crimes are the criminals' families, all offenders with knowledge or involvement in the crime must be executed. All personal, family properties, and all properties of their families of all criminals must be confiscated, and all properties of interest groups must be confiscated. In cases of family crimes, all members of the family must be sentenced to death. If apprehending the criminals is inconvenient, the victim country can conduct publicly devastating strikes against the criminal's family using missiles, thermobaric bombs, or cloud burst bombs. Not only are family assets used to compensate victims and the victim State, but 25% of confiscated assets of offenders or their families are used to reward the relevant individuals and institutions who strike against offenders. The close relatives within six generations of all the aforementioned criminals' family members are</p>

	<p>prohibited from engaging in finance, economics, government, law, military, police, or security affairs for the next 5,000 years. They can only reside in designated areas and must report to the national regulatory authority if they leave the area.</p>
5 0	<p>The world must purge a group of so-called politicians, economists, and financial experts. Despite their high intelligence, these individuals intentionally use distorted theories, academic positions, and titles to mislead the public and governments, serving the interests of financial oligarchs, seeking huge profits. They are fully aware of the negative consequences of implementing distorted theories, which inevitably lead to the plunder of most of society's wealth by financial oligarchs. Any so-called expert who causes exceptionally serious harm to some countries should be sentenced to death or exiled to Siberia or the Arctic, with themselves and their immediate family prohibited from engaging in any work in government, finance, economics, law, or military affairs.</p>
5 1	<p>The world or country wearing wigs cannot implement the new equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty.</p> <p>In fields where truth is most needed, disguises should be shed. It should be globally prohibited for judges to wear wigs.</p> <p>British judges wear wigs because members of the British royal family had syphilis. At the early 16th century, hygiene conditions in Europe were extremely poor, near the end of the dark ages of the medieval period. Poor hygiene and very casual personal lifestyles, including among members of the British royal family, prevailed. This casual personal lifestyle directly led to King Charles II of England to contract syphilis before the age of 20. In that era, there were certainly no antibiotics or other drugs (even if there were antibiotics, syphilis was a lifelong recurrent condition). As a result, syphilis caused extensive hair loss and left permanent scars on his scalp. To maintain his regal dignity, Charles II began wearing wigs, changing them several times a day, becoming the first recorded wearer of wigs in British history.</p> <p>The image of a judge suffering from syphilis is extremely ugly. Such a judge should feel ashamed.</p>
5 2	<p>It is wrong and childish for Western politicians to use ideology to create national opposition in philosophy and history.</p> <p>When Marx created the classification method of social systems, he overly emphasized ideology, which objectively caused opposition between countries with different systems.</p> <p>Marx lacked understanding and research on Chinese history and failed to clarify the socialist system, capitalist system, and communist system. China had extremely advanced socialist and even communist ideas as early as the dynasty founded by Wang Mang around 5 A.D. In the middle and late Tang Dynasty of China, the characteristics of monopoly capitalism characterized by the liberalist market economy were very obvious. The financial industry in the Tang Dynasty</p>

was very developed and radiated to the surrounding countries of the Silk Road, but the characteristics of privatization, private monopoly or market economy system were very obvious. **It can be said that according to Marx's classification method, the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China were all capitalist systems.**

From the perspective of historical origin, China's current social system originated from the improved version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. It was formed by the Communist Party of China and its leaders based on China's national conditions and practical development, and has the theoretical and practical basis of philosophy and history. Stalin, the supreme leader of the former Soviet Union, clearly pointed out that China's social system did not conform to the socialist system proposed by Marx. China's current socialist system **(the new Equal-field system)** is an original creation in China and is set up to solve the unavoidable historical cycle law that emerged when the equal-field system was implemented in the early Tang Dynasty. In China, public ownership and collective ownership of farmers are implemented for land, and private sale of land and permanent ownership of land is prohibited.

The human social system does not necessarily have to go through capitalist society first before entering socialist society. It may also experience a repeat cycle of the socialist (the new Equal-field system) and capitalist system.

The Tang Dynasty system was actually composed of the 1.0 version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty with the early characteristics of socialism. After experiencing institutional changes and loss of control in the middle period, the entire Tang society gradually entered the 2.0 version of the capitalist monopoly system of crazy mergers and acquisitions characterized by the new liberalist market economy. Finally, due to the large gap between the rich and poor in society and the high concentration of social wealth, **the Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义) occurred**. The rebel army killed hundreds of thousands of bureaucrats and plutocrats, eliminating the plutocrats who affected Chinese society and entering a new cycle of selecting talents through examinations and a new land distribution system. In the West, financial crises and economic crises keep emerging, which is also a repeatedly occurring situation formed by the monopoly of private capital based on liberal political and economic thinking. The reason why **the Huang Chao Uprising** has not yet occurred is largely related to the brainwashing of the Western public by the mainstream Western media. However, now the self-media has suddenly erupted, the Western public is gradually awakening, the right to issue currency in the West is monopolized by private plutocrats, and the manipulation of taxes by private institutions will be known to the public. Obviously, Western society based on new liberal political and economic thinking is bound to be unable to solve the dilemma brought about by this system.

Gorbachev once asked the Americans to help design the capitalist system, which resulted in the former Soviet Union's social wealth being concentrated in private hands in a short period of time. In the middle and late periods of the

Tang Dynasty in China, there were obvious typical characteristics of a capitalist system society. The financial industry was privatized, free transactions were realized, and mergers and monopolies were free. If Russia or the U.S. hopes that China can help design a freer method and system to concentrate social wealth on a few specific individuals or the rich, it is believed that the Chinese have more historical experience than the Americans. Rich Americans and politicians may provide consultation fees to Chinese companies. The Chinese only found that the free monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China would only bring disasters, so in the early periods of different dynasties after the Tang Dynasty in China, they tended to a non-liberal monopolistic capitalist system. If politicians, the public, and the media in the United States and around the world think that the improved version of the equal-field system implemented in China is not essentially superior to the liberalist merger and monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in the United States, it should be ignorance of history and the law of historical cycles.

Table 35 S 1. International conventions proposing Inherited estate or Grant tax

	Inherited estate or Grant tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million ≤ inherited estate < \$40 million	\$15million	between 10% and 14%
2	\$40 million ≤ inherited estate < \$60 million	\$16 million	between 10% and 14%
3	\$60 million ≤ inherited estate < \$80 million	\$17 million	between 12% and 16%
4	\$80 million ≤ inherited estate < \$100 million	\$18 million	between 12% and 18%
5	\$100 million ≤ inherited estate < \$300 million	\$20 million	between 15% and 26%
6	\$300 million ≤ inherited estate < \$500 million	\$30 million	between 20% and 28%
7	\$500 million ≤ inherited estate < \$700 million	\$40 million	between 23% and 28%
8	\$700 million ≤ inherited estate < \$900 million	\$50 million	between 23% and 28%
9	\$900 million ≤ inherited estate < \$1.2 billion	\$60 million	between 24% and 28%
10	\$1.2 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.5 billion	\$70 million	between 25% and 28%
11	\$1.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.7 billion	\$80 million	between 25% and 28%
12	\$1.7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.9 billion	\$90 million	between 25% and 28%

13	\$1.9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.1 billion	\$100 million	between 25% and 30%
14	\$2.1 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.5 billion	\$110 million	between 28% and 32%
15	\$2.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$3 billion	\$120 million	between 28% and 32%
16	\$3 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 billion	\$130 million	between 28% and 32%
17	\$4 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 billion	\$140 million	between 35% and 38%
18	\$5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 billion	\$150 million	between 35% and 38%
19	\$6 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 billion	\$160 million	between 35% and 38%
20	\$7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 billion	\$170 million	between 35% and 38%
21	\$9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 billion	\$180 million	between 40% and 45%
22	\$10 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$15 billion	\$190 million	between 40% and 45%
23	\$15 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$20 billion	\$200 million	between 50% and 55%
24	\$20 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$25 billion	\$210 million	between 50% and 55%
25	\$25 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$30 billion	\$220 million	between 55% and 60%
26	\$30 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$35 billion	\$230 million	between 55% and 60%
27	\$35 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$40 billion	\$240 million	between 55% and 60%
28	\$40 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$45 billion	\$250 million	between 55% and 60%
29	\$45 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$50 billion	\$260 million	between 55% and 60%
30	\$50 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$55 billion	\$270 million	between 55% and 60%
31	\$55 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$60 billion	\$280 million	between 55% and 60%
32	\$60 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$65 billion	\$290 million	between 55% and 60%
33	\$65 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$70 billion	\$300 million	between 55% and 60%
34	\$70 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$75 billion	\$310 million	between 55% and

	billion		60%
35	\$75 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$80 billion	\$320 million	between 55% and 60%
36	\$80 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$85 billion	\$330 million	between 55% and 60%
37	\$85 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$90 billion	\$340 million	between 55% and 60%
38	\$90 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$95 billion	\$350 million	between 55% and 60%
39	\$95 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1 trillion	\$360 million	between 55% and 60%
40	\$1 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$2 trillion	\$370 million	between 61% and 62%
41	\$2 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$3 trillion	\$380 million	between 61% and 62%
42	\$3 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 trillion	\$390 million	between 61% and 62%
43	\$4 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 trillion	\$400 million	between 61% and 62%
44	\$5 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 trillion	\$410 million	between 63% and 64%
45	\$6 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 trillion	\$420 million	between 63% and 64%
46	\$7 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 trillion	\$430 million	between 64% and 65%
47	\$8 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$9 trillion	\$440 million	between 64% and 65%
48	\$9 trillion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 trillion	\$450 million	between 64% and 65%
49	\$10 trillion ≤ inherited estate	\$460 million	between 67% and 68%

Prohibiting individuals or institutions from using charitable trusts or other means for tax evasion. Estate and gift tax rates should adhere to the rules outlined in Table 35 S 1, which all countries worldwide must follow. Any country or region found aiding tax evasion will have its assets frozen FIVEfold.

Table 35 S2. International Convention on the Personal Income Tax Rates for Rich Individuals with Extraordinary Assets

	Personal total assets	income tax rate
1	\$80 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$100 million	between 29% and 30%
2	\$100 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$300 million	between 30% and 32%
3	\$300 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$500 million	between 32% and 33%
4	\$500 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$700 million	between 32% and 33%

5	\$700 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$900 million	between 32% and 33%
6	\$900 million ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.2 billion	between 32% and 33%
7	\$1.2 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.5 billion	between 34% and 38%
8	\$1.5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.7 billion	between 34% and 38%
9	\$1.7 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1.9 billion	between 34% and 38%
10	\$1.9 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2.1 billion	between 34% and 38%
11	\$2.1 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2.5 billion	between 39% and 43%
12	\$2.5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$3 billion	between 39% and 43%
13	\$3 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$4 billion	between 39% and 43%
14	\$4 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$5 billion	between 44% and 47%
15	\$5 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$6 billion	between 44% and 47%
16	\$6 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$7 billion	between 44% and 47%
17	\$7 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$8 billion	between 48% and 51%
18	\$9 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$10 billion	between 48% and 51%
19	\$10 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$15 billion	between 48% and 51%
20	\$15 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$20 billion	between 48% and 51%
21	\$20 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$25 billion	between 48% and 51%
22	\$25 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$30 billion	between 48% and 51%
23	\$30 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$35 billion	between 52% and 56%
24	\$35 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$40 billion	between 52% and 56%
25	\$40 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$45 billion	between 52% and 56%
26	\$45 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$50 billion	between 52% and 56%
27	\$50 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$55 billion	between 57% and 59%
28	\$55 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$60 billion	between 57% and 59%
29	\$60 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$65 billion	between 57% and 59%
30	\$65 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$70 billion	between 57% and 59%
31	\$70 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$75 billion	between 60% and 61%
32	\$75 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$80 billion	between 60% and 61%
33	\$80 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$85 billion	between 60% and 61%
34	\$85 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$90 billion	between 60% and 61%
35	\$90 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$95 billion	between 60% and 61%
36	\$95 billion ≤ Personal total assets < \$1 trillion	between 60% and 61%
37	\$1 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$2 trillion	between 62% and 64%
38	\$2 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$3 trillion	between 62% and 64%
39	\$3 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$4 trillion	between 62% and 64%
40	\$4 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$5 trillion	between 62% and 64%
41	\$5 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$6 trillion	between 65% and 68%
42	\$6 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$7 trillion	between 68% and 70%
43	\$7 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$8 trillion	between 68% and 70%
44	\$8 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$9 trillion	between 68% and 70%
45	\$9 trillion ≤ Personal total assets < \$10 trillion	between 68% and 70%
46	\$10 trillion ≤ inherited estate	between 70% and 72%

Table 35 S 3. Suggested Tax Rate for Change of Nationality

	Nationality change tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million ≤total assets< \$40 million	\$1million	between 20% and 25%
2	\$40 million ≤total assets< \$60 million	\$2 million	between 20% and 25%
3	\$60 million ≤total assets< \$80 million	\$3 million	between 23% and 28%
4	\$80 million ≤total assets< \$100 million	\$4million	between 23% and 28%
5	\$100 million ≤total assets< \$300 million	\$5 million	between 28% and 32%
6	\$300 million ≤total assets< \$500 million	\$6 million	between 28% and 32%
7	\$500 million ≤total assets< \$700 million	\$7million	between 28% and 32%
8	\$700 million ≤total assets< \$900 million	\$8million	between 30% and 32%
9	\$900 million ≤total assets< \$1.2 billion	\$9 million	between 30% and 32%
10	\$1.2 billion≤total assets< \$1.5 billion	\$10million	between 30% and 35%
11	\$1.5 billion≤total assets< \$1.7 billion	\$11million	between 30% and 35%
12	\$1.7 billion≤total assets< \$1.9 billion	\$12million	between 30% and 35%
13	\$1.9 billion≤total assets< \$2.1 billion	\$13million	between 30% and 35%
14	\$2.1 billion≤total assets< \$2.5 billion	\$14 million	between 30% and 35%
15	\$2.5 billion≤total assets< \$3 billion	\$15million	between 33% and 35%
16	\$3 billion≤total assets< \$4 billion	\$16 million	between 33% and 35%
17	\$4 billion≤total assets< \$5 billion	\$17 million	between 33% and 35%
18	\$5 billion≤total assets< \$6 billion	\$18million	between 33% and 35%
19	\$6 billion≤total assets< \$7 billion	\$19 million	between 33% and 35%
20	\$7 billion≤total assets< \$8 billion	\$20million	between 33% and 35%
21	\$9 billion≤total assets< \$10 billion	\$21million	between 33% and 35%
22	\$10 billion≤total assets< \$15 billion	\$22 million	between 35% and 36%
23	\$15 billion≤total assets< \$20 billion	\$23 million	between 35% and 36%
24	\$20 billion≤total assets< \$25 billion	\$24million	between 35% and 36%
25	\$25billion≤total assets< \$30 billion	\$25 million	between 35% and 36%

26	\$30 billion≤total assets<\$35 billion	\$26 million	between 35% and 36%
27	\$35 billion≤total assets<\$40 billion	\$27 million	between 35% and 36%
28	\$40 billion≤total assets<\$45 billion	\$28million	between 36% and 38%
29	\$45 billion≤total assets<\$50 billion	\$29 million	between 36% and 38%
30	\$50 billion≤total assets<\$55 billion	\$30 million	between 36% and 38%
31	\$55 billion≤total assets<\$60 billion	\$31million	between 36% and 38%
32	\$60 billion≤total assets<\$65 billion	\$32 million	between 36% and 38%
33	\$65 billion≤total assets<\$70 billion	\$33 million	between 36% and 38%
34	\$70 billion≤total assets<\$75 billion	\$34million	between 36% and 38%
35	\$75 billion≤total assets<\$80 billion	\$35million	between 36% and 38%
36	\$80 billion≤total assets<\$85 billion	\$36million	between 36% and 38%
37	\$85 billion≤total assets<\$90 billion	\$37 million	between 36% and 38%
38	\$90 billion≤total assets<\$95 billion	\$38million	between 36% and 38%
39	\$95 billion≤total assets<\$1 trillion	\$39 million	between 36% and 38%
40	\$1 trillion≤total assets	\$40million	between 37% and 40%

In Chinese history, there has never been a dynasty like the United States, where 12 presidents have been assassinated. Judging from the number of assassinated presidents in the United States, a nation controlled by international financial oligarchs cannot govern with moral and ethical standards. Any president who damages the core interests of international financial oligarchs is subject to assassination. Compared to China, the moral and ethical standards of the United States have declined by at least 2,000 to 4,000 years. In ancient China, it was not permissible for financial oligarchs to interfere in government affairs. It is rare in Chinese history to see emperors being assassinated during prominent dynasties.

Table. 36. In U.S. history, a total of 12 presidents have been assassinated

	In U.S. history, a total of 12 presidents have been assassinated, some fatally, while others survived.
1	On January 30, 1835, during the funeral of a congressman on Capitol Hill, the 7th U.S. President, Andrew Jackson, narrowly escaped being shot by a British painter. Fortunately, the pistol malfunctioned, giving the president and his guards time to react, and the assailant was eventually subdued.
2	In the 1840 presidential election, the Whig Party nominated war hero William Henry Harrison. Due to an economic crisis that shifted public sentiment, Harrison easily won as the 9th President of the United States. Henry Clay, positioning himself as a leader within the Whig Party, often

	<p>"advised" Harrison on how to govern. After Harrison's election, tensions between the two escalated. Clay summoned the incoming president to his home in Lexington to discuss matters such as the national bank, independent fiscal policy, and other issues, but their meeting ended in discord. Clay, assuming a sort of "regent" role, had already drafted Harrison's inaugural address without his consent, which Harrison rejected. Harrison himself drafted a lengthy inaugural address of over 8,000 words, sharply opposing Clay's advocacy for a privately controlled central bank and abolishment of independent fiscal policy.</p> <p>On a bitterly cold day, March 4, 1841, Harrison delivered his inaugural speech outdoors, catching a cold that worsened rapidly. Despite his robust military background, Harrison's condition deteriorated unexpectedly, leading to his death on April 4. Historians have speculated that Harrison was poisoned with arsenic, possibly on March 30, just six days before his death.</p>
3	<p>Zachary Taylor was the 12th President of the United States and a hero of the Mexican-American War. In July 1850, shortly after participating in Independence Day celebrations, Zachary Taylor suddenly fell seriously ill. Doctors inexplicably made a misdiagnosis, ultimately resulting in Zachary Taylor's death while in office.</p> <p>The struggle for a privately controlled central bank and an independent fiscal system intensified following President Harrison's death. Led by Henry Clay, the Whig Party twice attempted to restore the central bank and abolish the independent fiscal system in 1841, only to be vetoed both times by Harrison's successor, former Vice President John Tyler. Outraged, Clay ordered Tyler's expulsion from the Whig Party, making Tyler the "fortunate" sole "orphan" president in American history to be expelled from his party.</p> <p>By 1849, with another Whig Party president, Zachary Taylor, elected, the prospect of restoring the central bank seemed within reach. Establishing a privately controlled central bank modeled entirely after the Bank of England was the ultimate dream of all bankers, signifying their ultimate control over the fate of the nation and its people. With the precedent set by President Harrison, Taylor remained somewhat ambiguous on the critical issue of the central bank but was unwilling to become Clay's puppet. Historian Michael Holt noted that President Taylor privately stated, "The idea of establishing a central bank is dead; it will not be considered during my term." However, it was not the idea of the central bank that was dead but rather President Taylor himself.</p> <p>On July 4, 1850, President Taylor attended Independence Day celebrations at the Washington Monument. The weather was exceptionally hot, and Taylor drank some iced milk and ate a few cherries, which upset his stomach. By July 9, this robustly healthy president mysteriously passed away.</p> <p>Such a seemingly minor illness that led to the deaths of two military men-turned-presidents naturally raised suspicions and sparked debate within the scholarly community for over a century. In 1991, with the consent of President Taylor's descendants, his body was exhumed. Analysis of the president's nails</p>

	and hair revealed traces of arsenic, but authorities quickly concluded that the amount was insufficient to be lethal and hastily closed the case. No one knows why the president's body contained these traces of arsenic.
4	On the evening of April 14, 1865, the 16th President, Abraham Lincoln, was assassinated while attending a play at a theater in Washington, D.C. The perpetrator was a professional actor named John Wilkes Booth, who supported the Southern slave system. He was found by the police the day after the assassination and successfully killed.
5	On July 2, 1881, the 20th President, James A. Garfield, was shot by a confused lawyer named Charles J. Guiteau at the Baltimore and Potomac Railroad Station in Washington, D.C. Despite weeks of treatment, he passed away on September 19.
6	On September 6, 1901, the 25th President, William McKinley, was shot at the Pan-American Exposition's Temple of Music in Buffalo, New York. The assailant, Leon Czolgosz, was an anarchist who used a concealed revolver to shoot McKinley while shaking hands with him. The wound proved fatal, and the president passed away on September 14, over a week later.
7	Warren Gamaliel Harding was the 29th President of the United States and one of the lowest-rated presidents in American history. Harding's presidency was marred by scandals, with his cabinet derisively labeled as the "Poker Cabinet." In August 1923, Harding suddenly passed away during a nationwide "Voyage of Understanding." Given the frequent scandals during Harding's presidency, including rumors of extramarital affairs, coupled with his wife Florence's refusal to allow an autopsy, many suspected that Harding was poisoned by his wife. However, the official cause of Harding's death, as announced by U.S. authorities, was a sudden stroke.
8	On February 15, 1933, during a speech in Miami, the 32nd President, Franklin D. Roosevelt, was targeted by Giuseppe Zangara, who fired five shots but failed to hit the president.
9	On November 1, 1950, the 33rd President, Harry S. Truman, narrowly escaped an assassination attempt at the Blair House, where he was residing at the time. The two would-be assassins, Oscar Collazo and Griselio Torresola, members of the Puerto Rican Nationalist Party, were discovered and stopped by security guards.
10	On November 22, 1963, the 35th President, John F. Kennedy, was assassinated while riding in an open-top car with his wife Jacqueline Kennedy and Texas Governor John Connally through Dealey Plaza in Dallas, Texas.
11	On September 5, 1975, the 38th President, Gerald Ford, narrowly avoided being shot by one of Charles Manson's followers in Sacramento, California, but the gun did not fire, and the assailant was apprehended. Seventeen days later, another female assailant attempted to shoot Ford in San Francisco, but a bystander deflected her gun, preventing a successful assassination.
12	On March 30, 1981, the 40th President, Ronald Reagan, was shot by John Hinckley Jr., a mentally ill man who ambushed him amidst a crowd of journalists

	outside the Hilton Hotel in Washington, D.C., using a .22 caliber revolver. However, the president was only hit by one bullet and not in a vital area, allowing him to survive.
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Table. 37. Which philosophy, religion, politics, finance, and economic theories guiding the operation of the United States and China are more advanced and superior? **The Trends of Global Future Social Institutions.**

1	Can a currency deliberately causing financial crises still be widely used as the world's currency for international settlements and reserves?
2	Can a currency deliberately causing frequent financial crises still be widely used as the world's currency for international settlements and reserves?
3	Can a currency deliberately create large fluctuations in benchmark interest rates, leading to financial crises, still be widely used as the world's currency?
4	How can a currency deliberately causing significant fluctuations in benchmark interest rates, leading to financial crises and the plundering of other countries' wealth, be widely accepted as an international settlement and reserve currency?
5	Isn't this evil currency nothing but a money launderer for weaker nations? A reaper or a harvester of the commoners' wealth?
6	How can a country with a currency that frequently triggers financial or economic crises take on the leadership responsibility for the healthy operation of the global economy?
7	How can a country with a currency that frequently triggers financial or economic crises serve as a beacon for the world?
8	Would it be right for a country with a currency that frequently triggers financial or economic crises to guide its financial and economic models?
9	Would it be correct to follow the financial and economic theories of a country with a currency that frequently triggers financial or economic crises?
10	Would the U.S. system that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced system?
11	Would the U.S. financial system that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced financial system?
12	Would the U.S. political system that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced political system?
13	Would the U.S. political-economic system that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced political-economic system?
14	Would the U.S. social system that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced social system?
15	Would a governing party in the United States that frequently creates financial crises or economic crises still be considered an advanced governing party?

16	Can the market optimally allocate the dollar through the invisible hand? If so, Janet Yellen, the U.S. Treasury Secretary and renowned economist, should not have visited China twice to seek Chinese purchases of U.S. bonds; instead, she should have waited for the market's automatic adjustment.
17	Can the market effectively regulate the allocation of the dollar? If so, Janet Yellen, the U.S. Treasury Secretary and renowned economist, should not have visited China twice to seek Chinese purchase of U.S. bonds; instead, she should have waited for the market's automatic adjustment.
18	Can the market effectively prevent economic crises caused by excessive issuance of the dollar? If so, Janet Yellen, the U.S. Treasury Secretary and renowned economist, should not have visited China twice to seek Chinese purchase of U.S. bonds; instead, she should have waited for the market's automatic adjustment.
19	Isn't there a fundamental error in the philosophy, religion, politics, finance, and economic theories guiding the operation of the United States?
20	Would the US, which often struggles to eliminate its own financial crises or economic crises, frequently resorting to various means to compel China to help alleviate the crises, still dare to claim itself as the beacon of the world?
21	Does this not prove that China's economic operating model is more advanced than that of the United States? Does the United States have the audacity to claim itself as the beacon of the world?
22	Does this not prove that China's financial system is more advanced than that of the United States?
23	Does this not prove that China's political system is more advanced than that of the United States?
24	Does this not prove that China's political-economic system is more advanced than that of the United States?
25	Does this not prove that China's social system is more advanced than that of the United States?
26	Does this not prove that China's ruling party is more competent than that of the US?
27	Does this not prove that political science majors in Chinese universities are superior to those in American universities?
28	Does this not prove that political economy majors in Chinese universities are superior to those in American universities?
29	Does this not prove that economics majors in Chinese universities are superior to those in American universities?
30	Does this not prove that finance majors in Chinese universities are superior to those in American universities?
31	Does this not prove that the current rankings of Western universities are merely a money-making game? Shouldn't global university rankings based on payment be abolished immediately?
32	The basic assumption of Western finance is that financial markets are in equilibrium. Hasn't the U.S. financial market been in disequilibrium in the past

	year, two years, three years?
33	The US insists that a market-oriented economic system is optimal, so why doesn't the US regulate the dollar and national debt through market freedom and force other countries to buy US bonds?
34	Isn't the US intervening in the allocation of relatively scarce resources through party actions, government actions, and organizations like the Federal Reserve?
35	Isn't the U.S. controlling the dollar and national debt through conglomerates like political parties, government, and the Federal Reserve? Is raising interest rates automatic rather than intentional?
36	The Fed's rate hikes caused the dollar to rebound, leading to significant depreciation of currencies in Sri Lanka, Venezuela, and Turkey. The sharp depreciation of the Sri Lankan rupee may indeed be market-driven, but isn't the dominant change in the exchange rate between the US dollar and the Sri Lankan rupee controlled by the Federal Reserve?
37	Isn't the U.S. controlling the exchange rates of the dollar and other currencies through organizations like the Federal Reserve?
38	Isn't the U.S. manipulating the exchange rates of the dollar and other currencies through party actions, government actions, and organizations like the Federal Reserve? Isn't the United States a controlling country in terms of currency exchange rates?
39	Isn't the U.S. economy characterized by party-driven economics (party behavioral economics), government-driven economics [government (public or state) behavioral economics], and oligarchic economics?
40	Wouldn't the United States, struggling to eliminate its own financial or economic crises and frequently resorting to various means to compel China to help alleviate these crises, prove that China's contemporary social system, an improved version 4.0 of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty, is more advanced than the social systems of the late Tang or late Ming Dynasty or a capitalist slavery system or a capitalist colonial society in the present-day United States?
41	History has already proved that the serious intervention of financial magnates in government operations and the complete marketization of the late Tang Dynasty will inevitably lead to its downfall. This is the inevitability of history. In order to establish a new society, a new equal-field system must be implemented. If vested interests are unwilling to relinquish their plundered wealth, this country may have to endure cruel wars. The history of ancient Europe was fabricated by missionaries and believers, seriously obscuring the truth of history, making it difficult for Westerners to see the inevitability of history and the historical trend of social system development. A United States controlled by financial magnates for a long time, although the capitalist system may generate varying degrees of prosperity, but over time, the repeated marketization of assets will inevitably accelerate the plunder of social wealth and the wealth of the middle and lower classes by financial magnates through

	<p>pre-designed, seemingly legitimate means. This system will inevitably lead to destruction, and the country may face disintegration.</p> <p>The current social system in China – the 4.0 version of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty (socialist system) – will inevitably progress through continual strengthening of institutionalized anti-corruption efforts and system optimization. If a series of global consensus can be reached on core issues such as crime prevention, crime suppression, regulatory management, and economic development, there will inevitably emerge versions 4.5 and 5.0 of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty, moving towards a continuously fairer and more just new version of the equal-field system.</p> <p>If the vast majority of people in other countries do not wish to be intentionally plundered of their wealth by international financial oligarchs through manufactured financial crises, economic crises, conflicts, or wars, they will also inevitably aspire to achieve a system similar to China's Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty (though Marx referred to it as the socialist system).</p>
42	<p>If a doctor frequently makes mistakes, often causing patients to feel unwell after taking medication or unable to effectively solve problems after consultation, and this becomes widely known, would you American politicians, financial experts from the Federal Reserve, or finance professors from American universities still frequently seek medical advice from this incompetent doctor? Wouldn't you change doctors? Almost all of you are graduates of Ivy League universities in the United States. Would you be so foolish as not to change doctors?</p>

Table. 38. Comparison of the political and economic systems of China and the United States from a historical perspective.

	China	The U.S.
1	The historical inheritance of the political-economic system:	
	<p>The current political-economic systems in China: A new Equal field system, an improved version of the early Tang Dynasty Equal field system, which Marx referred to as the socialist system. The current social system in China – the 4.0 version of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty (Chinese socialist system) A fairer and more reasonable</p>	<p>The current political-economic systems in the U.S.: A non Equal field system, and a capital freedom system. Essentially, it is a capitalist slavery system. The political-economic system that inevitably often experiences financial or economic crises. Similar to the political, economic, and financial systems of the late Tang or Ming dynasties in China. The current reality is that the United States is nominally a country, but in fact, it is a company or playground disguised as a country. The US government and the nation itself have been controlled by financial magnates, forming an alliance of capitalist interest groups. The true</p>

<p>system.</p> <p>In rural China, every farmer's or peasant's household usually has housing without the need to pay annual property taxes. They also don't have to pay agricultural taxes, water charges (unless they use urban tap water), property management fees, or mortgages. They can sustain themselves by cultivating crops and vegetables on their own land, and by raising poultry and livestock, enabling them to live self-sufficiently.</p>	<p>controllers of the United States are capital or financial magnates. The US media, finance sector, police, and military are all completely controlled by capital.</p> <p>From the point of view of political economy, the social system in the United States is a form of capitalist slavery system.</p> <p>Once Americans lose their ability to earn money and fail to pay property taxes on time, even their homes can be controlled by the international financial magnates controlling the IRS, and auctioned off. From birth to death, Americans are continually utilized as money-making tools for international financial magnates, essentially functioning as invisible slaves. While American society may appear to be a capitalist society as Karl Marx described it, in reality, it operates under a system of capitalist slavery.</p>
<p>The extent of intervention in government operations by businessmen or private financiers: relatively low</p>	<p>The extent of intervention in government operations by businessmen or private financiers: very serious.</p> <p>Businessmen or private financiers seriously interfere with government operations, which is contrary to the management philosophy of ancient China, and inevitably leads to irregular economic or financial crises.</p>
<p>Hong Kong, China, has experienced a decline from prosperity in the 1980s to today, which proves the enormous harm to society caused by the intervention of businessmen and financiers in government operations and the total dominance of private assets in the market. Between 1984 and 1997, 40,000 manufacturing enterprises disappeared, with only a few special interest groups making huge profits.</p> <p>If Hong Kong was truly a society or region of absolute democracy, full freedom, and care for human rights, and if the Hong Kong government really cared about people's livelihoods, when the privileged and vested interest classes in Hong Kong refuse the government's large-scale construction of basic affordable housing to reduce abnormally high housing prices and ensure rapid access to secure housing for low-income groups, Hong Kong must be governed by splitting it into two regions. One region would consist of the high-priced housing population unwilling to lower prices, and the other region would comprise people eager to lower prices and purchasing secure housing. Hong Kong should allocate its common land resources evenly based on the respective populations to demonstrate the fairness and justice of its</p>	

	<p>autonomous government and uphold the human rights of lower-income groups. Otherwise, Hong Kong would be a region of pseudo-freedom, pseudo-democracy, and pseudo-human rights, serving the interests of elite predators and exploiting lower-class civilians.</p> <p>Similar to the political, economic, and financial systems of the late Tang or Ming dynasties.</p>	
	<p>The prosperity of the United States in the 20th century and the current difficulties it faces can be seen to some extent as a microcosm of the political and economic situation in Hong Kong. This serves as evidence that the lack of correct philosophical theory guiding economic operations, the intervention of businessmen and financiers in government operations, and the total dominance of private assets in the market have caused enormous harm to American society. The excessive pursuit of high profit margins by businesses has led to the disappearance of a large number of manufacturing enterprises, while a few interest groups have reaped huge profits. Despite its size, the United States relies on coercing others to continue to supply it with blood, resulting in a distorted political and economic situation.</p> <p>In American politics, there is a lack of independence, and many people believe that the United States is the son or grandson of Israel, politically heavily influenced by Jewish financial groups. Losing ethical values and basic empathy.</p> <p>With the rise of self-media, the vast majority of Chinese people now know that the United States is a corporation disguised as a country or nation, with capital, especially Jewish capital, truly controlling America.</p> <p>The current political ethics and ethics of politicians in the United States have regressed at least 2,000-4,000 years compared to Chinese history.</p> <p>According to Chinese history, the legal punishment rules and ideologies formulated by Europe and the United States for serious crimes have caused global judicial ethics to regress by at least 2,000-4,000 years. China is a major victim of these rules and ideologies. A country that is extremely selfish and self-serving cannot become a global leader. Instead, it tends to enact cost-free financial rules and utilize financial techniques, under the guise of democracy and freedom, to harvest the wealth created by people in other countries, leaving them in economic crises or poverty. Due to the control of the media by interest groups, these serious criminal behaviors are ironically legitimized under the banner of freedom and democracy. People in the victimized countries, after being brainwashed by Western ideologies, astonishingly do not perceive these egregious actions as serious crimes.</p> <p>The United States resorting to unconventional and unethical means to drive up energy prices in Europe has led to the closure of some old European enterprises and a continuous increase in manufacturing costs, forcing some European companies to shift manufacturing to the United States. This reduction in Europe's self-sustaining capability is extremely</p>	

		<p>wrong and profoundly selfish. Once the inertia of reduced purchasing power in Europe sets in, American high-priced products will find no market in Europe, inevitably leading to overproduction in the United States and a dire situation for the country.</p>
	<p>Can China break free from the cyclical traps of the Tang Dynasty? The possibility of replicating the successful political and economic model: History has proven that all that is needed is to establish a good, strong negative feedback mechanism, and this model will inevitably be sustainable.</p>	<p>Can the U.S. break free from the cyclical trap of the Tang Dynasty? The possibility of replicating the successful political and economic model: History has proven that this model is bound to fail. The United States lacks a moral and cultural foundation similar to China's. The vast majority of American politicians generally lack the most basic moral principles and empathy. The vast majority of American politicians generally lack the essential logical consistency required for human equality. The philosophical framework underpinning America has structural flaws. There are structural flaws in the religious ideologies that shape America. The economic and financial thinking and theories that drive the operation of the United States suffer from structural deficiencies. Both the U.S. economy and finance are controlled by international financial magnates and their proxy politicians.</p>
2	<p>Social systems corresponding to dynasties</p>	<p>based on philosophical analysis:</p>
	<p>The current social system in China – the 4.0 version of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty (Karl Marx described it as a socialist system)</p> <p>In rural China, every farmer's or peasant's household usually has housing without the need to pay annual property taxes. They also don't have to pay agricultural taxes, water charges (unless they use urban tap water), property management</p>	<p>Late Tang Dynasty or Late Ming Dynasty From the point of view of political economy, the social system in the United States is a form of capitalist slavery system. Once Americans lose their ability to earn money and fail to pay property taxes on time, even their homes can be controlled by the international financial magnates controlling the IRS, and auctioned off. From birth to death, Americans are continually utilized as money-making</p>

	<p>fees, or mortgages. They can sustain themselves by cultivating crops and vegetables on their own land, and by raising poultry and livestock, enabling them to live self-sufficiently.</p>	<p>tools for international financial magnates, essentially functioning as invisible slaves. While American society may appear to be a capitalist society as Karl Marx described it, in reality, it operates under a system of capitalist slavery.</p>
	<p>The social system in China is based on public ownership. Chinese farmers and peasants have the right to use their land, but are not required to pay property and agricultural taxes.</p> <p>According to the National Bureau of Statistics in 2022, the number of farmers reached 900 million. However, the so-called 900 million farmers generally refer to the population registered under the agricultural household registration. In reality, only 797 million people live in rural areas, accounting for 88.4% of the total number of registered agricultural households, while the remaining 105 million registered under agricultural household registration live in urban areas.</p>	<p>From a philosophical and political economic perspective, fundamentally, the social system in the United States is a form of capitalist colonial society.</p> <p>Because both the U.S. economy and finance are controlled by international financial magnates and their proxy politicians.</p>
		<p>The founding of political parties for private gain is a characteristic of American politics, using freedom and democracy as a façade while plundering the wealth of the nation and its citizens. This political system is at least 2,000 years behind China.</p> <p>Israel massacred 35,000 innocent Palestinian women and children, yet the vast majority of members of the United States House of Representatives actually support Israel. On May 1, 2024, the U.S. House of Representatives passed the "Antisemitism Awareness Act" with a vote of 320 in favor and 91 against, relegating the Palestinian people to second-class citizenship and making the United States a global laughingstock. According to the criteria for "anti-Semitic" behavior outlined in the bill, many passages from the Bible, on which the U.S. president swears, would be considered "anti-Semitic speech," making all U.S. presidents and Supreme Court justices since the nation's founding criminals. This not only severely damages U.S. interests but also demonstrates extreme self-interest among U.S. government officials and an alarmingly low level of intelligence. If such a situation had occurred during the Tang Dynasty, the 320 members who voted in favour would most likely have been executed.</p>
		<p>The hereditary system of family inheritance had been phased out through alternative means in China prior to the year 2365 AD. By the end</p>

		of the Tang Dynasty, during the Huang Chao Rebellion, the uprising forces massacred the majority of hereditary officials of the Tang Dynasty, effectively putting an end to China's hereditary system. President Trump had to resort to a similar method to groom his son, which may be reasonable in the context of the United States, but this political system in America is at least a thousand years behind China.
3	The current Economic System or Model	
	The composite model of government behavior finance, political party behavior finance, party behavior economy, government behavior economy, and market-oriented economy, continues to achieve economic success and lift almost all impoverished people in a populous country out of poverty, instead of causing trouble for the world and plunging the world into economic crisis again and again like the United States.	The economic system of the United States is not a complete market economy system or a complete market-oriented economic system, but a highly centralized political party, politics, finance, market, monopoly, war, military and state-owned behavioral economy system composed of two political parties, the government, and the backstage monopolistic consortium. The visionary and renowned economist Prof. Jeffrey Sachs is not utilized by the U.S. government, which is influenced by oligarchic economics.
4	National management and economic operation models supported by economic theory	
	<p>China-F(EBC)=F(EBC)=Economic benefits of the country= financial statements of each company + Social benefits=Money earned+ Social benefits</p> <p>Once faced with a crisis, self-interested companies immediately abandon the most basic and core economic element – people. State-owned enterprises may not lay off employees and instead employ various methods to weather the storm together.</p> <p>Formula: $F(EBC)=F(x)+F(sb)=f(x_1)+ f(x_2)+ f(x_3)+...+ f(x_i) + f(sb_1) + f(sb_2) + f(sb_3) +...+f(sb_i)$ $F(EBC)=F(x)= \text{Money earned}+ \text{Social benefits}$</p> <p>The fact that people, who should be the fundamental factor contributing to economic benefits, are excluded from the equation of economic benefits in Western mainstream economics is</p>	<p>USA-F(EBC)=F(EBC)=Economic benefits of the country= financial statements of each company =Money earned</p> <p>Once faced with a crisis, self-interested companies immediately abandon the most basic and core economic element – people, and even abandon all people.</p> <p>Formula: $F(EBC)=F(x)=f(x_1)+ f(x_2)+ f(x_3)+...+ f(x_i)$ $F(EBC)=F(x)= \text{Money earned}$</p> <p>Almost all mainstream economists in the United States, Europe, or China believe that the above viewpoint is correct.</p> <p>Without a correct philosophical foundation, it cannot be called economics, it is only alchemy.</p> <p>Although Western economists consider the labor force to be the most fundamental and core element of economic growth, when an economic crisis strikes, massive layoffs become inevitable. In their eyes, labor no longer</p>

	<p>against human nature and lacks ecological consideration. This indicates that in Western countries, anyone can be discarded during economic operations, creating a paradox within the economic theories established by Western economics. This suggests that Western mainstream economic theories are rigid and focused solely on profit, rather than truly serving as a key framework for sustainable national development, making them unsuitable as core theories for governing a country's operations. Consequently, neoliberal economic theories inevitably lead to cyclical crises in both a country's or the global economy and the daily lives of ordinary people.</p>	<p>equals people. If you refute this mainstream economic theory, you are bound to face numerous attacks. However, if we logically and empathetically argue for this Western economic theory that massive layoffs become inevitable when an economic crisis strikes, how about this: First, let's lay off the economists, business managers, and government officials who adhere to this theory, along with all of their relatives, friends, and classmates, and then consider laying off others. Even if this economic crisis lasts for five years, should we not employ them?</p> <p>The vast majority of the world's top 100 universities in economics and finance are located in Europe and America. These economists and finance experts possess exceptional intelligence, often publishing papers on complex issues. Yet, why do they turn a blind eye to this glaring problem that clearly leads to serious crises for countries?</p>
5	<p>Issuing banknotes</p>	
	<p>State issues banknotes.</p> <p>China refers to the currency issued by the state as the renminbi, which translates to "the people's currency," a unique concept worldwide. Moreover, Mao Zedong disagreed with the idea of having his portrait printed on the renminbi. Instead, he suggested featuring portraits of farmers, workers, intellectuals, and ethnic minorities. It wasn't until 1987, after Chairman Mao's passing, that his image, along with those of three other leaders, appeared on the fourth series of currency.</p> <p>This signifies China's desire for the renminbi to truly represent the people after its issuance. This level of democracy and freedom, achieved in the realm of currency, is unprecedented globally. The abbreviation for the renminbi in China is RMB, not CNY, with RMB translating to "people's currency" in Chinese.</p>	
	<p>The name of issuing banknotes is that the state issues banknotes, but in reality, private banks control the issuance of banknotes. The Federal Reserve is an institution controlled by private banks, representing the interest groups of private bankers.</p> <p>The political, military, judicial, and economic hegemonic system of a</p>	

	<p>country is subservient to private financial capital interest groups, which thereby determine the monetary policy and currency operation of the United States.</p> <p>The more the US government issues treasury bonds, theoretically, the more financially secure it should be. However, most of this money is controlled by wealthy Americans.</p> <p>It would not be an exaggeration to say that until 2008, there were probably not many economists in China who knew that the Federal Reserve was actually a private central bank. The so-called "Federal Reserve Bank" is neither "federal," nor does it have any "reserves," nor can it be considered a "bank." However, almost everyone in China today knows about it. But even today, there may not be many people in the United States who know that the Federal Reserve is actually a private central bank. The so-called "Federal Reserve Bank" is neither "federal," nor does it have any "reserves," nor can it be considered a "bank." Most Americans probably assume that the U.S. government issues the dollar, but in reality, the U.S. government does not have the authority to issue currency.</p> <p>Rothschild: "As long as I can control a country's currency issuance, I don't care who makes the law."</p> <p>Before her death, Mrs. Rothschild once said, "If my sons did not want wars, there would be none."</p> <p>The Federal Reserve has never been audited by creditors. If the United States requires other countries to buy and act as the world currency, it must accept audits from other countries. U.S. accounting standards favor concealing historical costs and must be audited according to Chinese accounting standards.</p> <p>The IRS and the Federal Reserve must undergo annual audits by any country or institution holding US treasury bonds.</p>
	<p>Most Americans don't truly understand how international lenders operate. The Federal Reserve's accounts have never been audited. It operates entirely outside the control of Congress, manipulating America's credit supply.</p> <p>— Senator Barry Goldwater</p> <p>[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]</p>
	<p>To create high prices, the Fed only needs to lower interest rates to expand credit and foster a booming stock market. Once businesses are accustomed to this rate environment, the Fed will halt this prosperity by arbitrarily raising interest rates. It (the Fed and the bankers who own it) can gently sway market prices by slightly adjusting interest rates, or violently fluctuate them by aggressively adjusting rates. In either case, it possesses insider information about financial conditions, knowing in advance of impending changes. This is the strangest and most dangerous</p>

		<p>form of insider trading, a privilege not granted by any government but held by a select few. This system is private, operating solely to maximize profits using others' money. They know when to create panic to create the most advantageous situation for themselves and when to stop the panic. When they control finance, both inflation and deflation are equally effective in achieving their goals.</p> <p>— Congressman Charles Lindbergh [Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]</p>
		<p>The Federal Reserve is one of the most corrupt institutions in the world. Everyone who can hear me speak (Congressional speech) knows that our country is actually ruled by international bankers. Some people think that Federal Reserve Banks are government institutions. They are not government institutions. They are private credit monopolists, exploiting the American people for their own and foreign fraudsters' benefit.</p> <p>— Congressman Mike Padden [Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]</p>
		<p>From 1913 to 1949, the assets of the Federal Reserve soared from \$ 0.143 billion to \$45 billion, directly lining the pockets of the Fed's bank shareholders.</p> <p>— Estes Kefauver [Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]</p>
		<p>Can you imagine? When you're the world's number one richest person like Gates, if the second richest is Buffett, or the 20th richest is Sassoon family (these rankings are hypothetical), would Gates have to borrow money from Buffett or Sassoon family to keep his company or family running? Now, the United States is the world's richest country, why is it always forcing other countries ranked lower in GDP than the United States to buy US Treasury bonds every year to sustain the operation of the US government? Isn't this extremely unusual? The United States is the issuer of the dollar, the dollar is the world's currency, and the issuance of the dollar is extremely profitable. However, all of these benefits have long been controlled by private individuals.</p> <p>The Sassoon family, which controls the Hong Kong and Shanghai Banking Corporation, holds 58% of the Hong Kong dollar issuance authority. Although the Hong Kong dollar is merely a regional currency, the Sassoon family never seems to run out of money every year. By contrast, the Federal Reserve has the authority to issue U.S. dollars, a global currency, and recently the global share of currency payments in U.S. dollars rose to 41.1%. How could it be possible that the United States is continuously short of money?</p> <p>if you still can't understand the meaning of the above words, may I ask,</p>

		<p>would the richest person in your company keep forcing you to buy the corporate debt they issue every year?</p> <p>If you still can't understand the meaning of the above words, may I ask, would the richest person in your company or your university keep borrowing money from you every year?</p>
		<p>Is the real US national debt \$32 trillion or 142 trillion or \$200 trillion?</p> <p>A famous American investor, Jim Rogers said in an interview with the media on April 30, "The United States is the largest debtor country in the world, and its actual debt is nearly seven times that publicly acknowledged by the US Treasury, reaching almost \$ 200 trillion.⁴⁰ The current debt problem of the United States cannot be solved by simply raising the ceiling." According to the relevant reports of American media in May this year, American billionaire Stanley Druckenmiller believes that although the maximum amount of debt raised by the US government is \$31.4 trillion dollars, there is actually 200 trillion hidden off-balance sheet debt, and this debt will not end with the end of the collapse of small and medium-sized banks or the wave of real estate defaults, at least before hyperinflation or default in the United States. However, according to the website 'www.truthinaccounting.org' on August 23, 2022, the true total national debt of the United States was far from \$31 trillion, but \$142 trillion.</p> <p>The United States and the Federal Reserve are always seeking for super-benefits, which fundamentally contradicts the principles of morality. The Jewish-Anglo-Saxon model will inevitably develop a malignant tumor and develop complications such as cerebrovascular disorders and sepsis. If the United States experiences sustained and severe inflation, because the vast majority of Americans have no awareness of saving, let alone the awareness of saving other countries' currencies, the U.S. dollar could collapse. At this point, it will be difficult for the United States to avoid internal turmoil, which could potentially lead to division, and repayment of U.S. debt may become a problem with holders suffering significant losses.</p>
6		<p>Tax collection agency</p>
	<p>Tax is levied by the national government institution.</p>	<p>Taxes are nominally collected by government institutions, but in reality by private commercial financial institutions (IRS). Research suggests that the Internal Revenue Service (IRS) of the United States is a registered offshore company in Puerto Rico. Its ultimate shareholders are unknown. The Internal Revenue Service of the United States is not a civil department under the U.S. government. Its nature, as its name implies, is a national revenue service agency. Although it is under the auspices of the U.S. Department of the Treasury, it is not a government agency itself, but rather a private company employed by the federal government. Its primary function is to collect individual income taxes from U.S.</p>

		<p>citizens and then transfer them directly to its undisclosed shareholders and bosses.</p> <p>The flow of funds collected by the IRS controlled by private commercial financial institutions? Would the IRS have controlled by commercial financial institutions tax themselves fairly and justly?</p> <p>The IRS has never been audited by creditors. The United States, which demands other countries to buy its treasury bonds and acts as the world's currency, must accept joint audits by other countries. U.S. accounting standards favor concealing historical costs and must be audited according to Chinese accounting standards.</p> <p>The IRS and the Federal Reserve must undergo annual audits by any country or institution holding US treasury bonds.</p>
7	The reasonability of the tax rate for the wealthy	
	Unreasonable	The rules established by the government are beneficial to the rich for tax avoidance.
	No withdrawal nationality tax, beneficial for the rich to avoid taxes.	The rich are easy to avoid tax.
	No gift tax, beneficial for the rich to avoid taxes.	The rich are easy to avoid tax.
	The tax rate is unreasonable and too high, leading to the rich avoiding taxes.	The tax rate is unreasonable and too high, leading to the rich avoiding tax.
8	The reasonability of the tax rate for the poor	
	The self-occupied homes of any family do not need to pay property tax annually.	<p>The self-occupied homes of any family must pay property tax annually.</p> <p>The homeowner only owes \$6.3 in taxes, and the house is actually going to be auctioned off by the IRS. Homeless elderly homeowners will be left wandering in the wind and rain.</p> <p>The annual tax on basic family housing is one of the primary means by which the state and private capital monopolize and continuously harvest the property of the poor and middle class. It constitutes a gross violation of human rights and represents the pinnacle of human unfreedom.</p>
9	Agricultural land tax	
	Farmers in China have the right to land use, but currently agricultural land is exempt from taxation.	Need to pay land tax.
10	Land consolidation situation	
	Prohibition of annexation of rural land	<p>Serious land consolidation</p> <p>Land consolidation has shown characteristics of the mid to late Tang</p>

		Dynasty.
		<p>The land consolidation in rural America is extremely severe, likely surpassing that of the late Tang Dynasty in China. Farmers who have lost their land can only resign themselves to fate, with their lives hanging in the balance. It is astonishing that even self-built homes are subject to taxation, making survival nearly impossible for these landless farmers. In a country controlled by financial conglomerates or chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch, if these conglomerates do not willingly relinquish land consolidation, abandon monopolies, reform the tax system, and enable ordinary Americans to live, America will inevitably descend into disintegration and war.</p> <p>The following is a textual translation of the narration of a recent video filmed by netizens in rural America.</p> <p>Hello everyone, today we drove to the rural areas of Detroit, USA, to explore these desolate and disappearing rural areas of America. First and foremost, the disappearance of these rural areas in the United States is not due to their development into large cities, but rather the gradual vanishing of the original rural areas. The entire countryside has become almost uninhabited wasteland. The houses that once housed American villagers along the roadside are now deserted and dilapidated. Some houses we see are already in a semi-collapsed state. This is because most farmers in the United States no longer have their own land; their original farmland has been taken over by capital and slowly occupied. Such situations are frequent in America, essentially severing the livelihood of American farmers. Not only that, the United States also imposes high property taxes on American farmers. Most of these houses in the United States were built by Americans themselves, but the burden of property taxes and maintenance costs overwhelms them.</p> <p>In addition to these pressures, there has recently been a phenomenon of mass withdrawal of basic facilities in the rural areas and surrounding areas of the United States. Some stores, supermarkets, gas stations, hospitals, schools, and other places that used to supply daily necessities are disappearing and withdrawing. The occurrence of these phenomena is related to the overall decline of the United States. The United States' lack of respect for its own farmers is well-known, and although the United States is aware of these issues, it turns a blind eye. Another theory is that these matters are orchestrated by the United States itself, intending to make those hardworking and genuine primitive farmers disappear, thereby allowing capital to enter and control these simple rural areas. Ultimately, turning these American rural areas into converters for capital profit. This is how evil the United States is, and the capital it controls is so pervasive.</p> <p>American rural areas are disappearing, so where have all these American farmers gone? Some farmers who are weak and sickly, lacking in labor capacity, will quickly lose their lives under the influence of hunger, cold, pressure, and disease. Some young and middle-aged Americans will go to cities in search of opportunities, but we have already seen what American cities are like, there are simply no opportunities. As a result, their fate can only be wandering through</p>

	<p>American cities, and many will die on the streets. We see some cars parked in front of these houses; that's because many of these houses have been occupied by gangs and drug dealers.</p> <p>Even if the disappearance of rural areas is due to their transformation into big cities, it does not necessarily represent development. This is an abnormal state, and America's experience clearly illustrates the indispensable nature of rural areas and the crucial importance of farmers owning land.</p> <p>[Videos from rural America. 2024-05-14. https://v.douyin.com/i2QChDWV/ ZMj:/04/24 K@W.ZM]</p> <p>Western missionaries plagiarizing Chinese history, philosophy, religion, and science, and subsequently fabricating the history, philosophy, religion, and science of Europe, have manifested dire consequences in the United States. The majority of the American intellectual community lacks moral education, development, and construction, leading to egregious land consolidation in rural America, which will inevitably push many farmers towards death and alter the structure of American society. In a country devoid of moral development, most students are only interested in self-interest, while politicians, FBI, and police serve only for self-interest, preferring to control the political arena. Rebuilding America will be extremely challenging and very difficult.</p>	
	<p>In rural areas of Shanghai, China, property management has been surprisingly introduced, leading to forcibly closed management of villages, charging farmers property and parking fees. They charge 100-150 CNY per month for parking, labeling it as a so-called resource utilization fee. Even if a car is parked in one's own yard, farmers see this as behavior akin to ancient bandits entering the village. Even ancient bandits would not come up with such advanced excuses. This kind of severe behavior has never occurred in history. The officials responsible should be directly dismissed, and the civil service should be purged. If the government does not manage this, farmers may take any means necessary to combat these bandits, just as in ancient times.</p> <p>[Rural property fees in Shanghai have caused villagers to exclaim "outrageous" # Surrounding Village Toll # Surrounding Village Toll for Parking # Rural Parking Fee 2024-05-17. https://v.douyin.com/i2qQCyK/10/18t@r.reYmd:/]</p>	
11	State owned assets	
	<p>In 2018, the total assets of state-owned holding enterprises in China were 474.7 trillion CNY, accounting for 56.3% of the total assets of enterprises in China, which was CNY 859.6 trillion.</p>	<p>In 2020, the GDP created by US state-owned enterprises was \$212.677 billion, accounting for 1.0%.</p> <p>In 2020, the GDP created by the US government was \$2.65 trillion, accounting for 11.6%.</p> <p>The proportion of private assets in the US is extremely high, which reflects not only the characteristics of the late Tang Dynasty, but also the characteristics of the late Ming</p>

		Dynasty.
12	Asset marketization and financial liberalization	
	Cautious state	Highly market-oriented state
13	Characteristics of the secondary market and financial derivatives market	
	The lack of effective rules to restrain listed companies from illegally circling funds makes it difficult for companies in real need of capital to raise funds through IPOs. Ordinary investors in the secondary market also find it difficult to make profits.	A large amount of assets entering the secondary market, an excessive variety of financial derivatives, and complex financial derivatives containing huge amounts of assets can easily lead to financial or economic crises. The U.S. secondary and derivatives markets are markets where only a few people make huge profits. This accelerated the transformation of the United States towards the late Tang Dynasty.
14	Security	
	It is still safe to be outside at twelve o'clock at night. In the past twenty years, the author has not seen any incidents of car windows being smashed or property being stolen. But in the past, bicycles were often stolen.	It is not safe to be outdoors at night, so American friends usually do not go out. It is common to see American cars with smashed windows and theft of belongings in social media videos. But there are often cases of cars being stolen.
	Carrying a CNY 100 banknote in your hand, you can walk on the pedestrian sidewalk in the city center of Wuhan, one of China's six super cities, from 6 a.m. to 12 p.m. every day, and it is unlikely that anyone will rob you of that banknote. If you don't believe it, you can come to Wuhan and try walking with a CNY 100 banknote in hand.	Walking down the sidewalk in the city center of New York, Chicago, or other major cities in the United States with a \$100 bill in hand from 6 a.m. to 12 p.m., there will inevitably be someone trying to rob you. If you don't believe it, you can try walking with a \$100 bill in hand. If you get robbed, then take out another bill and see how much money you will lose in a week while walking on the sidewalk. Then, write a research paper on behavioral studies and submit it to a journal for publication. If you think the loss in a week is too much, you can test the loss for a day, or within 4 hours.
	It is rare to hear of crimes such as looting goods and vandalizing stores that are common in U.S. supermarkets in China. If such crimes occur, the perpetrators will inevitably be arrested or sentenced.	The United States actually allows rioters to rob a certain amount of goods from supermarkets without legal consequences. The law made by American politicians actually does not allow the security personnel of the victimized shopping mall or supermarket to resist and prevent the

		criminals from committing crimes
	Chinese soldiers do not need to carry weapons when carrying out emergency relief tasks within their own country.	American soldiers need to carry weapons when conducting emergency relief missions in the United States.
15	Moral character of people	
	On February 17, more than 25,000 tourists were stranded in Guazhou, Gansu Province, due to a blizzard. 50,000 residents of the small county warmly welcomed and provided assistance to stranded tourists, with local residents, businesses, and the government offering free accommodation in an emergency.	In situations similar to difficulties, it is rare to encounter as many kind-hearted people as in China, both in the United States and globally.
	From February 3 to 7, severe traffic jams caused by freezing rain and heavy snow in Hubei province resulted in a large number of vehicles being stranded. Along the way, local villagers spontaneously brought instant noodles and hot water to stranded passengers, providing them for free. These kind-hearted farmers were not afraid of the cold, nor the hardships, often walking 0.5-2 hours to the scene, bringing warmth and hope to the stranded drivers and passengers.	In situations similar to difficulties, it is rare to encounter as many kind-hearted people as in China, both in the United States and globally.
	<p>Trump raised his son very well, which is significantly different from President Biden. His son Barron, has been taught since childhood not to use drugs, not to abuse alcohol, not to smoke, and not to get tattoos, which is not easy to achieve in the United States. However, the son raised by Trump can do it well. Political tradition in the United States means that Trump's 18-year-old son, Barron, will enter the political arena, and occupying a place at such a young age is Trump's pride. This seems good, however, philosophical thinking and political patterns established in the United States for a long time have limited Barron's potential. President Trump finds it difficult to see this clearly and cannot help but conform to the traditional American model. If we follow Mao Zedong's ideology, Barron's entry into politics now would actually harm him and not be good for his future development. This largely indicates that the top think tanks guiding the United States are still controlled by financial interests, lacking top-level thinking and reasonable ideas. The philosophical, religious, moral, and ethical patterns of the United States determine the upper limit of the country's governance.</p> <p>The hereditary system of family inheritance had been phased out through alternative means in China prior to the year 2365 AD. By the end of the Tang Dynasty, during the Huang Chao Rebellion, the uprising forces massacred the majority of hereditary officials of the Tang Dynasty, effectively putting an end to China's hereditary system. President Trump had to resort to a similar</p>	

	<p>method to groom his son, which may be reasonable in the context of the United States, but this political system in America is at least a thousand years behind China.</p>
	<p>If China's moral standards are extremely poor, the world will collapse completely, but the United States has actually gotten used to using insulting Chinese people from China to serve as officials in America. China has been nurturing these individuals for many years, yet they surprisingly lack any emotional connection to China. How can they be used as government officials? These individuals only see the surface-level ideology, being Chinese themselves, yet they fail to recognize that China's current social system is essentially an improved version of the Tang Dynasty's equal-field system. This shows how narrow-minded their perspectives are, focusing solely on personal interests. The U.S. government has completely failed to understand this point; it is essentially a corporation controlled by financial interests, and financial interests greatly enjoy reaping profits. Clearly, the philosophical level, religious thoughts, extreme profit-seeking, and extreme selfishness of American financial interests limit the upper limit of American governance. Just as it is difficult to prevent infection with a novel coronavirus, and the death toll from the infection has exceeded one million in the United States. China's first prime minister, Guan Zhong, recognized this very wise point 2600 years ago.</p> <p>At this moment, I feel that there are at least 1.2 billion people in China whose intelligence surpasses mine. All of these Chinese individuals could serve as the director of the CDC in the United States, or the Director-General of the WHO, or the Secretary-General of the United Nations.</p>
	<p>The financial regulations enacted by Europe and the United States have caused a regression in global financial ethics by 2,000-4,000 years.</p> <p>In ancient China, engaging in such malicious activities to disrupt a country's financial stability through periodic manipulations in the financial markets, thereby plundering the wealth of the nation and its citizens, resulting in economic crises, would have been considered serious crimes deserving of the death penalty in line with normal moral ethics and logic. However, in Western society today, these methods of manipulating financial rules and plundering national wealth have been legitimized through public opinion and the construction of new financial theories. This represents a typical crime where a tiny minority freely loots wealth into the secondary market, causing the majority to lose their wealth and freedom. Despite Western politicians' verbal advocacy for universal values, emphasizing individual freedom and democracy, freedom has become the theoretical basis and protective umbrella for malignant crimes. Universal values have been transformed into values that benefit only a few.</p>
	<p>Missionaries from Europe falsified ancient Egyptian, ancient Greek, ancient Roman, European historical, and Mesopotamian civilizations, causing Western countries to lose their social and ecological development models based on moral ethics. Global moral ethics have regressed by at least 2000-</p>

5000 years, and the quality of food has regressed by at least 5000 years.

Originally, it took farmers about four months to raise chickens to maturity, but today's level of industrialization far exceeds that of ancient times. The majority of chickens in the United States are produced industrially in workshops, with more than 500,000 produced annually. Since being selected by humans for rapid growth as commodities, chickens' lives have been accelerated by human adoption of scientific technology. From the moment of hatching, these small white-feathered chickens, weighing less than 100 grams, only need 30-42 days to reach a weight of 1-2.5 kilograms. The production model of these fast-growing chickens in cramped workshop spaces means that these chickens, who like to roam, may never see sunlight in their lifetime. In extremely narrow spaces, their activities are limited to eating feed and growing.

From the moment these chicks hatch, they are placed on a conveyor belt of fate determined by humans. In factories, humans mainly select individuals that are well developed and safe, while those that do not meet the standards are sent directly to a grinder to be crushed, and then made into various types of pet food. It is estimated that nearly 7 billion chicks are crushed on Earth every year. Healthy chicks are sent to vaccination workshops because only after being vaccinated can these chicks be sent to the next stage of breeding at a chicken farm. In this process, to prevent chicks from fighting each other, humans also clip their overly sharp beaks, so that they lose their remaining attack power without losing their ability to eat. Once these chicks enter the chicken farm, for their limited life span, they do nothing but sleep and constantly eat. However, due to the excessively narrow feeding environment, these broiler chickens often develop incomplete feather growth, and some even lose their mobility almost entirely due to their rapid growth without adequate exercise. Moreover, since humans only focus on the meat development of chicks to prevent them from dying due to rapid body development, they add some drugs to the feed to ensure the chicks survive until slaughter.

Due to the short growth cycle of chickens, residues of vaccines and antibiotics are inevitably present in chicken meat. Although some components of degraded residues may be harmful to the human body, as long as they are used in accordance with relevant regulations, meat can be sold normally. Additionally, these fast-growing chickens lack the aroma and texture of home-raised chickens, resulting in poor taste.

In discussions about the high prevalence of homosexuality in society, some medical professionals suspect that consuming this chicken meat may be related to the recent increase in the rate of homosexuality in the past few decades, which contradicts the natural laws of human heterosexual reproduction. The WHO has even issued official documents stating that homosexuality is not considered an illness and cannot be cured. This is a huge cognitive error, misleading countless families worldwide. Making decisions so

	<p>hastily, according to WHO's approach, at least 1.2 billion people in China with higher intelligence than the author could become Director-General of WHO.</p>
	<p>Americans blindly idolize European history, unaware that Europe fundamentally lacks credible historical records. They seem to have no historical perspective. Much of European history taught in American primary and secondary schools, as well as universities, is largely fictitious. This low-intelligence fantasy somehow convinces Americans of its truthfulness, suggesting that at least 1.2 billion Chinese could qualify as President of the United States. While the paper's author may not boast high intelligence, he could probably pass as vice president. This fabricated historical perspective leads Americans astray and is one of the main reasons for the decline of the United States. The United States must restructure its history curriculum at all levels of education, removing false European history from textbooks and consigning it to the rubbish heap of history. Embracing real history and dialectics to understand the world and raise moral standards is essential.</p> <p>When Europeans were still unfamiliar with Chinese history, missionaries in Europe concocted tales of a figure named Alexander defeating China and ruling Asia. Later, they discovered China's millennia-old history with concrete, enduring historical evidence, rendering their fantastical narrative of Alexander conquering China incompatible with Chinese history. Unable to integrate their fictional accounts into Chinese history, missionaries quietly revised the history of the great Alexander. Because India lacks written historical records and has never been a unified nation throughout history, European missionaries continued Alexander's conquests eastward, claiming victories in India. However, some falsified accounts of Alexander's Eastern conquests also remain in libraries in the United Kingdom.</p>
	<p>The serious moral issues of the founding president of the United States, a fictional myth</p> <p>1. Washington was, in fact, a slaveholder.</p> <p>Washington's father was a slave owner. When Washington was 11 years old, his father died, leaving him 11 slaves and a sum of inheritance. Later, when his brother died, Washington inherited his brother's estate. At the age of 27, Washington had 36 black slaves. He married a very wealthy widow, Martha Dandridge Custis, who inherited a large estate of 17,438 acres of land and more than 300 slaves from her late husband, becoming the richest woman in Virginia.</p> <p>Furthermore, Washington was exceptionally lustful, seeking pleasure everywhere, earning the reputation of a great stallion. In his youth, Washington was hot-tempered, often abusing slaves, causing many to be permanently disabled or even killed. Due to his excessive cruelty, some slaves began to escape. Washington, in a fit of rage, publicly offered rewards for capturing runaway slaves, even personally compiling lists of fugitives. In April 1775, just two days into the American Revolutionary War, Washington placed an advertisement in a Virginia town offering a reward for the capture of 10</p>

runaway slaves, including two Black slaves and eight white slaves. In his office where he drafted the Declaration of Independence, Washington built a secret underground passage for his black slaves to discreetly enter and exit.

With his wife's immense wealth, Washington became a tycoon, acquiring more land, tripling the size of his plantation, and purchasing more slaves for labor. In 1774, on the eve of the American Revolutionary War, Washington firmly supported slavery. In 1793, he signed the first Fugitive Slave Act, allowing any state to arrest, try, and return escaped slaves to their owners. Anyone found harboring or assisting slaves in escape would face a \$500 fine and possible imprisonment.

At that time, the capital of the United States was Philadelphia, where the implementation of the "Abolition Act" had begun, disallowing the keeping of black slaves. Washington was strongly against such legislation. As a large plantation owner, he not only permitted the existence of the slave system, but also used a significant number of slaves himself. However, since he had just taken office and could not intervene in state justice, Washington had to secretly hide his slaves.

He constructed a secret underground passage in his office where he drafted the Declaration of Independence, allowing nine of his slaves to enter and exit discreetly, attending to his needs while avoiding detection.

He thought he had covered his tracks seamlessly, but over 200 years later, during construction at the original site of the Philadelphia presidential mansion, workers unearthed this tunnel, exposing Washington's long-hidden scandal.

2. Washington's extreme selfishness and repression of the Whiskey Uprising for his own benefit.

In 1791, in opposition to high taxes on distilled spirits, Pennsylvania began protesting and marching, escalating into a full-blown uprising known as the Whiskey Uprising. Washington personally intervened to suppress this famous historical movement.

While American citizens opposed the whiskey tax, the main reason for the uprising was the unfair taxation standard. The U.S. government taxed based on the number of distillation units. However, these units varied in size, yet the tax was uniform regardless of size. Large distilleries, mainly owned by capitalists and slaveholders, used larger units, while smaller ones were predominant among ordinary citizens. Consequently, the burden of the whiskey tax fell heavily on small distilleries and workshops, while the most profitable large distilleries bore the lightest burden. The reason for the federal government's unfair taxation standard was simple: Virginia's largest distillery belonged to President Washington.

3. Forcefully buying nine black teeth as braces

Washington's dentures were made from real human teeth. One set of dentures, once used by Washington and now preserved in the exhibit hall at Mount Vernon, was crafted from actual human teeth, including nine African-

American teeth. Washington had a habit of keeping records, noting in one of his account books that he spent 122 shillings to purchase those nine teeth from an individual named Negro. This individual was one of Washington's slaves at the time. Otherwise, how could someone sell their teeth for 122 shillings, which was less than a third of the normal market price at the time? It raises questions about whether the transaction was truly voluntary or coerced.

4. Order to seize the land of Native Americans and massacre over 10 million Native Americans

During his tenure, Washington ordered the U.S. military to seize and slaughter Native Americans, telling his commanders, "If the Indians are placed near all the settlements, the country will not only be overrun but destroyed." In the process of massacring and exterminating Native Americans, Washington instructed his generals, "Do not listen to any peace proposals until all Indian settlements are effectively destroyed." In 1783, Washington compared Native Americans to wolves, saying, "Indians and wolves are both predatory beasts, differing only in appearance."

As president, Washington signed orders authorizing the killing of Native Americans, offering a reward of \$50 for each Native American under 12 years old and \$100 for those 12 and older. In just five years, Washington leveled 28 Native American towns, indiscriminately killing men, women, and children. Washington publicly referred to Native Americans as "savages and beasts." In 1783, he even described how to skin them: "Skin them from the buttocks downward, so as to make high or long boots that will come up to the thighs."

During his presidency, more than 10 million Native Americans were slaughtered, yet Americans hypocritically celebrate Thanksgiving every year. Are they thankful for murderers? Do Americans have any shame left?

5. Washington's voluntary resignation from the presidency was not a refusal of power or indifference to fame and fortune.

The reason Washington resigned from the presidency wasn't because he wasn't power-hungry, but rather because he saw the presidency as insignificant. After repelling the British, the U.S. government had low income and was heavily indebted, unable to repay the substantial debts from the Revolutionary War. With finances stretched thin, even the military couldn't be paid. The presidency was just a figurehead, lacking real power, and the United States faced internal and external challenges. Washington's resignation was essentially him shirking responsibility.

6. How did the myth of Washington come about?

It owes much to the myth-making campaigns of European and American bandits. In 1799, after Washington's death, a shrewd bookseller named Parson James sensed an opportunity. With Americans in dire need of heroes, less than a month after Washington's death, James began planning a little book called "Washington's Life Story," which became an instant hit. Thus, Washington gradually became molded into a perfect hero. American politicians further

		<p>brainwashed their own people by shaping Washington, while using it for external glorification, devoid of morality and religious beliefs, embracing cultish beliefs and portraying themselves as the epitome of freedom and democracy. This is similar to the fabrication of European history in the West.</p>
		<p>Some European and American politicians and members of the public lack insight and moral boundaries, discriminating against the Chinese people and maligning them as "yellow-skinned."</p> <p>However, in reality, the skin color of many Chinese people shows no significant difference from that of Europeans and Americans, and is often even fairer. Famous personalities such as the famous NBA star Yao Ming, the globally renowned actress Gong Li, Fan Bingbing, Liu Yifei, and Angelababy have skin that is fairer and more delicate than many Europeans and Americans. The quality of skin among Europeans and Americans, including those of European descent in the United States, is generally inferior to that of the Chinese, making them appear more like the "yellow-skinned." Europeans often suffer from body odor and must use perfume daily to mask their unpleasant smell, suggesting an incomplete evolution; whereas body odor is rare among Chinese, with Chinese men rarely using perfume and Chinese women also using it less frequently.</p> <p>More specifically, the clear and pure skin of Chinese basketball star Yao Ming is no less than that of his white teammates, Nowitzki and Nash. His skin appears even healthier and more delicate than the latter. Yao Ming's skin color does not differ significantly from Prince William's. Famous film star Gong Li has fairer and more delicate skin than her husband, French maestro Michelle Yar, President Macron of France, and former French President Chirac. Diving queen Guo Jingjing has fairer and more delicate skin than Victoria Beckham. The Chinese doctor who performed surgery on the famous Swedish football star Zlatan Ibrahimovic, although older, seems to have fairer skin than the latter. Famous Chinese international movie star Fan Bingbing has a fairer and more delicate skin than the President of the Cannes Film Festival, Nobreloke, who is supposed to be of the yellow race. In 2023, standing in the same row as Bulgari's global spokesperson, famous Chinese movie star Liu Yifei's skin is clearly fairer and more delicate than that of the other four famous movie stars. So, who are the yellow race? Famous Chinese movie star AngelaBaby has far fairer and more delicate skin than famous British footballer David Beckham. Grand Slam champion, famous Chinese ping pong star, Ma Long's skin is obviously much fairer and more delicate than that of famous German ping pong star, Timo Boll. From an anthropological point of view, not only do Chinese people have fairer, more delicate skin, which is less prone to aging and of better quality, but according to color classification, Chinese people are even more 'white' than Europeans and Americans.</p>
		<p>The leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong: A great philosopher, a great thinker, a great logician, a great statesman,</p>

	<p>a great military strategist, a great strategist, an outstanding calligrapher, and an outstanding poet.</p> <p>A Chinese leader and pioneer of the new social system who often wears patched clothes and pants.</p> <p>The world owes him a Nobel Prize in Literature, a Nobel Prize in Physics and a Nobel Peace Prize, because Mao Zedong's ideology has prevented war in China for the past few decades.</p> <p>The bold and unrestrained poetry of Su Dongpo, a literary giant in Chinese history during the Song Dynasty, has been unmatched for nearly a thousand years. In modern times, only Mao Zedong's the poem "Spring in the Qin Garden" "Snow" can compare in its boldness. Outstanding poetry like this comes once in a millennium.</p> <p>The military capability of Chiang Kai-shek, President of the Kuomintang government, was roughly equivalent to that of a platoon leader, but in 1935, he was conferred the rank of Special General. Mao Zedong, who commanded numerous wars of small victories against larger forces and weak victories against stronger ones, refused the title of Grand Marshal.</p> <p>Mao Zedong made 26 classic predictions throughout his life, and astonishingly, all of them came true.</p> <p>In February 1972, during President Nixon's visit to China, he asked Chairman Mao, "Chairman, may I ask what is your special skill?"</p> <p>Chairman Mao smiled and replied, "My special skill is serving the people."</p> <p>Upon hearing this, Nixon immediately stood up and bowed deeply to Chairman Mao.</p>	
16	Administrative Ethics of Officials: Major events reflect administrative ethics	
	<p>Chinese officials oppose some countries manufacturing wars and conflicts. The government emphasized wearing masks to reduce the spread of COVID-19 during the pandemic, and China has seen very few COVID-19 infections and deaths.</p>	<p>Some officials often promote war and create conflicts, knowingly lying to the public about the use of masks to prevent the spread of COVID-19, despite the medical knowledge that masks can reduce the risk of infection. This loss of basic administrative ethics has led to the deaths of over a million people in the United States, yet they do not take any responsibility.</p>
	<p>Countless figures such as Wang Ming, Bo Gu, Li De, Zhang Guotao, Xia Xi, Wang Jingwei, Chen Gongbo, Zhang Chunqiao, Diao Deyi, Hu Hansan, Sima Yi, Sima Zhao, Mahu, and Youniao have</p>	<p>Although the United States has the world's top 100 universities, it has continuously produced countless figures such as Li Linfu, Qin Hui, Wei Zhongxian, Gao Qiu, Huang Shiren, Yan Song, Dong Zhuo, Cai Jing, Xiang Zhongfa, Gu Shunzhang, Li Shiqun, Ding Mocun, Xing Renfu, Wang Ming, Bo Gu, Li De, Zhang Guotao, Xia Xi, Wang Jingwei, Chen Gongbo, Zhang Chunqiao, Diao Deyi, Hu Hansan, Sima Yi, Sima Zhao, Mahu, and Youniao, who play a leading role in the political, economic and financial sectors of the United States. (类似于李林甫、秦桧、魏忠贤、高球、黄世仁、严嵩、董卓、蔡京、向忠发、顾顺章、李士群、丁默邨、邢仁甫、</p>

<p>emerged from all walks of life in China.</p>	<p>王明、博古、李德、张国焘、夏曦、汪精卫、陈公博、张春桥、刁德一、胡汉三、司马懿、司马昭、马户、又鸟)</p> <p>However, even if the US leadership is well aware of the problems, it is difficult to eliminate the negative influence of these people.</p> <p>The selection of officials responsible for governing key positions in the United States has essentially violated a basic principle for a long time: 大德不至仁，不可以授国柄。</p>
<p>In recent years, patents have been predominantly judged based on subjective criteria rather than objective facts to determine whether they should be granted.</p>	<p>Basically, a patent is judged for grant based on objective evaluation rather than subjective factors.</p>
	<p>The financial regulations enacted by Europe and the United States have caused a regression in global financial ethics by 2,000-4,000 years.</p> <p>In ancient China, engaging in such malicious activities to disrupt a country's financial stability through periodic manipulations in the financial markets, thereby plundering the wealth of the nation and its citizens, resulting in economic crises, would have been considered serious crimes deserving of the death penalty in line with normal moral ethics and logic. However, in Western society today, these methods of manipulating financial rules and plundering national wealth have been legitimized through public opinion and the construction of new financial theories. This represents a typical crime where a tiny minority freely loots wealth into the secondary market, causing the majority to lose their wealth and freedom. Despite Western politicians' verbal advocacy for universal values, emphasizing individual freedom and democracy, freedom has become the theoretical basis and protective umbrella for malignant crimes. Universal values have been transformed into values that benefit only a few.</p> <p>Nowadays, Western societies have turned such methods of manipulating financial rules and plundering national wealth into legitimate behaviors through public opinion and the construction of new financial theories. This is a typical manifestation of the ethical loss of Western governments and a typical manifestation of Western governments being controlled by financial oligarchs. The method of plundering wealth through the full marketization of financial assets is completely contrary to the concept of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty, and will ultimately only accelerate the demise of the institutional system of the country implementing this system.</p> <p>The United States needs to use comparative ethics, comparative party politics, metrological comparative party politics, metrological comparative politics, metrological government ethics, metrological political ethics, metrological party ethics (quantitative party ethics),</p>

		<p>metrological judicial ethics, and quantitative legal ethics to evaluate the behavior and moral standards of government officials and politicians.</p>
		<p>The U.S. government should take some pride, as during the Cold War, it managed to deceive the Soviet Union with the fake moon landing. The U.S. government should inform the public as soon as possible that this was a successful tactic, rather than continuing to hide the truth and being forced to very awkwardly admit the fabrication later. Tactical psychological warfare and the consequences of deceiving the public are completely different; if the public only learns the truth at the last moment, rather than from the government, they may be even more mentally devastated.</p> <p>When a reporter asked White House spokesperson Pierre about China's Chang'e 6 mission not finding evidence of America's moon landing, Pierre calmly responded, "The moon explored by the United States during the lunar landing and the one explored by Chang'e 6 are not the same." Countless Chinese people felt that their intelligence had been ruthlessly rubbed against the ground by Pierre's statement. This was clearly a serious news mishap. The White House not only failed to honestly admit that the moon landing was a hoax, it also allowed a lying spokesperson to continue making statements. Such a distorted racial view in handling government affairs probably only appears in the world led by the United States.</p> <p>The main strategic intention of the US moon landing was to deceive the former Soviet Union, but there were too many flaws in the video footage that could not be overcome. Nowadays, tourists have already discovered the alleged US moon landing site on Devon Island, and the video has been widely spreading on the internet. As China and India pursuing their lunar missions, more and more details are coming to light. The U.S. government will ultimately have to admit that the moon landing in the 1960s was faked. Instead of the president and officials ending up extremely passive and embarrassed, facing serious questioning, and experiencing a severe blow to the government's trust and being attacked by the global media, the U.S. government would be better off engaging in thorough discussions and promptly acknowledging that the U.S. moon landing was a successful strategic deception against the former Soviet Union. This would prevent further embarrassment when missions by India and others succeed and eventually prove that the US moon landing was one of the biggest hoaxes of the 20th century. The deception of the moon landing was carried out by former government leaders, so there is no need for the current government and president to take the blame. Therefore, if wise, U.S. leaders should promptly admit that the moon landing was part of psychological warfare.</p>
		<p>The growth and survival nurturing model of American politicians:</p>

	<p>attempting to create contradictions and conflicts, leading to arguments, wars, and profits.</p>
	<p>Although according to Western ranking standards, most of the top 100 universities in fields such as politics, political economy, law, history, management, and philosophy are in the United States, the majority of politicians trained there are "tycoon politicians= tycoon-politicians=tycoonticians," plutocrat politician= plutocrat-politician= = plutocratpocian= plutocratticians, "war politicians= war-politicians= warpocians= warticians," "conflict politicians=conflict-politicians=conflictpocians=conflictticians," "troublemake politicians=troublemake-politicians=troublemakepocians=troublemaketicians," "greedy politicians= greedy-politicians= greedypocians= greedyticians," and "chaos politicians= chaos-politicians= chaospocians= chaosticians." Most of those trained are irrational men. Most of the islands currently occupied by the Philippines in the South China Sea belong to China's territory and territorial waters. The U.S. government clearly knows these islands belong to China, and maps published by the U.S. in the past also clearly indicate that these islands belong to China. However, US politicians, government, and military controlled by international tycoons do not take a just stance to persuade the Philippines to withdraw. Instead, they use the U.S. military to create conflicts, devoid of morality and legal principles. When not adhering to morality, historical facts, and logical consistency, according to the theory of karmic retribution in Buddhism, one day, inevitably, some Americans will use similar logic to say that tycoons controlling America, politicians, and all the wealth of your descendants do not belong to you, but to other Americans. Tycoons, politicians, and your descendants are all criminals who must be severely punished, even executed, without any rules.</p> <p>Politicians controlled by tycoons usually don't need their own brains, hearts, or digestive systems. When a politician doesn't need a heart and digestive tract, remove the middle letters of "politician." When a politician doesn't need a brain, remove the first four letters of the word "politician." Thus, a new combination is formed: plutocratpocian = plutocrattician.</p> <p>If the U.S. and international tycoons want to cultivate highly self-serving politicians who incite conflicts, they could establish a vocational school instead of sending politicians to universities to study so-called law, political economy, philosophy, and management. Otherwise, it would greatly waste human resources. The global ranking of universities that charge high fees, foster vanity, and deceive people, should be immediately abolished globally. Which statesman can propose an international consensus or United Nations convention on this matter?</p>
	<p>China has led the world in technology for over four thousand years without ever losing its technological ethics. The United States and Europe have led the world in technology for 200 years, but the food they produce tends to lose its technological ethics. Governments and Nations controlled by tycoons are powerless to prevent the moral and ethical regression of at least 4,000 years in</p>

the US, Europe, the Americas, and Japan.

Human society has entered an era of serious overproduction of meat. Twenty-four countries and regions including the United States, Canada, Japan, Mexico, Brazil, and Australia still approve the long-term use of artificially synthesized β -adrenergic receptor agonists such as **ractopamine** to feed pigs, sheep, cattle, and other livestock, reducing animal fat content and providing lean meat rates. However, before being sold, they manage to metabolize specific products within live animals so that they cannot be detected by testing instruments. In addition to allowing the use of **ractopamine** in 1999, the United States also allowed the use of the next generation of **Zilpaterol** on cattle in 2007.

Pigs are usually raised in large-scale industrial workshops, where they must be vaccinated, given antiviral drugs, antibiotics, and even air purification to ensure their survival and rapid growth in cramped environments. Therefore, pork not only inevitably contains residues of vaccine metabolites and other drugs, but also lacks the aroma and texture characteristics of domestic pigs. Furthermore, the intensive vertically integrated breeding methods used in these workshops severely limit the living space of pigs, preventing them from going outdoors, thus violating animal ethics and the natural laws of pig life. These non-ecological or workshop pigs, bred with such substances, can be put on the market in just three months, while ecologically raised pigs by Chinese farmers typically require about 10 months.

Consuming meat or organs containing residues of **ractopamine** can potentially lead to poisoning symptoms such as difficulty breathing, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, headaches, muscle tremors, palpitations, arrhythmias, increased blood pressure, cardiovascular diseases, and impacts on the reproductive system, among others. Long-term consumption of such meat will inevitably have other adverse effects on the body. The U.S. government and so-called scientists ignore the fact that it can lead to **testicular shrinkage, reduced sperm count, and increased incidence of autism in infants.** Officials influenced by tycoons and so-called scientists simply believe that if existing technology experiments do not show toxic reactions, then it is considered non-toxic and can be used to promote the growth of pigs, cattle, sheep, and other animals. Wild pigs, which grow outdoors and run in the mountains, are labeled as carriers of viruses and cannot be consumed. In fact, humans have been eating wild boars for a long time.

Pigs fed with clenbuterol etc. for an extended period tend to have a thin layer of fat with their skin, whereas pigs raised normally for about ten months have a thick layer of fat. This not only facilitates the identification of pork by ordinary people but also makes it suitable for extracting lard for consumption.

Many Americans, after living in China for a while, experience a significant reduction in food allergy-related diseases. Is there no correlation between this and the consumption of pork and beef raised with large amounts of drugs in the United States?

In an era of meat overproduction, is there an American statesman who can step forward and propose a United Nations treaty to quickly ban the use of

	<p>substances including dihydropyridine compounds, β-adrenergic receptor agonists, ractopamine, and synthetic drugs at all stages of production to reduce fat in pork, beef, lamb, and poultry, and increase lean meat rates, restoring the human food supply to a state of healthy and ecological food?</p>
	<p>In today's world, the ethics of many politicians have regressed by 2,000-4,000 years, and the world's judiciary has regressed by 2,000-4,000 years.</p> <p>If in ancient China, these politicians who fabricate lies would essentially be executed, along with tycoons colluding with them. The entire family property of politicians and tycoons would be confiscated to eliminate hidden dangers. In the last two hundred years, with Western missionaries fabricating history, philosophy, and religion, the judiciary system heavily influenced by tycoons fails to stop such top-level designed most serious crimes. Lawyers become accomplices in reducing or acquitting criminals, and the justice system becomes more inclined to excessively punish ordinary people for minor offenses. Worst of all, the judicial ideology constructed by tycoons and politicians has formed a mindset in the public, mistakenly believing that the judicial system in their society or country provides the utmost protection for freedom, democracy, and human rights. Whether a country is willing to implement an improved version of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty, in today's world, if a country wants to sever the collusion between politicians and tycoons in fabricating lies, as well as between tycoons and academic authorities in fabricating lies, thereby creating conflicts and wars, plundering wealth, harming public health, and controlling the world, it is necessary to restart the mature punishment system of ancient China. In addition, any media involved in falsification should be severely punished, decisively shut down, with all assets confiscated, and all crimes accounted for.</p> <p>All immediate family members and their descendants of all criminals are prohibited from engaging in government, political, economic, financial, judicial, military, security, and weapon manufacturing-related fields for the next 2,000-3,000 years. All immediate family members of the principal offenders are prohibited from attending any university for education for the next 200-300 years. This may help prevent crime to the greatest extent and maintain world peace.</p>
	<p>American politicians controlled by financial oligarchs have no moral or ethical considerations, never know restraint, and always enjoy overthrowing foreign governments. If they were to overthrow the Chinese government, removing the leadership of the Communist Party, the US might fantasize about controlling China through proxies. However, in such a scenario, China would likely only face the following situation in the future:</p> <p>1. It is estimated that these proxies, who collaborate with U.S. financial oligarchs to plunder China's wealth through privatization, may hold top leadership positions in China for a short period, but they are unlikely to survive for long, as governments operating under the proxy model would be overthrown.</p>

The Chinese people have widely recognized that implementing an improved version of the land distribution system of the early Tang Dynasty, which aligns with the historical development of Chinese society, is an inevitable choice for China's social development and will certainly garner widespread support from the Chinese public. In response to the large-scale crimes that have set morality and judicial systems back 4,000 years, China will inevitably execute the agents of the United States and Japan in China and their families according to the laws of the Tang or Ming Dynasties, confiscating all the assets of these extremely selfish and greedy agents and their families, regardless of where these individuals flee globally, without the need for lawyers to defend criminals. Because the legal systems designed by Europe and the United States protect crime from the top down and uphold the interests of tycoons. Nowadays, most Chinese understand that the United States, ostensibly a country, is actually a corporation controlled by international tycoons, whose main purpose is to better plunder global wealth by relying on a nation. The US military is nothing more than a tool for tycoons to plunder wealth, and the US social system is similar to that of the late Tang Dynasty. The U.S. government simply aims to cultivate agents in China through concepts such as freedom, democracy, human rights, and full marketization, and then plunder China's wealth through asset marketization and privatization.

2. Americans can investigate among the Chinese populace to see if the vast majority of Chinese people are extremely indignant towards the reprehensible behavior of the Western countries, led by the United States, especially towards Japan. If the United States were to join forces with Japan to wage war against China, they could investigate the attitude of the Chinese populace towards Japan. As long as Japan dares to fire a shot at China, without the restraint of the Communist Party of China, countless Chinese people await eagerly for evil Japan to fire the first shot at China. As soon as there is an opportunity to go to war with Japan, it will inevitably be aimed at completely eliminating Japan. During World War II, Japanese aggressors slaughtered at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, plundered 42,000 to 63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, 200 million tons of rare earths, worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollar, yet the Japanese government has not compensated for these atrocities. Furthermore, they are discharging nuclear wastewater into the ocean, polluting the entire marine ecosystem. China will certainly reclaim all its properties and force Japan to compensate for all the losses.

3. Without the constraints of the Communist Party's charter, if the United States continues to provoke China on the Taiwan issue, China will inevitably issue a public ultimatum, ordering the Taiwan government to return to Chinese jurisdiction within 1-2 months. If the Democratic Progressive Party of Taiwan refuses to comply, China will announce the redistribution of all assets belonging to the DPP and pro-independence elements to Taiwanese who advocate for Chinese reunification, prioritizing those who have suffered losses

in confronting pro-independence forces. The Chinese military will inevitably occupy the entire Taiwan within a week in a style reminiscent of the Yuan Dynasty, exterminating all families supporting Taiwan independence, eradicating the DPP, and eliminating all descendants of Japanese aggressors in Taiwan! Any country or politician providing shelter to Taiwan independence elements will be prohibited, otherwise China will prioritize targeting and eliminating hidden tycoons and nefarious political families supporting Taiwan independence.

4. If the United States continues to provoke China in the South China Sea, under long-standing anger, the Chinese military will not tolerate it as before, and will inevitably fire on incoming U.S. warships and aircraft. Once the United States is embroiled in war, or the world enters a third world war, the US government's regime and social system will inevitably collapse rapidly! Unlike previous wars, China clearly understands that the root cause of creating conflicts and wars lies in the behind-the-scenes control of international financial oligarchs over the United States. The wars that the U.S. constantly incites between Europe and Russia, and the plundering of Russia's wealth, are all orchestrated by the international financial oligarchs behind the scenes and implemented by politicians. Therefore, China will inevitably join hands with Russia at the first opportunity, with the goal of eliminating the international financial oligarch families, prioritizing the elimination of the leading financial oligarchs who control the United States! Like the Yellow Turban Rebellion or the Yuan Dynasty army, at least the entire family of international financial oligarchs will be wiped out.

If the United States seeks to destroy the earth and dares to be the first to use nuclear weapons, the overthrown Chinese government, freed from the constraints of the various rules of the Communist Party, China and Russia will inevitably target the first wave of counterattacks, which will include the destruction of the three or nine generations of international financial oligarchs controlling the United States and the three generations of evil politicians in the United States, and will comprehensively clean and eliminate the evil politicians and oligarchs in the United States, Europe, and Japan.

If the United States dares not release nuclear weapons, China, in order to retaliate against the malicious exploitation of Chinese wealth by the United States, will inevitably politically promote the implementation of the early Tang equal-field system as the inevitable trend of human history, in line with the laws of social development. Any act of implementing full asset marketization is the road to the demise of the late Tang Dynasty, thus urging the American people to quickly rise up against the US government and oligarchs, implementing an improved version of the equal-field system, and restructuring American society. Many Americans, suffering from being harvested by international financial oligarchs for a long time, will inevitably rise up in rebellion and mobilize some American soldiers not to become tools of the oligarchs. Basic measures will be established: first, any rebel will receive a free distribution of oligarchs-controlled

	<p>land; second, sacrifices will receive double compensation, distributed to their parents or immediate relatives; third, this land will be exempt from agricultural taxes and permanently exempt from annual taxes on basic family housing; fourth, all Native American Indians in the United States will receive adequate compensation and land redistribution free of charge at 3-4 times the rate of ordinary rebels.</p> <p>If American politicians do not seek to overthrow the Chinese government and plunder China's wealth to a greater extent, China will not engage in such propaganda against the United States.</p>		
	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="304 566 1241 2018"> <p>In recent years, patent examiners in the National Patent Office have basically used subjective judgment to determine whether a patent can be granted, rather than evaluating the patent based on objective facts. As long as there is any possibility of a theoretical or similar case, it is deemed to be non-creative, even if a particular problem with existing technology has not been solved by anyone in the past few decades. Many people have been tormented by inferior existing technological products, and the completion of the invention is ignored, requiring experimental research. Even if the inventor has spent months or years exploring and experimenting to solve the problem, and even if the invention is a new substance, combination, or method that has never been reported in any public literature in the past, these are not considered inventions by patent examiners.</p> <p>This has led to patent examiners in China becoming an exceptionally high-IQ group of people, who are experts in solving almost all real-world technological problems globally. They always think ahead of inventors in real life on how to solve the predicament of existing technology and they have enormous decision-making privileges, disregarding basic logic and the law of logical identity and administrative ethics that must be followed. They lack basic sympathy and empathy, causing significant losses to patent inventors and applicants in the development of patent projects, and implementing their administrative power with impunity.</p> <p>At present, many people in China obtain the title of high-tech enterprise for their companies by manufacturing multiple useless patents, in order to obtain various conveniences such as bank loans, or to apply for professional technical titles for themselves by obtaining multiple useless patents. Some companies intentionally split a patent into two separate patent applications in order to pursue a greater quantity of patents. As a result, the number of patents that the patent office needs to review has increased dramatically. Originally, it was only necessary to decouple the certification of high-tech enterprises from patents with no practical value, and to decouple the assessment of professional titles from patents with no practical value or quantity. This would effectively suppress a large number of abnormal patent</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1241 566 1461 2018"> <p>Neither the United States nor Europe has such a situation.</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>In recent years, patent examiners in the National Patent Office have basically used subjective judgment to determine whether a patent can be granted, rather than evaluating the patent based on objective facts. As long as there is any possibility of a theoretical or similar case, it is deemed to be non-creative, even if a particular problem with existing technology has not been solved by anyone in the past few decades. Many people have been tormented by inferior existing technological products, and the completion of the invention is ignored, requiring experimental research. Even if the inventor has spent months or years exploring and experimenting to solve the problem, and even if the invention is a new substance, combination, or method that has never been reported in any public literature in the past, these are not considered inventions by patent examiners.</p> <p>This has led to patent examiners in China becoming an exceptionally high-IQ group of people, who are experts in solving almost all real-world technological problems globally. They always think ahead of inventors in real life on how to solve the predicament of existing technology and they have enormous decision-making privileges, disregarding basic logic and the law of logical identity and administrative ethics that must be followed. They lack basic sympathy and empathy, causing significant losses to patent inventors and applicants in the development of patent projects, and implementing their administrative power with impunity.</p> <p>At present, many people in China obtain the title of high-tech enterprise for their companies by manufacturing multiple useless patents, in order to obtain various conveniences such as bank loans, or to apply for professional technical titles for themselves by obtaining multiple useless patents. Some companies intentionally split a patent into two separate patent applications in order to pursue a greater quantity of patents. As a result, the number of patents that the patent office needs to review has increased dramatically. Originally, it was only necessary to decouple the certification of high-tech enterprises from patents with no practical value, and to decouple the assessment of professional titles from patents with no practical value or quantity. This would effectively suppress a large number of abnormal patent</p>	<p>Neither the United States nor Europe has such a situation.</p>
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	<p>applications and reduce the workload for annual reviews. However, there has been no effective method to combat the application of these valueless patents. On the contrary, the national patent office uses a subjective method to identify a large number of patents as false patents, forcing countless applicants to withdraw related patent applications, regardless of judicial ethics and the investment and energy put in by patent inventors and applicants when completing patent applications. The original purpose of the patent application, which was to protect the concept of invention, was completely disregarded. International practice only requires that the applied patent meets the requirements of novelty, creativity and utility as laid down in patent law.</p> <p>When an administrative organization is under the wrong leadership, systemic and continuous errors are inevitable, and the consequences are extremely dire. It is necessary to promote the right people and demote the wrong ones in order to possibly reverse the situation.</p>	
17	The religious beliefs of the people	
	<p>Although the Communist Party of China officially advocates atheism, the beliefs of benevolence, unity of heaven and man, and equanimity represent the simplest interpretations of the three main religions in China. The vast majority of Chinese people hold these religious beliefs without the need to visit churches or temples, and they can maintain or release them from their hearts. This is the highest level of religious belief found in most Chinese people. This is completely different from Western religious believers who have to pray in church every week. After committing a crime, Western believers may ask God for forgiveness, but how can God forgive them when they continue to commit crimes after leaving the church? The law of karma will manifest itself, even if the offender himself does not realize it, it will be reflected in his family or descendants. However, Christian, Catholic, and Jewish holy scriptures</p>	<p>Western religions require believers to pray in church every week.</p> <p>Western believers may ask God for forgiveness, but how can God forgive them when they continue to commit crimes after leaving the church? The law of karma will manifest itself, even if the offender himself does not realize it, it will be reflected in his family or descendants. However, Christian, Catholic, and Jewish holy scriptures are fabricated by missionaries to falsify ancient European history, and they have significant philosophical and scientific flaws. They are not genuine religious scriptures, and the Bible cannot explain that.</p> <p>The current national religion prevalent in the United States is fundamentally selfish, which is completely different from Taoism or Buddhism practiced in ancient China during the Tang Dynasty, which implemented a system of Equal-field land allocation. This has led to the production of issues related to war and conflict in the United States every month, every week, and even every day.</p> <p>The number of mosques in the United States is less than one-tenth of that in Xinjiang, a province in China. China has ample religious</p>

<p>are fabricated by missionaries to falsify ancient European history, and they have significant philosophical and scientific flaws. They are not genuine religious scriptures, and the Bible cannot explain that.</p>	<p>freedom. Should a country that allows another country to carry out large-scale bombing and killing of children in Palestine be considered a righteous and pious country, or a country with a cult-like belief?</p>
<p>Nobel laureate in medicine from Japan, Professor Honjo of Kyoto University, has publicly boasted in recent years that "if Japan and China go to war, Japan still has the strength to win." He pointed out that while China has developed, Japan has infiltrated many areas of China and has the ability to disintegrate China from within. This indicates that Japan has never forgotten its desire to invade China again after the end of World War II, massacring Chinese people, raping and gang-raping Chinese women, killing Chinese children, and turning children into a source of blood and daily meat for the Japanese army, while plundering China's natural resources. It is astonishing that a Nobel Prize-winning Japanese is well aware of Japanese espionage infiltrating various sectors of China, validating the words of judges and diplomats who have said that almost every Japanese person in China is a spy. The Japanese laureate completely violates the intentions of Mr. Nobel in establishing the Nobel Prize, disregarding Mr. Nobel's desire to maintain world peace and hoping to launch a war again. Japan slaughtered about 100 million Chinese people, and the international community should form a consensus that any evil country that has slaughtered a million people in other countries</p>	<p>The Japanese forced U.S. generals, both Lieutenant General and Major General, to eat Japanese feces almost every day for three consecutive years. This is a level of depravity never before seen in thousands of years of Chinese history, and only the evil Japanese would stoop to such depths in the history of world war. However, just six years after the World War II, the United States actually allied with Japan, showing the complete lack of moral integrity of the United States, controlled by international financiers, and completely forgetting the torture inflicted on its generals. If you were to start a company, would you be willing to hire murderers as employees? I believe you wouldn't. Yet, the U.S. military agreed to ally with Japan, which clearly shows that the U.S. military is a faithless army, and the United States is a country without faith, where only interests matter. Even in the future, the Japanese were to force American military leaders to eat Japanese feces every day for three consecutive years.</p>

	<p>since 1900 should not be awarded any Nobel Prize for the next 100 years. The Japanese invaders slaughtered about 100 million Chinese people, so they should be prohibited from being awarded any Nobel Prize for the next 10,000 years.</p>	
		<p>After the President of the United States takes the oath with his hand on the Bible, the American government confronts China. This shows that Americans, American politicians, the American government, and the American military have no religious beliefs and only pretend to be religious believers.</p> <p>Chinese Hong Xiuquan, as the Son of God, was certified by the Vatican, with written records and identity authentication.</p> <p>Hong Xiuquan's descendants are also in China. Therefore, Hong Xiuquan and his descendants, of course, have inheritance rights to Jerusalem. Therefore, the birthplace of Hong Xiuquan, Huadu District, Guangdong, should also be a holy place for Christianity. The government of Huadu District can certainly build a Hong Xiuquan Cathedral, and Christians from all over the world must come to Huadu District, China, every year to pilgrimage, accept the baptism of our bishops, and accept the leadership of Chinese bishops. The whole world of Christianity must also accept the leadership of Chinese bishops and be appointed by the Chinese ruling party and government. Americans, American politicians, the American government, and the American military should listen to the words of the Chinese people, Chinese bishops of Christianity, and the Chinese government.</p>
		<p>From the surplus of grains and the approval of genetically modified foods, it can be seen that Americans, American politicians, and the American government lack religious beliefs.</p> <p>There is a serious surplus of agricultural products, and the safety assessment of genetically modified foods is seriously lagging behind. Countries with high GM food production have a high incidence of allergic diseases among their civilian populations, and GM crops also pose significant ecological hazards. It is unbelievable that the United States has not legislated to stop research on genetically modified foods and even forced China to buy genetically modified corn and soybeans. This kind of behavior by the United States is obviously a moral regression of 2,000-4,000 years, with no religious beliefs among the U.S. government, U.S. companies, and U.S. genetic engineering researchers.</p> <p>The safety assessment of genetically modified (GM) foods involves highly specialized issues. Typically, even professionals find it challenging to conduct a rational assessment, leading to the proliferation of GM foods with potentially significant safety hazards driven by vested interests. Moreover, in recent years, the United States has experienced four consecutive years of surplus production of GM soybeans and GM corn, contributing to a global surplus in food supply.</p>

	<p>Scientists at the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) have repeatedly warned that GM foods can result in unforeseeable and difficult to detect side effects, including allergies, toxicity, novel diseases, and nutritional problems. They have strongly advocated for long-term safety studies of such foods, but their calls have largely been ignored.</p> <p>In China, some bloggers conducted experiments using genetically modified soybeans to grow soybean sprouts and found that even newly genetically modified soybeans or mung beans from the same year struggled to grow into edible sprouts of 6-9cm, while non-genetically modified soybeans or mung beans could grow into normal-length sprouts.</p> <p>The United States is the world's largest producer of genetically modified crops, including corn, soybeans, cotton, rapeseed, sugar beets, alfalfa, papaya, and squash. Many individuals prone to allergies in the United States experience fewer allergic reactions after living in China for a period, even when consuming the same foods. This is because China uses genetically modified foods in food production far less frequently.</p> <p>Since the consumption period of genetically modified foods is usually much longer than the treatment period of drugs, the examination of reproductive toxicity and chronic toxicity should be more stringent than the safety examination of drugs. Currently, it is actually easier than drugs, so there should be regulations that are at least as rigorous as those for drugs. Genetically modified foods must undergo large-scale safety experiments and clinical trials before being marketed. In addition, the developers and research institutions of genetically modified foods have a better understanding of the safety and potential hazards of these foods than the public does. Before genetically modified foods are put on the market, all employees and shareholders of the genetically modified food company, as well as their family members, must consume the food for an extended period of time and prove its safety. They should not be developing genetically modified foods for global consumption while they themselves and their families only consume natural foods.</p> <p>Furthermore, all employees of the food regulatory agency and their family members must consume genetically modified foods that they are mandated to approve or have already approved. Those responsible for approval should have a clear understanding of the safety of genetically modified foods. If they object, GM foods cannot be marketed, and any already on the market must have their permits revoked. The above must form a United Nations convention.</p>
	<p>After being brainwashed by Japan, over 600,000 Taiwanese joined the Japanese military, with more than 200,000 fighting against US and Chinese forces in the Pacific theater. After WWII, 26 Taiwanese members of the Japanese military were sentenced to death by the Allied International Military Tribunal for mistreating prisoners of war at the Rabaul camp. Additionally, 175 were found guilty and sentenced to imprisonment or hard labour. Some Taiwanese soldiers even forced Allied and American POWs to eat feces. These Taiwanese Japanese soldiers were</p>

not only accomplices of Japanese aggression, but also criminals against the Chinese nation. Many Taiwanese are descendants of Japanese war criminals and are considered criminals.

Today, the U.S. military is actually protecting the accomplices of the Japanese aggressors, the Taiwanese who once forced American POWs to eat feces. The United States, controlled by international financiers, has completely lost its moral compass. U.S. politicians and military personnel have no moral standards; they lack religious beliefs.

It is absurd that the U.S. government seeks to protect Taiwan and collaborates with Japanese and Taiwanese politicians and evildoers to divide China, forgetting who subjected U.S. generals and soldiers to three years of eating feces in POW camps.

U.S. soldiers are just tools for U.S. politicians and financiers, and perhaps for them, consuming feces from Japanese and Taiwanese individuals is just a normal part of life.

On April 18, 1942, Doolittle led 16 planes to bomb Tokyo, Nagoya, Yokohama, Yokosuka, Kobe, and Osaka in Japan, but only about 50 people were killed and about 90 buildings were destroyed on the Japanese mainland. The 75 pilots of the 15 B25 bombers who returned to Chinese territory were forced to parachute, but with the heroic rescue efforts of the Chinese people, 64 pilots were successfully rescued in the Jiangxi, Zhejiang, Anhui, and Fujian regions and safely evacuated to the rear areas. The evil Japanese military searched for American parachutists, killing all suspected individuals who had aided Doolittle's pilots, and implemented a cruel **"three kill all policy"** in villages where American pilots passed. Near Quzhou Airport, nine villages were massacred by the Japanese army. **A total of 100,000 houses were burned down, and over 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians were killed in three months.** Chiang Kai-shek specifically telephoned the U.S. government, pointing out that the "Doolittle Operation" had cost China 250,000 lives. **When U.S. pilots withdrew to coastal areas of China, the evil Japanese launched attacks there, "slaughtering every man, woman, and child."**

In 1950, the US bombed Chinese territory, leading to China's participation in the Korean War. However, the Chinese People's Volunteer Army was a civilized military force. General Ridgway, the Supreme Commander of the United Nations forces, noted in his memoirs: "We later came to appreciate that the Chinese were strong and fierce fighters, often launching attacks regardless of casualties. However, we found them to be more civilized enemies. They shared the little food they had with the prisoners and showed kindness to them..."

After capturing American soldiers in the Korean War, China hosted the only global POW Olympic Games in 1952. The theme of the event was "The Games are a Path to Friendship"; "Peace is the Goal of All".

Among the 13,107 POW participants, British George Blake won the 1500m race, Turkish POWs excelled in wrestling, and a Turkish POW, Arif Gokce, set a record with a seven-game winning streak. South Korean POWs showed exceptional long-distance running skills, sweeping all the medals in the 3000m race.

American soldiers won the 200m race and dominated the boxing event, while

	<p>various American-based teams also excelled in the competitions.</p> <p>However, the "American athletes" were also involved in the only doping scandal. It was reported that an American boxer had a significant performance improvement after drinking cooking wine before the match. When a black soldier reported the incident, medals were revoked, and the "champion" was punished by being assigned to feed pigs.</p> <p>The POWs from various countries greatly enjoyed the Olympics, and the all-around champion, Delmar G. Miller, wrote in a letter to his mother: "I have participated in a sports competition in the Korean POW camp, involving athletes from over a dozen countries. This has never happened before in the world. I won the obstacle race, the high jump, and the all-around championship. I have gained a lot of honor here. I have also obtained many exquisite Chinese crafts as prizes, and I really like them. I will bring them home and share my honor with you."</p> <p>The narrator for the Olympic Games was British POW George E. Newhouse, a soldier from the elite Gloucestershire Regiment.</p> <p>The Gloucestershire Regiment was annihilated by the Chinese Volunteer Army in the Battle of Imjin River, and Newhouse became a POW. Due to his "versatility," he played a vital role in the Olympic Games.</p> <p>Newhouse later returned to the UK and served as a member of the House of Lords.</p>
	<p>Chinese people's super religious views and Western people's narrow religious views</p> <p>The Chinese people have created many religions around the world, including Taoism, Buddhism, and Confucianism. Current research suggests that the Bible was also created in China during the Qing Dynasty under the oppressive rule of Manchu emperors, when literary persecution was rampant. It was fabricated by members of the Tianzhu Association (the name of the external missionary organization: Tianhui Society), including Xu Guangqi and Qu Taisu, pretending to be Westerners. Before 1582, the time when Matteo Ricci came to China, the Western alphabet did not even exist. Therefore, all documents written in the Western alphabet, including but not limited to books, manuscripts, inscriptions, and maps, that are dated earlier than 1582, are forgeries created by later generations. Because a member of the Jewish Zhang Tao's family betrayed them and opened the city gates, leading to the executions of Sun Yuanhua and Zhang Tao, the story of Jewish betrayal appears in the Bible. The author believes that the founders of Christianity were Xu Guangqi, Qu Taisu, and others during the late Ming Dynasty.</p> <p>The Chinese have culturally led multiple religions. Although the Chinese people have created many world-renowned religions, religious conflicts and wars are rare in Chinese history. With the support of their advantageous culture, the Chinese form a belief system that transcends religious belief, which clearly surpasses the Western concept of religion. Chinese can cultivate themselves without attending religious ceremonies in a church. In Western history, religious wars are frequent, and new religions often turn</p>

	<p>their followers into an ethnic group that continually engages in wars with other groups. For instance, those who believe in Judaism are called Jews. If the Chinese people created Taoism, they would become Taoist people; if they believed in Buddhism, they would become Buddhist people; if they believed in Confucianism, they would become Confucian people. This is a very primitive approach, yet the West adopts this primitive approach. If Indians believed in Judaism and became Jews, how many Jews would there be on Earth? Wouldn't it be ridiculous if Indians changed their ethnicity because of their beliefs?</p> <p>The United States attacks China for suppressing Christianity. Even so, Christianity was created by the Chinese. Isn't this a matter for the Chinese themselves?</p> <p>The West is completely controlled by Jewish media. Brainwashed Westerners never find it laughable that a group of people claiming to convert to a religion can be considered a nation. Some people abandon their Jewish identity after awakening, while others who convert to Judaism leave the nation when they feel their interests are harmed, becoming part of another nation.</p> <p>A typical example is the Rothschild family, who were recognized as Jews in the 19th and 20th centuries; however, at the beginning of 2024, they renounced their Jewish identity, and now the family is no longer considered Jewish. In 2008, Israeli scholar and Tel Aviv University historian Shlomo Sand faced widespread condemnation from the Jewish community for his book "The Invention of the Jewish People." In his book, Sand completely denies the history of modern Jews, arguing that Jews do not share a common ancestry and that their ancestors never lived in the Palestinian region. He even claims that the Jewish nation is a fabrication. Unable to bear the "Jewish nation" attribute imposed by Israel, Sand publicly announced that he was renouncing his Jewish identity and would only live as an Israeli.</p> <p>In China, if you belong to the Tujia ethnic group, you remain Tujia regardless of whether you practice Taoism, Buddhism, or Confucianism; this cannot be changed.</p> <p>[43. 一个令举世震惊的观点：当代巴勒斯坦人才是早期犹太人的后裔 A shocking view that shocked the world: contemporary Palestinians are descendants of early Jews. November 16, 2023. https://www.sohu.com/a/736724590_120271802</p> <p>44. 罗斯柴尔德家族宣布退出犹太民族血统，重新登记为欧洲人 The Rothschild family announced their withdrawal from Jewish ancestry and re registration as Europeans. 2024-01-10. https://www.163.com/dy/article/IO371F2V05563MKD.html]</p>	
18	From taxation, look at the government's religious beliefs.	
	Criminals' illicit gains must be confiscated and cannot be subjected to	Internal Revenue Service (IRS): Even the ill-gotten gains from criminal activities must be taxed. This illustrates that the U.S. government, American politicians and

<p>taxation.</p>	<p>Americans lack any religious belief and only adheres to a cult-like faith. It marks the most severe regression and greatest shame in national civilization in the last 5,000 years globally.</p> <p>Surprisingly, neither the American people nor the U.S. government consider it a regression or shame.</p> <p>The legal facade of the United States is ostensibly fair and just, but in essence, it serves the interests of the financial elites or chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch, with the most crucial moral and ethical foundations of the judiciary completely disregarded.</p> <p>When a country's moral and ethical standards fall back 2,000-4,000 years, the current justice system is designed by financial elites to evade punishment. It is necessary to adopt past laws in order to eliminate criminals completely and quickly.</p> <p>The current Chinese legal system has been adversely affected by the corrupt legal systems of the United States and Europe. To save the United States, most of China's 300-2,000-year-old judicial systems must be implemented in the United States.</p>
<p>99.9% of houses in China are usually made of concrete, and basic household housing does not need to be taxed annually.</p> <p>When natural disasters occur and homes are destroyed by earthquakes, the Chinese government even provides free construction of permanent concrete structures for the victims.</p>	<p>It is well known that the United States frequently experiences hurricanes, which easily destroy wooden houses, causing huge financial losses to the people. However, at the legislative level, laws and tax provisions unfavorable to using concrete for housing construction are deliberately created, and false information promoting the environmental friendliness of wooden houses is spread. Politicians bought by tycoons naturally accept:</p> <p>Fragile housing—destroyed by natural disasters—insurance compensation—profits from reconstruction, such repeated traps that continuously drain people's wealth.</p>
<p>Basic household housing in China does not require annual taxation.</p>	<p>All land in the United States was plundered from the indigenous Native Americans by and Jews, yet legislation requires every household to pay property taxes every year, completely disregarding basic housing rights. From birth to death, the American people create wealth for international tycoons or financial magnates, who control the taxation tools and the armed forces, capable of</p>

		<p>striking the American people at any time. International tycoons only need to provide relatively high personal treatment to nurture a force that collects taxes by force for them. Every ordinary American is either a pawn or a servant of chaebol or tycoons or financial magnates or international financial oligarchs.</p>
19	<p>Chinese Dream, American Dream and freedom, democracy Is the United States the freest nation?</p>	
	<p>Basic residential housing owned by Chinese households is not required to pay real estate tax annually.</p> <p>According to the official explanation, the essence of the Chinese Dream is to achieve national prosperity, revitalization of the nation, and the happiness of the people; the Chinese Dream is a dream of peace, development, cooperation, and win-win results.</p> <p>In recent years, the U.S. government has arrested a Chinese activist on absurd charges for advocating peaceful relations with China and opposing a new Cold War. It is worth noting that this person was arrested just for advocating peace and opposing a Cold War, without slandering the U.S. government or spreading rumors. He is not a spy either. If we flip the situation and think about it, there are many people on the Internet in China who help foreign or hostile forces and harm the interests of their own country. Their absurd remarks are much more exaggerated than those of the arrested person, yet none of them have been arrested. It just goes to show that the Chinese people are not against America, and China actually has much more freedom of speech than America. China really allows dissidents to exist.</p> <p>In China, at least in the city centers of major cities, people can freely walk around at 10 o'clock at night, and both men and women do not have to worry about safety. This kind of freedom is much harder to come by in major cities in the United States.</p>	
	<p>The basic housing of American families must pay property taxes every year, otherwise the government will sell it, and these Americans will immediately become homeless wanderers, and the American dream will fly to the roadside.</p> <p>Democratic system: Democracy means that the public has the right to speak, and the final voting result must represent the interests of the majority. The democracy of the United States seems to represent the majority, but in reality, it represents a very small number of people, using the system to conceal the truth of democracy.</p> <p>TikTok has more than 170 million users in the United States, with nearly one out of every two Americans being a TikTok user. However, on March 13, the U.S. House of Representatives overwhelmingly passed a bill by a 352-65 vote to ban TikTok nationwide.</p> <p>The bill stipulates that TikTok's parent company, ByteDance, will have six</p>	

	<p>months to sell its majority stake. If the divestment is not completed within the specified time frame, TikTok will be removed from the United States.</p> <p>Americans protested the ban with a march to the Capitol. A TikTok spokesperson said: "The U.S. government is trying to deprive 170 million Americans of their constitutional right to free speech. Banning TikTok will harm the interests of millions of businesses and disrupt the livelihoods of countless creators nationwide."</p> <p>If the U.S. political system is truly democratic, based on the proportion of 170 million TikTok users, excluding infants, the ratio of votes in support of and against the removal of TikTok by both parties should be at least 207 to 210. However, the actual voting result should have been against removing TikTok, but the reality is the opposite.</p> <p>This means at least four things about the U.S. political system: first, there is no democracy, only the interests of a minority. Second, there is no freedom of use, because the freedom of 170 million users is greatly restricted. Third, there is no freedom of speech, as TikTok media brings the truth, but interest groups seek to cover it up and must use seemingly legal means to suppress it. Fourth, it reflects the serious intervention of businessmen and financiers in politics. Guan Zhong, the first prime minister of ancient China, once said that the intervention of businessmen in government operations is extremely dangerous.</p> <p>The number of mosques in the United States is less than one-tenth of that in Xinjiang, a province in China. China has ample religious freedom.</p> <p>The United States is not a country that advocates for freedom for all, as if Americans were free, every American would be eligible to run for president or Senate President.</p> <p>If the United States is truly free, the author of this article would have the opportunity to run for Speaker of the House or CDC Director. But the answer is clearly no, the author doesn't even have the chance to experience it. Freedom in America is very limited.</p> <p>Famous actor Charlie Chaplin lived in the U.S. for a long time, shooting a large number of films in Hollywood, but was maliciously slandered as an extremist by McCarthyists and barred from entering the U.S.</p> <p>The U.S. bans the sale of popular Chinese brand Huawei phones in the U.S., while China allows the sale of U.S. Apple phones in China. This shows a huge difference in freedom between the two countries, despite the fact that Chinese descendants are native to the United States and the Americas.</p>
	<p>Top-level designs before and after the founding of the United States both have significant flaws. Americans do not have a natural bloodline connection, and the United States does not coalesce around a shared pursuit of good morals and conscience. Voracious international tycoons or financial magnates fear most the elevation of human moral standards, empathy, and adherence to logical consistency, as well as facing the execution of ancient</p>

		<p>Chinese laws after committing crimes. The United States is merely a tool controlled by these tycoons, or financial magnates utilized to threaten with military force or instigate wars, to create panic and profit from volatile financial derivatives, to issue US bonds and dollars, to manipulate interest rates and plunder the world, and to swiftly plunder assets after fully marketizing assets of other countries. American politicians fabricate an American dream to benefit a few individuals. When these tycoons or financial magnates cannot plunder wealth from other countries, they resort to repeatedly pillaging Americans domestically. Once contradictions become irreconcilable, the United States will erupt into war and disintegrate.</p>
		<p>The declassified Nixon tapes from 1972 reveal that most of the media in the United States is controlled by Jews, there are many Jewish spies, and the government is full of Jews. President Nixon himself hoped that Jewish dominance must be broken. With the US media largely controlled by financial magnates, how can America truly be considered free?</p> <p>In May 2024, the U.S. Congress even passed the Anti-Semitism Awareness Act, which established Americans into six different categories, with Jews being considered a superior ethnicity and Anglo-Saxons as second-class citizens. Speech about Jews in the US is restricted, so how can America really be considered free?</p> <p>[Nixon. 2023-11-19. https://v.douyin.com/i2Ehs1TU/o@D.uFXzg:/04/15/];</p> <p>[Why is it said that America today is the backyard of Jews? They control most of the media in the United States. 2024-02-20. in Chinese. https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1791408205903782825&wfr=spider&for=pc];</p> <p>[The Anti-Semitic Act of the United States established Americans into six levels. 2024-05-05. https://www.163.com/v/video/VLOGJQ8TT.html]</p>
20	The morality, discipline, and beliefs of the national army.	
	<p>The military has strict discipline and the officers and soldiers have high moral character.</p>	<p>The military discipline has been relaxed, and soldiers often engage in sexual assault practices.</p>
	<p>Historical evaluation of military discipline level: The discipline of the Chinese People's Liberation Army has surpassed the military discipline of Li Shimin's army in the early Tang Dynasty, making it the best disciplined army in Chinese history.</p>	<p>Historical evaluation of military discipline level: The military discipline of the US military is far behind that of the early Tang Dynasty army led by Li Shimin of China, and even far behind that of the army led by the ancient Chinese warlord Cao Cao. Cao Cao leads the army with strict military discipline! It is not allowed to take even a chicken from the civilians. Not only do military officers condone crimes committed by soldiers, but the president also allows and protects military officers and soldiers who commit serious crimes, such as rape and gang rape. This is tantamount to a country and military with no faith or morality. It is completely incompatible with the status of a great power.</p>
	<p>An army with lofty beliefs. This makes it</p>	<p>An army lacking noble beliefs. This makes</p>

<p>difficult for this army to do bad things. The military discipline of the Chinese army today is at least in line with the military discipline of the ancient Chinese army led by Cao Cao, where even the chicken of an ordinary civilian is not allowed to be touched. This shows that Chinese soldiers have a human-centered religious belief. In contrast, U.S. soldiers essentially only have a superficial religious beliefs. In reality, American soldiers lack religious beliefs, and can kill and rape at will, with American officers or government officials even protecting criminals, showing a complete lack of faith.</p>	<p>the army often fighting for personal gain, with relatively lax military discipline, making it easier for soldiers to engage in wrongdoing. Soldiers are more prone to violate military discipline, leading to cases of robbery, intentional injury, rape, gang rape, and murder.</p>
	<p>In Shanghai, atrocities committed by the U.S. military have become a daily occurrence. They drove recklessly, causing accidents that resulted in the deaths or injuries of 495 Chinese people in just four months from September 1945 to January 1946. This number increased to over 800 cases in the four months from August to December 1946.</p> <p>On July 30, 1946, an American soldier stationed in Shanghai called a rickshaw, but when the driver did not understand English and took a moment to respond, the soldier pulled out a knife and cut off half of the driver's hand. Lu Yingui, a rickshaw driver in Shanghai, was beaten into a disabled person by several U.S. soldiers for demanding payment from the U.S. soldiers who took his rickshaw.</p> <p>On June 28, 1946, in Chongqing, China, four U.S. soldiers injured the guards at the entrance and forcibly entered the women's bathhouse at Hui Xian Building Hotel. They insulted and raped the women who were bathing. During the assault, they were confronted by citizens and hotel staff who arrived at the scene. After the four assaulting soldiers left, they gathered more than 20 U.S. soldiers to return to Hui Xian Building Hotel and ultimately destroy it. The military and police present were too afraid to intervene, and the soldiers were extremely arrogant.</p> <p>Such atrocities by the U.S. military were widespread in Shanghai, Nanjing, Beijing, Tianjin, and Qingdao. From August 1945 to November 1946, there were over 3,800 reported cases of misconduct, resulting in the death or injury of over 3,300 people and the humiliation of over 300 women. The U.S. military often acted collectively, and the police were too afraid to intervene, allowing their crimes to go unchecked. Their behavior was outrageous and arrogant in the extreme.</p> <p>Both the United States and its military lack the correct philosophical guidance. The military lacks basic moral and ethical education and restraint, and many soldiers lack faith, often resulting in disciplinary violations or sexual assault. Surprisingly, senior U.S. military officials always protect criminal soldiers rather than executing</p>

	<p>rapists. Most U.S. voters also want to protect criminal soldiers, leading to many rape or murder by U.S. soldiers every year. The discipline of the U.S. military is far behind that of the ancient Chinese military under Cao Cao, marking a significant regression in the level of military discipline in human history, despite being better than the most evil Japanese army in the world.</p>
	<p>In the 1940s, the regulations of the Second Field Army of the Chinese People's Liberation Army were: those who shoot civilians will be executed; those who loot civilian property will be executed; and those who rape women will be executed. It is not allowed to force civilians to be guides, not to ask for things from civilians, not to beat or curse the masses.</p> <p>The deputy platoon leader of the directly affiliated guard battalion of the headquarters, who had just achieved military merit, was a combat hero and a model laborer. When there were no people in town, he went to the store and took a bundle of noodles and a piece of cloth. The cloth was for making a cotton jacket for a young soldier, and the noodles were used for cooking to improve the life of an injured soldier.</p> <p>During the public trial to execute a disciplined officer, someone suddenly shouted from afar, "spare his life!" A middle-aged man ran to the front of the rostrum and introduced himself as the owner of the store. He said that he heard that a soldier had taken things from his store and came down from the mountain to the trial. He said, "If I had known this would happen, I would not have run up the mountain. If I had been at home, this would never have happened. Please spare him..."</p> <p>An elderly woman looked at the soldier with great pity, knelt down and begged, "These things are not worth much. The shopkeeper does not pursue it, so please spare him..." Soldiers immediately helped her up, and some of them also pleaded for the undisciplined deputy platoon leader.</p> <p>However, the military leadership believed that "although the matter is small, military discipline is like a mountain. Our discipline should be ironclad, not like tofu. If we spare him this time, what should we do if more people violate discipline in the future? My opinion is to strictly enforce discipline..."</p> <p>As a result, the army is basically free from disciplinary violations, and many civilians are aware that this army belongs to the civilians themselves.</p>
<p>The Chinese volunteer army in North Korea is disciplined and there are no cases of raping women, let alone comfort women.</p>	<p>From 1945 to the early 1990s, the term "comfort women" was commonly used by South Korean media and officials to describe women who provided special services to the U.S. military. A 1961 census showed that there were at least 10,000 such comfort women for the U.S. military, serving about 50,000 U.S. troops stationed in South Korea. The "Unified Nation" of South Korea stated that by the 1980s, the total number of such women had reached one million, many of whom suffered from illnesses due to years of medication and heavy drinking.</p>

In 1946, American soldiers gang-raped a female student of Peking University, Shen Chong.

December 24, 1946, which was supposed to be Christmas Eve in Christianity, turned into a tragic day for Shen Chong, a female student in Beiping. After watching a movie, she was kidnapped by two American soldiers as she walked home alone in the woods across from Ping'an Cinema. Shen Chong tried to call for help, but was choked and gagged, and then dragged to the wall of Nanda University where she was raped for the first time.

During the incident, Shen Chong managed to call for help and attracted some passersby. Afraid of being exposed, U.S. soldiers dragged Shen Chong to an empty room at Dongda University. Shen Chong attempted to escape, but was caught by the soldiers again, and then raped for the second time in a corner of the room. Her cries for help attracted some people, but unfortunately they were unable to rescue her. Police later arrived and arrested one of the criminals, Pearson, while the other, Richard, managed to escape.

The Beiping authorities were afraid of angering the American troops and decided to cover up the incident. The captured American soldiers were also released. Most large newspapers were strictly prohibited from reporting the incident, except for the urgent news published by the Yaguang news agency that night, which was the only report at the time.

On the 27th, students at Beiping University quickly responded to the situation and held a large-scale demonstration, demanding the withdrawal of American troops from China and severe punishment for the perpetrators. During the demonstration, they shouted slogans such as "American troops get out of China." The protest quickly spread across the country, with more than 500,000 students in cities like Shanghai, Nanjing, Wuhan, Chongqing, and Kunming taking to the streets to protest.

Before the trial, the former Chinese First Lady Soong Mei-ling personally comforted the victimized student Shen Chong, provided him with a baptism, accepted his conversion to Christianity, and recognized him as her goddaughter. She arranged for Shen Chong to change his appearance, change his name, and transfer schools. Soong Mei-ling requested that Shen Chong refrain from appearing in newspapers and making any statements in order to calm the situation.

However, on the one hand, the US authorities sentenced the bandit soldier Pearson, but on the other hand, immediately seized US aid supplies to China. The U.S. presidential envoy bluntly stated that in order to receive U.S. assistance, Chiang Kai-shek must revoke Pearson's sentence, to which Chiang Kai-shek reluctantly agreed.

On June 17, the Commander of the U.S. Marine Corps publicly stated that there was insufficient evidence to support Pearson's crime, and he would soon be released and reinstated. Upon learning of this news, major Chinese academic institutions immediately protested, sending letters to Chiang Kai-shek, the U.S. Embassy in China, and the U.S. President, demanding fair U.S. justice and

	<p>upholding the original judgment.</p> <p>However, disregarding all assertions of justice, the United States insisted on releasing Pearson. On August 12, the U.S. Secretary of the Navy publicly announced the revocation of Pearson's sentence, releasing him and reinstating him that same day.</p> <p>Chiang Kai-shek's government police beat and arrested protesting students in public. They also tightly controlled and censored information, prohibiting any related news from being reported in major newspapers, with only a few small publications and progressive groups covering the events.</p> <p>But because the victim Shen Chong no longer made any statement, the parties involved no longer expressed their opinions, and the matter gradually subsided. In this way, this shocking incident, which greatly provoked the Chinese people oppressed by the presence of American troops in China, was finally left unresolved due to the shameless protection of the American authorities and the inaction of the Chiang Kai-shek government towards foreign countries, under high pressure and oppression of the people, leaving the world amazed at such a government. To some extent, the crimes of the U.S. military enabled the Chinese people to recognize the true nature of Chiang Kai-shek government, leading to its downfall. This is probably the karmic retribution of Buddhism.</p>
	<p>Mass rape and gang rape of women by U.S. military officers at Jingming Building in Wuhan in 1948</p> <p>On the evening of August 7, 1948, an American-hosted ball inviting Chinese socialites was held in the Jingming Building in Hankou. The male guests were mostly American, with some British; the female guests were all Chinese, including many wives of senior officials and wealthy businessmen, totaling more than thirty people.</p> <p>At about 9:30 p.m. that night, the elevator was secretly locked, and the ball began to appear to be "normal." But as the ball continued, the foreign men present began to reveal their true nature, beginning to molest the Chinese women in attendance. Some women realized that something was wrong and made excuses to leave, managing to escape the ordeal.</p> <p>As the party continued, suddenly, an American military officer picked up a woman named Cao Xiuying, then pushed her to the ground and tore off her underwear and bra. At that moment, the lights in the ballroom were turned off, the dance floor descended into chaos, with only the sounds of Chinese women's pleas for help and the lascivious laughter of foreigners coming through. During this time, only Cao Xiuying managed to struggle and escape, while the other women present fell into the abyss.</p> <p>Around midnight, the gang rape of Chinese women came to an end. A dancer named Qiaoqiao also managed to escape and went to Hankou Police Headquarters to report the incident. Police chief Ma Buyun, was immediately sent to investigate. However, the American guards downstairs did not allow the police to go upstairs. After hours of negotiation, they were finally allowed to go up at around three in the morning, by which time only the organizers of the ball,</p>

	<p>Li Fu and Lincoln, were still there. The scene on the floor and couch, as well as the scattered pieces of clothing and the pervasive smell in the air, all indicated what had just happened.</p> <p>The news spread on the second day, causing a public outcry, with people from all over demanding that the authorities punish the perpetrators. However, as usual, Chiang Kai-shek remained silent and took no stance. It wasn't until more than ten days later, in the face of increasingly fierce public opinion, that the authorities reluctantly launched an "investigation", which was a carefully orchestrated show that left people "suffocated".</p> <p>The real American and British perpetrators who gang-raped Chinese women were not arrested at all, only a few Chinese people responsible for assisting in the crime were taken into custody. The real masterminds were not caught. Faced with strong public skepticism, the authorities "helplessly" decided to re-examine the case to appease public anger.</p> <p>But then an even more shocking turn of events occurred. Instead of capturing American and British criminals, the Kuomintang government actually arrested the people who reported the crime, as long as they could be convicted of a crime, their reports were deemed false. Ultimately, those who worked for the Americans and those who had escaped earlier, including the victim Cao Xiuying, were arrested and charged with "undermining public morals", and sentenced to one year in prison.</p> <p>The handling of this incident further demonstrated the extreme flattery of the Chiang regime towards foreign powers, completely disregarding national dignity and the interests of the people. Not only did the thugs harm the Chinese people, but the government also oppressed the people. However, just as the People's Liberation Army advanced south and the authorities in Wuhan fled, the focus of attention shifted away from the incident, and the scandal gradually subsided, with the absurd verdict only causing limited protests.</p>
21	<p>In seemingly complex situations, it is possible to quickly determine whether a country is aggressive, trustworthy, or if its military is aggressive toward other countries.</p> <p>If you have not exceeded my level in predicting the following complex issues, you may consider accepting the viewpoint of this clause.</p> <p>As countless people in China and around the world scolded the people of Wuhan for eating wild animals and causing the global COVID-19 pandemic, the author of this article discovered four core issues regarding the novel coronavirus in January 2020. First, the claim that the Huahan Seafood Market in Wuhan was the origin of the virus is not possible. Second, the idea that the virus originated from wild animals in the seafood market is also not possible. Third, it is highly unlikely that the novel coronavirus came directly from bats. Fourth, the current methodology used to trace the source of the virus in the seafood market is incorrect, and it is suggested that the virus may have come from imported frozen seafood. Unfortunately, despite submitting the article to some top journals from March 2020 to 2021, it was rejected by all of them, which is evident from the history of submission or rejection. On January 16, 2024, Professor Zhao Chongnuo from Hong Kong Baptist University and Dietrich Stoyan from the</p>

University of Freiberg, Germany, published a research paper titled "Statistics did not prove that the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market was the early epicentre of the COVID-19 pandemic" in the Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series A: Statistics in Society. This new paper carefully analyzes the evidence presented in the aforementioned Science paper and finds significant statistical errors, highlighting that the statistical data does not prove that the Huanan Seafood Market was the early epicenter of the COVID-19 pandemic. Researchers from the University of Milan, Italy, detected COVID-19 in the throat secretion of a 4-year-old child who lived near Milan, Italy, without overseas history in 2019, and inferred that COVID-19 had appeared in Italy and began spreading at least in November 2019.

When almost everyone around the world was eagerly anticipating a COVID-19 vaccine to prevent infection, **the author made a prediction in February 2020 that the COVID-19 vaccine would not be effective in preventing virus transmission and could potentially have adverse consequences** (The relevant article was published on the paper preprint server in 2021.). The author believed that the development and administration of the COVID-19 vaccine would be a waste of global resources and place a tremendous economic burden on governments. As a result, neither the author nor his family received the COVID-19 vaccine, and the author also encouraged his friends not to get vaccinated. Furthermore, the author has never been infected with the novel coronavirus despite frequent visits to COVID-19 patients' wards. Later facts proved that the COVID-19 vaccine could not prevent COVID-19 infection, and could only reduce the incidence of severe illness in a short time. In addition, the COVID-19 vaccine should be vaccinated many times.

If you don't approach the problems with depth and perspective, you won't be able to understand any problem clearly.

Due to the relatively low cost of lung CT diagnosis in Chinese public hospitals, at about \$33 each time (in Wuhan City), with results available the same day, many people undergo lung CT scans after a period of vaccination. The author found that lung nodules have appeared in a majority of young people vaccinated against COVID-19 in some institutions. Despite the author's previous articulation of a viewpoint against COVID-19 vaccination in a scholarly paper, it has been rejected by some top-tier journals. In the future, countries around the world will have to pay a price to solve the problem of pulmonary nodules.

[http://www.360doc.com/content/22/1110/16/10674521_1055366730.shtml], [<https://www.tanmizhi.com/html/926.html>],[Li Liu. (2023). Accurate prediction on COVID-19 vaccination's effectiveness in the past. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10215444>], [This sensational Science paper was found to be wrong. The conclusion that COVID-19 originated from South China Seafood Market in Wuhan was incorrect. Source: The biological world. January 22, 2024. <https://news.bioon.com/article/b0b3810534b2.html>],[Last November, a child in Italy was infected with COVID-19. COVID-19 traces back to the source, with a major discovery. Medical Messenger. December 11, 2020. https://www.sohu.com/a/437529728_169774]

The military song "Three Big Disciplines and **Soldiers are equal to voters.**

<p>Eight Points of Attention" of the Chinese army determines that it is not an aggressive force, but rather a defensive one that only engages in counterattacks. The song reflects the army's commitment to resisting aggression against its own territory and threats to its security.</p> <p>If you have read the Chinese military anthem "Three Big Disciplines and Eight Points of Attention" and still think that China would threaten the United States or Europe, unless you are truly suffering from dementia or have extremely low IQ.</p>	<p>Soldiers = Voters</p> <p>The fact that the US military or government officials protect military officers and soldiers who rape women or commit crimes can be judged within one minute that the military and the country are inevitably aggressive. The facts in recent decades also support this, such as the invasion of Iraq.</p>
<p>"Three Big Disciplines and Eight Points of Attention" is a fixed command in the form of a military song, and it has become a unified discipline for the entire army. This highlights that China is not a country that favours aggression against other nations.</p> <p>The military song "Three Big Disciplines and Eight Points of Attention":</p> <p>Revolutionary soldiers must always remember, the three major disciplines and the eight points for attention.</p> <p>First, all actions must follow orders, only with unified steps can we achieve victory.</p> <p>Second, do not take a needle or thread from the masses, the people support and like us.</p> <p>Third, all confiscated items must be turned over to the public, working hard to lighten the burden on the people.</p> <p>We must adhere to the three major disciplines and never forget the eight points for attention.</p> <p>First, speak with a good attitude, do not be arrogant and respect the masses.</p> <p>Second, trade at fair prices, no bullying in buying or selling.</p> <p>Third, return borrowed items when done using them, do not lose them.</p> <p>Fourth, if something is damaged, compensate in full without any deductions.</p> <p>Fifth, no hitting or cursing, eliminate warlord behavior decisively.</p> <p>Sixth, protect the crops of the people, pay attention to them everywhere during marches and battles.</p> <p>Seventh, no harassing women, eliminate thuggish behavior.</p>	<p>The United States has the world's best universities, with the highest number of universities in the top 100 globally. These universities produce highly intelligent individuals, who should be able to determine within minutes that China is not likely to engage in aggression or threats against other countries. It is obvious that this is the case, so why do they, like a poorly skilled doctor, make completely inaccurate judgments and intentionally create the threat of China? The best explanation is that this is the result of influential interest groups. It should be known that when a poorly trained doctor administers incorrect treatment to a seriously ill patient, it can lead to the patient's death. Politicians lacking moral integrity in their governance can be the greatest threat to a country once they come to power.</p>

	<p>Eighth, no mistreating prisoners of war, no hitting, cursing, or searching their pockets.</p> <p>Everyone must conscientiously follow the rules, and be vigilant against violations.</p> <p>Remember every aspect of revolutionary discipline, and love people everywhere as soldiers of the people.</p> <p>Forever advance in defending the motherland, welcomed and supported by the people nationwide.</p>	
22	The nature of prisons reasonably reflects the social system	
	<p>Prisons are only allowed to be managed by the Chinese government.</p>	<p>The world's largest country actually has a large number of privately built and managed private prisons, where the lives and deaths of prisoners are difficult to not say all controlled by the operators of these private prisons. It can be seen that the so-called judicial independence of the United States is just a cover-up, and the entire U.S. national machinery has been entwined by capital.</p> <p>Even in the late period of the Tang Dynasty in ancient China, there was never such a binding of private capital and the government, with a large number of privately managed national prisons.</p>
23	Individuals with a spirit of dedication nurtured on their respective lands	
	<p>There is a large group of selfless and dedicated leaders, such as Zhou Enlai, Zhu De, Liu Shaoqi, Ren Bishi, Cai Hesen, Chen Yi, Peng Dehuai, He Long, Luo Ronghuan, Nie Rongzhen, Xu Xiangqian, Liu Bocheng, Huang Kecheng, Luo Ruiqing, Zhang Yunyi, Li Xiannian, Tan Zhenlin, Zhang Dingcheng, Su Yu, Chen Geng, Chen Yun, Chen Shiqu, Yao Yilin, Xiao Jingguang, Xi Zhongxun, Han Xianchu, Xu Shiyong, Zuoquan, Li Tianyou, Wang Zhen, Li Kenong, Lin Yuying, Yang Dezhi, Yang Chengwu, Yang Yong, Zhang Aiping, Wang Shangrong, Pi Dingjun, Nie Fengzhi, Li Da, Liu Zhen, Liu Zhidan, Wu Kehua, Yang Dezh, Zhong Wei, Wang Bicheng, Qin Jiwei, Tao Zhiyue, Zeng Zesheng, Chen Mingren, Huang Chaotian, Deng Yue, Wu Yunduo, He Bingyan, Peng Shaohui, Yu Qiuli, Zhong Chibing, Peng Qingyun, Yan Fusheng, Zuoqi, Chen Bo, Gan Zuchang, Tong Yansheng, Sulu, Liao Zhengguo, Liang Xingchu, Zhao Zhangcheng, Lei Yingfu, Wu Huanxian, Duan Dechang, Jiao Yulu, Yang Gui, Zong Qinghou, Jiang Zhuyun, Xiang Jingyu, Yang Kaihui, He Ying, Zhao Yiman, Guo Junqing, and Ren Changxia, etc.</p> <p>There is a large group of selfless and dedicated scientists and educators, such as Zhu Kezhen, Li Siguang, Zhao Zhongyao, Qian Xuesen, Qian Sanqiang, Qian Weichang, Wang Ganchang, Deng Jiaxian, Zhao Jiuzhang, Yao Tongbin, Qian Ji, Guo Yonghuai, Wu Ziliang, Chen Fangyun, Yang Jiachi, Peng Huanwu, Zhu Guangya, Wang Daheng, Cheng Kaijia, Huang Weilu, Tu Shou'e, Wang Xiji, Sun Jiadong, Ren Xinmin, Chen Nengkuan, Zhou Guangzhao, Yu Min, Yuan Longping, Hua Luogeng, Liang Sicheng, Lin Qiaozhi, Hou</p>	<p>There seem to be few prominent figures in the leadership in the United States.</p>

	<p>Debang, Jiang Zhuying, Lin Weiyin, Lin Junde, Xu Shuyun, Gu Fangzhou, Hou Debang, Wu Liande, Lv Fuhua, Wu Xirui, Qiu Fazu, Chi Zhiqiang, Ding Weipei, Zhou Ziqing, Zeng Fanding, Zhu Zhihao, Lin Xunzhong and Mo dingsen etc.</p> <p>There is a large group of grassroots ordinary people who are selflessly dedicated, such as Lei Feng, Zhang Side, Yang Gensi, Tan Bingyun, Liu Zilin, Liu Guangzi, Liu Hulan, Shi Chuanxiang, Wang Jinxi, Zhang Binggui, Chen Yonggui, Xiang Xiuli, Ma Wanshui, Ma Hengchang, Meng Tai, Zhao Mengtao, Shen Jilan, Li Suli, Xing Yanzi, Hu Xiudao, Guo Zhongtian, Pang Xinguo, Wu Jichang, Dong Yong'an, Xiang Xiaoping, Yan Long, Miao Tinglong, Gao Yujing, Yang Qiliang, Huang Dengping, Niu Zhiqiang, Tian Guiying, Kuerbantulum, Alipa Alimahong, Brumahan Mulledo, Bashbaiqiaolak, Jin Maofang, Sarengwa, Tingbalt, Baori Ledai, Zhao Mengtao, Liu Cuilan, Huang Jiguang, Zhang Side, Tao Shaowen, Ni Niansheng, Liu Songbai, Li Weijing, Xu Rumei, Liu Yaomei, Five Warriors of Langya Mountain and so on.</p> <p>Whether they are leaders, scientists or ordinary people, they silently work and contribute in their respective positions, making important contributions to society. They represent the excellent qualities of different levels in China and demonstrate the strength of core socialist values.</p> <p>Their deeds inspire generations of people, become role models in society and inspire more people to dedicate themselves to the great cause of serving society and the people. They leave a profound imprint on everyone's heart and become an eternal spiritual force. Their spirit of dedication and sacrifice will always be remembered in people's hearts, inspiring the progress and development of society. The above examples are just a tiny fraction.</p>	
24	The speeding pattern of accumulated wealth in recent decades.	
	<p>Accumulation is mainly based on the manufacturing industry.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Advanced manufacturing, high-tech, and brand output 2. Under the banner of liberal democracy, using the media and politicians, to mislead or force another country to implement full financial openness, and to extract the enormous wealth accumulated through labor from that country in a manner similar to war.
25	Poor issues in the judicial system	
	<p>The ruling parties in the United States and the West do not resemble a moral group at all, but rather resemble a mafia organization, drug trafficking group, or criminal organization. When Western drug traffickers are arrested and sentenced in Singapore or China, the first reaction of the ruling parties in the United States and the West is to rescue the criminals from Singapore</p>	

		<p>or China, allowing American criminals to escape legal punishment, pleasing the families of the criminals and the wicked voters in America. Is drug trafficking not punishable by law? China would never do such a thing. According to the logic of the United States and the West, drug trafficking should be encouraged in the United States and the West. Why do the ruling parties in the United States behave so wickedly? Does the United States have laws? Does the United States have humanity? Shouldn't the wickedness index of the ruling parties in the United States be tested?</p>
		<p>The U.S. justice system serves to some extent to mitigate culpability or secure acquittals for financially powerful criminals, and serves the interests of lawyers seeking high returns.</p>
		<p>As long as there's enough money, lawyers, judges, and forensic experts can clear criminals of all charges! Yet smart judicial agencies and lawmakers never design strict rules to severely punish these potential criminals in the judicial field. On June 12, 1994, Simpson's ex-wife Nicole and her friend Ron Goldman were both killed at her Los Angeles residence. After the crime, the primary suspect identified by police was Simpson. When police searched Simpson's residence, they found bloodstains matching the victims' blood type, as well as gloves, shoes, and other physical evidence that matched traces found at the crime scene. Forensic analysis also confirmed that the bloodstains at the crime scene were of the same blood type as Simpson's.</p> <p>A key witness in the murder of Simpson's ex-wife, 62-year-old John Dutton, broke his silence 30 years later, revealing in an audio recording to the British Daily Mail that Simpson was indeed at the scene during the crime and that he had hired four gangsters from the Gambino crime family to kill his ex-wife and her friend.</p> <p>In 2006, Simpson wrote a book titled "If I Did It." In the book, Simpson hypothetically described how he might have committed murders 12 years earlier. The American media called Simpson's book "merciless mockery" of the American judicial system.</p>
		<p>At the legislative level in the United States, deliberate loopholes are intentionally left, deliberately creating backdoors for subsequent judicial trials, allowing tycoons or financial magnates to evade legal punishment. The U.S. judiciary lacks essential empathy at the legislative level, and lacks logical consistency in handling similar matters and media coverage. Therefore, the foundation of the U.S. judiciary cannot achieve fairness and justice. Some judicial trials in the United States may seem intense, leading the public to mistakenly believe that the United States has the freedom to fully express and realize democracy, freedom, human rights, and universal values. However, in reality, this system turns lawyers into accomplices who help criminal groups evade legal punishment and profit. Police often collude with lawyers, giving lawyers the opportunity to profit once someone is detained by the police. Citizens may be detained by the police for minor matters, prompting lawyers to start profiting by representing them. People often have to cooperate with</p>

	<p>lawyers to get rid of the stain. Usually, having money can win lawsuits, as long as the procedures seem legitimate. The whole country is governed not by moral methods but by interests.</p> <p>It is well known that the United States frequently experiences hurricanes, which easily destroy wooden houses, causing huge financial losses to the people. However, at the legislative level, laws and tax provisions unfavorable to using concrete for housing construction are deliberately created, and false information promoting the environmental friendliness of wooden houses is spread. Politicians bought by tycoons naturally accept: fragile housing–destroyed by natural disasters–insurance compensation– profits from reconstruction, such repeated traps that continuously drain people's wealth.</p>
	<p>In 2011, after returning from the United States for two years, Dr. Zhang Hao established the North Company, beginning the development of China's own filtering chips.</p> <p>On May 16, 2015, Dr. Zhang Hao set out on a journey to Phoenix, full of joy, thinking that he would be greeted with a grand academic exchange. However, what awaited him was conspiracy and imprisonment. Upon landing, Zhang Hao was forcibly taken away by personnel from the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), on the grounds of being a Chinese spy violating US laws and posing a serious threat to US national security. The detention of Zhang Hao caused a sensation in China. It's worth noting that Zhang Hao had been away from the United States for six years, and before leaving, all industry-related information was left behind after inspection; the only thing he took with him was his knowledge. How could he possibly be a spy?</p> <p>Nevertheless, the US side, without any evidence, solely based on suspicion, brought Dr. Zhang Hao to court.</p> <p>Anhua High-Tech Co., Ltd. in the United States presented Zhang Hao's personal emails from Tianjin University as evidence, which shocked everyone. How could they obtain personal emails? The United States didn't realize their own actions, but instead found themselves in the midst of public opinion turmoil. By exposing their interception of personal data from others, they revealed their covert acquisition of communication data circulating on campus networks, which ended up in the hands of a US company. This proves that the US government is openly stealing secrets from other countries and then providing them to US companies as evidence.</p> <p>The US court eventually succumbed to pressure and announced bail for Zhang Hao, but the US government wanted time to verify the authenticity of the evidence. However, the judgment stated that Zhang Hao had infringed upon the legitimate rights of two companies in his past business activities, demanding compensation of \$477,000 and an 18-month prison sentence.</p> <p>In fact, these two US companies were the real thieves, stealing Zhang Hao's patented technology to mass-produce their own products. Just as Zhang Hao compromised and paid the fine, the US once again brought up more lawsuits. Now, Zhang Hao's return journey has become distant and uncertain. This is</p>

		<p>precisely the ultimate goal of the United States—to make Zhang Hao stay in the US permanently.</p> <p>In the blink of an eye, Dr. Zhang Hao has lived in the US for nine years, and these nine years have been devoid of freedom, dignity, and hope.</p> <p>If tycoons or financial magnates and politicians who control the United States still have a shred of conscience, morality, empathy, and law, they should immediately and unconditionally release Dr. Zhang Hao to ensure his safe return to China.</p>
		<p>All land in the United States was plundered from the indigenous Native Americans by Anglos and Jews, yet legislation requires every household to pay property taxes every year, completely disregarding basic housing rights. From birth to death, the American people create wealth for international tycoons or financial magnates, who control the taxation tools and the armed forces, capable of striking the American people at any time. International tycoons only need to provide relatively high personal treatment to nurture a force that collects taxes by force for them. Every ordinary American is either a pawn or a servant of tycoons or financial magnates.</p>
		<p>Mentally ill individuals who commit murder should indeed be sentenced to death, but American tycoons or financial magnates are manipulating the top levels of the judiciary to deliberately exploit mentally ill individuals committing murder in order to evade legal punishment.</p>
		<p>The separation of powers in the United States, including judicial independence, is completely hypocritical. If the United States were to achieve judicial independence, all judges and lawyers in the United States would not be allowed to join any political party. Those who have not joined a party should not be affiliated, and those who have should immediately declare their withdrawal from the party. If any judge refuses to withdraw from the party, they should be considered to have resigned automatically from that moment onwards, and they should be prohibited from engaging in judicial work. The role of a judge must be absolutely independent, with the judiciary unable to interfere in other political matters, and political parties and administrative agencies unable to interfere with the judiciary.</p>
		<p>The Democratic Party's efforts to manufacture President Trump's guilt and push for his imprisonment, in contrast to the Republican Party's belief in Trump's innocence, highlight that the United States fundamentally lacks a system of checks and balances.</p>
		<p>In today's world, the ethics of many politicians have regressed by 2,000-4,000 years, and the world's judiciary has regressed by 2,000-4,000 years.</p> <p>If in ancient China, these politicians who fabricate lies would essentially be executed, along with tycoons colluding with them. The entire family property of politicians and tycoons would be confiscated to eliminate hidden dangers. In the last two hundred years, with Western missionaries fabricating history, philosophy, and religion, the judiciary system heavily influenced by tycoons fails to stop such top-level designed most serious crimes. Lawyers become</p>

	<p>accomplices in reducing or acquitting criminals, and the justice system becomes more inclined to excessively punish ordinary people for minor offenses. Worst of all, the judicial ideology constructed by tycoons and politicians has formed a mindset in the public, mistakenly believing that the judicial system in their society or country provides the utmost protection for freedom, democracy, and human rights. Whether a country is willing to implement an improved version of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty, in today's world, if a country wants to sever the collusion between politicians and tycoons in fabricating lies, as well as between tycoons and academic authorities in fabricating lies, thereby creating conflicts and wars, plundering wealth, harming public health, and controlling the world, it is necessary to restart the mature punishment system of ancient China. In addition, any media involved in falsification should be severely punished, decisively shut down, with all assets confiscated, and all crimes accounted for.</p> <p>All immediate family members and their descendants of all criminals are prohibited from engaging in government, political, economic, financial, judicial, military, security, and weapon manufacturing-related fields for the next 2,000-3,000 years. All immediate family members of the principal offenders are prohibited from attending any university for education for the next 200-300 years. This may help prevent crime to the greatest extent and maintain world peace.</p>
	<p>The medical technology led by the United States today does not contemplate how to use rational methods to prevent and manage uremia, but ultimately opts for the simplest solution—transplanting healthy human kidneys into patients. This has led to a large number of minors and adults being abducted annually. Their kidneys are forcibly harvested for illegal organ transplants. Myanmar is now one of the most notorious regions for this crime, with criminal groups brazenly engaging in kidnapping, human trafficking, and openly harvesting human organs. The Myanmar government and military openly protect these criminal organizations and co-govern the northern region with them, jointly launching armed attacks against anti-telecom fraud militias. Despite China's vigorous crackdown on such crimes, under the protection of the Myanmar government, it cannot penetrate Myanmar to combat criminals more effectively, due to the so-called UN conventions. Myanmar's characteristic crime of establishing telecom fraud rings has never ceased. These criminal groups first force victims to commit fraud, and if it does not yield profit, they resort to torture and organ harvesting. Women who end up in Myanmar are often forced into sexual slavery, impregnated, their breast milk extracted, and newborns used as organ donors. Once the value of a sex slave is exhausted in a fraudulent ring, they are usually resold, or their organs are harvested, after which they are buried alive or slaughtered. China is well aware that large numbers of women and civilians are being kidnapped in Myanmar, subjected to daily torture, rape, or facing organ harvesting, slaughter, or burial alive. They also know that the Myanmar government and military serve as protectors of</p>

criminals, earning trillions of CNY in illegal profits, yet they cannot send troops to rescue and thoroughly dismantle Myanmar as a criminal state and some criminal organizations. Today's United Nations is like a retirement institution that only consumes salaries, utterly worthless, and only protects criminal states and organizations like Myanmar.

The dire situation vividly demonstrates that under the leadership of the United States and the judicial systems established in the West, today's moral standards have regressed for at least 4,000 years, along with judicial systems and ethics. Greedy Aung San created an unprecedented combination of hypocritical democracy and freedom to create a new country in Myanmar, and the Nobel Peace Prize was awarded to Aung San's daughter Aung San Jisu, ignoring the fact that it was Aung San's greed that led to the 70-year civil war in which Burmese oppressed ethnic minorities. If the beacon country really wants to reduce warfare, decrease the military presence, and truly care about the livelihoods and human rights of the impoverished people in the northern region of Myanmar, which originally belonged to China, they should propose to the international community to consider restructuring Myanmar and allow the impoverished northern region to return to China.

The American politicians must fully realize that a US controlled by interest groups will only fill the world with conflict. The notion that profiting from conflict is acceptable reflects the lowest level of political and economic thinking, devoid of any ethical considerations. If these low-level politicians and magnates lived in China, such a flagrant violation of moral ethics would have led to their execution long ago. If they lived in ancient China, not only would the individual be executed, but all members of their family lineage for at least three generations would face the same fate. A country or world can only achieve tranquility and peace by effectively eliminating evil forces.

According to online media reports, criminal groups in Southeast Asia have even established a clandestine school, continuously abducting students to become organ donors, while other kidnapped individuals are covertly subjected to organ harvesting at this location. These criminal syndicates' crimes cannot be erased by destroying bodies, and evidence will inevitably remain, as quantum entanglement will prove. All members of these criminal syndicates and their informed family members must be publicly tried and sentenced to death, with the entire family wealth, up to six generations, confiscated. Only then can the world effectively control such malignant crimes and save this chaotic world, allowing innocent and kind people to receive effective protection. **When the judicial ethics regress by 4,000 years, some vicious crimes must be dealt with according to past methods and laws.**

All immediate family members and their descendants of all criminals are prohibited from engaging in government, political, economic, financial, judicial, educational, medical, military, security, and weapon manufacturing-related fields for the next 2,000-3,000 years. All immediate family members of the principal offenders are prohibited from attending any university for education

		for the next 200-300 years. This may help prevent crime to the greatest extent and maintain world peace.
		In China, some lawyers view the successful defense by O.J. Simpson's legal team in the Simpson murder case as a victory for judicial fairness. This represents a significant regression in Chinese moral, ethical, and judicial standards, leading to similar cases in China that remain unresolved. In reality, criminals of this nature, once involved in a crime, inevitably leave traces, which can be identified through quantum entanglement. Such crimes must be severely punished as they were in ancient China to prevent and control further criminal activities.
		The modern Chinese judiciary has been severely polluted by Western pseudo-history and false moral and ethical views, making it difficult to render impartial judgments. China needs to revise some of its current judicial articles according to the judicial system and legislative principles of ancient China in order to possibly curb crime.
26	Several key issues of repeated mistakes in national governance in China or the United States and the difficulties in solving them.	
		It is very difficult for the United States to achieve equal land distribution and reclaim land assets from self-interested individuals. It is also difficult to change the profit model of the financial industry and to reclaim the right to issue currency and collect taxes. This requires not only addressing the mindset of the American people, but also relying on the government to solve these issues. Only one of the three statues on the lintel of the U.S. Supreme Court is a real historical figure, Confucius, while the other two are fictional. The founding philosophy of the United States is based on the erroneous philosophical ideas formed from Western pseudo-history, and the country was founded with the central idea of massacring the indigenous peoples, laying down roots that are difficult to repair. Zero-dollar purchases are often carried out as organized crime in U.S. supermarkets, and it is shocking that politicians have actually passed laws supporting this criminal behavior by stating that amounts under \$950 are not considered criminal. The United States lacks a cohesive national culture to guide the public, and the government system established by the country's founders is difficult to correct.
		In 1972, President Nixon visited China. As they were parting ways, Nixon asked Chairman Mao for a piece of calligraphy. After some thought, Chairman Mao wrote a calligraphic piece of twelve characters on rice paper and gifted it to Nixon. However, Nixon never understood its meaning in his life. To this day, neither Nixon nor the U.S. government has fully comprehended the significance of "嫦娥奔月" ("Chang'e Flying to the Moon"). Americans once interpreted "Chang'e Flying to the Moon." as China's artificial satellite, symbolizing China's strength, or referring to the U.S. lunar landing program. However, these interpretations were inadequate and superficial, far from the historical depth and philosophical considerations mentioned by

		<p>Chairman Mao. Looking back, the trajectory of Nixon, the U.S., and China's relations essentially conforms to the ultimate outcome of "Chang'e Flying to the Moon.", just as Chairman Mao may have anticipated when he wrote these characters.</p> <p>By the way, the alleged success of the Apollo moon landing in the United States is entirely fabricated. According to U.S. FDA standards for assessing process authenticity, there is plenty of evidence to prove it is completely false or fake or fictional or illogical. If the United States, controlled by international financial elites or chaebol or plutocrat or financial oligarch, can fabricate something as significant as the moon landing, how can there be any justice, fairness, freedom, democracy, or human rights in its justice system?</p> <p>Dever Island in Canada, one of Earth's eight Mars-like landscapes, closely resembles the scenery of the 1969 U.S. moon landing. American netizens have found the filming location for the fake moon landing on Dever Island.</p>
	<p>The ancestors of China made enormous sacrifices to create a new China through great bloodshed. However, there are four major issues in the system construction that have led to the inability to eradicate major mistakes in governance, as well as recurring outbreaks. First, there is no death penalty or severe punishment for wrongful killings. Second, the main culprits of wrongful crimes are not punished. Third, there is a failure to fully hold accountable for significant losses resulting from leadership errors, and a failure to strictly enforce accountability for the wrong path and methods. Fourth, there is excessive protection for maliciously wrong or criminal officials, and a lack of theoretical support for the resistance of the people against officials who deliberately harm them, rather than using the law to punish the victims.</p> <p>The most difficult aspect of national or regional governance is the governance of officials. The Chinese government's inadequate understanding of the historical handling of official crimes and major mistakes has led to the continuous recurrence of similar thorny issues. The government must reflect on history and recognize that in the past, in some cities, more than 50% of Communist Party members were unable to withstand the torture of the Kuomintang and betrayed the party. In the early days of the founding of the Communist Party, a large number of elites held prominent positions because the ruthless laws of the Kuomintang helped to weed out a large number of those who could not withstand the test. However, now, there is no opposing force using harsh methods to test the worth of the "golden" ones and eliminate unqualified individuals, leading to various problems in government management.</p> <p>Viruses are present in the human body, and even in a sterile and clean environment, a physically strong individual can quickly develop a viral infection if they are exposed to excessive airflow. This may require medical treatment to prevent the development of viral myocarditis or pneumonia. In other words, it is difficult for government institutions to be completely free of a small number of bad elements, which can lead to the exploitation of ordinary citizens,</p>	

wrongful imprisonment, or even loss of life. When such issues or criminal behavior by officials arise, victims hope for swift government intervention, but the government's efforts to rectify the situation are typically slow and may lag behind for a long time. When innocent and impoverished individuals are harmed by criminals, the law's justice inevitably lags behind violence, and it is difficult for the justice system to fully compensate victims for the harm they have suffered. If the actions of government officials exacerbate the harm suffered by victims, this will undoubtedly have a negative impact on the credibility of the government. Therefore, the government should allow victims to retaliate against any criminal or harmful actions at their disposal during unbearable or crisis situations, as long as the victims are not attacking the country or its social system. The government must differentiate between the actions of the victims against suspected criminal public servants or criminals and attacks against the State or ruling party. Allowing victims to retaliate against these criminal individuals would not be considered a crime, and it would greatly facilitate governance for the government.

Of course, the government should establish various systems. First, civil service recruitment must undergo several years of tough training. Second, the personal and family assets of civil servants and their units with serious crimes should be publicly disclosed. Third, a system should be established to punish and demote civil servants for mistakes or inaction, using their work to either improve them or eliminate those unsuitable for the profession. If a demoted civil servant can still perform well and demonstrate patience, sincerity in serving the country and the public, measures should be put in place for potential re-promotion. Fourth, lessons should be learned from the promotion and demotion of officials in ancient history and pre-revolution China, establishing the principle that civil servants guilty of serious errors must be demoted.

Fifth, lessons should be drawn from the promotion and punishment of officials involved in serious crimes before and after the founding of the People's Republic of China, establishing the principle that civil servants involved in serious crimes must be severely punished. The importance of harsh punishment for officials involved in serious crimes cannot be ignored. We cannot tolerate innocent people being wrongly killed. If such handling is improper, it will inevitably lead others to believe that as long as they wave a flag, they can get away with killing others. Those who assist murderers, knowing that their leaders have committed serious mistakes but fail to oppose them, should not be allowed to remain in the ranks of officials or promoted, as they will inevitably have a huge negative impact. The continuous tragedies that have occurred include, according to incomplete statistics: in the "Great Purge" in the areas of Hubei, Henan, Anhui, and Jiangsu, outstanding military leaders such as Xujishen, Zhou Weijiong, and 2500 others were killed by Zhang Guotao. In the end, Zhang Guotao was not sentenced or executed. During the anti-communist campaign, Xia Xi was responsible for the killing of General

	<p>Duan Dechang, a high-ranking leader of the Hunan and Hubei Provincial Committee, Red Army Commissar Wan Tao, and many other founders of the revolutionary base and Red Army, as well as more than 1,000 senior officers and soldiers at all levels. Over 7,000 innocent people, including local government leaders and innocent civilians, were also mistakenly killed. Despite the efforts of Marshal He Long, General Duan Dechang could not be saved, and Xia Xi was ultimately not held accountable for these heinous crimes and sentenced to death.</p> <p>These power-holders who commit crimes with impunity and do not bear equal responsibility are setting a bad precedent, especially Zhang Guotao. Even after killing many innocent people and realizing his mistake, he still pursues power. The government's failure to immediately publicly trial and execute Zhang Guotao is a great mistake.</p> <p>China has long been misled into fully privatizing state-owned assets and into fully opening up and marketizing its finance. Failure to recognize that these actions belong to the characteristics of the late Tang political economy. Lack of nationality change tax, gift tax, and inheritance tax.</p>	
27	Philosophy	
	<p>Attempting to create panic, conflict, crisis, war, and division to profit from them, creating or exploiting pseudo-theories with apparent flaws, investing funds, nurturing certain representatives, granting various titles, thereby gradually developing them into systematic pseudo-theories, harming the health or interests of the majority, enabling financial magnates and politicians to obtain long-term high illegal profits. Once a pseudo-theory is exposed, another one has already received the 800-meter relay baton behind it.</p> <p>The public unknowingly forms cognitive patterns, consciously or unconsciously upholding pseudo-theories or pseudo-methodologies, while rejecting correct theories and methods, perfectly fulfilling the expected outcome of driving out good money with bad.</p> <p>The United States basically has no philosophy, only interests.</p>	
	<p>Argentinian President Javier Milei may have the passion for reforming Argentina, but he clearly lacks fundamental philosophical thinking. Guided by the erroneous economic theories advocated by the United States, it is inevitably transitioning from one failure to another new failure.</p>	
	<p>The U.S. economic model includes components of party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, corporate behavioral economy, and market economy, which are basically similar to China. Despite the fact that over the past century, the United States has led the world in terms of GDP, and has temporarily held a leading position globally in technology and economics, its philosophical ideas differ significantly from those of China. This ultimately leads to the inevitable decline or disintegration of the United States.</p>	
	<p>The United States lacks philosophy, so both the academic community and the Americans disregard scientific ethics, lack religious beliefs, and, by adopting philosophical methods, clearly see that Pythagoras' theorem and the</p>	

	<p>mathematical system of ancient Greece were plagiarized from ancient Chinese books through simple mathematical calculations in a very short time, but they never revise textbooks.</p> <p>First, the largest Roman numeral is M, representing 1000. Counting with Roman numerals requires adding up each numeral. To represent ten million (10,000,000) in Roman numerals, one would need to write ten thousand M's. This is a very cumbersome arithmetic. Second, Roman numerals cannot perform addition, subtraction, multiplication, or division because they lack the concept of decimal places. One of the dumbest aspects of Roman numerals is that the Roman numeral system cannot perform exponentiation or square root mathematical operations. So, how could Pythagoras' theorem and geometry originally be proposed by ancient Greece? If any American believes that Roman numerals can perform multiplication, division, exponentiation, or square roots, they should try it themselves manually. Therefore, with such a level of calculation and a numeral system that cannot perform square roots, what is left of Pythagoras' theorem and the mathematical systems of ancient Greece and Rome? Obviously, the mathematical systems of ancient Greece and Rome were plagiarized from ancient Chinese books. Without a decimal-based mathematical foundation, how could ancient Europe have systematic research achievements in mathematics, physics, and astronomy? The astronomical and mathematical achievements of ancient Europe were all plagiarized from China and falsely claimed as European originals. The scientific and technological level of ancient China has been at the forefront of the world for at least 4,700 years.</p>
	<p>Since the 1950s, the pseudo-theory "Lipid Hypothesis," designed by Ancel Keys, a professor at the University of Minnesota, which was bought by financial oligarchs, has led to a sharp increase in the sale of various harmful vegetable oils, such as transgenic soybean oil, while the use of animal fat, which is more beneficial to the human body, has greatly decreased. At the same time, there has been a significant increase in the consumption of sugar, resulting in a continuous increase in obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases among the population in the United States and globally.</p> <p>From the 1950s to the present, obesity has spread like a plague, and the incidence of diabetes has also increased rapidly. The proportion of U.S. adults with diabetes has increased from less than 1% to over 11.6%. At the same time, the incidence of heart disease has not been alleviated or suppressed and remains the leading cause of death.</p> <p>On June 15, 2017, the American Heart Association (AHA) issued a misleading statement, suggesting that saturated fats increase LDL (so-called bad cholesterol) levels, thereby increasing the risk of cardiovascular disease. Foods rich in saturated fats, such as pork and coconut oil, have been advised to be consumed less, with recommendations to use vegetable oils like soybean oil instead. Meanwhile, genetically modified soybeans with glyphosate residues were being highly produced, with higher oil yields than non-genetically modified soybeans, providing producers with a better profit opportunity. Producers and promoters</p>

completely disregarded the long-term health hazards of consuming genetically modified soybeans with glyphosate residues. However, over the past four years, global soybean production has been severely excessive. **If the U.S. government is guided by philosophy in governing the country and safeguarding public health, it should at least cease the cultivation of genetically modified soybeans and switch to non-GM soybeans.** However, the oligarchs-controlled U.S. government has consistently failed to make any correct negative feedback decisions, not even harshly punishing the AHA or revoking its charter, compensating victims and their families for the harm caused. **If this had happened in ancient China, all criminals would have been exterminated, the assets of the financial oligarchs confiscated by the state, and the victims and their families compensated. This illustrates that the moral and judicial systems in the United States have regressed by 2,000-4,000 years.** Constrained by the democratic, freedom, and human rights-based judicial system constructed and promoted by the beacon nation, it is **fundamentally impossible to control such crimes globally.** Instead, it leads to a marathon relay of pseudo-theories, where public wealth and health are repeatedly harvested. The long-term profit model derived from various pseudo-theories constructed by academic masters nurtured by oligarchs has become the engine driving economic growth in the United States.

Under the erroneous guidance of nutrition and medical theories in the United States, from 1999 to 2018, the obesity rate increased from 30.5% to 42.4%. It is worth noting that the obesity rate among adults aged 20 to 39 was 40%, 40 to 59-year-olds was 45%, and those aged 60 and above was 43%. **The obesity population in China has also doubled. According to data provided at a press conference on the "Report on Nutrition and Chronic Diseases of Chinese Residents (2020)" by the Information Office of the State Council, more than 50% of Chinese adults are overweight or obese,** nearly 20% of children and adolescents aged 6 to 17 are overweight or obese, and those under 6 years old reach 10%.

In a study from 2015, mice on a soybean oil-rich diet gained nearly 25% more weight than mice on a coconut oil diet and 9% more weight than mice on a high-fructose diet.

"This was a major surprise for us -- that soybean oil is causing more obesity and diabetes than fructose -- especially when you see headlines everyday about the potential role of sugar consumption in the current obesity epidemic," said Poonamjot Deol, the assistant project scientist who directed the project in the lab of Frances M. Sladek, a professor of cell biology and neuroscience.

[University of California - Riverside. "Soybean oil causes more obesity than coconut oil, fructose." ScienceDaily. ScienceDaily, 22 July 2015. <www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2015/07/150722144640.htm>.]

In 1961, in order to lower cholesterol, the American Heart Association recommended using polyunsaturated seed oils instead of butter and advised consuming less animal fat, such as lard.

Later, in 1970, the U.S. Senate supported the Department of Agriculture's dietary guidelines and released the first clear government statement, the Food

Guide Pyramid, emphasizing low-fat diets as an important strategy. Of course, this was also supported by many large interest groups.

As a result, Ancel Keys popularized the low-fat diet and established absolute authority in the field of nutrition, as American nutrition was the most advanced and the rest of the world was studying and emulating it.

Over the decades, the dietary structure of the world has been adjusted, with many people being afraid to eat fat, and those who do are only willing to consume vegetable oils, avoiding animal fats.

But the reality is quite honest: low-fat diets not only failed to reduce the incidence of heart disease, but also increased the risk of various chronic diseases. The number of obese people and the prevalence of diabetes and heart disease are increasing all over the world, as consumption of refined carbohydrates and processed vegetable oils has rapidly spread chronic diseases globally.

In the early 20th century, someone at Procter & Gamble discovered a clever way to get rich. Initially using cottonseed oil for candles and soap, they discovered it could be hydrogenated into a solid resembling animal fat. Leveraging this cheap animal fat substitute, they launched Crisco vegetable shortening.

From then on, Crisco was ingeniously marketed as a budget-friendly alternative to lard.

In 1911, Procter & Gamble launched a massive campaign to bring Crisco into American households. They produced a recipe book (for promoting Crisco) and distributed it for free, leading to a significant shift in dietary habits.

Crisco became the "healthy butter" of its time, suitable for frying, baking, and daily cooking, and could be stored at room temperature. They even claimed it was healthier, more digestible, and had cholesterol-lowering effects.

In the early 1960s, the American Heart Association recommended using Crisco and other unsaturated vegetable oils, leading to a rapid increase in sales of processed vegetable oils.

However, this so-called "healthy" vegetable oil undergoes hydrogenation during processing, producing trans fats, which are extremely harmful. Subsequent research has found that for every 2% increase in trans fat intake, the risk of heart disease doubles. It was only in recent years that the World Health Organization began advocating for a complete ban on trans fats.

According to conservative estimates from years ago, trans fats have already caused 100,000 deaths.

During those years, the American Heart Association, entrusted with the nation's nutritional well-being, essentially recommended that people consume this junk food (poison).

The consequences of this dietary advice have been disastrous:

1. Over 60% of Americans have diabetes or are prediabetic;
2. Only 12% of people have healthy metabolism;
3. The annual cost for chronic disease exceeds \$1.7 trillion.

From 1975 to 2018, global obesity rates doubled, with 2 billion adults currently obese. All of this is not merely coincidental.

The popularity of low-fat diets is not just simple academic fraud.

Behind it lies decades of collaboration between authoritative institutions, major food corporations, and pharmaceutical companies, the entire process rife with corruption. The American Heart Association (AHA) has close ties with major food corporations. The AHA, originally funded by Procter & Gamble, the manufacturer of Crisco, is one of the main supporters of the diet-heart hypothesis.

Now, 10 companies control the world's nutrition, with a total value exceeding \$1 trillion. They ignore the health threats posed by vegetable oils and sugar, profiting immensely at the expense of global health.

In 2017, data from the Minnesota Coronary Experiment, dormant for 40 years, was finally unearthed.

A research team reexamined and analyzed previously unpublished data from Ancel Keys and conducted a randomized double-blind trial to investigate whether replacing saturated fats with vegetable oils could reduce the risk of heart disease and death.

The intervention group consumed diets with vegetable oils (corn oil and corn oil margarine), which replaced saturated fats, while the control group consumed diets rich in saturated fats.

The results revealed that while the intervention group saw a 14% decrease in cholesterol, the mortality rate actually increased. For every 30 mg/dL decrease in cholesterol, the risk of death increased by 22%.

If we approach food in relevant fields philosophically and then contemplate using β -adrenergic receptor agonists like ractopamine to raise pigs, sheep, cattle, and poultry, reducing fat and increasing lean meat, isn't this commercial practice highly correlated with obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and so on?

Moreover, given that most animal fats consumed by humans are derived from pig fat, sourced from pig fat tissue, when using **ractopamine**, the beneficial pig fat tissue for human health inevitably undergoes a significant reduction. In addition, before selling pigs, cows, or poultry, stop using **ractopamine** to ensure that the test data at the time of sale are qualified. How could meat with qualified **ractopamine** test data be harmless to the human body? Isn't the consumption of such harmful products in a vicious cycle a huge threat to human health if consumed over the long term?

From this perspective, shouldn't there be an immediate global ban on β -adrenergic receptor agonists like ractopamine in the livestock industry?

Such deception has brought severe consequences globally. All individuals and companies involved in the deception and misleading of the public must have all their assets confiscated, and all criminals should be sentenced to a minimum of 20 years in prison or to the death penalty, with no possibility of parole.

[Deol P, Evans JR, Dhahbi J, Chellappa K, Han DS, Spindler S, Sladek FM. Soybean Oil Is More Obesogenic and Diabetogenic than Coconut Oil and Fructose

	<p>in Mouse: Potential Role for the Liver. PLoS One. 2015 Jul 22;10(7):e0132672. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0132672. PMID: 26200659; PMCID: PMC4511588.] [清淡饮食的鼻祖，一个让全世界害怕脂肪的牛人，涉嫌学术作假.The founder of a light diet, a fearsome figure in the world who fears fat, is suspected of academic fraud.2020-06 10. https://www.163.com/dy/article/FEORJ9GU0514DDQJ.html]</p>
	<p>Transgenic soybeans containing glyphosate residues, when used in conjunction with herbicides, have indeed simplified transgenic soybean cultivation and increased soybean yields. However, the ecological damage caused by herbicides is serious. Post-herbicide use, aquatic life such as fish and shrimp in rural fields decreases, leading to soil degradation. In addition, a more significant concern is the high toxicity of herbicides when sprayed on vegetables, causing severe damage to the lungs, kidneys, liver, digestive system, and discomfort for those poisoned by herbicide ingestion, as evidenced by videos. Second, herbicides are associated with allergic reactions and tumors, two autoimmune diseases. Compared to pre-usage, the use of herbicides in rural areas leads to a much higher incidence of tumors, associated with the high incidence of childhood leukemia. Third, herbicides are linked to difficulties in pregnancy, as well as an increase in miscarriages, stillbirths, and birth defects. Fourth, herbicides pose a risk to the cardiovascular system, increasing the frequency of cardiovascular disease occurrences.</p> <p>When lacking philosophical awareness of weeds, the public inevitably misunderstands the presence of weeds in the soil, believing them to be entirely harmful, absorbing crop nutrients, affecting crop growth, and necessitating herbicide use for weed elimination. From a philosophical and dialectical perspective, everything has two sides. Most people are unaware that weed root secretions also attract a large number of microorganisms, enriching the soil's microbial community, balancing the soil's micro-ecosystem, improving land quality, and playing a role in regulating soil moisture and temperature. For example, when cotton cloth is buried in an orange grove, there is a significant difference between areas with weeds and areas without weeds. The fabric decomposes rapidly in weed-infested areas, while in weed-free areas, decomposition is much slower, indicating that weeds play an important role in eliminating fiber waste and improving the ecosystem. Global food production has been surplus for four consecutive years, making it unnecessary to expand ecological risks by using herbicides. Even if herbicide use is stopped, other physical methods are often used for weed control.</p> <p>Based on the above issues, it is imperative to establish an international convention to completely ban the use of herbicides globally within 3-4 years.</p>
	<p>In the United States, there are no moral limits to how they conduct themselves. They never view issues from a philosophical standpoint. In the event of a war between Japan and the United States in the future, even if American generals were to be captured by the Japanese military again, and even if they were forced to eat the feces of Japanese soldiers for three or even four years, not exceeding ten years, as long as America remains controlled by</p>

	<p>financial oligarchs, and as long as there are benefits to be exchanged between the United States and Japan, America will still consider Japan as a close ally. U.S. military leaders and soldiers are nothing more than tools of financial oligarchs.</p>
	<p>The philosophy in the United States rarely embraces the concept of reciprocity; it's all about self-interest.</p> <p>Even if the United States was in a state of peril, on the verge of death, and you disregarded threats and dangers to save America, however, as long as America is controlled by financial oligarchs or selfish individuals, once America recovers, they would quickly show no loyalty, no religious faith, and will try to release toxins or plunder the wealth of those who saved America. Religious beliefs, democracy, freedom, and human rights are nothing but the best disguise for the scams of the United States, politicians, and financial oligarchs. Despite being the world's top military and economic power, the United States does not need to rely on alliances to govern the world, but instead seeks alliances everywhere, creating conflicts. Once competing for the same target or having different interests from its allies, the U.S. immediately treats their allies as enemies.</p>
	<p>The United States is a nation of shareholders formed by the plunder of Native American land through immigration. Excellent culture and philosophy are difficult to settle in the hearts of plunderers to build a moral American society; instead, self-interest and plunder are instinctual in constructing the national spirit of Americans, where plunder and slaughter inevitably become frequently used means. To make opponents relax their vigilance, feeling legitimately plundered, it is necessary to design at the top level, remove the strict past laws, design a hamburger with the three elements of freedom, democracy, and human rights, give you American-style hamburgers, and then take away your silver, gold, or jewels.</p>
	<p>President Trump said that the current America is not respected at all, this is because the greedy United States produces only a philosophy of bullying, enslaving, and plundering other countries and their wealth.</p> <p>In history, China has assisted the United States at least ten times, while the United States has betrayed China at least thirty times. The fourth and sixth betrayals were the most lethal, as China lost 110.42 million people and nearly 16% of its territory. The United States owes much of its present strength to China, using it as a stepping stone at least nine times before turning against it. Without China's help, the United States would not exist today. It would not have had the resources to purchase land and become a major power in the Americas, nor would it have been able to occupy Hawaii with the help of China, establishing itself as the dominant power in the Pacific. Unlike other Western powers, the United States, since its formal establishment in 1776, was a poor and weak country. It was during the most destitute period of the early United States that China first provided assistance. At that time, the newly formed United States had an area of about 800,000 square kilometers and a population of 2.5 million. Meanwhile, China was in the golden age of the Qing Dynasty under the reign of</p>

	<p>Emperor Qianlong, with an area of over 13 million square kilometers and a population of nearly 300 million. The United States, which was predominantly agricultural at the time, accounted for only 6% of the Qing Dynasty's territory and less than 1% of its population, making it a truly small and weak country.</p> <p>According to the philosophical thinking and logic of American politicians and financiers towards China, who had once saved their country's lives, when they are seriously ill and in need of emergency medical attention, they go to find an excellent doctor to save their lives. However, as soon as the doctor saves their lives and their health is restored, they (American politicians and financiers) may at any time plunder the doctor's wealth and kill the doctor. The question is: What kind of animal is the United States? Why should others respect the United States?</p>
	<p>In the early days of the United States, driven by the fervent expectations of the American people, China risked confrontation with Britain to rescue America from British and Spanish oppression. However, once the United States made money, it shamelessly flooded China with opium, not only depleting China's silver, but also causing physical harm to tens of millions of Chinese people. This is the philosophy of life of the American people and politicians, as well as the true history of the United States. Why do Americans expect other countries to respect the evil United States?</p> <p>{By 1890, China was losing annually 30 million taels of silver due to opium purchases, with the total amount of opium imported between 1854 and 1894 reaching 1.5 billion taels of silver. The evil opium sales in the Chinese market are mainly contributed by the UK and the US. A large portion of the initial capital accumulation (the first bucket of gold) of American industrialization came from opium trade with China. The massive outflow of silver caused financial difficulties for the Qing Dynasty in China, and the common people had to endure hunger and cold.</p> <p>In the process of opium smuggling, American businesses and merchants in Guangzhou, except for the Olyphant family, all participated in opium smuggling activities, which is evidence of the greed of American businessmen.⁵⁰</p> <p>The rapid development of the opium trade between the United States and China was due to the support of the US government, the protection of officials, and their direct involvement.⁵⁰ The first person to suggest opium trade with China was Samuel Shaw, the first American consul in Guangzhou.⁵⁰ The first person to suggest transporting opium from Turkey was Thomas Sandys, the consul in Smyrna (now Izmir, Turkey). "Before and after the Opium War, several consuls stationed in Guangzhou... were all involved in opium smuggling" (Shaoxi: "Nineteenth Century American Aggression on Opium Trade to China").⁵⁰</p> <p>At the end of 1838, Emperor Daoguang sent Lin Zexu as imperial commissioner to Guangdong to ban opium, initiating the impactful and dramatic event known as the First Opium War.⁵² The British, naturally unwilling to give up, realized that a box of opium cost 237 rupees but could be sold in China for ten times that amount. Charles Elliot, a representative of the British trading firm</p>

Jardine, Matheson & Co., admitted, "In good years, every box of opium can generate a profit of one thousand silver yuan." Consequently, using the excuse of the blockade of the Bogue forts, the British launched the First Opium War, forcing the defeated Qing government of China to sign unequal treaties such as the Treaty of Nanjing.

At that time, however, the opium trade had still not been legalized. Despite multiple hints and bribes from British colonialists to Chinese government officials, the Qing government did not give in and continued to implement a series of internal bans on opium.⁵⁰

In May 1843, the U.S. government sent Caleb Cushing as a special envoy to China. The American side employed a combination of extortion (including displays of force) and bribes, coercing Chinese negotiators to sign the Wanghia Treaty and the Customs Tariff.⁵⁰ Because the signing location was at the village of Mong Ha in Macau, it was also known as the "Treaty of Wanghia". After the Wanghia Treaty, U.S. opium smuggling became even more rampant, spreading throughout the entire coastline of China without being limited to the five designated treaty ports. Guangzhou, Wusong, Fuzhou, Ningbo, Xiamen, Zhoushan, Liugong Island, Jinzhou, and other coastal cities were all favored stopover points for opium ships.

It is estimated that by 1836, there were already 12.5 million smokers in China, causing immeasurable harm to countless Chinese soldiers and civilians.

In 2017, National Public Radio (NPR) Boston affiliate station WBUR reported on "How Opium Profits Shaped 19th Century Boston."⁵³ Several American families were involved, including the Cabot, Cushing, Weld, Delano, and Forbes families, all of whom prospered through the opium trade in Boston. Other families, such as the Lowell and Kirkland families, maintained enormous wealth through opium transactions. The Sturgis, Payne, Eliot, and Winthrop families were also mentioned.

The Boston Brahmins were generous donors to Harvard University and Yale University.⁵³ The Skull and Bones Society at Yale University was originally founded and supported by members of the Russell family. Samuel Russell founded the Russell & Company, with opium as its main business.⁵³ Another partner in the company, John Cleve Green, became Princeton University's largest donor, with funds from the opium trade. Princeton's School of Science was even named after him. New York University also benefitted from his bequest. These opium profits were also invested in hospitals, railways, and factories. John Murray Forbes invested opium profits into steamships, mines, and railways across the United States. His uncle, Thomas H. Perkins, was a fervent opium merchant, and the Perkins family held the largest share of U.S. merchants involved in the opium trade.

The book "China Bound: America's First Adventure in Imperialism: Trade, Treaty, Opium War, and Redeemer's Mission" by John Rogers Haddad, a professor at Pennsylvania State University, delves into the relationship between the American Industrial Revolution and the opium trade.⁵³ Haddad frankly states that China's economic strength in the 19th century allowed Americans to trade opium

	<p>for tea, and the opium trade became a means for the United States to transfer China's economic power to its own industrial revolution.</p> <p>Today's Americans should constantly overcome Alzheimer's syndrome and should not forget the history of the United States. Perhaps today's Americans can use the methods of metrological historical ethics and metrological economic ethics (econometric ethics) to measure the economic history of the United States. Early American businessmen who participated in trade between the United States and China became wealthy, becoming the first group of millionaires and multimillionaires. John Jacob Astor, a fur trader from New York, took part in the maiden voyage of the China Queen. He was the first U.S. multimillionaire and left behind an estate worth at least \$20 million when he passed away, equivalent to 1/107 of the entire U.S. GDP at the time. By 2006, on Forbes' list of the "wealthiest Americans of all time," John Jacob Astor ranked fourth with an estimated net worth of \$110.1 billion.^{53}}</p> <p>[The above paragraph is in Chapter 8 of the paper. Liu, L. (2023). Should U.S.-China Relations Be Normalized: A Historical, Religious, and Philosophical Perspective.]</p> <p>Can Americans accept the greedy and ungrateful philosophy of the United States? Each family has its own style. President Trump educates his children not to drink alcohol, get tattoos, use drugs, or smoke, which sets an example for the American people. Some Americans are aware that President Trump's children have four "NOT" good characteristics, but after Trump became business partners with them, these business partners intentionally influenced President Trump's children to adopt all of the above negative habits. Wouldn't President Trump be angry and punish these so-called business partners for it?</p>
	<p>The philosophy of the American financial oligarchs and politicians in controlling the challenge of the currency issuance system and the control of the Federal Reserve, which seriously affects their interests, is to assassinate the president, or a congressman, or a challenger, and then systematically eliminate the assassin and all those involved.</p> <p>International financiers may think that the current legal system, which they have designed in collaboration with the judiciary, only needs to deal with the immediate assassin, and then assemble a team of lawyers to argue for mitigating circumstances for the criminal. In fact, it is actually a protective umbrella designed by financiers. Despite the fact that the world now has a much higher level of university education than ancient China, ethical standards are much lower. The relentless pursuit and long-term possession of national interests by financiers is the core reason for the constant outbreaks of chaos, conflict, and war in the world. Therefore, for criminals representing the interests of their families and for crimes that significantly impact the country and the global order, the entire family must be eradicated in order to truly control crime. For such serious crimes, the involvement of any lawyer for the defense should be prohibited. Legislation at any time will never be absolutely fair, but to exchange a small injustice for more fairness on a global scale is in line with philosophical principles. In the future, if</p>

	<p>the laws are modified to have severe punishment for murderers according to the ancient Chinese legal system or according to the discipline on the battlefield, the families of financiers or politicians involved in murder would be exterminated for three or six generations. This world would soon see a significant reduction in conflict and war. Those who are involved in planning murders may believe they can destroy evidence by eliminating assassins, but as long as they are involved in murder, they will inevitably leave behind evidence that cannot be eliminated, and it can be extracted using quantum entanglement to retrieve information.</p>
	<p>The inferior philosophical thinking cultivated by American financial magnates has led to the greed, arrogance, lack of ethics, and lawlessness of politicians, which will inevitably doom the United States. If the United States wants to reverse its decline, it needs to at least replace the majority of politicians in the House and Senate, or at least change their thinking. However, it is unlikely for the mentality of a greedy, arrogant, unethical, and lawless politician to change easily.</p>
	<p>Since April 2010, China has lifted the restrictions on entry for individuals with HIV/AIDS, sexually transmitted diseases, leprosy, etc., and signed the "Agreement on the Entry of Persons with HIV/AIDS into China", stating the reason as respect for human rights and foreign individuals with HIV/AIDS. However, the author believes that, given China's current situation, such an agreement is extremely irresponsible and criminal, placing the lives and health of billions of Chinese people in a more dangerous environment. The coercion by the United States and the World Health Organization for China to sign such an agreement is absolutely wrong, shameless, and evil.</p> <p>By 2022, there were 39 million people living with HIV/AIDS globally, with 29.8 million receiving antiretroviral therapy. China reported 1.223 million existing cases of HIV/AIDS, including 689,000 HIV-infected individuals and 534,000 AIDS patients, significantly higher than the 740,000 reported in 2009. These results demonstrate that the decision was incorrect, a predictable outcome. Consequently, all officials from the United States, the United Nations, and the World Health Organization who supported the agreement should resign, and all their salaries should be returned. In addition, the agencies related to the inefficient United Nations and the World Health Organization should be dissolved.</p> <p>Mao Zedong, the greatest politician, philosopher, logician, strategist, military strategist, and poet in the world, once said, "The most important thing for a leader is foresight. If they lack foresight, what use are these useless politicians? Paying them every year just to create conflicts and contradictions around the world every day?"</p> <p>My IQ is slightly below average, yet I can clearly predict this outcome. However, at least 1.2 billion people in China surpass me, indicating that at least 1.2 billion people in China are capable of predicting this outcome. The most important aspect of leadership is foresight. This suggests that at least 0.1 billion people in China could serve as the Secretary-General of the United Nations or the Director-General of WHO, or as the President of the United States or any</p>

government official in the United States. Since the United States claims to be the most free and democratic country globally, if American politicians are not lying, they should immediately select some people from the 0.1 billion to serve as senators in the U.S. Their foresight abilities are typically much stronger than the current U.S. politicians. If some of the 0.1 billion Chinese people were to serve as members of the Senate and House of Representatives, Secretary-General of the United Nations, or the Director-General of the WHO, and in other positions, it is estimated that within 2-3 years, AIDS infection rates in China will significantly decrease, as will AIDS infection rates in the United States. However, if they are to take on roles in the United States, they must have a certain level of authority in military or police deployment.

AIDS is not an inherent disease in China, but is transmitted from abroad. The rapid spread and increasing incidence of AIDS have seriously damaged the health and human rights of the uninformed. If politicians still believe that human rights and health are both important, shouldn't they immediately enact an "International Convention on AIDS Patients Not Being Allowed to Enter the Country" to demonstrate their political achievements by voting quickly and passing it through the United Nations? At least this can prove that you are being paid and still working for the public.

Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." **Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises.** They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.

Therefore, anyone who formulates and approves erroneous AIDS policies resulting in increased infection rates among the population should be punished. They are unfit for government and decision-making roles and should be immediately dismissed and demoted, along with other assigned roles. Additionally, decision-makers must bear responsibility for misleading the public and compensate victims and the nation for losses. Serious losses should incur the necessary criminal penalties. Failure to compensate victims' losses should result in a ban on any government, judicial, military, financial or economic work for their immediate family and descendants for up to 1,000 years. Implementing such policies aims to remove politicians lacking foresight from decision-making circles and prevent decision-making failures caused by poor foresight and excessive vanity. Hence, there is a global need to establish a system of punishment and compensation for politicians who defy common sense or logic, leading to failure

	<p>of decisions. Which statesman can propose an international consensus or a United Nations convention on this matter?</p> <p>Anyone who compels China or any other country to adopt such erroneous AIDS policies must compensate with personal and family assets. If compensation is not completed within their generation, their descendants must continue the compensation. Any politician who confesses to collusion with tycoons leading to an increase in AIDS cases in China should have all personal assets of the tycoons confiscated. If profits were illegally obtained through pharmaceutical companies controlled by these tycoons, those companies should be dissolved. If there are cases of death, offenders should be sentenced to death; for each death, one offender is sentenced to death.</p> <p>The greatest threats to the world are evil or incompetent politicians, as well as malevolent tycoons. To maintain global stability and peace, it is necessary to respect Chairman Mao Zedong's ideology and address core issues by focusing on the primary contradictions. Therefore, it is necessary to prevent the adverse consequences caused by such individuals and, at the same time, to deal promptly and severely with the serious consequences of the crimes of these two types of persons.</p>
	<p>The United States lacks a philosophy of science, and its politicians have extremely low levels of philosophical knowledge. Moreover, the historical, political, and economic knowledge of American politicians is also very low. A group of short-sighted individuals, selected by the financial magnates controlling America, hold leadership positions in the country. American politicians and "McKinseyites" are completely incapable of recognizing that China's socialist system is actually an improved version of the early Tang Dynasty's equal-field system. They fail to see the trends and inevitability of human historical development. Marx did not hint at the historical origins of the socialist system. It is astonishing that low-intelligence "McKinseyites" engaged in politics can actually command the U.S. government to disrupt American politics and society. Furthermore, even Charlie Chaplin was expelled from the United States, signaling to the world that America lacks freedom of speech.</p>
	<p>From a philosophical and logical perspective, it is entirely possible to conclude that the atomic bomb dropped by the U.S. military in Hiroshima was fake. This successful psychological tactic used to defeat the war criminal Japan should no longer be kept hidden, otherwise the whole world will perceive the United States, its military, its politicians, and its people as deceivers, which would be very detrimental to the image of the United States.</p> <p>After the atomic bomb explosion, traces of radioactive materials from the explosion can certainly be found in the soil around the blast center through analysis for at least 20 years. However, American and German scientists collected soil samples from Hiroshima and Nagasaki after the explosions and found that these soils were almost indistinguishable from normal soil, with no abnormal levels of radiation. Whether from a philosophical or logical perspective, or according to the evaluation standards of the US FDA for process authenticity, this</p>

	<p>alone is enough to confirm that the United States was fabricating information. Furthermore, from a philosophical perspective, this is clearly illogical.</p> <p>The United States should not continue to keep the success of the atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima a secret. If this information is kept secret, the psychological tactics that were successfully employed during the war should be widely promoted by the United States to the outside world. Instead, it has become a classic case of lies told by American politicians and the military, leading to serious disdain for the United States, its military, its people, and its politicians in the international community.</p> <p>The U.S. government should take some pride, as during World War II, it managed to deceive Japan and other countries with the fake atomic bombs. The U.S. government should inform the public as soon as possible that this was a successful tactic, rather than continuing to hide the truth and being forced to very awkwardly admit the fabrication later. Tactical psychological warfare and the consequences of deceiving the public are completely different; if the public only learns the truth at the last moment, rather than from the government, they may be even more mentally devastated.</p> <p>After dropping the fake atomic bomb on Hiroshima, there was no residual contamination, which may have misled some countries. This could lead to nuclear-armed nations following the Hiroshima model for dropping nuclear weapons, which is a very serious problem. Maybe the United States is harming itself.</p> <p>According to simulations by British scientists, it would only take 100 nuclear weapons to disrupt global ecological stability, trigger a nuclear winter, and lead to the destruction of many people and civilizations around the world. However, in reality, the conclusion of the British scientists is considered completely wrong by many. This is because they based their conclusion on the famous Hiroshima atomic bomb incident, which was actually a psychological warfare deception by the United States against Japan. The weather in Hiroshima returned to normal within 2-3 weeks after the bombing, and a few years later, Hiroshima had regained its former prosperity. If such erroneous assumptions led to the United States being hit by 25-50 atomic bombs, the U.S. would have already entered a nuclear winter.</p> <p>Therefore, the United States must quickly announce to the world that the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki were a very successful psychological warfare.</p>
	<p>The Philosophy of the U.S. Toward Japan and the Consequences of Japan's Philosophy of Endurance</p> <p>According to media reports, at a gathering of the Japanese Liberal Democratic Party, former Prime Minister Koizumi's son shouted, "Destroy America," followed by similar shouts from the attendees. At this high-level party event, Koizumi Junichiro's son, Koizumi Shinjiro, expressed a truth that has been buried in the hearts of the Japanese for 80 years: Japan wants to destroy America. Despite his father Koizumi Junichiro, who had served as Prime Minister of Japan, always obeying the U.S. without ever daring to oppose, Koizumi Shinjiro knew that his</p>

	<p>father harbored hatred in his heart. Therefore, he boldly shouted, "Destroy America, give them 500 hydrogen bombs." Subsequently, other senior Liberal Democratic Party officials echoed this statement.</p> <p>[日本自民党聚会，前首相小泉儿子高喊灭掉美国，其余人紧随高喊 At a gathering of the Japanese Liberal Democratic Party, former Prime Minister Koizumi's son shouted to destroy the United States, while the rest followed closely in shouting.2024-06-01. https://www.163.com/dy/article/J3JRQ3T8055369FX.html]</p>
	<p>Although my intelligence may be below average, I can still judge from a philosophical perspective that homosexuality is both a physiological and psychological disorder. It is a huge mistake that American politicians believe that homosexuality is not a disease, and this misconception has misled countless families in the United States and around the world. In order to gain votes, American politicians intentionally seek to legalize various abnormal behaviors associated with homosexuality, which is a serious mistake. Based on the philosophical level of some politicians in the United States and Europe, there are at least 1.2 billion people in China with higher intelligence than the author who could become the Director General of WHO or a Member of Parliament in the United States.</p> <p>Among the top 100 universities globally in the fields of medicine, political science, management, and philosophy, although the United States and Europe have the majority of these universities, they have actually been consistently mistaken on these most basic issues for a long time. Instead, they have long misled victims and their families, misguided many countries, and misled the global public on the issue of homosexuality. This reflects that the rankings of these universities are not based on their true standards but on false logic. Politicians or medical professionals who make erroneous administrative decisions based on the aforementioned views regarding homosexuality should be punished. Politicians who hold incorrect views are no longer suitable for government affairs work and should be dismissed and replaced with other jobs as soon as possible. Moreover, these rankings of global universities, which are expensive, promote vanity and self-deception, and mislead the global public, should bear the responsibility for misleading the public. Such rankings should be immediately abolished globally, and those primarily responsible for using rankings to mislead the global public through charging should face the necessary criminal penalties. Which statesman can propose an international consensus or a UN convention on the subject?</p>
	<p>The promotion of transgender identities and the arbitrary change of gender by evil politicians is evidence that the ethical, philosophical, political, administrative, managerial, and medical standards of the modern Western world have regressed by 2000-4000 years.</p> <p>President Trump's family is well educated, and his son and daughter have not adopted the common bad habits of the West. If his daughter was in a women's restroom in a public place and suddenly encountered a man of the caliber of Shaquille O'Neal or O.J. Simpson claiming to be female, would she not feel unsafe? Can these evil politicians ensure that President Trump's daughter has the safety,</p>

	<p>freedom, and human rights she deserves?</p> <p>Shouldn't politicians who promote transgender identities and arbitrary gender changes be labeled as crocodile-grade inferior politicians?</p> <p>Shouldn't these unpredictable and evil politicians be permanently banned from engaging in government work?</p>
	<p>Influential media and professional journals are controlled by the United States and the West. Articles that deviate from mainstream Western views, or reveal errors or falsifications in clinical trial data, are difficult to publish in the West. Articles addressing errors in Phase III clinical trial data of certain drugs today almost have no chance of being published in the West, even though countless patients are treated under incorrect clinical guidelines or expert consensus formulated by the U.S. and Western countries. Ethical standards in medical practice in the U.S. and Western societies have regressed by 2000 years.</p>
	<p>Transgender issues are clearly a mental health issue, and have become a tool driven by plutocrats to profit from gender reassignment. The issue of transgender has seriously disrupted the social order of the United States and Western countries. Selfish and foolish politicians use this group to change their gender to showcase their political support for freedom, democracy, and human rights. These politicians have such a poor level of philosophy that they completely lack the foresight required of a leader. However, Western societies are unable to immediately expel such politicians from leadership positions, prohibit them from government work, and send them to prison for reflection. France first practiced Buddhism, then turned to Catholicism. The Ming Dynasty's "Zui Wei Lu 《罪惟录》" also mentioned that France believed in Buddhism. In the 17th century, the crown worn by the French king was the Buddhist Vairocana hat, which originated from Daoism's "Five Elders" hat. However, after the Western world extensively plagiarized China's cultural and technological achievements, in order to satisfy their vanity, they massively fabricated European history, culture, science, technology, and legal systems, resulting in a regression of 2,000-4,000 years in the judicial system brought to the world today. This has led to the inability of today's society to quickly and effectively address such low-level transgender issues. The United States must legislate, and the losses caused by this misleading information to the public should be compensated by these foolish politicians.</p> <p>The narrow-minded and foolish international medical professional organizations have actually removed transgender from the classification of mental illnesses. These so-called medical experts have a very low level of philosophy, seriously misleading the public and patients' families. It is a serious dereliction of duty by WHO to allow these individuals to occupy leadership positions for an extended period. These officials are not fit for leadership positions and must resign immediately. They should compensate all the victims for the losses caused by forcefully establishing such terrible rules.</p> <p>If the leadership level of the WHO is so poor, at least 1.2 billion Chinese people are capable of taking up the position. The moral and judicial system of Western society has regressed by 2000-4000 years. President Trump, knowing</p>

	<p>that some journalists are advocating for transgender issues and disrupting social order, is forced to spend a lot of effort dealing with such low-level issues, but is unable to reverse the poor social conditions and systems in the United States, and is unable to effectively govern the country. President Trump's son told a talk show host that his father faces public criticism every day, but the host prefers to steal the limelight. Perhaps the United States could design a legal system in which anyone who promotes transgender freedom must have all members of their household go to the streets and shout about changing their current gender every two hours during the day for 12 consecutive months. Anyone failing to do so will be fined and sentenced to one month in prison, and the penalty will increase with each subsequent offense, without the possibility of bail. Politicians, plutocrats, hosts, and writers must accept double imprisonment because they are more inflammatory.</p>
	<p>The Republican and Democratic parties in the United States are engaged in fierce battles over immigration policy, but the philosophical and governance levels of the Democratic Party on this issue are very low.</p> <p>Immigration without cultural identity and integration, with different customs and cultural backgrounds gathering together, won't conflicts and tensions arise? Random immigration only increases the burden and chaos for the country, right? Mass immigration is akin to organ transplantation, where the patient must take anti-rejection drugs every day to survive! The body is basically uncomfortable every day. President Trump may need to find a different approach to debate with the Democratic Party.</p> <p>The Democratic Party of the United States, seemingly supporting democracy and freedom, is actually for the sake of votes, not for the United States.</p>
	<p>The majority of the world's top 100 universities in the fields of management, political science, philosophy, and economics are in the United States and Europe. However, in 2019, the U.S. banned the sale of high-end chips to China in an attempt to cripple its industry. Now, China's domestic production of high-end chips is continuously improving, with the localization rate expected to rise from 15% to 70% in the next three years. One has to wonder which planet's mutated philosophy, management, and economics guide the U.S. The more the US imposes a ban on the sale of high-end technology products to China, the more China can develop advanced products and break the US blockade. This is an inevitable historical trend. If the United States does not implement a blockade policy, China's development in this field will be very slow. At least 1.2 billion people in China have higher IQs than mine, and I can see this clearly, as can Chinese high school students. China is a trading partner of the United States, helping consume the products that America produced, which were high-end at the time.</p> <p>Why are American politicians so incompetent and narrow-minded? They keep pushing the government to ban the supply of advanced chip products to China, which is equivalent to accelerating the collapse of the U.S. economy and reducing corporate profits. How can American politicians be so "smart"? Are there real economists and management experts guiding the U.S. economy?</p>

	<p>As a suggestion, should the United States consider enacting one or more laws stating that any financial oligarchs and politicians who conspire to formulate policies that ultimately cause significant economic losses must compensate for these losses, or else have all their assets confiscated, with the descendants of their three generations banned from politics, finance, economics, and management for the next 1,000 years? They should be banned from taking high-speed trains and airplanes for the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city.</p> <p>Moreover, these rankings of global universities, which are expensive, promote vanity and self-deception, and mislead the global public, should bear the responsibility for misleading the public. Such rankings should be immediately abolished globally, and those primarily responsible for using rankings to mislead the global public through charging should face the necessary criminal penalties. Which statesman can propose an international consensus or a UN convention on the subject?</p>
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations regarding the seriously wrong perception of the planned economy under the socialist system by Western politicians and economists.</p> <p>Almost all large private enterprises, including Fortune 500 multinational corporations operating fully in a market economy, actually have significant elements of a planned economy. Without these elements, the company could not be properly managed or operated smoothly. However, Western politicians and economists ignore the planned economic aspects within business operations and instead show strong resistance to the planned economies of socialist countries (the 4.0 version of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty (Chinese socialist system)). Yet, not all products produced by state-owned enterprises in socialist countries follow a planned economic model; some are arranged according to market demand.</p>
	<p>How can the U.S. have genuinely correct economics, philosophical and political science?</p> <p>The more the United States imposes a ban on the sale of high-end technological products to China, the more China can develop advanced products and break the US blockade. This is an inevitable historical trend. If the United States does not implement a blockade policy, China's development in this field will be very slow.</p> <p>This is a very straightforward principle of philosophy, economics, political science, and management. Although most of the top 100 universities in management, political science, philosophy, and economics are in the United States, it seems that the United States lacks true philosophy. Without philosophy, how can the United States have proper leadership and leadership skills? How can the U.S. have genuinely correct economics and political science?</p>
	<p>American political parties lack basic philosophical and moral support. President Biden exhibits clear symptoms of senile dementia, which even people without a medical background can basically see. Yet, he is still being put forward for the next presidential election. This is not only irresponsible for President Biden's health,</p>

	<p>but also for the United States. It is an act lacking in political and administrative ethics. If the Republican Party or the Trump team were to evaluate behavior of the Democratic Party using metrological administrative ethics and metrological party ethics, the Democratic Party's terrible actions would go down in history.</p> <p>If the Democratic Party truly cannot find a suitable presidential candidate, they should consider giving the next presidency to Trump.</p>
	<p>The poor financial philosophy established by the United States in the secondary market</p> <p>If the United States believes that it has universal values, correct economics, and finance that benefit the majority, rather than just a few, the United Nations and the international community should establish a comprehensive UN convention to ban quantitative trading. This is because its negative impact on the market far outweighs its so-called "efficiency" and "objectivity."</p> <p>First, quantitative trading exacerbates market volatility and instability.</p> <p>Secondly, quantitative trading undermines the fairness and impartiality of the market, and quantitative short selling mechanisms are a large-scale harvesting device for big funds to exploit retail investors, which goes against the fairness of the stock market.</p> <p>Third, quantitative trading easily leads to market manipulation and fraudulent behavior. Because quantitative traders rely on algorithms and models, they are more likely to manipulate the market by manipulating data and models. Some criminals even use quantitative trading to engage in fraudulent activities, manipulating market prices through false trading and misleading information to gain illegal profits. Such market manipulation and fraudulent behavior not only harm investors' interests, but also seriously undermine the credibility and stability of the market.</p> <p>Fourth, quantitative trading is like a market vampire in the secondary market, causing the market to bleed. It allows a small number of wealthy individuals to become richer, enabling them to earn even more money.</p>
	<p>There is no legal philosophy in Europe and America. The legal system is designed for the middle and lower classes to appreciate.</p> <p>In the past, international financial oligarchs were accustomed to using assassination to eliminate people and presidents who attempted to change the issuance of American currency.</p> <p>In recent years, there have been incidents of fires in the buildings of these international financial oligarchs, destroying evidence. Highly secure banks, especially rooms storing critical documents, should not experience such fires. If, in the future, similar to the Huang Chao Uprising in the Tang Dynasty, uprisings occur in the U.S. or the U.K., and the rebels use quantum entanglement to extract information about the financial oligarchs ordering the burning of bank buildings, the entire families of these financial oligarchs might be completely exterminated, possibly wiping out three or even nine generations. Once the controllers of the banks issue evil orders, it is impossible to eliminate the evidence and the chain of evidence of their crimes. Destroying documents will only add to their crimes; it is</p>

	best not to burn them at all.
	<p>The Financial Philosophy of the United States:</p> <p>One of the ways the U.S. financial system controls America is by having financiers create a pervasive shortage of cash among Americans, leading to widespread borrowing. This results in most ordinary Americans being in debt for life, thus constructing a financial industry chain that deprives generation after generation of Americans of their wealth.</p>
	<p>During the COVID-19 pandemic, China had already suspected by early 2020 that the virus might have leaked from the U.S. military biolab at Fort Detrick. At the end of March, China Central Television (CCTV) stopped broadcasting public service announcements against the consumption of wild animals. China's reluctance to directly accuse the U.S. or its military biolabs of being the source of the virus was mainly to maintain diplomatic relations and save face. However, the U.S. retaliated by accusing the Wuhan Institute of Virology of leaking the virus. The governance philosophy in the U.S. is fundamentally flawed, and the U.S. should ban such synthetic research on viruses. Anyone engaged in this type of research must be prohibited from providing any medical insurance services for 20 years.</p> <p>In July 2019, the U.S. biological laboratory at Fort Detrick suddenly announced its closure, and an unknown pneumonia with symptoms strikingly similar to COVID-19 appeared at a nearby military base. At the beginning of 2023, the American "Project Veritas" released an undercover video featuring a conversation with a Pfizer executive. In the video, the executive revealed a shocking truth: Pfizer was creating and selecting COVID-19 variants to develop preventive vaccines and treating the vaccine business as a "cash cow." If the real truth needs to be uncovered, it would only require extracting quantum entanglement signals from the relevant subjects. However, this type of detection work can only be done by Americans themselves.</p> <p>[Video hammer! Pfizer R&D director acknowledges that COVID-19 variant is made by Pfizer. 2023-01-31. https://www.sohu.com/a/635867788_121124215]</p>
	<p>The Philosophy and Methodology of American Leadership in the World</p> <p>On February 25, 2024, U.S. Ambassador to China Nicholas Burns expressed his views on U.S.-China relations during an interview broadcast on CBS. Burns stated that China is an even stronger competitor than the Soviet Union and that U.S.-China relations are the "most important, competitive, and dangerous" in the world. He added that Americans "do not want to live in a world dominated by the Chinese."</p> <p>What kind of world is dominated by Americans?</p> <p>In a world led by the United States, America has initiated 201 wars since World War II without ever feeling shame or compensating the victims.</p> <p>At least ten American presidents have been assassinated, witnesses silenced, and cases intentionally left unsolved.</p> <p>In the assassination of President Kennedy, 115 witnesses were silenced, and the case was deliberately left unsolved.</p>

	<p>In the assassination attempt on President Reagan, the perpetrator was acquitted, and the case was intentionally left unresolved.</p> <p>The fictional characters Moses and Solon are portrayed as benchmarks in the U.S. Supreme Court, turning the judiciary into one of America's most lucrative professions. If a criminal has money to hire a skilled lawyer, guilt can be turned into innocence.</p> <p>Fabricated lunar landings have stimulated global space competition.</p> <p>The psychological warfare of fabricating the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki has long concealed the truth and seriously misled the world about the minimum number of atomic bombs needed to cause a nuclear winter. This has led to the continued waste of enormous funds by the United States in the development of nuclear weapons. In October 2023, the U.S. military announced the development of a new type of nuclear bomb, with a yield 24 times that of the atomic bomb dropped on Hiroshima, Japan.</p> <p>The United States has enacted laws that require all American families to pay an annual tax on basic housing. Retirees and those facing increased land values who are unable to pay the tax risk having their homes auctioned off by the privately controlled company, the IRS. This is likely to result in retirees and other vulnerable groups who cannot pay the housing tax becoming homeless. In a century dominated by the United States, is America the leader in human rights protection? In the U.S., thefts involving amounts below a certain threshold are not considered crimes—does this not encourage criminal behavior?</p> <p>The United States has long had the highest GDP in the world, and as the issuer of the world's currency, the dollar, it should be the wealthiest nation. Yet the U.S. forces poorer countries to buy U.S. debt every year, lending money to U.S. politicians, the government, and the public never feel ashamed of this situation, nor do they acknowledge the low level of governance in the country. How can a country with such poor governance lead the world? Consider a company where the board and shareholders find that the CEO's management is poor, causing continuous losses – would they continue to let him lead without firing the CEO?</p>
	<p>Is it the mission of American politicians and the U.S. government to protect the human rights of Americans?</p> <p>What is the philosophy of American politicians and the American government?</p> <p>Shouldn't U.S. politicians and the U.S. government submit some United Nations conventions to combat such crimes?</p> <p>Phone scams in northern Myanmar mainly target Chinese people, while those in India mainly target the white world, scamming Americans.</p> <p>In terms of scale, Indian scams can be said to be the king of international scams.</p> <p>How crazy can Indians be when they scam Americans? According to statistics, Americans lose billions of dollars every year due to scam calls. On average, one in every six people who receive Indian scam calls is deceived out of their money.</p> <p>And the data keeps reaching new heights. 2020 was even worse. According to</p>

data from The New York Times and an app called Truecaller, in 2020, 56 million Americans were deceived, and the Indian scam industry scammed around \$20 billion from the United States and approximately \$8 billion from Canada.

What does 56 million people mean? That's roughly 22% of the entire U.S. population. In other words, in just 2020 alone, 22% of Americans were cheated out of their money. In addition, according to surveys from previous years, 30% of Americans have been scammed for money by phone calls, with 17% being "scammed multiple times"!!

It is reported that there is an American woman who was scammed a whopping 13 times before she reported it to the police.

Indians generally prefer to form factions and commit crimes, preferring organized crime.

Indians say that they believe the mouth has two uses: one is for eating, and the other is for lying. Someone even wrote an article specifically about it.

The US government should learn from Musk to govern India's serious crimes from a philosophical standpoint; US politicians' level of governance should not remain at the elementary and middle school stages. Musk, in order to revive Twitter, has come up with two major strategies.

This statement most directly reflects the current personnel situation of Silicon Valley tech giants, but unfortunately, only Musk understands it and only he dares to change it.

Musk has publicly stated that there were factions within Twitter, who was he referring to? Of course, it's the Indian executives.

The first strategy is to clear out Indian executives.

When we find an Indian executive in a company, it's likely that half of the company is already filled with Indians who are close-knit.

They focus only on occupying executive positions and expanding the Indian community, completely losing confidence in developing the company. Over time, the company will be filled with Indians, and even native Americans will be sidelined.

So, on his first day in office, Musk fired a series of Indian-origin CEOs, CFOs, CLOs, CXOs, and so on.

Thus, Musk completed the first task of revitalizing Twitter.

CEO, CFO, and HR are the three most important positions in a company, with the highest moral requirements. Once people without morals control these positions, the company will inevitably face great risks.

The second strategy is "ending comfort."

	Questioning American politicians and the US government.
1	If the character of Indians were noble, would they deceive Americans of 20 billion dollars in a year?
2	If Indians had high moral character, would they defraud Americans of \$20 billion a year?
3	If the character of Indians were noble, would they deceive Americans of their

		money for a long time?
4		If Indians have a good moral character, will they deceive Americans for a long time?
5		If Indians truly had the correct religious beliefs, would they deceive Americans of 20 billion dollars in a year?
6		If Indians truly had the correct religious beliefs, rather than following a cult, would they deceive Americans of 20 billion dollars in a year?
7		If Indians truly had the correct religious beliefs, rather than following a cult, would they deceive Americans of their money for a long time?
8		If Indians truly had the correct religious beliefs, rather than following a cult, would they deceive at least 56 million Americans of their money?
9		If Indians truly had the correct religious beliefs, rather than following a cult, would they merely rely on a wicked Briton sitting in Britain, drawing a line on a map one night to establish a country that had never existed before, and seize so much land from China?
10		<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>Americans are deceived by Indians through telecommunications fraud, amounting to \$20 billion a year. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't America value human rights? Shouldn't American politicians, whose salaries are paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the US Congress and the United Nations to establish an international treaty?</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that has cheated citizens of other countries of \$2 billion through telecommunications fraud in three years has been a nation without genuine religious beliefs and following a cult.</p>
11		<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of Americans deceived by Indians through telecommunications fraud has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't America value human rights? Shouldn't American politicians, whose salaries are paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the US Congress and the United Nations to establish an international treaty?</p> <p>Any country deceiving more than 100,000 citizens of other countries through telecommunications fraud within five years is a nation without genuine religious beliefs and follows a cult.</p>
12		<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of Americans defrauded by Indians through telecom scams</p>

	<p>has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't the United States prioritize human rights? Shouldn't US politicians, whose salaries are paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the US Congress and the United Nations to establish an international convention?</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 100,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, that offending country should be prohibited from purchasing any weapons production lines and weapons manufacturing technology for the next 100 years. If the number reaches 200,000, the ban should be extended to 200 years. If it reaches 500,000, the ban should be extended to 500 years. If it reaches 1 million, the ban should be extended to 1,000 years. If it reaches 2 million, the ban should be extended to 2,000 years. If it reaches 3 million, the ban should be extended to 3,000 years.</p> <p>Any country, organization, or individual supplying weapons production lines and weapons manufacturing technology to the offending nation shall face a tenfold fine. Any nation reserves the right to freeze its assets abroad, with the value assessed by the international community or the United Nations.</p>
13	<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of Americans defrauded by Indians through telecom scams has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't the United States prioritize human rights? Shouldn't U.S. politicians, whose salaries are paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the US Congress and the United Nations to establish an international convention?</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 100,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, that offending country should be prohibited from having voting rights in the United Nations and from serving as a permanent member of the UN or any international organization for the next 100 years. If the number reaches 200,000, the ban should be extended to 200 years. If it reaches 1 million, the ban should be extended to 1,000 years. If it reaches 2 million, the ban should be extended to 2,000 years. If it reaches 3 million, the ban should be extended to 300 years.</p> <p>Any politician found to have violated these provisions by prematurely nominating the offending nation for the aforementioned prohibited rights shall be removed from the civil service within one week of the incident and</p>

	<p>prohibited from engaging in political or governmental work for the next 30 years.</p>
14	<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of people in the United States deceived by Indians through telecom scams has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't the United States emphasize human rights? Shouldn't American politicians, paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the U.S. Congress and the United Nations to establish an international treaty?</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 100,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 100 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding one hundredth of the total number of victims.</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 200,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 200 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding one in two hundredths of the total number of victims.</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 300,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 300 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding one in three hundredths of the total number of victims.</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 500,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 500 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding one in five hundredths of the total number of victims.</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 1,000,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 1,000 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding five ten-thousandth of the total number of victims.</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching</p>

	<p>3,000,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 3,000 years, the total number of immigrants or descendants from that offending country in any other country will be prohibited from exceeding two ten-thousandth of the total number of victims.</p>
15	<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of people in the United States deceived by Indians through telecom scams has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't the United States emphasize human rights? Shouldn't unconventional methods be adopted to govern the world? Shouldn't American politicians, paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the U.S. Congress and the United Nations to establish an international treaty?</p> <p>As long as criminals within the offending country manage to deceive citizens of other countries through telecommunications scams, reaching 100,000 victims in any five-year period since 2000, then for the next 100 years, any country should be prohibited from constructing railways, high-speed railways, airports, power plants, or dams for that offending country.</p> <p>As long as the number of citizens of other countries deceived by telecommunications scams in any five-year period since 2000 reaches 200,000, for the next 200 years, any country should be prohibited from constructing railways, high-speed railways, airports, power plants, or dams for that offending country.</p> <p>As long as the number of citizens of other countries deceived by telecommunications scams in any five-year period since 2000 reaches 1 million, for the next 1000 years, any country should be prohibited from constructing railways, high-speed railways, airports, power plants, or dams for that offending country.</p> <p>As long as the number of citizens of other countries deceived by telecommunications scams in any five-year period since 2000 reaches 2 million, for the next 2000 years, any country should be prohibited from constructing railways, high-speed railways, airports, power plants, or dams for that offending country.</p> <p>As long as the number of citizens of other countries deceived by telecommunications scams in any five-year period since 2000 reaches 3 million, for the next 3,000 years, any country should be prohibited from constructing railways, high-speed railways, airports, power plants, or dams for that offending country.</p>
16	<p>It's time to test whether American politicians are serving the numerous American voters and victims.</p> <p>The number of people in the United States deceived by Indians through telecom scams has exceeded 56 million. This is the largest number of victims</p>

ever recorded in history. It indicates a regression of global ethics and jurisprudence by 2000-4000 years due to the falsification of ancient European history and civilization by Western missionaries. Doesn't the United States emphasize human rights? Shouldn't unconventional methods be adopted to govern the world? Shouldn't American politicians, paid by taxpayers, immediately propose to the U.S. Congress and the United Nations to establish an international treaty?

As long as in any five-year period since 2000, if domestic criminals in the offending country have defrauded 100,000 citizens of other countries through telecommunication fraud, then for the next 100 years, the presidents or prime ministers of any country shall be prohibited from meeting with, inviting, or being invited by the president or prime minister of the offending country. If, in any five-year period since 2000, the number of citizens defrauded through telecommunication fraud reaches 200,000, this prohibition extends to 200 years. If the number reaches 1,000,000, the prohibition extends to 1,000 years. If the number reaches 2,000,000, the prohibition extends to 2,000 years. If the number reaches 3,000,000, the prohibition extends to 3,000 years. Otherwise, violators will be listed as approaching evil criminals.

[美国人被印度人骗麻了. Americans have become numb to being deceived by Indians. 2023-09-08. <https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/655003595>]; [印度的电信诈骗有多牛? 几百万人专坑美国, 一年骗美国 200 亿美元 How severe is telecommunications fraud in India? Millions of people specialize in deceiving the United States, deceiving the country of 20 billion dollars a year. 2022-08-15. <https://www.ixigua.com/7132019851132043813>]; [硅谷裁员潮下, 中国员工最难, 印度高管面临被清退, 谁将收益? Under the wave of layoffs in Silicon Valley, Chinese employees are facing the most difficulties, while Indian executives are facing dismissal. Who will benefit? 2022-11-29. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1750804726850308730&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

From a philosophical perspective, there is absolutely no possibility that the United States will replicate China's success in the next 300 years.

China's rapid economic development is due to the strong moral and ethical foundations of its society, which enable it to continue operating even in difficult times. This is something largely absent in Western societies. International financial oligarchs and politicians have never considered establishing a moral and ethical society in the United States, because if American society were founded on these principles and the true rule of law, the predatory behavior of many politicians and oligarchs would be constrained. Should they commit serious violations and amass excessive wealth through plunder, they could face severe consequences, possibly even the death penalty. In the U.S., only by promoting selfish and self-serving theories can international financial oligarchs and politicians create a long-term source of wealth extraction, similar to an oil field or oil well. Humorously, to the international financial oligarchs and politicians, the American people could be likened

	<p>to an oil field. The function of American politicians is to criticize China daily, engage in disputes, seek to start wars, and occasionally supply weapons to allies to kill innocent women and children. American society even encourages looting in domestic malls and supermarkets, with absurd politicians enacting laws that stipulate thefts under \$950 do not warrant arrest and can even be tax-deductible.</p> <p>The US probably needs to replace over 80% of its absurd politicians.</p> <p>The United States is a country brought together by interests, with immigrants coming together for the sake of benefits. Interest groups and politicians controlling the U.S. are constantly scheming to reduce costs and extract more benefits. When interests are misaligned, the United States will inevitably split. In 300 years, it is entirely impossible for today's America to exist. Remarkably, even now, 40 states have passed legislation refusing to assume the huge debt owed by the federal government. If the U.S. does not repay its debts, the states would achieve financial independence and issue their own currencies, leading to the immediate disintegration of the U.S. with military forces divided among different states. In this process of societal evolution, it is not only about metabolism within social systems, but also the turnover of moral and ethical constructs at various levels. The noble defeats the corrupt, becoming a biological inevitability. This is something that economic theories supporting the development of the United States, such as Friedman, Hayek, or general equilibrium theory, do not accept or cannot explain.</p> <p>However, if the United States were to split up and not repay its huge debt, the many countries holding US dollars would suddenly find their holdings worthless, and the Federal Reserve would immediately dissolve. The enormous wealth of these countries would be completely plundered by the international financial oligarchs who control the United States. Would not the entire families of these international financial oligarchs, who previously controlled the United States, be completely exterminated?</p> <p>In today's world, evil forces are more rampant than at any other time in history because they control the formulation and execution of the current global justice system. When the United States disintegrates and the dollars held by various countries become worthless, the judicial systems that temporarily sustained these evil forces will become garbage.</p> <p>There is only one way to achieve world peace: either the international financial oligarchs and corrupt politicians voluntarily withdraw from the historical stage, surrender the wealth they have plundered, and stop interfering with government operations and attempting to start wars, or, like the Huang Chao Rebellion (黄巢起义), they must be exterminated to achieve world peace. This aligns perfectly with Mao Zedong's thought of grasping the principal contradiction. Mao Zedong Thought is a product of the combination of theory and practice, characterized by high foresight and predictability.</p>	
	<p>China has suffered greatly from the systematic pseudo-theories manufactured by the Americans, which has led China to forget its own original correct philosophical ideas and methodology in many aspects.</p>	
	<p>The philosophy of Chinese people in doing business with others is to</p>	

	<p>collaborate and make money together. If the cooperating partner suffers losses, they will provide preferential measures next time, hoping that their friend can make a profit and aiming for long-term cooperation.</p>	
	<p>Definition of civilization: Respect for life, strict punishment for criminals, making the weak unafraid, making the strong not dare to be arrogant, preventing power from becoming arrogant, making the incompetent voluntarily step down, reducing the number of unethical individuals holding public office, not wasting the talents of the capable, making evildoers fear wrongdoing, allowing the righteous to live in peace, making society more fair, making society more just, making society vibrant, and ensuring inner peace for the people. To bring comfort to the elderly, foster trust among friends, and provide care for the young.</p> <p>Based on the new definition of civilization globally, and referring to some ancient Chinese legal systems, global political and judicial systems should be re-established to construct a new situation of effective governance in various countries and the world.</p>	
	<p>Chairman Mao Zedong should have long established that China's socialist system is an improved version of the equal field system of the early Tang Dynasty, as the country's social system was jointly created by him and the older generation of pioneers. He had already recognized that the capitalist system in the United States was a fully marketized system from the late Tang Dynasty, although the theoretical concept of marketization was not articulated at the time. Therefore, Chairman Mao Zedong should have early predicted that even a fully marketized capitalism in the United States would be unable to resolve its inherent contradictions and would inevitably decline and disintegrate.</p> <p>The Chinese leadership and philosophical community should thoroughly study the above viewpoint. The socialist system did not emerge out of thin air; it was the development and improvement of the systems created by China's ancestors. There were earlier versions of the socialist system in China, and the improved version 4.0 of the equal field system or socialism with Chinese characteristics, after addressing the shortcomings of the early system, better demonstrates the superiority of the system, representing the direction of future social system development. The historical inevitability of the disintegration of the fully marketized late Tang Dynasty social system or the American capitalist social system should be recognized.</p> <p>Based on strengthening anti-corruption efforts, improving people's livelihoods, and enhancing national governance capabilities and efficiency, China should unify the thinking and understanding of the whole Party and people of the whole country from a historical perspective and the inevitable trend of human social development, continuously improve itself, and move forward in development. Other countries can also discover the historical laws of social systems and the inevitability of history from China's history.</p>	
	<p>When any government agency in a country develops policies, the initiators, drafters, revisers, and responsible parties must be clearly identified and sign</p>	

	<p>their names. In cases of severe violations of public morals, serious breaches of natural laws, or when major losses occur, the above-mentioned individuals must be held accountable. They must be demoted before they can be employed again, and half of their personal and family assets must be compensated to their nation. The highest-ranking official who signs off on the policy must assume 70% of the responsibility.</p> <p>Those who have made mistakes, if they have undergone experience and training and have demonstrated outstanding work performance, should be allowed to advance three ranks in their position.</p> <p>Individuals who hold erroneous viewpoints on significant issues 3 or more times are not suitable for holding principal official positions or higher positions of authority.</p> <p>All employees of the unit where the wrong decision maker is located must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within two weeks.</p>	
	<p>By changing the philosophical approach to national governance, China can create an unprecedented sense of security and peace for its citizens in the healthcare sector.</p> <p>China should unconditionally provide a minimum level of medical insurance and pension insurance for all citizens and their families. China only needs to revise the relevant policies in the fields of treatment and prevention, and it can achieve this welfare at a lower cost for the entire society, thus stabilizing people's hearts. Of course, when implementing universal healthcare, it is necessary to severely crack down on illegal practices of obtaining medical insurance funds, and the punishment must be intensified.</p> <p>Anyone who fraudulently obtains or assists in obtaining medical insurance funds should be fined at least five times the amount. If a pharmacy or hospital fraudulently obtains medical insurance funds, the individuals involved, the legal representative, and the controllers of the pharmacy or hospital should all be fined five times the amount and be included on the credit blacklist. They should be banned from taking high-speed trains and airplanes for the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of the offenders should be prohibited from holding any position in government institutions and from working in financial institutions, military institutions, and security agencies. Those already working in these institutions must leave within two weeks. Individuals who fraudulently obtain more than 50,000 CNY in medical insurance funds within two years will have all their personal assets confiscated. All offenders will be held criminally responsible. Whistleblowers reporting violations will be rewarded with 20% of the amount involved, anonymously distributed to the informant.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for reducing the pressure of advanced consumer loans on residents</p> <p>The philosophy of high-debt advanced consumption has brought significant crises to many families in China and must be curbed through institutional measures to mitigate future uncertainties. If an individual or their</p>	

	<p>family's total legal income is insufficient to purchase a particular home or apartment within eight years, any institution is prohibited from providing a mortgage. Otherwise, the violating real estate company will be fined twice the amount, and the financial institution granting the loan will be fined three times the amount. If an individual or their family's total legal income is insufficient to purchase a car within two years, any institution is prohibited from providing an auto loan. Otherwise, the violating car sales company will be fined twice the amount, and the financial institution granting the loan will be fined three times the amount.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for regulating real estate company loans</p> <p>Any state-owned or private construction company engaged in building houses may not establish multiple firms; it can only own one company. All contracts must be signed under that company's name, and it is forbidden to set up a separate company for each real estate project. All contract projects are subject to lifelong accountability.</p> <p>In all residential, commercial, or industrial buildings constructed of concrete by the company, the names of the persons responsible for construction, development, and construction must be permanently marked in an appropriate location on the concrete walls of the building. If an individual is running or stomping in a room with closed doors and windows in the building, no noise should be heard in the rooms below; failure to meet this standard considers the building unqualified. The company and the developers must not only compensate the purchasers, but also take on legal responsibility. The main individuals responsible should face a minimum prison sentence of 8 to 15 years.</p> <p>The area of all houses can only be calculated on the basis of the usable area; it is forbidden to calculate their value and market them using the built-up area.</p> <p>Real estate companies are only allowed to take out loans through the parent company; it is forbidden to obtain loans through any subsidiaries or branches. If loans have already been taken out through subsidiaries or branches, all such loans must be accounted for under the parent company in terms of financial handling. Any financial audit conducted on the company must adhere to the above principle, otherwise the audit firm shall bear full responsibility.</p> <p>Violators who provide loans will be fined three times the amount and included in the credit blacklist. They will be prohibited from taking high-speed trains and airplanes for the next 30 years.</p> <p>If this leads to insolvency or serious losses for the company, all violators will be included in the credit blacklist, prohibited from taking high-speed trains and airplanes for the next 30 years, and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 300 years, all direct relatives of the offenders will be banned from holding any position in government institutions and from</p>	

	<p>working in financial institutions, military institutions, and security agencies. Personal and family assets of the offenders involved in institutions will be confiscated. If auditing institutions fail to conduct proper audits resulting in losses, the auditing institution must bear all losses and be fined three times the amount of the incorrect audit. The auditing institution, its legal representative, and the top ten shareholders will be held responsible.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations on loan interest rates</p> <p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>To an article titled SME Operating Performance on the Government of Canada website, margins for a small business operating between 2004 and 2012 were 7%.</p> <p>You will notice a big variance from the chart in the small business net profit margin ranging from as low as 1.5% to as high as 7%. The information obviously varies from year to year based on economic conditions, but a 7% net profit operating margin is a high watermark. That number, 7%, isn't very good.</p> <p>China should independently or jointly propose with the United States the establishment of a UN convention and international consensus on loan rates: Any financial institution or individual that lends money to enterprises and individuals at an annual interest rate exceeding 5% shall ensure that all expenses incurred in the loan process, including fees paid to third parties, do not result in an effective annual interest rate exceeding 5%. If exceeded, such charges cannot be considered legal, but rather as illegal income. Moreover, a penalty based on the loan amount shall be imposed, with confiscation of 20-30% of the principal. If the cumulative costs correspond to an effective annual interest rate exceeding 6.0%, the offender must face criminal charges and be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison. The above terms apply to any country.</p> <p>Any lender who sets or implements usurious loans with an interest rate exceeding 6.0% shall be permanently prohibited from owning, directly or indirectly, any shares in banks or financial companies. They shall be permanently prohibited from working in the financial industry and from holding government positions. Their immediate family members shall be prohibited from engaging in the financial industry for 60 years. They shall also be prohibited from boarding any aircraft or high-speed train for 30 years. When leaving or arriving in any city or region, they must report to the local police and make their itinerary public to society.</p> <p>If this world or the financial world still values philosophy and logic and respects human rights, it must prohibit all lending behavior with an annual interest rate exceeding 6.0%.</p> <p>Usury, under the guise of high interest rates, erodes social stability like a plague, bringing misfortune to people's livelihoods. It not only devours the wealth of borrowers, but also pushes vulnerable individuals to desperation,</p>	

	<p>leading to the breakup of families and the destruction of futures. Under the burden of excessive debt, victims often fall into the abyss of illegality, increasing crime rates and endangering public safety. It strays from the purpose of legitimate financial services, undermines normal economic order, and harms the interests of the disadvantaged majority. The United Nations should formulate a convention urging governments worldwide to crack down vigorously on usurious practices, protect citizens from their harm and maintain social harmony and stability. Advocating legal lending practices ensures the fair and orderly flow of wealth, bringing well-being to people.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations of widespread public anxiety about the safety of genetically modified foods</p> <p>The safety assessment of genetically modified (GM) foods involves highly specialized issues. Typically, even professionals find it challenging to conduct a rational assessment, leading to the proliferation of GM foods with potentially significant safety hazards driven by vested interests. Moreover, in recent years, the United States has experienced four consecutive years of surplus production of GM soybeans and GM corn, contributing to a global surplus in food supply.</p> <p>Scientists at the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) have repeatedly warned that GM foods can result in unforeseeable and difficult to detect side effects, including allergies, toxicity, novel diseases, and nutritional problems. They have strongly advocated for long-term safety studies of such foods, but their calls have largely been ignored.</p> <p>In China, some bloggers conducted experiments using genetically modified soybeans to grow soybean sprouts and found that even newly genetically modified soybeans or mung beans from the same year struggled to grow into edible sprouts of 6-9cm, while non-genetically modified soybeans or mung beans could grow into normal-length sprouts.</p> <p>The United States is the world's largest producer of genetically modified crops, including corn, soybeans, cotton, rapeseed, sugar beets, alfalfa, papaya, and squash. Many individuals prone to allergies in the United States experience fewer allergic reactions after living in China for a period, even when consuming the same foods. This is because China uses genetically modified foods in food production far less frequently.</p> <p>It is important to highlight that experiments involving transgenic animals and clinical trials often fall short in terms of duration, which results in an inadequate understanding of potential carcinogenic and other adverse effects. Presently, many studies on the safety of genetically modified (GM) foods are poorly structured, with insufficient experimental periods leading to largely unreliable outcomes.</p> <p>Moreover, the global production of organic foods currently exceeds demand. GM foods are not medications, nor are they essential or life-saving commodities. Natural foods, which have undergone thousands of years of</p>	

natural selection, already meet the safety requirements for consumption.

These foods can also adequately supply the world's food needs. Therefore, there is no necessity to research and develop genetically modified foods that have not undergone natural selection.

If the development of genetically modified (GM) foods is to be pursued, strict experiments must adhere to the following requirements. All involved parties must take responsibility because only developers and research institutions can know about its safety and the need for mitigation measures at the initial stage.

Before widespread consumption by the public, they must assume responsibility and obligation. Otherwise, high-risk GM foods should not be developed, nor should genetically modified foods that are harmful to humans or whose safety is unclear be pursued solely for obtaining research funding.

Currently, there are many safety issues with genetically modified foods that have not been fully exposed, which pose a great threat to human health. The United Nations should quickly form an international agreement on the following issues.

Since the consumption period of genetically modified foods is usually much longer than the treatment period of drugs, the examination of reproductive toxicity and chronic toxicity should be more stringent than the safety examination of drugs. Currently, it is actually easier than drugs, so there should be regulations that are at least as rigorous as those for drugs. Genetically modified foods must undergo large-scale safety experiments and clinical trials before being marketed. In addition, the developers and research institutions of genetically modified foods have a better understanding of the safety and potential hazards of these foods than the public does. Before genetically modified foods are put on the market, all employees and shareholders of the genetically modified food company, as well as their family members, must consume the food for an extended period of time and prove its safety. They should not be developing genetically modified foods for global consumption while they themselves and their families only consume natural foods.

It is typically impossible to obtain or observe long-term adverse effects on human health from the consumption of genetically modified foods through routine toxicity tests on conventional animals conducted by any company. The safety assessment and clinical trial period for food must absolutely not be shorter than that for pharmaceuticals. Pharmaceutical products undergo four phases of clinical trials or reassessment after market release, with tens of thousands of subjects typically involved in these trials. However, genetically modified foods completely lack such trials, which is extremely wrong. Given that the consumption period of GM foods is much longer than that of pharmaceuticals, clinical trial durations should be longer, and the number of subjects should be larger. Nonetheless, there are always fervent researchers of

genetically modified foods developing related products either publicly or privately, directly selling or providing genetically modified products to farmers for cultivation, which could potentially pose a huge crisis to humanity.

Therefore, especially for genetically modified corn, soybeans, wheat, rice, sorghum, potatoes, tomatoes, olives, rapeseed, tea oil, peanuts, sunflowers, or fruits before they are marketed, **they must undergo long-term toxicity tests on non-primate animals for at least two years**, and on primates for at least three years. In addition, before marketing, researchers studying genetically modified foods individually and their companies, as well as all shareholders, employees, and their immediate family members of the company, including pregnant women and children who consume them daily, must continuously consume them for at least five years at normal consumption levels. They must be tested at least six times a year to ensure that their sperm and egg counts do not decrease, there is no significant change in the rate of abnormalities, and that there is no impact on fertility. The number of persons in the aforementioned groups must be at least 3000.

It must be emphasized that transgenic animal experiments and clinical trials lack sufficient time, and often fail to reveal obvious carcinogenic and other potential side effects. Currently, many safety studies on genetically modified foods are poorly designed, with insufficient experimental duration, resulting in mostly unreliable conclusions.

Furthermore, all employees of the food regulatory agency and their family members must consume genetically modified foods that they are mandated to approve or have already approved. Those responsible for approval should have a clear understanding of the safety of genetically modified foods. If they object, GM foods cannot be marketed, and any already on the market must have their permits revoked.

Those who illegally cultivate genetically modified foods will be banned from receiving health insurance and have all their personal assets confiscated.

Before clinical trials of genetically modified (GM) foods, comprehensive general pharmacological experiments and toxicological tests matching long-term human consumption must be conducted. Clinical trials of GM foods must be discussed by a provincial or state-level ethics committee composed of 101 individuals from various industries who have no conflicts of interest with the GM research company. Approval for trials requires over 95% agreement from the committee members. Clinical trials are prohibited without proper approval procedures, but employees of the GM food development company may conduct voluntary self-consumption experiments. These volunteer subjects must be permanent employees of the GM research company (holding a university degree in a relevant biological field, having worked continuously for two years at the company, and receiving full salary and health insurance). The company must not force employees into participation; consumption must be voluntary.

	<p>Individuals conducting clinical trials of GM foods without regulatory approval will be banned from receiving health insurance, have all personal assets confiscated, be permanently barred from working in biology, agriculture, or fisheries, and must compensate victims for their losses. Those conducting illegal research, cultivation, or sale of GM foods that cause significant harm to society and the public will face a minimum of 5-20 years imprisonment. If the consumption of GM foods results in death, the principal offenders, including the legal representatives and the top ten shareholders of the production and sales companies, will be sentenced to death. These offenders will lose their health insurance, have all family assets confiscated, and must compensate the victims for their losses. They will be permanently banned from working in biology, agriculture, or fisheries, and their immediate family members will be prohibited from attending university.</p> <p>Anyone who illegally provides genetically modified (GM) food seeds to others for planting will lose their medical insurance for 5 years and be prohibited from engaging in GM research for 10 years. If the planting forms a large-scale operation with an area exceeding 3333 square meters and the products enter the consumer market, both the developer and the distributor will be banned from GM research and seed sales for 20 years, lose their medical insurance for 10 years, and be fined five times the total sales amount, in addition to facing criminal penalties. Illegal cultivation of genetically modified food covering an area exceeding 6,666,666 square meters resulted in the death penalty for the main culprit, accomplices being sentenced to more than 20 years in prison, and all illegal income being confiscated. Developers, promoter, sellers, and cultivators are fined three times the total amount involved.</p> <p>The personal and family assets of all individuals involved in GM violations and their associated institutions must be disclosed within one week. All violators will be blacklisted from the credit system, barred from high-speed rail and air travel for the next 30 years, and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of those convicted of GM food-related crimes will be prohibited from holding any government positions, and from working in financial, military, or security institutions. Those currently employed in these institutions must resign within two weeks. Anyone who has ever worked or is currently working in the GM food field must unconditionally disclose all personal and family assets. In any region where illegal GM food appears, if the regulatory agency is found to be ineffective, the responsible officials will be demoted by 2-3 levels, and the regulatory agency must disclose all personal and family assets of its staff. The first whistleblower will be rewarded anonymously with 15% of the fines and confiscated assets.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating financial fraud</p> <p>In the event of fraudulent marketing practices involving virtual currency, digital currency, token economy, token finance, or token-based tourism economic</p>	

products, which lead to significant losses for a large number of victims, the harm caused is immense. Principal offenders, masterminds, and key members must fully compensate the victims. If full restitution is not made to the victims, the government must freeze and confiscate all personal assets of the principal offenders, masterminds, key members, and the assets of the companies involved. In addition, they must be fined double the amount of the funds involved to compensate the victims. Those who successfully recruited others to purchase the aforementioned products or currency through a pyramid scheme will only be compensated later. If the amount involved exceeds \$10 million and the principal offenders, masterminds, and key members fail to fully compensate the victims, the government must confiscate all personal and family assets of these individuals. If criminals have transferred funds of \$100,000 or more, all their personal assets must be confiscated, with only basic living expenses allowed to remain.

After receiving complaints from victims, if the regulatory authority refuses or delays processing them, allowing the scam ring to continue its fraudulent activities, the responsible parties will be held legally accountable. A fine amounting to 10 % of the sum involved in the report will be imposed on the responsible individuals, followed by demotion and reassignment. In cases involving collusion in the crime, all personal assets of the individuals will be confiscated and they will be subject to criminal penalties.

Anyone who provides image support for such frauds, endorses their activities through promotional speeches, or recommends purchasing or supporting the purchase, including Internet celebrities, stars, government officials, senior members of industry associations, or legal institutions, shall be fined five times the amount of their profits from the case. The positions of any senior management involved in industry associations will be abolished. If the amount involved reaches or exceeds \$20 million, the practising qualifications of the personnel involved from the legal institutions will be revoked for five years, and the legal institution's licence will be revoked. If all major offenders and key members do not fully compensate victims, product spokespersons and those who publicly support them must compensate victims. If someone successfully recruits five or more people to join the purchasing scheme and they incur losses, the government will not provide compensation. The government must confiscate all personal assets of key offenders and key members for victim compensation. If the amount involved reaches or exceeds \$60 million, the government must confiscate all personal and family assets of the principal offenders and key members to compensate the victims, revoke the practising qualifications of the personnel involved from legal institutions for 10 years, and revoke the legal institution's license.

Anyone involved in criminal responsibility shall be subject to criminal punishment at the same time.

All individuals and their immediate family members who provide support for such fraud must fully disclose their personal and family assets, as well as the

	<p>assets of their three generations of relatives. All personnel of the institutions to which those who provide support for such fraud belong must also fully disclose their personal and family assets. The personal assets of all individuals who provide explicit image, policy, or legal support for such fraud must be confiscated. The positions of the aforementioned individuals serving in any institution must be reduced by five levels, and they must then be relieved of their duties.</p> <p>Anyone who deceives farmers into purchasing the aforementioned products or services in rural areas, causing financial losses to farmers, shall be fined three times the amount of farmers' losses for illegal direct promoters. If the individual's personal assets are insufficient to pay the fine, the government shall be responsible for confiscating their personal or family assets to compensate farmers.</p> <p>Fraudsters and all individuals who provide explicit image support, policy support, or legal support for such fraud must unconditionally give 100 public lectures on public welfare, explaining how fraud is carried out or how they assist in fraud, as well as analyzing fraud cases. The speaking time for each fraudster must not be less than 45 minutes per lecture.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for accelerating the search for missing children, women, and adults</p> <p>Children are the future of society and the hope of the family. However, cases of missing children are frequent, and some government agencies deal with these cases slowly or are unwilling to initiate timely investigations, resulting in a lack of control over crimes and putting children at risk of harm. The families of the victims are plunged into long-term pain. Strong corrective measures must be put in place to deter law enforcement from inaction. The United Nations and the international community should reach a consensus on the following issues and establish a convention:</p> <p>First, in any city or region, as long as there are cases of missing children, students, women, adult, or individuals, all official promotions are suspended until the missing individuals are found.</p> <p>Second, all personal and family assets of individuals in the unit where the police did not promptly initiate an investigation due to a missing case must be made public.</p> <p>Third, all individuals involved in criminal activities shall be included in a credit blacklist. They are prohibited from traveling by high-speed rail and airplane for the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of criminals are prohibited from holding any positions in government institutions, financial institutions, military institutions, and security institutions. Those currently working in these institutions must resign within two weeks.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating counterfeit meat</p> <p>Fraudulent practices of counterfeit meat products are often seen in modern</p>	

	<p>society, such as passing off horse meat or other meats like beef, using artificial synthetic meat as fresh meat, or labeling chicken as pork. There are even cases where low-quality minced meat is sold as normal fresh meat, or meat with viruses is ground up and sold as normal meat. It is suggested that the United Nations develop a relevant convention for the control of such criminal conduct: First, once verified, severe penalties will be imposed. Offenders will be fined five times the value of product fraud, banned from the industry for 20 years, and required to disclose all personal and family assets.</p> <p>Second, the names, photos, and specific details of the falsification of offenders will be publicly displayed on government websites for 10 years, and this information may not be deleted during this period.</p> <p>Third, first-time offenders will be criminally detained; repeat offenders will have all their personal property confiscated.</p> <p>Fourth, if the value of illegal meat exceeds 1 million, a prison sentence of 2-6 years will be imposed; fifth, offenders must be subject to travel restrictions, report to the police station when leaving their place of residence, and being prohibited from flying or taking high-speed trains.</p> <p>Sixth, the offender will be blacklisted for life, and all family members and relatives will be banned from entering the civil service system for life.</p> <p>Seventh, anyone who reports the fraudulent sale of other types of meat as meat or meat of inferior quality, once verified, will be rewarded with 25% of the offender's confiscated property.</p> <p>Eighth, the offender and all family members will be banned from entering public universities for 100 years.</p> <p>Ninth, anyone who grinds meat with viruses and sells it as normal meat, their family members and relatives will be banned from enjoying compulsory education and medical insurance services for 100 years.</p> <p>Tenth, any country or region where such incidents occur must inform every citizen of the provisions of this Convention through various fast communication or dissemination methods, at least once a week.</p> <p>The above-mentioned offenders must unconditionally give 100 public welfare lectures within three years, explaining how the crimes were committed, the harm caused by the products, and how to avoid being deceived. Each lecture must be at least 45 minutes long for each criminal.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating impostors going to college.</p> <p>The act of impersonating someone to attend university can cause lifelong harm to the victim, depriving them of the best educational opportunities. Therefore, strict punishment must be imposed on all perpetrators involved in forgery. All assets of the criminals, both personal and familial, must be confiscated, allowing only five years of basic living expenses to be retained. From the time of the crime to the revelation of the incident and until the victim receives adequate compensation, the duration of the victim's suffering determines the minimum sentence that the perpetrator must serve in prison, with no</p>	

	<p>possibility of parole for any reason. The principal offender should be sentenced to death. The main offender must receive double punishment, and no one is eligible for bail. These provisions apply to all countries.</p> <p>All personal and family assets of all criminals and the individuals within the organizations where the criminals belong must be fully disclosed.</p> <p>All individuals involved in criminal activities shall be included in a credit blacklist. They are prohibited from travelling by high-speed rail and plane for the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of criminals are prohibited from holding any positions in government institutions, financial institutions, military institutions, and security institutions. Those currently working in these institutions must resign within two weeks. Whistleblowers who report violations will be rewarded with 20 % of the fines, which will be anonymously distributed to them.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating impersonation of others for employment</p> <p>The act of impersonating someone and taking their position can inflict lifelong harm to the displaced individual. Therefore, in cases involving identity theft, the main perpetrator's personal and family assets must be confiscated, allowing only five years of basic living expenses and essentials to be retained. From the time of the crime to the revelation of the incident and until the victim receives adequate compensation, the duration of the victim's suffering determines the minimum sentence that the perpetrator must serve in prison, with no possibility of parole for any reason. The main perpetrator must receive double punishment, and no one is eligible for bail. These provisions apply to all countries.</p> <p>All personal and family assets of all criminals and the individuals within the organizations where the criminals belong must be fully disclosed.</p> <p>All individuals involved in criminal activities shall be included in a credit blacklist. They are prohibited from travelling by high-speed rail and plane for the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of criminals are prohibited from holding any positions in government institutions, financial institutions, military institutions, and security institutions. Those currently working in these institutions must resign within two weeks. Whistleblowers who report violations will be rewarded with 20 % of the fines, which will be anonymously distributed to them.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for maintaining cultural customs</p> <p>Setting off fireworks and firecrackers is a traditional custom. In ancient times, it was allowed in houses made of wood, but today, in an age of predominantly concrete houses, cities paradoxically prohibit the use of fireworks and firecrackers, which to some extent is illogical. To prevent fires caused by fireworks or injuries from firecrackers with a high powder content, there</p>	

	<p>should be a differentiated management system for the use of fireworks and firecrackers. When cities establish rules prohibiting the use of fireworks and firecrackers, they must distinguish between the types of these items. There may be a need to ban certain fireworks and skyrockets in densely populated urban areas, but no city government should ever prohibit citizens from using firecrackers with the lowest powder content designed before or in the 1980s outside their homes or during ceremonies for festivals, celebrations, or funerals. However, the number of firecrackers per string could be limited to between 100-1,000. The government should not ban the sale of firecrackers in cities, nor should it ban the sale of fireworks and firecrackers in rural areas or towns, as this would effectively destroy traditional customs and suggest that modern governance is less capable than in previous eras.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for reducing the impact of online platforms or e-commerce on the real economy</p> <p>Any intermediary company, especially those in e-commerce or network platform, providing intermediary services for the products and commercial activities of other companies, can only charge a maximum of 20% of the transaction amount as intermediary fees or commissions within the first 18 months of its establishment, or if the sales volume of intermediary products is less than 20 million US dollars. Once either of these two milestones is exceeded, the intermediary or e-commerce company may only charge up to 15% in intermediary fees. If this limit is exceeded, it is considered illegal, and regulatory authorities must fine the violator ten times the amount illegally charged. If a company changes its name, but retains 25% of its workforce from the previous entity, it shall be regarded as the same company by the regulatory bodies, which must then impose harsher penalties. Companies not meeting the above criteria shall not be permitted to list on any exchange.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for improving employee employment rate and sense of security</p> <p>Any organization that hires employees must, upon accumulation of work exceeding six months in one year or ten months in two years, be prohibited from employing the individual under a third-party labor dispatch model. Instead, the organization must enter into a direct hiring contract with the employee, where the salary is paid directly by the organization. In addition, the organization is required to contribute to the employee's pension insurance, medical insurance, and other expenses in the same manner as it does for other employees. Failure to comply will result in the government imposing a fine on the organization equivalent to five times the total amount of wages and bonuses paid for the illegal employment of the worker. If the offence is repeated a second time, the person in charge of the organization must face criminal penalties with a prison sentence of 2-3 years.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for reducing burden and respecting deceased predecessors</p> <p>Once a cemetery has been legally used for the burial of the deceased, the land</p>	

	<p>permanently belongs to those who have passed away. No one may remove or desecrate the gravesite for any reason, except in cases involving illegal activities. The price per square meter for general public cemetery plots must not exceed half of the lowest housing price in the same city or town during the same period. The government must provide sufficient burial grounds for the deceased to rest in peace. The above terms apply to any country.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for reducing the burden on doctors and reducing low-value papers. No hospital should determine the level of a clinical doctor's professional title based on the writing or publication of papers. Instead, they should measure or evaluate clinicians using humane indicators such as cure rates, improvement rates, and successful resuscitation rates, and determine their professional titles accordingly.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for respecting sacrificial soldiers and reducing the burden on military families The country should provide preferential treatment to soldiers who have sacrificed for a just war or who have lost some or all of their labour capacity, as well as their families. If there are any direct blood relatives or siblings in the household, the government must provide the family with a reinforced concrete structure residential unit, with a living area (not the constructed area) of 100-140 square meters, at the same location where the sacrificed or incapacitated servicemember used to reside. If the family of the soldier who has either sacrificed or lost some or all of their labor capabilities owns land and proposes to the government to help build a house on their land, the government must assist the family in constructing a two-story house with a maximum construction area of 140 square meters on their original residential site. The cost of constructing the courtyard outside the house is to be borne by the family itself; for direct descendants of blood relation, regardless of gender, if there are multiple descendants reaching the legal marriageable age, in addition to one who must inherit the house previously provided by the government to their family, the government must provide separate residential units with a living area of 100-120 square meters for each in the county or district where the sacrificial or completely incapacitated individual resided. The minimum acceptance standard for housing stipulates that if the housing is part of an apartment building, movement, jumping or stomping by two people upstairs should not be felt in the rooms downstairs when doors and windows are closed. Militia members who have sacrificed or lost all labour capacity for a just war should receive treatment similar to the aforementioned, with housing area benefits provided at 80% of the above standard area. The Government must unconditionally provide the minimum level of medical and pension insurance for its family members. For the above-mentioned private housing, it is exempt from taxes for life, and it must not be sold or traded within 50 years. The country must unconditionally provide the minimum level of medical</p>	

	<p>insurance and pension insurance for disabled veterans and their families. All employees of the unit where the violator is located must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within two weeks.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations based on respecting traditional therapies</p> <p>Anyone who practices traditional natural healing methods or traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) to treat others, provided that the government of that country does not deny the validity of such practices as unscientific in their country, and provided that such traditions have existed in the country for over 100 years without the requirement of examinations or credentials, may do so legally. As long as the patient voluntarily seeks treatment from the practitioner, or in emergency situations where the practitioner acts to save the life of someone who has fallen ill accidentally, no institution should regard it as illegal medical practice. The practitioner assumes all legal liability incurred in the practice of medicine and must not engage in false advertising. Otherwise, they may be fined an amount equivalent to five times the income generated from false advertising claims as per the victim's pursuit of medical help. The government's health insurance agency will not cover any medical expenses for treatments received under the above-mentioned medical practices. This could ease pressure on the government's health insurance spending.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating frequent stock trading fraud</p> <p>Employees of some unscrupulous investment firms frequently engage in deliberate acts to entice or mislead the public into buying stocks, using phone calls to mislead strangers into joining stock investment groups. They claim to be able to guide stock purchases to achieve high returns or prevent losses. In such cases, the misleaders and their companies must compensate the victims for their total losses. If the loss exceeds \$1,000, the fraudsters and the company will be fined 3 to 5 times the amount of the loss. The personal and family assets of the fraudsters and the company's legal person and upper management must be made public. All persons involved in fraud must be monitored and their movements monitored; leaving the city or place of residence must be reported to the police station. If the amount of fraud exceeds \$1 million, in addition to the aforementioned penalties, the personal and family properties of the fraudsters, as well as the personal and family properties of the legal person and senior management of the fraudulent investment firm, will be confiscated. Additionally, the company's assets will be seized. All senior executives of the company shall be sentenced to at least 5 - 20 years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Mobile phone companies are required to obtain real-name registrations of all phone number holders. If not available, upon receipt of any complaint, they must take immediate action. If criminal information cannot be obtained, the use of this number must be suspended. If the offender calls to inquire, they must register with their real identity card to lift the relevant restrictions, thus</p>	

	<p>attaining the true information of the offender. Otherwise, the company continues to be viewed as abetting crime. The person directly responsible and the executive of the company must pay a fine equivalent to their monthly income.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for combating common fraud in Internet education and training</p> <p>Any company that provides educational and training services on the Internet and receives fees must ensure that the subsequent training content they provide is consistent with what the institution or responsible individuals previously claimed. If most or all of the content is inconsistent, it constitutes a serious fraud. When a victim requests a refund within 30 days of the incident, if the company or responsible individuals refuse to return all fees within five working days, the relevant government authorities must fine the directly responsible individuals and company between 5 to 10 times the amount involved in the case. All personnel involved in the incident, all senior management, and all shareholders of the company must permanently disclose their entire personal and family assets within one week of the incident. Any movement from their original residence to other cities or regions must be reported to the police and will be monitored by them. In cases where the total amount involved exceeds CNY 10,000, a minimum sentence of 1 year in prison shall be imposed.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in punishing the formulation of erroneous agricultural policies</p> <p>The United States and Europe, such as Lithuania and France, have a tradition of preying on crows.</p> <p>New Zealand holds a yearly Hokitika Wildfoods Festival featuring cuisine such as magpie meat pies, seagull eggs, and even wild hare testicles, which greatly surpass the variety of games traditionally consumed in China, challenging conventional thinking.</p> <p>In many towns in Texas, USA, there is also a traditional festival surrounding rattlesnakes. On the second weekend of March each year, residents come together to celebrate "Rattlesnake Roundup." In this festival, about 130,000 rattlesnakes are killed annually, yielding 136,000 kilograms of rattlesnake meat (Fig 84. Fig 85.),⁹⁸ all of which is eaten by food enthusiasts irrespective of whether it is before or after the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p>Despite the lack of direct evidence that the novel coronavirus originated directly from wild animals such as snakes, civets, bamboo rats, wild hares, wild boars, etc., and no direct evidence that it originated from bats or civets secretions, many wild animals raised by farmers were culled and buried during the COVID-19 pandemic. Traditional practices of hunting wild boar has also been banned, leading to overabundance of wild boar, which in turn causes damage to crops. Farmers, unable to control the situation, are left helpless. Such misguided policies have led to poverty in many farming families, affecting their protein sources. The United Nations should therefore establish a</p>	

<p>convention with the following provisions:</p> <p>First, before the COVID-19 pandemic, any country that did not legislate against the artificial breeding and consumption of wild animals and had traditional practices of breeding and consumption of such animals should not be prohibited from breeding and consumption. No reason should be used to ban breeding and selling, cutting off the livelihoods and incomes of poor farmers, unless there is direct evidence of the virus originating in a specific species of wild animal, in which case a ban on breeding and consumption of that animal may be considered.</p> <p>Second, anyone who is threatened by wild animals, whose domesticated animals are attacked by wild animals, or whose crops are destroyed by wild animals resulting in severe losses should be allowed to injure or kill those animals without any penalty. The meat of these killed animals can be eaten by those who are threatened.</p> <p>Third, from now on, anyone responsible for formulating faulty regulations that result in significant economic losses to farmers must donate one year's salary to the government's agricultural poverty alleviation fund. They are also prohibited from participating in the formulation of any major policies or regulations for the next eight years. The purpose of this convention is to reduce the occurrence of decisions made without scientific basis and where policymakers do not bear any consequences. Those who have made such serious mistakes must undergo repeated learning and training in other positions before they can again participate in the formulation of regulations on major issues. [Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>	
<p>From a philosophical and methodological perspective, China should immediately begin implementing an expatriation tax and a gift tax.</p> <p>Specific standards for these taxes can refer to Table 35 S 3 (Table 35 S 3. Suggested Tax Rate for Change of Nationality) in this article. These emergency laws should be drafted within two weeks. Relevant management departments should proactively legislate. If it is known to be beneficial to China and can reduce significant losses, but legislation is still delayed, those responsible for the delay will have all personal and family assets confiscated. Those colluding with financial oligarchs to cause significant asset losses will face confiscation of all personal and family assets of the involved oligarchs, a fine of twice the lost amount, and criminal liability.</p> <p>All violators and all personnel from the involved institutions must disclose all personal and family assets within one week.</p> <p>All violators will be included in a credit blacklist, banned from taking high-speed trains and planes for the next thirty years, and required to report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of the offenders are prohibited from working in government institutions, financial institutions, military, or security agencies. Those currently employed in these</p>	

	institutions must resign within two weeks.	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for promoting the development of rural economy and traditional health therapies</p> <p>To promote rural economic development and increase farmers' enthusiasm for production, the United Nations and the international community should form the following convention on the production and sale of processed agricultural products in rural areas:</p> <p>To promote rural economic development, as long as wild plants in rural areas are non-toxic substances, and there are historical records of past use for foot soaking, health care, beauty, or bathing, non-edible products produced by simple processing such as grinding or mild fermentation can be produced and sold without administrative approval, with the specific functions mentioned on the packaging. Producers and sellers are responsible for the quality and after-sales service of the products.</p>	
	<p>China should form a consensus and conventions on speeding up the circulation of agricultural products, promoting rural economic development and strengthening government governance to address common problems in the transportation of agricultural products. Any toll collector at a toll booth who extorts agricultural transportation vehicles must be severely punished, including relevant personnel:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The toll collector claims that bell peppers are not a type of chili pepper, or that purple sweet potatoes are not a type of sweet potato, etc. 2. If a few fish in a shipment of live fish have incomplete bodies, the toll collector denies that the whole shipment is fresh agricultural products. 3. A whole shipment of fruit is required to be unloaded for inspection by the toll collector. 4. If the green leafy part of the scallions has been removed during harvesting, leaving only the white stem and root, the toll collector deems the scallions not to be agricultural products. 5. After the vegetables experience strong winds on the highway, some of them become dried out. When passing through the toll booth, the toll collectors at this toll station intentionally refuse to recognize the fact that the transportation vehicle is carrying agricultural products, and insist on inspecting the entire load of agricultural products in order to approve them. They may require unloading for inspection, or deny the vehicle transporting agricultural products access to the green channel for free passage, and instead demand a high toll fee before allowing passage. These are all unacceptable behaviors. 6. Any agricultural product falls under the green channel as a free product, regardless of whether the product or fruit is ripe, fresh, sun dried, or dried. <p>In the case of such misconduct, the relevant regulatory authorities must dismiss the violator at the toll station within one day, report the incident nationwide, prohibit any toll station from re-hiring this individual, and impose a double fine on the responsible person and the toll station. All fines will be paid into the national treasury, and the toll station must compensate the</p>	

	<p>owner of the vehicle and cargo owner for all losses. Any leader who recommends or advocates the hiring of this individual at the toll station must be demoted to two levels of position and salary within 15 days. Meanwhile, the entire personal and family assets of the individual and his or her relatives within three generations must be disclosed within one week. The personal and family assets of all individuals involved misconduct in this incident, as well as all employees of the toll station, must be disclosed within one week. All family members of violators are prohibited from entering the civil service system for life. If the amount of loss caused to the cargo owner or vehicle owner exceeds CNY10,000, toll collectors who intentionally extort money from the vehicle owner must be subject to criminal penalties.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for gradually banning herbicides</p> <p>The coexistence of weeds and crops conforms to dialectics</p> <p>The United Nations must urgently establish a convention whereby all countries globally must completely ban the use of any chemical substances that do not meet food-grade standards for weed control within 2-4 years. The use of weed control agents that leave residues or are inedible biologics should also be prohibited. It is recommended to adopt ecological cultivation models where weeds coexist with crops, or to use physical methods for weed removal. The United States has advanced non-herbicidal models and mechanical methods for weed control, which could be promoted globally with the influence of the United Nations.</p> <p>If herbicide manufacturers are unwilling to stop production, they should face the strictest measures or legal cases in the event that any incidences are found related to their product. The top 20 controlling shareholders and corporate legal persons holding shares in herbicide-producing companies will be required to assume legal responsibility.</p> <p>Grass is a part of the ecosystem in crop growth, much like the extranuclear electrons in atoms within the nucleus of a molecule, whether chemical or philosophical terms. Removing the extranuclear electrons from the nucleus will inevitably produce substances with a high oxidation state similar to positively charged materials. High oxidation state substances lead to accelerated aging of human body cells and will inevitably disrupt the ecological balance of the soil.</p> <p>Herbicides are highly toxic. Recently, a family in Guangdong Province claimed to have suffered from oral herbicide poisoning. Currently, there is no way to treat the condition, and no one has come forward to help identify the poisoner. A video was released showing the patient in extreme pain (Fig 80).⁸⁵</p> <p>The public has many misconceptions about the presence of weeds in the soil, believing that the appearance of weeds necessitates the use of herbicides. In fact, weeds in the soil can be beneficial to soil quality and crop growth. Weeds play a role in regulating soil moisture and temperature, and they also attract a diverse array of microorganisms. For example, when cotton cloths were buried</p>	

	<p>in an orange grove, there was a significant difference between areas with weeds and those without. The cloth in weedy areas decomposed quickly, while in areas without weeds, the decomposition was much slower (Fig 81).⁸⁶</p> <p>Plants and microorganisms assist each other; the byproducts of photosynthesis are secreted by plant roots into the soil, attracting many microorganisms that feed on these secretions. In turn, microorganisms help dissolve nutrients that have been immobilized in the soil, making them available for plant uptake. Thus, they complement each other. When there are weeds in our orchards, in addition to regulating moisture and temperature, they also help attract various microorganisms that enliven the soil. This significantly enhances the effectiveness of fertilization and can also reduce the incidence of soil-borne diseases, such as root rot. While there can be some issues with weeds, it is important for the public to recognize their benefits (Fig 81, Fig 82, Fig 83).⁸⁶</p> <p>The main hazards of herbicides to human health are as follows:⁸⁷⁻⁹¹</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Herbicides have been linked to allergies and tumors, two types of autoimmune diseases. The use of herbicides in rural areas has led to a much higher prevalence of tumors compared to the times before their use. 2. Herbicides pose a risk to the cardiovascular system, leading to an increased frequency of cardiovascular diseases. 3. Herbicides have been associated with difficulties becoming pregnant and an increase in miscarriages, stillbirths, and birth defects. In the past, pregnant women would take leave shortly before giving birth, but now there are more cases of miscarriage from simple actions such as sneezing or walking a few steps. This is because many people have been inadvertently consuming herbicides since birth. 4. Herbicides are associated with a high incidence of childhood leukemia. 5. Respiratory system damage: Symptoms such as coughing, expectoration, chest tightness, and cyanosis may occur. 6. Digestive system harm: Accidental ingestion of herbicides can cause a burning sensation in the mouth, with erosion or ulcers of mucous membranes in the lips, tongue, pharynx, esophagus, stomach, etc., accompanied by gastrointestinal discomfort such as difficulty swallowing, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, etc., as well as vomiting blood, bloody stool, and gastrointestinal perforation. <p>[Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for reducing officials who only execute the wrong decisions of their superiors and do nothing.</p> <p>Government governance is largely linked to the moral qualities of the officials. It is suggested that the United Nations develop a relevant convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Some officials know that the decision made by their superiors is wrong, but they do not remind their superiors to pay attention or correct the error at all.</p>	

	<p>Instead, they continue to incite others to execute the decision, ultimately leading to major losses. Such officials should be prohibited from promotion for 15 years. Even if they are promoted, they should not hold a substantive position and should be given at most a deputy position.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for combating the situation where evil officials seriously violate the rights of innocent people and the deceased.</p> <p>In the event of any accident or disaster resulting in the death of the victims, no institution shall prohibit the inspection and visitation of the body of the victims by their relatives. The ownership of the victim's body belongs to the relatives, not to any institution. The cremation of the victim's body is prohibited, and any act of preventing the victim's relatives from visiting and inspecting the victim's body, as well as forcibly cremating the victim's body, constitute serious violations of the law. Throughout history, it has been a basic ethical principle for the relatives of executed criminals to examine and collect the bodies. In the event of the above circumstances, at least those who conceal a homicide or obstruct the victim's relatives from visiting or cremating the victim shall be charged with at least two offences: obstructing the investigation of a homicide and destroying evidence of a crime, and shall compensate the victim's family. At present, such crimes occur from time to time. The United Nations and the international community must form the following conventions on the above issues:</p> <p>First, anyone who orders the above heinous acts, as well as personnel from the government agencies primarily involved, will have their administrative ranks and benefits reduced by five levels. Direct law enforcement personnel must have their salaries suspended for at least one year, be transferred from their positions, and be subject to criminal penalties. Secondly, anyone who harms journalists or the relatives of victims, as well as those who give orders or are the primary responsible parties or commanders at the scene, will be considered as criminals and subject to criminal penalties, and will be removed from their positions. Non-governmental personnel would be subject to criminal law sanctions, and must pay triple compensation for damage to property or injury to journalists. Third, all criminals and their family members must report their travel itineraries to the police before leaving their place of residence to go to another city or region. Fourth, they are prohibited from travelling on airplanes and high-speed trains. Fifth, all family members are blacklisted for life. Sixth, all offenders are prohibited for life from receiving medical insurance services. Seventh, all family members and direct relatives of the above-mentioned criminals are prohibited from entering any university in the world for 1,000 years, and from working in the civil service system of any country or region. As long as offenders or their descendants are reported by informed individuals for violations, any university or government agency must complete the processing within 48 hours. Eighth, the personal and family wealth of the offender and all close relatives within three generations must be</p>	

	<p>made public. Ninth, the personal and family wealth of all individuals in the unit involved in the case must be made public.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Philosophical and methodological considerations in combating the production of edible oil from waste</p> <p>In recent decades, some countries have seen the frequent sale of inferior gutter oil as edible oil, which poses a great danger to human health. Many criminals have profited from this, so it is recommended that the United Nations form a relevant convention to control crime related to the above issue. The method of producing gutter oil involves collecting large amounts of dark, turbid sludge or leftover food from restaurants flowing through the city sewer, and then filtering, heating, precipitating, and separating it overnight to produce harmful gutter oil. Criminals who turn sewage oil into edible oil or sell it as a mixture of edible oil pose a great threat to society, and it is difficult to completely prevent. It is necessary to deter these criminals by adopting the following methods to eradicate these crimes.</p> <p>First, if any individual or entity produces or sells cooking oil containing gutter oil, they must be sentenced to criminal penalties, and all personal and family assets of the individuals involved in the crime and their relatives within three generations must be publicly disclosed.</p> <p>Second, if any person or entity produces or sells 10 tons of cooking oil containing gutter oil, the principal and chief culprits must be sentenced to 5-8 years' imprisonment, and all personal property must be confiscated. If any person or entity produces or sells 10-99 tons of cooking oil containing gutter oil, the principal and chief culprits must be sentenced to 8-19 years' imprisonment, and all personal property must be confiscated. If any individual or entity produces or sells 100 tons of cooking oil containing gutter oil, the principal and chief culprits must be sentenced to 20 years' imprisonment, and all personal property must be confiscated. If any individual or entity produces or sells 101-999 tons of cooking oil containing gutter oil, the principal and chief culprits must be sentenced to 60-80 years' imprisonment, fined five times the amount, and all personal and family property must be confiscated. If any individual or entity produces or sells 1,000 tons of cooking oil containing gutter oil, the principal and chief culprits must be sentenced to death, fined five times the amount, and all personal and family property must be confiscated.</p> <p>Third, law enforcement must impose travel restrictions on offenders. If they leave their place of residence to go to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station and are prohibited from taking flights and high-speed trains.</p> <p>Fourth, criminals will be blacklisted for life, and all family members and immediate relatives will be permanently banned from entering the civil service system.</p>	

	<p>Fifth, all family members and direct relatives of offenders are prohibited from receiving compulsory education and medical insurance for 100 years, and are banned from entering public universities.</p> <p>Sixth, whistleblowers who report the crime of turning sewage oil into edible oil or selling it as a mixture of edible oil will be rewarded with 25% of the confiscated assets of the criminal once their report is verified.</p> <p>Seventh, governments of countries or regions where such incidents occur must inform every citizen of the provisions of this Convention through various means of rapid communication or dissemination, at least once a week.</p> <p>Eighth, in any region where the annual sale of cooking oil containing gutter oil exceeds 30 tons, if the regulatory agency is found to be ineffective, the responsible officials will be demoted by 2-3 levels, and the regulatory agency must disclose the personal and family assets of all its staff members. In any region where the annual sale of cooking oil containing gutter oil exceeds 500 tons, the primary related administrative officials in that region must be demoted by 3 levels, and the regulatory agency must disclose the personal and family assets of all its staff members.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for dealing with the situation where non-performing officials make serious mistakes in judicial trials.</p> <p>Any wrongful judgment resulting in the death or wrongful killing of innocent people shall result in the public disclosure of the personal and family assets of all responsible parties, as well as their extended families for three generations. The personal and family assets of everyone in their unit must also be made public, and the assets of the main responsible person and his or her family must be confiscated and turned over to the national treasury. In the event of such a serious incident, it is clear that the main responsible person lacks foresight and is unfit to hold a leadership position, and should be sentenced to at least 10 years' imprisonment or the death penalty. All responsible parties shall be prohibited from promotion for 20 years, and their descendants must undergo six years of training in harsh environments, followed by a public evaluation by the people of all training units, and must receive unanimous approval before being eligible for a civil service career, otherwise they shall be prohibited from working in the field. The last successful proposal to appoint the main responsible person's leader must be demoted by three levels of position and benefits within one month after the incident.</p> <p>For any wrongful sentence resulting in the imprisonment of innocent persons, the personal and family assets of all responsible parties, as well as their extended families for three generations, shall be made public. The assets of the main responsible person shall be confiscated and turned over to the national treasury, and all responsible parties shall be prohibited from</p>	

	<p>promotion within 15 years. Innocent victims were sentenced to imprisonment for how many years, the primary responsible person (including judge) must be sentenced to the same period of imprisonment, without parole, and without any reason for reduction of sentence.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for addressing the serious illegal collection of information by Apps</p> <p>There is a significant association between contemporary crime and the leakage of personal information. The United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions to the maximum extent possible to prevent such crimes and enhance global governance levels.</p> <p>Any commercial software or app intended for public use must include an option to prohibit the software from accessing personal information on mobile phones or computers, and the user should be able to easily locate this option. Violators who are suspected of committing a crime can be held accountable. If a company forces its public-facing apps or commercial software to access or obtain user information and is unwilling to make changes, users can claim compensation for losses caused by the violation. The company must also make changes to the software within 48 hours. Otherwise, the government must impose the following penalties: First, the legal person, CEO, and controlling shareholder of the company must be sentenced to 1-3 years in prison, and all assets of individuals and families of the crime unit and their relatives within three generations must be made public. Any illegal profits made using this information must be confiscated, and the company and its responsible persons must be fined twice. Secondly, the police must impose travel restrictions on the offender, requiring them to report their travel plans to the police station when leaving their place of residence, and they are forbidden from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. Third, the offender will be permanently included on the credit blacklist, and all family members and immediate relatives will be permanently banned from entering the civil servant system.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for governing the infringement on minors and serious crimes committed by minors.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus and establish conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For the rape of girls under 12 years of age, a minimum of 20 years' imprisonment; for the rape of underage girls twice or more, the death penalty. For gang rape of underage girls, the death penalty. The penalty for false accusation should be the same as the above offences. Regardless of whether the offender has reached adulthood or not.</p>	

	<p>Criminals who kill underage girls or children or students, regardless of whether the offender is an adult, must be sentenced to death. If anyone does not allow the criminal to be sentenced to death, then if the criminal commits a crime in the future, the loss caused by the criminal will be borne by the judge, the advocates of not sentencing to death in court and behind the scenes, and these individuals and their families will have all their personal and family property confiscated, and be sentenced to at least 30 years in prison, experiencing the taste of death. The guardians must be held accountable for the crimes committed by minors.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for regulating employment agencies that exploit workers' finances indirectly</p> <p>The intermediary company introduces jobs to employees, usually on a two-way fee model, charging an introduction fee to the company that needs employees. However, some intermediary companies continue to charge the employee a long-term intermediary fee after successfully introducing the employee to a job. The intermediary fee can be as high as 24% of the employee's monthly income, far exceeding the average annual return on investment for small and medium-sized enterprises in the United States. This long-term exploitation of other people's wealth is extremely serious, as employees have become borrowers of high-interest loans from intermediary companies. The United Nations and the international community should reach a consensus as soon as possible and establish a convention on the following issues: After assisting an employee successfully introduce a job, an intermediary in any occupation can only charge a reasonable intermediary fee to the employee for the first three months. After three months, no further fees can be charged. Otherwise, the intermediary company will be fined twice and its operating qualification will be suspended for six months.</p> <p>All violators will be included in a credit blacklist, banned from taking high-speed trains and planes for the next thirty years, and required to report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 100 years, all direct relatives of the offenders are prohibited from working in government institutions, financial institutions, military, or security agencies.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations on severely punishing the crime of poisoning poultry raised by farmers.</p> <p>Rural poisoning incidents occur frequently, resulting in the death of all fish, chickens, and ducks raised by farmers, causing heavy losses. A single poisoning incident can lead to a year's worth of lost household income, making it difficult to sustain life and reproduce. Some rural families are already in poverty, and</p>	

	<p>the poisoning of their fish or poultry exacerbates the situation. However, current penalties for such poisoning are too low to deter criminals. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Any criminal who poisons and kills fish, shrimp, ducks, chickens, geese, and other poultry raised by rural breeders must not only compensate for all losses, but also face criminal punishment. Anyone found guilty of poisoning must be detained for at least 7 days. Those causing the death of ducks with losses ranging from CNY 10,000 to 99,999 must be sentenced to 1-4 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 100,000 to 499,999 must be sentenced to 5-10 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 500,000 to 999,999 must be sentenced to 10-20 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 1,000,000 to 1,500,000 must be sentenced to 20-30 years in prison. Failure to compensate will result in the government confiscating their personal and family property. 2. The government must disclose the identity of the perpetrator and his family members who committed the poisoning crime in the mainstream media of the region once a week for three consecutive months, publishing their photos to expose their wrongdoing and warn others. 3. Police must impose travel restrictions on the poisoner's family members. If they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. 4. All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their immediate family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system. 5. The personal and family assets of the offender and his three generations of relatives must be made public. 6. If, during the process of preventing poisoning, searching for the poisoner, or apprehending the poisoner, the victim engages in any conflict with the poisoner, resulting in injury or death to the poisoner, the victim bears no responsibility. <p>It should be noted that compensation for the losses suffered by the victims, which must be paid by the perpetrators, should be actively enforced by the court to complete the entire process.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Some public hospitals give nurses with the same skills in the same position completely different treatment, resulting in some nurses earning high incomes while others earn very low incomes, despite doing the same job and working very hard. This is suspected of serious discrimination and it is essential for the United Nations and the international community to establish the following convention to prohibit different systemic treatment of nurses with the same skills and in the same position. Otherwise, the medical institution should be fined five times the normal income that all</p>	

	<p>affected nurses should receive during the period of the offence, and compensate the victims.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in deterring and combating crimes against children</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>In recent decades, there have been frequent cases of children going missing in public places, often taken by criminals who then cut off their hands or feet, render them mute (a dumb person), or burn their faces or bodies to leave visible scars. These criminal gangs force children to beg for profit, using their tragic appearance to gain the sympathy of passersby. The situation these children find themselves in is extremely dire, and once they fall into the hands of these criminals, their lives are essentially over.</p> <p>However, the current legal system severely hinders efforts to combat and deter these criminals, failing to effectively protect children and instead showing leniency towards perpetrators. The justice and fairness of the law lags far behind the atrocities committed, and this is the greatest crime of legislators at the top of the food chain. If so many children are still victimized in this society, these lawmakers should also be sentenced to death. Nevertheless, there is imperative to amend the law and form a global consensus and a United Nations convention. Any criminal found in the act of kidnapping, abducting, or stealing a child, if apprehended, physically assaulted, or dealt with on the spot by the child's relatives or by any conscientious individuals, shall not be held legally responsible for their actions.</p> <p>If the criminal's family seeks retribution, they will be considered accomplices and sentenced accordingly by the courts. In addition, any criminal who caused disability to a child must be sentenced to death, as trafficking in children could bring enormous profits. The assets of the criminal and his or her family, including up to three generations, must be made public. Any falsification of the abduction of children and harm to innocent persons shall be punishable by death.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for making corruption and low-level soccer relatively transparent</p> <p>Soccer is a popular sport among the global public, but over the past twenty years, people have discovered serious problems within it, leading to great disappointment with the sport. The United Nations and the international</p>	

	<p>community should reach a consensus on the following issues and establish a convention:</p> <p>For countries with a long history of poor soccer performance and a FIFA ranking outside the top 50, if there is serious corruption within the country's football association or soccer community during the last two World Cup cycles, fans had expressed serious dissatisfaction. All personnel of the national football association, coaches and staff of all national teams must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within one week of the entry into force of this UN convention. Individuals and organizations involved in intermediary activities related to soccer must operate their funds transparently and disclose their personal and family assets. This is to prevent soccer from becoming the darkest sport in the world.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for preventing serious judicial injustice</p> <p>History has proven that in any large organization or government that believes in the highest ideals of communism, there are always corrupt elements. These criminals, who cause serious harm to innocent civilians, must be severely punished.</p> <p>Serious judicial injustice is the root cause of the occurrence of malignant cases, and must be corrected with strong measures to deter law enforcement officials from committing crimes. The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus on the following issues and establish conventions:</p> <p>If there is evidence that the suspect was not present at the scene in a case, completely contradicting the logic of the criminal investigation, the judge should not make a wrongful judgment. The reasons for the suspect's crime could not be established, but the judge disregarded the facts and maliciously convicted him, resulting in the victim's wrongful imprisonment. In such a case, the relevant judicial personnel are equally guilty, and their prison sentences should be the same as the victim's. If the victim is wrongly sentenced to death, once the error is corrected, the judge should be sentenced to at least 80 years in prison or the death penalty. In addition, the personal and family assets of the relevant judges should be confiscated to compensate the families of the victims or be turned over to the national treasury. The personal and family assets of all individuals in the relevant unit, as well as those of relatives within three generations, should be made public. All family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Considerations on the Philosophy and Methodology for Addressing the Illegal Exploitation of Civilian Wealth through the Misuse of Intelligent Public Billing Systems</p>	

	<p>The use of smart meters for billing electricity, water, and natural gas in households often leads to disputes, which may be due to fraudulent practices by relevant companies. It is essential for the United Nations and the international community to establish the following conventions to regulate this smart billing system.</p> <p>First, if users have doubts, electricity, water and gas companies must provide a fast and clear way to prove the accuracy of the smart metering system within half an hour. Otherwise, if users cannot eliminate their doubts about significantly higher monthly use of electricity, water, or gas, they may refuse to pay. If the company supplying these essential resources cannot prove the accuracy of the data, and if fraud is found, the fraudulent company must be fined three times the amount cheated by users to compensate for their losses. In addition, similar issues in the past must be investigated, and the company's responsible individuals must be fined three times the amount, and all personal and family assets of the company's employees must be made public.</p> <p>Second, the government must disclose the information of the responsible person and their company's fraud using the mainstream media of the city or region every day for one month, and publish the criminals' photos in the media;</p> <p>Third, the police must criminally detain fraudsters and swindlers for at least 7 days, and if multiple users jointly discover that a company's smart metering has defrauded them of more than 10,000 CNY, the company's responsible persons and those involved must be sentenced to more than one year in prison.</p> <p>Fourth, if the criminal and his family members leave their place of residence to go to another city or area, they must report their itinerary to the police station, and are prohibited from travelling by plane and high-speed rail.</p> <p>Fifth, all family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system.</p> <p>Sixth, if it is found that a company is using smart meters to falsify data, the individuals involved and the company's responsible parties must be immediately placed under criminal detention.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for handling large-scale sales and use of spoiled grains</p> <p>It should be noted that moldy and deteriorated rice contains a highly toxic aflatoxin, which poses a significant threat to the liver and has strong carcinogenic properties. Even at a high temperature of 200°C, its toxicity cannot be eliminated, and ingesting just 1 milligram can lead to cancer, while a one-time intake of 20 milligrams can be fatal. However, some unscrupulous merchants often sell moldy and deteriorated rice to university canteens and restaurants, which is equivalent to poisoning. Meanwhile, some university cafeteria staff and manager, knowing that the rice is moldy, still prepare it as food for students and teachers, committing a joint poisoning crime. Therefore,</p>	

	<p>the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Anyone involved in the sale and use of mouldy and deteriorated rice shall be treated as committing a poisoning crime. They must be fined five times the sales amount. University cafeterias or public canteens using moldy rice to make food shall be fined three times the purchase amount and their sales revenue shall be confiscated. Anyone involved in cases exceeding 5000 CNY must be detained for at least 7 days. 2. For moldy rice already made into food, based on the normal consumption of one meal for an adult, those selling food for 1000-5000 meals should be sentenced to 1-5 years in prison; for 5001-10000 meals, 5-10 years; for 10001-20000 meals, 10-20 years; for 20001-30000 meals, 20-30 years; for 30001-40000 meals, 30-40 years; for 40001-50000 meals, 40-50 years; and for over 50001 meals, the death penalty shall be imposed. 3. Police must impose travel restrictions on the poisoner's family members. If they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. 4. All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their direct family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system. 5. The personal and family properties of the criminal and their three generations of relatives must be made public. 6. The personal and family properties of all owners of the units involved must be made public. 7. Anyone who purchases mouldy or deteriorated rice or grains in bulk must report it to the authorities immediately upon discovery. Failure to do so will be considered as knowingly withholding information and will result in punishment. Government employees involved will be dismissed from their positions, and private sector employees will be blacklisted. <p>Anyone who sells mouldy or deteriorated rice or grains for human consumption, with a sales or purchase volume of 2-10 tons and before it has been made into cooked food, and if the buyer was aware of it beforehand, the principal offenders of both the sale and purchase must be sentenced to 3-6 years' imprisonment. If the volume of the sale or purchase is 11-50 tons and before it has been made into cooked food, and if the buyer was aware of it beforehand, the principal offenders of both the sale and purchase must be sentenced to 7-15 years' imprisonment. If the volume of the sale or purchase is 51-100 tons and before it has been made into cooked food, and if the buyer was aware of it beforehand, the principal offenders of both the sale and purchase must be sentenced to 16-25 years' imprisonment. If the volume of the sale or purchase is 101 tons or more, and before it has been made into cooked food, and if the buyer was aware of it beforehand, the principal offenders of both the sale and purchase must be sentenced to death.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations on dealing with animal</p>	

	<p>harm to children</p> <p>In today's society, due to the extensive copying of Chinese cultural and technological achievements by the West, and to satisfy their vanity, they have massively falsified European history, culture, and legal systems. This has caused some of the modern world's judicial ethics and systems to regress by 2000-4000 years. Influenced by this Western ideology, some people believe that animal rights surpass everything else, overturning traditional views held for thousands of years.</p> <p>When a dog attacks a child, the dog owner does not actively and promptly intervene to stop the attack. Instead of controlling aggressive dogs, they prioritize the lives of dogs over those of humans. After a child is bitten, there is a lack of proactive compensation, and various excuses are used to deny responsibility. Children who are attacked by aggressive dogs suffer severe psychological trauma. It is necessary for the United Nations and the international community to form the following consensus and conventions: Once a child or person is bitten by a dog, in addition to bearing medical expenses, the dog owner must compensate for mental and other losses. They should be fined an administrative penalty equivalent to half the price of the dog, which will supplement local finances. If a child is disabled or left with permanent scars as a result of the attack, the dog owner must be sentenced to 3-5 years in prison and compensate the victim. If the attack results in death, the dog owner should be sentenced to death or 30 years of imprisonment. In addition, the dog owner must compensate the victim using their personal and family assets. The personal and family assets of the dog owner must be fully disclosed to the judicial authorities within three days after the incident. Violators must be severely punished with a fine of \$10,000. Failure to disclose within seven days will result in a double fine and criminal detention.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations on dealing with farmers or households logging self-planted trees</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current world has failed to rapidly and effectively curb the excessive global wealth gap, reduce long-term rural poverty in remote areas or mountainous regions, and sustainably develop rural economies and increase the incomes of rural families. This reflects a lack of philosophical understanding and methodological cognition in reducing the population affected by war. The inability to achieve long-term world peace is the result of significant problems in implementing national governance and maintaining world peace philosophically and methodologically. It is also the result of Europe's modern theft and incomplete imitation of China's legislative ideology, and the false claim that Europe is the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must undergo a philosophical and methodological change in order to rapidly and effectively curb excessive global wealth disparities and increase the income of the rural population in impoverished areas, and form a permanent consensus or convention.</p>	

	<p>Any family or farmer can cut down the trees they have planted, especially those planted for their own livelihood. As long as the number of mature trees cut down within one year is less than 20, there is no need to report to any institution, and the cutting is legal. If the number of trees cut down in a year exceeds 20 but is less than 500, it is legal to cut down after reporting to the regulatory agency, without approval. If the number of trees cut down in a year exceeds 500, it is legal to cut down after reporting to the regulatory agency and replanting 50% of the trees within six months of cutting. The United Nations and the international community should reach a permanent consensus or agreement on this issue.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations on evading regulation by registering overseas offshore companies</p> <p>The offshore registration of companies through overseas offshore registration leads to low transparency, making it impossible to trace the identity of hidden shareholders, reducing regulation, facilitating tax evasion and money laundering. Secondly, the reduced amount of tax due to the main company harms the interests of the location where the main company is based. Thirdly, some companies, even after registering offshore companies through BVI's structure, deceive banks in the location of the main company by seemingly legally diverting funds borrowed from the bank, leaving behind debt and causing significant losses to the bank where the company actually operates or to the home country's economy. This practice is shameless, unethical, and completely contrary to universal values. Fourth, transferring tax revenues and benefits that should belong to the host country of the main company is equivalent to creating a wealth gap, which goes against the universal values advocated by the West and its concept of human rights. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community should form a consensus and a convention to immediately ban the registration of companies using the above methods to avoid taxes, evade regulation, and launder money, and comprehensively prohibit the establishment of offshore companies to control the main company. Companies registered through offshore design should be revoked. Publicly listed companies should strengthen regulation and have their registration location at the location of the main company.</p> <p>All employees of the unit where the violator is located must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within two weeks.</p>	
	<p>The United Nations and the international community should reach the following consensus and agreement:</p> <p>Any civil aircraft produced by a company must have at least one black box battery that can effectively maintain operation for at least 60 days. If the black box produced or equipped in the past cannot meet the above standard, it must be added free of charge.</p> <p>With significant advances in battery technology today, it is absolutely unacceptable that the standards for black box batteries remain at the level of over 20 years ago, only maintaining a 30-day status. This seriously hinders</p>	

	rescue efforts in the event of an aviation disaster.	
	<p>Fishing is both a leisure activity and a sport. In the public waters of any country, as long as fishing is not prohibited during that period by the country, no institution, organization or individual may prohibit citizens of that country from engaging in fishing activities using one rod per person with a single hook and without electronic fish detection. Any deliberate action to repeatedly create obstacles to vessels interfering with fishing is illegal, as is any confiscation or destruction of fishing gear. Therefore, the full responsibility for any escalation of conflicts lies with those who violate regulations by disrupting fishing activities. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>	
	<p>Considerations of Philosophy and Methodology for Severely Cracking Down on Crimes of Robbery and Rape of Women and Preventing Incompetent and Unethical Individuals from Becoming Officials or Decision-Makers</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any evildoer who attacks women with the intent to rob, rape, or harm them, the woman's husband, or any third party upholder of justice may execute any necessary counterattack. Regardless of the degree of harm inflicted on the perpetrator, the defender is not guilty. If the criminal uses a knife or any other weapon, or if the criminal's fighting ability is superior to that of the victim or any person with a sense of justice, the victim and their family, or any person with a sense of justice, will not be convicted for using a vehicle or other means to attack the criminal. If the criminal's family insists that punishing the rapist is a crime, the criminal's family must be subject to criminal punishment.</p> <p>Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises. They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent</p>	

	<p>limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.</p> <p>Politicians, lawyers, or judges, as leaders in their respective fields, must possess foresight; otherwise, they cannot assume leadership or propose policies. Anyone who proposes erroneous policies that fail to protect victims, cause greater harm to victims, impede the strict punishment of criminals, or provide criminals with more opportunities to commit crimes must bear adequate responsibility and compensation for the consequences. If any politician, lawyer, or judge disagrees with this proposal, under the principles of empathy and equality in the judicial system, any past victim can find three individuals willing to rape the wife or daughter of the dissident politician, judge, or lawyer. If they can completely single-handedly protect their wife or daughter from being raped and gang-raped, and if more than half of the state's voters support them, this convention will be void for that part of the state's electorate. Once any voter has suffered such harm, all responsibility and compensation will be borne jointly by the criminal, politician, lawyer, and judge. For other voters who do not agree to cancel this convention, it will continue to be enforced.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in dealing with officials formulating erroneous policies</p> <p>Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises. They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.</p> <p>Any means of transportation that is government-approved for production and legally sold can be legally used by the public. No individual or institution has the right to deprive the public of the use of such transportation. Anyone who violates the above principles and causes loss to the public shall be held accountable for abuse of power. Those who make wrong regulations and those who abuse regulations must compensate the public for their losses with their personal and family assets. Those who make erroneous regulations are not fit to hold any public office.</p>	
	<p>Considerations of Philosophy and Methodology for Addressing Unfinished Buildings, Energy Consumption, and Safety Risks of Commercial Buildings in the Virtual Era</p>	

	<p>To truly establish an environmentally friendly society and reduce the difficulty of carbon emissions and firefighting, in any city's residential or mixed-use buildings, only 1% of the building height is allowed to exceed 12 floors, but not more than 24 floors. The remaining residential floors must not exceed 12 floors. Any violation will result in the government confiscating all illegal income from the developers and imposing a fine of five times the amount. These provisions apply to all countries. All responsible individuals and their respective units must publicly disclose all personal and family assets within one week after the incident. Violators will be fined an amount equivalent to one-twentieth of their personal assets.</p> <p>Except for buildings with special purposes, any commercial buildings in any city or region that have not yet been constructed are prohibited from exceeding 200 meters.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in dealing with losses caused by errors in official promotion</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The capacity and character of officials are closely linked to the governance of the region. The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus and conventions on the following issues to the greatest extent possible in order to prevent official crimes and improve the governance level of global governments.</p> <p>The ability of a region to be well managed depends on the foresight, management skills, and character of government officials. The promotion of officials requires more foresight to reduce the promotion of incompetent officials and minimize the improper promotion of civil servants who may be prone to serious crimes, while increasing the promotion of officials with good character and capability. Logically, those who propose promotions should be the most familiar with and understand the officials being promoted, and they must bear a certain responsibility. Correct promotions should be commended, with a Bole Award given every three or four years. If a promoted official commits a serious crime, the person who proposed their recent promotion must be held responsible. Any person who proposed and executed the promotion of a criminal official must be demoted by three levels and their benefits reduced, with all personal and family assets made public. They can only be promoted again if they have new achievements or continue to work</p>	

<p>diligently.</p> <p>In the case of multiple or collective decisions to promote a criminal official, those involved must also bear responsibility. All promotions within the group must be suspended for five years, with the individual primarily responsible for promotion being demoted, and other rules consistent with the previous ones.</p> <p>Any official who makes a major mistake in his or her job should be demoted, and the position of the person who proposed his or her promotion should also be downgraded until he or she achieves new success and can be promoted again.</p> <p>Officials who cause significant losses to State assets or major obstacles to the national economy must be demoted and compensated with 1-3 years' personal salary or half of their personal property. All personal and family assets must be made public. The position of the person who proposed the promotion of such an official must be demoted by three levels, and their benefits reduced, with all personal and family assets made public. They can only be promoted again if they have new achievements or continue to work diligently.</p> <p>Any person who proposes and implements an action that results in significant losses of State assets must also be punished.</p>	
<p>Philosophical and Methodological Considerations for Combating Internet Lottery Advertisement Fraud</p> <p>Any false advertising on online platforms that offers items for purchase at a price more than five times lower than the normal price of the goods sold, such as misleading consumers with the opportunity to purchase products actually worth CNY 10 to 7,000 or more for CNY 1-1.9, or leading consumers to buy products actually worth CNY 50-7,000 for CNY 9.9-39.9, and enticing customers to spend, the full loss of customers deceived by such schemes shall be borne by the online platform concerned. Both the fraudster and the online platform will be fined five times the amount of the victim's loss! If the total amount of fraud exceeds \$1 million, all personal assets of the fraudster will be confiscated, and the platform will face a fine of eight times the amount. In such cases, the photos of the fraudster and the legal representative and major shareholders of the online platform, together with their crimes, must be permanently displayed on the anti-fraud network, and the online platform also commits a serious fraud crime.</p> <p>Even if no fraud has been temporarily committed, or there have been no complaints or lawsuits from victims, as soon as such advertisements appear on the online platform, criminal suspects preparing to commit fraud and the complicit online platform will face a minimum fine of \$10,000 to \$30,000. Photos and crimes of the fraudster, the legal representative, and the main shareholders of the online platform must be permanently displayed on the anti-fraud network.</p> <p>All individuals involved in criminal activities shall be included in a credit blacklist. They are prohibited from traveling by high-speed rail and airplane for</p>	

	<p>the next 30 years and must report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 200 years, all direct relatives of criminals are prohibited from holding any positions in government institutions, financial institutions, military institutions, and security institutions. Those currently working in these institutions must resign within two weeks. Whistleblowers who report violations will be rewarded with 20% of the fines, which will be anonymously distributed to them.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations in cracking down on food counterfeiting</p> <p>Some people use bone powder instead of meat to make ham sausage, resulting in a lack of the necessary nutrients in the food. In order to make seafood and other meat products appear fresh, some criminals use formaldehyde, borax, excessive sodium benzoate, or excessive potassium benzoate and other preservatives to produce toxic food, allowing for longer shelf life. Some even add formaldehyde or excessive alum and other toxic substances to rice noodles to make them more resilient. Some even use gelatin etc. to make fake sea cucumbers or jellyfish. Some criminals process sick and dying chickens, ducks, and pigs into meat products for sale. Generally, ordinary people cannot distinguish toxic food, inferior food, or fake food. These illegally manufactured foods are likely to cause damage to the liver, kidneys, or other systems, posing a great danger to human health, while counterfeiters reap huge profits. The United Nations should as soon as possible form the following international conventions on this issue:</p> <p>First, in the case of any manufacturer of toxic food, substandard food, and other food counterfeiters, the first offence will result in a fine of five times the amount involved. For a second offence, the fine will be ten times the amount involved, and for a third offence, personal property will be confiscated and a sentence of 2-5 years' imprisonment must be imposed.</p> <p>Second, anyone involved in a case involving CNY 1 million must be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison.</p> <p>Third, all offenders and their family members must report their travel itinerary to the police station before leaving their place of residence for another city or region.</p> <p>Fourth, criminals are prohibited from flying on airplanes or taking high-speed trains when traveling.</p> <p>Fifth, all family members are placed on the lifetime credit blacklist.</p> <p>Sixth, all offenders and their family members are prohibited from entering into any country or region's civil service system for life, and those already working in the civil service system must resign.</p> <p>Seventh, once a second offence has occurred, all offenders are prohibited from enjoying medical insurance services for life.</p>	

	<p>Eighth, once a second offence has occurred, all family members and direct relatives of the above-mentioned offenders are prohibited from entering any university in the world for 100 years. If the offender or their descendants are reported by an informed person for violations, any university or government agency must deal with the case within 48 hours.</p> <p>Ninth, whistleblowers will receive a 40% reward for the confiscated amount.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and Methodological Considerations for Combating Luxury Car Traffic Accident Fraud</p> <p>Daily traffic accidents involving luxury vehicles have caused many ordinary families to go bankrupt. If there is a hope for global fairness and justice, the United Nations should rapidly develop a global convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Luxury cars are often used as a tool for showing off, and many luxury car drivers do not follow traffic rules, leading to accidents. However, vehicles that are passive in these accidents are often forced to provide a certain proportion of compensation to the luxury car, because the value of luxury vehicles is much higher than that of ordinary cars. Even a low percentage of compensation can result in the annual or even decade-long income of ordinary car drivers being wiped out in a single traffic accident.</p> <p>When ordinary cars are involved in major accidents with luxury vehicles, the amount of compensation is usually in the millions, which may far exceed the lifetime income of many ordinary people or families. Normal insurance coverage is simply unable to meet this amount of compensation. This means that ordinary car drivers either have to increase their insurance coverage by purchasing high amounts of insurance (which is an additional financial burden for the majority of ordinary people, adding to their daily economic burden), or they have to compensate for the remaining amount themselves (resulting in bankruptcy or even the death of the family). Bankruptcy or death often leads to desperate action, and ordinary car drivers may end up directly causing harm to luxury car drivers (for example, a truck that loses control of its brakes and is unable to kill the luxury car driver ends up accelerating and causing death). This is because they can't afford to pay, so they might also harm the person.</p> <p>Driving luxury cars will force other vehicles to increase their insurance claims, adding to the daily economic burden of ordinary families. It is common for vehicles to be involved in traffic accidents on the road. A luxury car driving on the road as a means of transportation will instinctively put pressure on nearby drivers with lower incomes. Some criminal groups even take advantage of the fact that luxury vehicles can obtain high compensation and set traps, intentionally driving luxury cars to collide with other vehicles in order to claim high illegal profits.</p> <p>Therefore, in the event of a traffic accident, compensation for the loss of luxury cars should not be based on a luxury model. There should be a limit on the amount of compensation for scratches or collisions. The maximum compensation for individual drivers should not exceed one twenty-fourth of</p>	

	<p>middle class income in the region, or the maximum total compensation amount should not exceed one-twelfth of the average annual income of ordinary vehicle drivers or low-income individuals in the region. Any excess amount should be borne by the luxury car driver himself. Luxury cars are not like diamonds or jewelry worn or kept at home. Vehicles driving on the road are depreciating products and are a means of transportation. Any luxury vehicle driving on the road may pose a danger to others. Drivers of luxury cars must have psychological and financial resilience; otherwise, they should not buy luxury cars.</p> <p>Lastly, if the perpetrator intentionally crashes into or deliberately damages a luxury car, causing it to be damaged, everything will be handled according to the local traffic regulations.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and Methodological Considerations for Protecting Farmers' Long-Term Interests and Preventing Deceptive Housing Purchase Frauds</p> <p>In order to sell real estate, some people use various means to tempt peasants with insufficient assets to leave the countryside and buy houses in the city. However, farmers lacking life skills are likely to fall deeper into poverty and cause social problems or crime after being deceived into entering the city or town. The United Nations should promptly form the following international convention on this issue:</p> <p>Any person who deceives peasants into buying houses in urban or rural areas, making it difficult to sustain their livelihood and becoming impoverished, shall be prohibited from entering or staying the civil service system. The personal and family assets of all the individuals involved shall be made public, and they must compensate the peasants for all their losses within three months. The ringleader is permanently banned from flying on airplanes or high-speed trains.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for safeguarding the family life of sacrificial and injured firefighters</p> <p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For firefighters who have sacrificed in the line of duty, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For firefighters who are injured and disabled while extinguishing fires, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is fully waived. For firefighters who are completely unable to work, their bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the firefighters or members of their families had any bank loans before the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities.</p> <p>If the above-mentioned warrior's family needs to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for safeguarding the family</p>	

	<p>life of martyrs who sacrificed and were injured in the fight against criminals</p> <p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For any warriors who have sacrificed themselves in the fight against the crimes listed in this table, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For warriors who are injured and disabled in the fight against the crimes listed, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is completely waived; For warriors who are completely unable to work, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the warriors or their family members had any bank loans prior to the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities. If the above-mentioned warriors or their families need to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>	
	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for safeguarding the family life of martyrs who sacrificed or were injured while saving children</p> <p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For any warriors who have sacrificed themselves in saving children from accidents, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For warriors who are injured and disabled while saving children from accidents, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is fully waived; For warriors who are completely unable to work, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the warriors or their family members had any bank loans prior to the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities. If the above-mentioned warriors or their families need to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>	
	<p>Low-income people or farmers in any country have the freedom to sell daily necessities or essentials like vegetables or fruits on any street in any city, as long as the products being sold do not exceed the scope of their normal means of transport, such as baskets, pushcarts, etc. As long as the street is not closed to pedestrian traffic and is not under martial law, no city management personnel may prohibit their trading activities.</p>	
28	The Sign of Future Progress in American Society or China	
	<p>Levying renunciation of nationality tax, gift tax, and estate tax.</p> <p>Establish a reasonable mechanism to prevent officials and civil servants from dereliction of duty and corruption.</p>	

	<p>Real estate returns to its original attributes, universal health insurance is implemented, and all costs of compulsory education are free. The government's governance achieves a rapid negative feedback mechanism.</p>	
	<p>Let's make a prediction: the moral level of the US government and military will only significantly improve when there are multiple individuals with outstanding moral character, similar to Chinese leaders such as Premier Zhou Enlai, Foreign Minister Chen Yi, Marshal Zhu De, Marshal Peng Dehuai, Marshal Luo Ronghuan, Huang Kecheng, Zhang Aiping, Liu Yalou, Wang Bicheng, Zhang Zhen, Chen Geng, Xiao Jingguang, Hong Xuezi, Zhong Wei, and other well-known Chinese figures mentioned in Article 20 of this table.</p> <p>Charitable funds and trust funds cannot be used to avoid taxes, including individual income tax and estate tax.</p> <p>The Internal Revenue Service (IRS) of the United States will no longer function as a private financial institution.</p> <p>The Federal Reserve will no longer be owned by private banks.</p> <p>Abandoning the Statues of Two Fictional Historical Figures on the Pediment of the United States Supreme Court.</p> <p>When the President of the United States takes office, they opt out of placing their hand on the Bible for the oath. The majority of Americans no longer adhere to religions based on the fictional Bible (Judaism, Christianity, Catholicism, Protestantism).</p> <p>Do not impose a ban on exporting high-tech products from the United States to China, and do not impose policy restrictions on products exported from China to the United States.</p> <p>Carbon emissions from the consumption of a product in a consumer country should be treated equally to carbon emissions from the production of that product in the producing country.</p> <p>Government officials adhere to basic political ethics and administrative ethics in international affairs.</p> <p>After being re-elected as President of the United States, Trump received the Nobel Peace Prize 3-4 times in 4-7 years due to his outstanding achievements in adhering to the four major principles of the Nobel Peace Prize, thus making history. However, after Trump took office, if he continues with the previous presidency's ideas or Biden's governing principles, America will inevitably accelerate its path towards division.</p> <p>The U.S. government is returning large amounts of high-quality land that was previously taken from Native Americans to them, providing full compensation for the harm caused by the European settlers' massacre of Native Americans.</p>	
29	<p>The premise of the collapse of two countries' societies or social systems.</p>	
	<p>The approach involves covertly privatizing farmers' land, legalizing the transactions of self-built houses by farmers, and inducing large numbers of skillful farmers without industrial production or business to buy</p>	

	<p>houses in cities, thus rendering them impoverished. Most financial assets or state-owned assets are privatized, disrupting the 4.0 version of equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty (socialist system). China abandons or no longer promotes Mao Zedong Thought. Crimes and government corruption are only addressed when they cannot be concealed anymore. Officials deliberately formulate deeply flawed policies, allowing a minority to profit immensely until the flaws become too obvious to conceal and revisions are made.</p> <p>If the current socialist regime in China collapses under the influence of privatization and marketization from the United States, Europe, and Japan, China's future will only see the establishment of a society with an equal-field system similar to the 4.5 or 5.0 version of the early Tang Dynasty, even if the ruling party is not the Communist Party. This is the inevitable course of history.</p> <p>When China's system collapses and the gene for eradicating evil forces is awakened, during the process of transition and establishment of a new system, entire families of corrupt and incompetent politicians, as well as oligarchic families that have illegally accumulated wealth, will be eradicated. Similar to the Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义), the entire families of some international oligarchs from other countries, who led to the change in China's system and the plundering of its wealth, will also be eradicated. Countries that directly caused the collapse of China's system, plundered its wealth, and plunged the general public into poverty will be regarded as enemies by reformed China. War between these nations will be inevitable, and most of the families of politicians and oligarchs controlling these countries are expected to be eradicated.</p>	
	<p>Future optimized version of China's socialist system: Further improved version 5.0 will be available (The 5.0 version of the Improved Equal-field System of the Early Tang Dynasty or the 5.0 version, 6.0 version, 7.0 version or 8.0 version of the New Equal-field System):</p> <p>Land is collectively owned by all people and labor collectives, ensuring the rights of the people to basic living, work, medical care, and education. It aims to establish good moral standards and norms of national governance, realizing the people's mastery of their own affairs. In particular, every family has the basic right to housing, ensuring each household possesses a property for basic living needs. Once purchased or built, there is no need to pay annual property taxes. There is basic social security for the elderly, basic medical insurance, unemployment benefits, and pre-reemployment training systems. Compulsory education implements a completely free system. The tuition, accommodation, and miscellaneous fees for students of certain majors in some universities and vocational schools are completely waived. The families of those who uphold social justice and are injured or sacrifice their lives should receive adequate social welfare benefits. Society operates on morality and</p>	

	<p>ethics, with laws regulating social behavior and punishing crimes. Interest rates on loans and deposits are reasonably set, and illegal activities like usury are severely punished. The state has a complete set of rules for selecting talented individuals to govern the country and a comprehensive negative feedback mechanism to prevent the excessive execution of policies or errors in policies, systems, laws, and actions.</p>	
		<p>The United States would only collapse if it encountered an irreparable financial, economic, or political crisis that couldn't be mitigated.</p> <p>Six ways to solve crises.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The United States assisting China and Chinese or overseas Chinese in seeking reparations from war criminal countries and offending nations like Japan could temporarily alleviate the financial crisis, followed by a gradual reform in the United States. 2. Americans driving Tesla cars to the graveyard perceive the true meaning of life. Essentially, Americans have abandoned the religion fabricated by missionary missionaries and formed by the fictitious Bible. Almost all Americans recognize the necessity of implementing China's Tang Dynasty equal-field system in the United States. Banks return to national control, and the U.S. national tax is controlled by the state. Americans' moral standards are rapidly improving. The wealthy no longer demand charitable funds and trust funds to avoid income and estate taxes. The United States exempts all households from basic housing taxes and agrees to pay income tax, inheritance tax, and gift tax according to the tax rates proposed in this article. Interest groups in the United States are redefining their perception of the Buddhist nature of wealth and the meaning of life, no longer seeking to create wars and conflicts around the world for profit. Members of these interest groups in the United States are realizing that the ability to generate wealth in one generation represents only their personal achievements during their lifetime and contributions to society. They acknowledge that wealth passed on to future generations must be taxed and recognize the necessity of nurturing good moral character in their descendants. 3. Inspired by the historical story of Feng Xuan from the Warring States period in ancient China buying righteousness for Lord Mengchang, the financial tycoons controlling the United States relinquished a significant portion of their wealth. 4. The financial tycoons had understood the philosophical and Buddhist attributes of wealth and money. 5. Using quantum entanglement to identify politicians and members of wealthy families involved in the assassination of presidents does not require additional evidence. All implicated criminals must be sentenced to death. In cases where mentally ill individuals voluntarily commit murder, their caregivers and the forces behind the scenes must also be sentenced to death, and all assets of the criminals' families must be confiscated. Any country or armed force participating in the crackdown of criminals is entitled to a 25%

		<p>bonus from the confiscated assets of the criminals' families. This could potentially alleviate the financial crisis in the United States temporarily.</p> <p>6. Some tycoons and politicians like to kill and murder, especially those who hinder them from obtaining huge profits. As long as there are relevant murders anywhere in the world in the future, regardless of whether the victims perish, they will be thoroughly investigated through quantum entanglement, and all participants, behind-the-scene personalities, and masterminds will be publicly executed, with all assets of the masterminds, behind-the-scene personalities, all participants, and the families and clans of the murderers confiscated.</p> <p>In today's world, where the judicial system and moral ethics have regressed for 2,000-4,000 years, in an era where a missionary fabricates ancient Egyptian history, ancient European history, and the formation of civilizations, it is necessary to implement the judicial system of ancient China to effectively govern the country and the world. Those who contribute to punishing criminals, whether individuals, nations, or organizations, will collectively receive 25% of confiscated assets as a reward. The above income is tax-free.</p> <p>7. During an economic or financial crisis in the United States, the president, who attempted to reform American society and challenge the interests of powerful groups, is once again assassinated by a hired killer from these interest groups. However, the killer is depicted as mentally unstable, and these assassins once again meet seemingly accidental deaths. American citizens are outraged. Most soldiers in the military realize that the United States is controlled by interest groups; they are not serving the country, but rather serving these controlling interest groups. Consequently, enraged citizens, armed with powerful military equipment, organized themselves akin to Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义) at the end of the Tang Dynasty, eliminating all members of interest groups controlling the United States and then redistribute the country's land and assets.</p> <p>In addition, they need to be aware of the necessity and urgency highlighted by the author of this article in another piece on the establishment of hundreds of United Nations conventions and global consensus to address relevant challenging issues and maintain world peace. [Liu, L. (2023). Long-term poverty, discrimination, drugs, civil war, fraud, kidnapping organ harvesting, and massacre in Myanmar: peaceful solutions. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10994559]</p>
		<p>The West and Japan have relied on waging wars to plunder China's wealth for enrichment, but this has become history. China's military strength is now no less than that of the West, possessing the power to uphold justice. If the West and Japan persist in such actions, Western countries will rapidly disintegrate, and Japan will face destruction. Many evil tycoons and politicians will be wiped out.</p> <p>The West has led the world for more than 300 years, plagiarizing and stealing Chinese culture and technology, systematically fabricating false</p>

African and European histories, and forming philosophies and religions with significant flaws. They have never established their nations on the basis of morality and ethics, nor have they cultivated a political and national culture, "be the first to worry about the affairs of the state and the people, and the last to enjoy oneself", the fundamental purpose of education. Instead, they cultivate politicians at the presidential level who openly teach and spread misinformation at world-renowned universities, deceive other nations, disrupt their public opinion, and cause ideological confusion among the population. This is all in pursuit of the maximum plundering of other countries' wealth, without the slightest sense of shame. University students also feel no shame or evil in this. How can a society ruled by such thoughts not lead to continuous human conflicts, various crises, and endless wars, plunging humanity into unsolvable misery?

If current human society does not want to fall into this dilemma, Western society must recognize that European missionaries have systematically fabricated false African and European history and civilization. They must quickly revise the fictional history of Africa and Europe. They must change the educational model of Western society, gradually cultivate and improve the moral level of children and students. Take "be the first to worry about the affairs of the state and the people, and the last to enjoy oneself" as the standard, cultivate excellent political, military, and management talents, change pure utilitarian thinking, severely punish evil forces, and then gradually implement the improved version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. Only in this way can human society be freed from the dilemma and move towards long-term peace.

Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises. They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.

If the United States and Western societies genuinely wish to prevent the world from falling into increasing wars and conflicts, it is necessary to adopt a compensation system based on Mao Zedong's thought for politicians and tycoons who formulate erroneous policies. This system would remove incompetent and evil politicians from the national governance structure and strip the malevolent tycoons, who control the government and make bad

	<p>decisions, of all their wealth. Once widely implemented, this method will be far more effective than the Nobel Peace Prize in achieving world peace more effectively and quickly.</p>
	<p>U.S. politicians and the U.S. military should clearly realize that if Marshal Stalin had not been shortsighted and overly selfish during the Korean War, and provided the Chinese Volunteer Army with weapons and equipment for each division up to half the level of the Soviet Army at the beginning of the conflict, at least five U.S. divisions would have been annihilated at that time. American politicians should stop clamoring every day about arming Taiwan and deliberately trying to split China, finding joy in doing evil after being well-fed. Please remember, the US military, that today's Chinese military equipment is on par with that of the US military.</p> <p>The world today lacks morals and ethics, with continuous crime and conflict under the leadership of the United States and Europe. This world needs restructuring, and the justice system needs to be replaced.</p> <p>If the U.S. were to really go to war with China, China's strategy might be different from before. China might approach it like playing a game, first inviting netizens worldwide to list the top 200-300 financial oligarch families controlling and influencing the U.S., and then collaborating with Russia to eliminate them using thermobaric bombs. Next, they would invite netizens to list the top 600 politicians controlling the U.S., and once Russia eliminates the top 50-100 of them, the war would be almost over. Most Americans are aware that the U.S. is controlled by oligarchs, and once these oligarchs disappear, the redistribution of interests will begin. The morale of the U.S. military has long been shaken, and soldiers are just waiting for the right moment. The remaining US politicians and oligarchs are likely to be dealt with by a coalition of the U.S. military, the National Guard, and the American people, who would then collectively redistribute the assets left by the oligarchs.</p> <p>If any American politician doesn't want to live any longer, they decide to drop a nuclear bomb. There is probably not a family of global tycoons and politicians who can survive.</p>

Ref. The population of farmers in our country. March 24, 2023.
<https://wen.baidu.com/question/2020789184967425628.html>

Fig. 231-01. The preserved Washington upper and lower dentures come from black people. 2022-12-12.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1751967048970600900&wfr=spider&for=pc>

2. 纽约联储的激励机制

美联储是个特殊的金融机构，它一再声明自己不是政府部门，不依靠纳税人税金维持运行，也不需要受到政府的调遣和换届的左右，在行动决策上有其独立自主性。同时，它又依靠其中央银行的垄断地位，通过持有政府债券而获得丰厚的利息收入，通过为金融机构提供支付和清算服务而获得巨额的手续费，每年早涝保收，绰绰有余（第三章的第三节有具体数字说明）。美联储不仅上交国库数亿盈余，还免费提供辖内银行的检查监管，免费为其他国家保管金条、金块，在培训检查员方面也不遗余力、不计成本，还免费提供很多社区服务项目，诸如大、中、小学和金融、经济和政策的课程。

美联储存在的合理性取决于《联邦储备法》，它听命于国会，本着为大众百姓服务的非营利目的，再加上取之不尽、用之不竭的雄厚资金，就使它有别于一般的企业。一般企业是以利润为挂帅，适者生存，亏本了就要破产倒闭，盈利低的也要遭受兼并吞噬的威胁。企业的中心任务就是围绕这一点，谁能为企业带来利润，谁就是龙头老大，有发言权和决策权，这是黑白分明的考核指标。而纽约联储/美联储的特殊性，也就决定了它独特的激励机制和风险意识。

纽约联储支付给职员的工资薪金，在整个美联储系统是最高的。纽约地区生活消费水平高是一大原因；身处华尔街金融中心，对人才争夺不惜代价，也使得纽约联储相应地要提升工资，留住人才。同时，因为纽约联储上交美联储盈余最多，也使得它有较大的自主权。纽约联储总裁的工资（二十多万）就要比美联储主席的（十多万）高出一倍，纽约联储拥有的豪华轿车也比总部要多。当然，纽约联储也不能做得太过分，以免联储银行间差异太大，难以摆平，还有损联储非营利机构的光辉形象。

即便纽约联储已是做得相当力所能及了，但身处华尔街中心，每天在钱堆里摸爬滚打，耳濡目染，纽约联储的工资薪金，同华尔街比起来还是捉襟见肘。相似的学历、经历和能力，在商业界的工资比纽约联储高出最起码 30%。而且，随着金融业的突飞猛进，华尔街越来越舍得一掷千金雇用最优秀的人才，它的总体工资水平同纽约联储的距离越拉越大，靠工资薪金来吸引挽留人才，纽约联储是打赤脚都赶不上的。

所以，纽约联储便想出种种奇奇妙妙的点子，在福利方面“曲线救国”。其中最

Fig. 231-1. The following is the English translation of the screenshot section of the book.

The Federal Reserve is a special financial institution. It repeatedly declares itself as not a government entity, not relying on taxpayer funds for its operations, and not subject to government directives or changes in leadership. It operates independently in its actions and decisions. At the same time, it relies on its monopoly position as a central bank to generate substantial interest income through holding government bonds and to accrue significant fees by providing payment and clearing services to

financial institutions. It consistently generates surplus income year after year, as detailed in Chapter Three, Section Three. Not only does the Federal Reserve contribute hundreds of millions of dollars in surplus to the Treasury annually, but it also provides free inspection and supervision for banks within its jurisdiction. It offers free custody of gold bars and bullion for other countries and spares no effort or expense in training inspectors. Additionally, it provides numerous community service projects free of charge, such as financial, economic, and policy education courses for schools at all levels.

"I Supervise Banks at the Federal Reserve" 《我在美联储监管银行》 (Lu Jing, China Marketing Communication Network, 2007-11-15); [Lu Jing, I Supervise Banks at the Federal Reserve.p154, 2007, Beijing, Tsinghua University Press. 2007年, 清华大学出版社]

Fig. 231-2. [Book: Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007年]

The book "货币战争 Currency War" might be available for borrowing at some university libraries in the United States, and the paperback version of the book can be purchased

on online shopping websites. The fastest delivery usually takes about 4-5 days to reach some cities in the United States.

The chapters on "Currency War" are as follows:

Chapter One: The Rothschild Family – Europe's Singular Power

1.1 Napoleon's Waterloo and Rothschild's Triumphal Arch

1.2 The Era of Rothschild's Rise

1.3 The First Fortune of the Rothschilds

1.4 Nathan Dominates the City of London

1.5 James Conquers France

1.6 Solomon Aims for Austria

1.7 Germany and Italy Under the Rothschild Coat of Arms

1.8 The Rothschild Financial Empire

1.9 Summary of Chapter One

Chapter Two: The Century-Long War Between International Bankers and American Presidents

2.1 The Assassination of President Lincoln

2.2 Monetary Issuance and the American Revolutionary War

2.3 International Bankers' First War: The First Bank of the United States (1791-1811)

2.4 International Bankers Resurge: The Second Bank of the United States (1816-1832)

2.5 "The Bank wants to kill me, but I will kill the Bank."

2.6 A New Front: The Independent Financial System

2.7 International Bankers Strike Again: The Panic of 1857

2.8 The Causes of the American Civil War: European International Financial Power

2.9 Lincoln's Currency Revolution

2.10 Lincoln's Alliance with Russia

2.11 Who was the Real Assassin of Lincoln

2.12 Deadly Compromise: The National Banking Act of 1863

2.13 Summary of Chapter Two

Chapter Three: The Federal Reserve – A Private Central Bank

3.1 The Mysterious Jekyll Island: Birthplace of the Federal Reserve

3.2 The Wall Street Seven Titans: Behind-the-Scenes Drivers of the Federal Reserve

3.3 The Prelude to Establishing the Federal Reserve: The 1907 Banking Crisis

3.4 From Gold Standard to Fiat Currency: The Major Shift in Banking Worldview

3.5 The Smoke of the 1912 Election

3.6 Plan B

3.7 The Passage of the Federal Reserve Act, Bankers' Dream Come True

3.8 Who Owns the Federal Reserve

3.9 The First Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve

3.10 The Unknown Federal Advisory Council

3.11 Where is the Truth?

3.12 Conclusion

Chapter Four: "The Great War" and the Great Depression: Harvest Time for International Bankers

4.1 Without the Federal Reserve, There Would Be No World War I

- 4.2 War-Time Federal Reserve under Strong's Manipulation
- 4.3 "For Democracy and Moral Principles," Wilson Enters the War
- 4.4 Bankers Profiteering from the War
- 4.5 The Treaty of Versailles: A 20-Year Truce
- 4.6 "Shearing the Sheep" and the U.S. Agricultural Recession of 1921
- 4.7 The International Bankers' Conspiracy of 1927
- 4.8 The Bursting of the 1929 Bubble: Another Round of "Shearing the Sheep"
- 4.9 The Real Scheme behind Planning the Great Depression
- 4.10 Conclusion
- Chapter Five: The "New Deal" of Cheap Currency
- 5.1 Keynes's "Cheap Currency"
- 5.2 The Presidential Election of 1932
- 5.3 Who was Franklin D. Roosevelt
- 5.4 Abandoning the Gold Standard: The Historical Mission Given to Roosevelt by Bankers
- 5.5 "Venture Capital" Chooses Hitler
- 5.6 Nazi Germany Sponsored by Wall Street
- 5.7 Expensive Wars and Cheap Currency
- 5.8 Conclusion
- Chapter Six: The Elite Club that Rules the World
- 6.1 "Godfather" House, Colonel
- 6.2 The Bank for International Settlements: The Bank of Central Bankers
- 6.3 International Monetary Fund and World Bank
- 6.4 The Elite Group that Rules the World
- 6.5 The Bilderberg Group
- 6.6 The Trilateral Commission
- 6.7 Conclusion
- Chapter Seven: The Final Struggle of Honest Currency
- 7.1 Executive Order 11110: Kennedy's Death Warrant
- 7.2 The Historical Status of Silver Dollars
- 7.3 The End of the Gold Standard
- 7.4 The Gold Pool
- 7.5 Special Drawing Rights
- 7.6 The Total Assault on the Gold Standard
- 7.7 "Economic Hitmen" and the Return of Petrodollars
- 7.8 Reagan's Assassination: The Last Hope of Shattering the Gold Standard
- 7.9 Conclusion
- Chapter 8: The Unannounced Currency War
- 8.1 The 1973 Middle East War: The Dollar's Counterattack
- 8.2 Paul Volcker: The "Controlled Disintegration" of the World Economy
- 8.3 The World Environmental Bank: Aiming to Enclose 30% of the Earth's Land
- 8.4 Financial Nuclear Bomb: Target Tokyo
- 8.5 Soros: Financial Hacker of International Bankers
- 8.6 The "Arc of Crisis" Attacking European Currencies

- 8.7 The Asian Currency Strangulation War
 - 8.8 A Parable of China's Future
 - 8.9 Conclusion
- Chapter 9: The Dollar's Achilles' Heel and the Gold One-Yang Finger
- 9.1 Partial Reserve System: The Source of Inflation
 - 9.2 How Debt Dollars Are "Forged"
 - 9.3 America's "Debt Mountain" and Asia's "IOUs"
 - 9.4 The Monopoly Business of Financial Derivatives Markets
 - 9.5 Government-Sanctioned Entities: "The Second Fed"
 - 9.6 The Currency King Under House Arrest
 - 9.7 Level One Alert: Rothschild's Withdrawal from Gold Pricing in 2004
 - 9.8 The Achilles' Heel of the Dollar Bubble Economy
 - 9.9 Conclusion
- Chapter 10: Plotters for Eternity
- 10.1 Currency: The Yardstick of the Economic World
 - 10.2 Gold and Silver: The Anchors in Price Turbulence
 - 10.3 Debt Currency Fat and GDP Slimming
 - 10.4 Finance Industry: The "Strategic Air Force" of China's Economic Development
 - 10.5 Future Strategies of Chinese Finance: "Build High Walls, Accumulate Grain Widely, and Delay Assuming Kingship"
 - 10.6 On the Road to Becoming the World's Reserve Currency
 - 10.7 Conclusion
- Afterword: Some Thoughts on China's Financial Opening
- 11.1 The Greatest Risk of China's Financial Opening Is the Lack of "War" Consciousness
 - 11.2 Sovereignty or Stability: Which is More Important for Currency?
 - 11.3 Currency Appreciation and "Endocrine Disorders" in the Financial System
 - 11.4 External Line Operations Under Equitable Opening
 - 11.5 Avoiding Exchange Controls by the People is Better than Avoiding Gold by the People
- Attachment: US Debt Implosion and Global Liquidity Contraction
- 12.1 Crisis Redux
 - 12.2 Asset Securitization and Excessive Liquidity
 - 12.3 Subprime and ALT-A Mortgages: Toxic Assets
 - 12.4 Subprime Mortgage CDOs: Concentrated Toxic Assets
 - 12.5 "Synthetic CDOs": High-Purity Concentrated Toxic Assets
 - 12.6 Asset Rating Agencies: Accomplices in Fraud
 - 12.7 Debt Implosion and Liquidity Contraction
 - 12.8 The Future of the World Financial Markets

刺杀林肯总统

1865年4月14日星期五晚上，在艰难困苦和重重危机中度过了四年残酷内战的林肯总统，终于在五天前迎来了南军将领罗伯特·李将军向北方格兰特将军投降的胜利消息，总统高度紧张的神经一下子松弛下来，兴致颇高地来到华盛顿的福特剧院看表演。10点15分，凶手潜入没有守卫的总统包厢，在距离林肯不到两英尺的后方，用一把大口径手枪向总统的头部开枪，林肯中弹后倒向前方。第二天凌晨，林肯总统去世。

凶手是一个名叫布斯 (John Wilkes Booth) 的颇有名气的演员。他在刺杀林肯之后仓皇出逃，据说4月26日凶手在逃亡途中被击毙。在凶手的马车里，发现了很多用密码写成的信件和一些犹太·本杰明的私人物品，这

↑ 林肯遇刺
(来源：维基百科)

个犹太人是当时南方政府的战争部长和后来的国务卿，也是南方金融方面的实权人物，因为他和欧洲的大银行家们过从甚密。他后来逃到了英国。刺杀林肯事件被广泛认为是一个大规模的阴谋。参与阴谋的可能有林肯的内阁成员、纽约和费城的银行家、南方的政府高官、纽约的报纸出版商和北方的激进分子。

当时流传甚广的一个说法是，布斯并没有被杀死，而是被放走了，

Fig. 231-3. On the evening of Friday, April 14, 1865, after enduring four years of grueling Civil War and numerous crises, President Lincoln, who had received news of Confederate General Robert E. Lee's surrender to General Grant just five days prior, finally relaxed his highly tense nerves and enthusiastically attended a performance at Ford's Theatre in Washington. At 10:15 p.m., the assassin crept into the unguarded

presidential box, positioned himself less than two feet behind Lincoln, and fired a large-caliber pistol at the president's head, causing Lincoln to slump forward after being struck by the bullet. The following morning, President Lincoln passed away.

The assassin was a well-known actor named John Wilkes Booth. After assassinating Lincoln, he fled in haste and was reportedly shot dead while on the run on April 26. In the assassin's carriage, numerous letters written in code and some personal belongings of Judah Benjamin were found. This Judah was the former Confederate Secretary of War and later Secretary of State, as well as a significant figure in Southern finance due to his close ties to European bankers. He later fled to England. The assassination of Lincoln was widely believed to be part of a large-scale conspiracy involving members of Lincoln's cabinet, bankers from New York and Philadelphia, high-ranking officials of the Southern government, publishers of New York newspapers, and radicals from the North.

A widely circulated theory at the time was that Booth was not killed but rather released, and the body buried was that of one of his accomplices. The truth was covered up by the powerful Secretary of War, Edwin Stanton. At first glance, this might seem like another absurd conspiracy theory. However, when a large number of secret documents held by the Secretary of War were declassified in the mid-1930s, historians were astonished to find that the truth closely matched folklore.

The first to delve into these astounding materials was historian Otto Eisenschiml, whose publication "Why was Lincoln Murdered?" rocked the historical community. Later, Theodore Roscoe published even more widely influential research results, pointing out that much of the 19th-century historical research on Lincoln's assassination reads more like a grand opera tragedy at Ford's Theatre... Few saw it as a murder: Lincoln died at the hands of a reckless criminal... The criminal received due legal punishment; the conspiracy was suppressed; virtue ultimately triumphed, and Lincoln was "a thing of the past."

However, the explanations for the assassination neither satisfy nor convince. The facts indicate that the relevant criminals in Lincoln's death had long evaded justice.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p27, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

后来埋葬的尸体是他同谋的。当时手握重权的战争部长埃德温·斯坦顿 (Edwin Stanton) 掩盖了事实真相。乍听之下，这又是一个荒谬的阴谋论说法。但是，当战争部长的大量秘密文件到20世纪30年代中期被解密之后，历史学家吃惊地发现，真相竟和民间传说高度吻合。

第一个深入研究这些惊人史料的是历史学家奥托·爱森斯默 (Otto Eisenschiml)，他发表的《为什么林肯被刺杀？》震动了当时的史学界。后来，西奥多·罗斯科 (Theodore Roscoe) 出版了影响更广泛的研究结果，他指出：

19世纪大量有关刺杀林肯事件的历史研究，对福特剧院的悲剧描述更像是在展示一部大型歌剧……只有少数人将其作为一个谋杀事件来看待：林肯死于一个鲁莽的罪犯手中……罪犯得到了经典的法律惩罚；阴谋论被扼杀了；美德最终取得了胜利，林肯也“属于过去”了。

但是，刺杀事件的解释既不能使人满意也难以令人信服。事实表明，林肯之死的相关罪犯一直逍遥法外。^[2]

凶手的孙女伊左拉 (Izola Forrester) 在她的回忆录《这个疯狂的行动》(This One Mad Act) 中提到，她发现“金色圆圈骑士” (Knights of the Golden Circle) 的秘密记录被政府小心地收藏在一个文件库里，并被战争部长埃德温·斯坦顿列为机密材料。林肯遇刺后，任何人都不允许接触这些文件。由于伊左拉与布斯血缘关系，以及她作为专业作家的身份，她最终成为第一个获准查阅这些材料的学者。她在书中说道：

这些神秘的旧文件包，被隐藏在存放“阴谋审判”的遗迹和展览的房间角落的一个保险箱里。如果不是五年前，我偶然跪在（那个房间的）地上翻阅资料时看到了保险箱的一侧，我可能永远都不会发现它们（秘密文件）。

这里（的文件）与我祖父有关。我知道他曾是一个秘密组织的成员，这个组织就是由比克利 (Bickley) 建立的“金色圆圈骑士”。

Fig. 231-4. The assassin's granddaughter, Izola Forrester, mentioned in her memoir "This One Mad Act" that she discovered the secret records of the Knights of the Golden Circle carefully hidden by the government in a vault and classified as confidential by Secretary of War Edwin Stanton. After Lincoln's assassination, access to these documents was denied to anyone. Due to Izola's familial connection to Booth and her status as a professional writer, she ultimately became the first scholar granted access to these materials. She wrote in her book:

"These mysterious old document pouches were concealed in a safe tucked away in a corner of the room housing remnants and exhibits of the 'conspiracy trial'. Had I not chanced to kneel down five years ago and observed one side of the safe while rummaging through the material on the floor, I might never have found them (the secret documents).

They (the documents) pertained to my grandfather. I knew he had been a member of a secret organization, which was the Knights of the Golden Circle established by Bickley. I have a photograph of him (grandfather) taken with them, all in full uniform, which I found in my grandmother's Bible... I recall my grandmother saying that her husband (Booth) was 'a tool of others'.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p28, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

我有一张他（祖父）的照片，是和他们一起照的，他们全都穿着全套的制服，这张照片是从我祖母的《圣经》中发现的……我还记得祖母曾说过她的丈夫（布斯）是“别人的工具”。^[3]

“金色圆圈骑士”和纽约的金融势力到底是什么样的关系？林肯政府内部有多少人卷入了刺杀林肯的阴谋？对林肯遇刺的研究怎么会长期系统地偏离正确方向？林肯的遇刺和一百年后的肯尼迪遇刺颇为相似，同样都是大规模的组织协调，全方位的证据封杀，系统性的调查误导，真相始终隐藏在一片浓厚的历史迷雾之中。

要理解刺杀林肯的真正动机和图谋，我们必须以更大的历史纵深来审视美国立国以来，民选政府和金钱权力在控制货币发行权这一国家战略制高点上的反复与殊死较量。

货币发行权与美国独立战争

有关美国独立战争的起源分析的历史课本，比较多地采取了全面地和抽象地论述大的原则和意义的方式。在这里我们将从另一个视角，去阐述这场革命的金融背景及其所起到的核心作用。

最早到美洲大陆谋生的人大多是非常穷困的贫民，他们除了随身的简单行李，几乎没有什么财产和金钱。当时的北美还没有发现大型的金矿和银矿，所以在市场上流通的货币极为短缺。加之与母国英国的严重贸易逆差使得大量金银货币流向英国，更加剧了流通货币的稀缺^[4]。

北美的新移民通过辛勤的劳动所创造出来的大量产品和服务，由于流通货币短缺而无法进行充分和有效的交换，从而严重地制约了经济的进一步发展。为了应对这个难题，人们不得不使用各种替代货币进行商品交易。诸如动物的皮毛、贝壳、烟草、大米、小麦、玉米等接受程度较高的物品被各地用来当钱使。仅在北卡罗来纳州，1715年时就有多达17种不同的物品被当做法定货币（Legal Tender），政府和民间可用这些物品进行税务缴纳、公私债务偿还和商品服务买卖。当时所有这一切替

Fig. 231-5. What was the relationship between the Knights of the Golden Circle and the financial powers of New York? How many people within the Lincoln government were involved in the conspiracy to assassinate him? Why has the research into Lincoln's assassination long been systematically diverted in the right direction? Lincoln's assassination bears striking similarities to that of Kennedy a hundred years later: both were coordinated by large-scale organizations, evidence was suppressed on all fronts, investigations were systematically misled, and the truth remained shrouded in a thick historical fog.

To understand the true motives and conspiracies behind Lincoln's assassination, we must examine the repeated and desperate struggles between elected governments and financial powers for control over the issuance of currency, a strategic pinnade in the nation's history since its inception."

2.2 Currency Issuance Rights and the American Revolutionary War

Textbooks analyzing the origins of the American Revolutionary War often take a comprehensive and abstract approach to discussing the overarching principles and significance of the event. Here, we will elucidate the financial backdrop of this revolution and its pivotal role.

Most of the earliest settlers in the American continent were extremely impoverished, possessing little property or money besides basic belongings. At the time, large-scale gold and silver mines had not yet been discovered in North America, resulting in a severe shortage of currency in circulation. Additionally, the significant trade deficit with the mother country, Britain, led to a massive outflow of gold and silver currency to Britain, exacerbating the scarcity of circulating currency.

Immigrants in North America, through diligent labor, produced a large quantity of goods and services. However, due to the shortage of circulating currency, they were unable to engage in sufficient and effective exchange, severely restricting further economic development. To cope with this difficulty, people had to resort to various substitute currencies for trading goods. Items such as animal furs, shells, tobacco, rice, wheat, and corn, which were widely accepted, were used as money in various regions. In North Carolina alone, as many as 17 different items were designated as legal tender in 1715, accepted by both the government and private individuals for tax payment, debt repayment, and the buying and selling of goods and services. All these substitute currencies were pegged to the pound sterling or shilling as the accounting standard. However, in practice, these items varied significantly in quality, specification, acceptability, and durability, making standard measurement difficult. While they alleviated the immediate need for currency to some extent, they still constituted a significant bottleneck to the development of the commodity economy.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p29, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007.
Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

代货币都以英镑、先令作为会计结算标准。在实际运作中，这些物品由于成色、规格、接受度和可保存性都相差很大，难以进行标准计量，所以虽然在一定程度上缓解了没有货币的燃眉之急，但仍然构成了商品经济发展的重要瓶颈。^[5]

长期的金属货币奇缺和替代实物货币应用的不便，促使当地政府跳出传统思维，开始了一种崭新的尝试，那就是由政府印刷和发行纸币 (Colonial Script) 来作为统一和标准的法币。这种纸币和欧洲流行的银行券最大的区别就是，它没有任何金银实物做抵押，是一种完全由政府信用货币。社会上的所有人都需要向政府交税，而只要政府接受这种纸币作为缴税的凭证，它便具备了在市场上流通的基本要素。

新的货币果然大大地促进了社会经济的迅速发展，商品贸易日趋繁荣。

与此同时，英国的亚当·斯密也注意到了北美殖民地政府这一新的货币尝试，他相当清楚这种纸币所带来的对商业的巨大刺激作用，特别是对于缺少金属货币的北美地区，“基于信用的买和卖，使得商家可以每月或每年定期结算相互之间的信用余额，这将减少（交易的）不便。一个管理良好的纸币系统，不仅不会产生任何不便，甚至可以在某些情况下拥有更多的优势”。^[6]

但是，一种没有抵押的货币是银行家的天敌，因为没有政府债务做抵押，政府就不需要向银行借当时最为稀缺的金属货币，银行家手上最大的砝码一下子就失去了威力。

当本杰明·富兰克林在1763年访问英国时，英格兰银行的主管问他新大陆的殖民地如此兴旺发达的原因，富兰克林回答：“这很简单。在殖民地，我们发行自己的货币，名叫‘殖民券’。我们按照商业和工业的需要来发行等比例的货币，这样，产品就很容易地从生产者那里传递到消费者手中。用这种方式创造我们自己的纸货币，并保证它的购买力，我们（政府）不需要向任何人支付利息。”^[7]

这种新的纸货币必然会导致美洲殖民地脱离英格兰银行的控制。

愤怒的英国银行家们立刻行动起来，在他们控制之下的英国议会于1764年通过《货币法案》(Currency Act)，严厉禁止美洲殖民地各州印

Fig. 231-6. The long-term scarcity of metallic currency and the inconvenience of using substitute physical currency prompted local governments to break away from traditional thinking and embark on a new experiment: printing and issuing paper currency (Colonial Script) as a uniform and standard legal tender. The most significant

difference between this paper currency and the banknotes popular in Europe was that it was not backed by any gold or silver reserves; it was a purely government credit currency. Everyone in society needed to pay taxes to the government, and as long as the government accepted this paper currency as proof of tax payment, it possessed the basic elements for circulation in the market.

The new currency indeed greatly promoted the rapid development of the socio-economic situation, and commodity trading flourished day by day.

At the same time, Adam Smith in Britain also took note of this new currency experiment by the colonial governments. He was quite aware of the tremendous stimulating effect of this paper currency on trade, especially for the North American region lacking metallic currency. "Credit-based buying and selling allow merchants to settle credit balances with each other regularly, either monthly or annually, reducing transaction inconvenience. A well-governed paper currency system not only does not generate any inconvenience, but can even have more advantages in certain cases."

However, a currency without collateral was the bane of bankers. Because there was no government debt to serve as collateral, the government did not need to borrow the then-scarce metallic currency from banks. The biggest leverage in the hands of bankers suddenly lost its power.

When Benjamin Franklin visited England in 1763, the director of the Bank of England asked him about the reason for the prosperity of the colonies in the New World. Franklin replied, "It is simple. In the colonies, we issue our own currency called the colonial scrip. We issue a proportional amount of currency according to the needs of trade and industry, thus facilitating the easy transfer of goods from producers to consumers. By creating our own paper currency in this manner and ensuring its purchasing power, we (the government) do not need to pay interest to anyone."

This new paper currency would inevitably lead to the American colonies breaking away from the control of the Bank of England.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p30, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

发自己的纸币，并强迫当地政府必须使用黄金和白银来支付全部向英国政府缴纳的税收。

富兰克林痛苦地描述这个法案给殖民地各州带来的严重经济后果，“只一年的时间，（殖民地的）情况就完全逆转了，繁荣时代结束了，经济严重衰退到大街小巷都站满了失业的人群。”^[8]

“如果英格兰不剥夺殖民地的发币权，殖民地人民是乐意支付茶叶和其他商品作为额外的少量税赋的。这个法案造成了失业和不满。殖民地不能发行自己的货币，从而将无法永久地摆脱国王乔治三世和国际银行家的控制，这是美国独立战争爆发最主要的原因。”^[9]

美国的开国奠基者们对于英格兰银行对英国政治的控制和对人民的不公有着相当清醒的认识。年仅33岁就完成了万古流芳的美国《独立宣言》的作者，也是美国第三届总统的托马斯·杰斐逊有一句警世名言：

如果美国人民最终让私有银行控制了国家的货币发行，那么这些银行将先是通过通货膨胀，然后是通货紧缩，来剥夺人民的财产，直到有一天早晨当他们的孩子们一觉醒来时，他们已经失去了自己的家园和父辈曾经开拓过的土地。^[10]

两百多年后再来聆听1791年杰斐逊的这一段话时，我们不禁惊叹他的预见惊人的准确。今天，美国私有银行果然发行了国家货币流通量的97%，美国人民也果然欠着银行44万亿美元的天文数字般的债务，他们也许真的有一天一觉醒来就会失去家园和财产，就像1929年发生过的一样。

当美利坚的伟大先驱们用他们智慧和深邃的目光审视着历史和未来时，他们在美国《宪法》第一章第八节开宗明义地写下：“国会拥有货币的制造和价值设定的权利。”^[11]

↑ 美国第三届总统
托马斯·杰斐逊
(来源：维基百科)

Fig. 231-7. Angry British bankers immediately took action, and the British Parliament, under their control, passed the Currency Act in 1764, severely prohibiting the various states of the American colonies from issuing their own paper money and forcing local governments to use gold and silver to pay all taxes to the British government.

Franklin painfully described the serious economic consequences that this act

brought to the colonies: "In just one year, the situation completely reversed, the era of prosperity ended, and the economy declined severely to the point where the streets were filled with unemployed people."

If England did not deprive the colonies of their right to issue currency, the colonial people would be willing to pay tea and other goods as additional taxes. This act caused unemployment and dissatisfaction. Colonies couldn't issue their own currency, thus unable to permanently escape the control of King George III and international bankers, which was the main reason for the outbreak of the American Revolutionary War.

The founding fathers of America were quite familiar with the control of English banks over British politics and the injustice to the people. Thomas Jefferson, who completed the immortal American Declaration of Independence at the age of only 33 and also served as the third president of the United States, has a famous saying:

"If the American people ever allow private banks to control the issue of their currency, first by inflation, then by deflation, the banks and corporations that will grow up around them will deprive the people of all property until their children wake up homeless on the continent their fathers conquered."

More than two hundred years later, when we hear these words of Jefferson from 1791, we cannot help but admire his astonishing foresight. Today, indeed, private banks in America issue 97% of the nation's currency in circulation, and the American people owe banks astronomical debts of \$34 trillion. Perhaps one day they will indeed wake up to find themselves homeless and devoid of property, just as happened in 1929.

When the great pioneers of America scrutinized history and the future with their intelligence and profound insight, they wrote unequivocally in the first section of Article I of the U.S. Constitution: "Congress shall have the power to coin money and to regulate the value thereof."

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p31, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

国际银行家的第一次战役： 美国第一银行（1791~1811）

我坚信银行机构对我们自由的威胁比敌人的军队更严重。他们已经创造出了一个金钱贵族阶级，并且藐视政府。（货币的）发行权应该从银行手中夺回来，它应该属于它正当的主人——人民。^[12]

托马斯·杰斐逊，1802年

亚历山大·汉密尔顿是一个与罗斯柴尔德家族有着密切联系的重量级人物。他出生在英属西印度群岛，在隐瞒了他的年龄、真名和出生地的情况下来到美国并与纽约望族的女儿成亲。大英博物馆收藏的付款收据显示，汉密尔顿接受过罗斯柴尔德家族的资助。^[13]

↑ 汉密尔顿
(来源：维基百科)

1789年，汉密尔顿被华盛顿总统任命为美国第一任财政部长，他始终是美国中央银行制度的主要推动者。1790年，面对独立战争之后严重的经济困境和债务危机，他强烈建议国会成立类似于英格兰银行的私有的中央银行，以彻底履行发行货币的职责。他的主要思路是：中央银行由私人拥有，总部设在费城，各地设立分支银行，政府的货币和税收必须放在这个银行系统中，该银行负责发行国家货币来满足经济发展的需要，向美国政府贷款并收取利息。该银行总股本为1 000万美元，私人拥有80%的股份，美国政府拥有剩余的20%。25人所组成的董事会中的20人由股东推举，5人由政府任命。

汉密尔顿代表着精英阶级的利益，他曾经指出：“所有的社会都分成极少数和大多数人群。前者出身良好而富有，后者则是普罗大众。大众是动荡和变化的，他们很少能做出正确的判断和决定。”

而杰斐逊则代表着人民大众的利益，对于汉密尔顿的观点，他的回应是：“我们认为下述真理是不言而喻的：人人生而平等，造物主赋予他们若干不可剥夺的权利，其中包括生存权、自由权和追求幸福的权利。”

Fig. 231-8. 2.3 The First War of International Bankers: The First Bank of the United States (1791-1811)

I firmly believe that the threat posed by banking institutions to our freedom is more severe than that of enemy armies. They created a moneyed aristocracy and disdain the government. The power of issuing currency should be taken back from the banks and rightfully belong to its masters—the people.

----- **Thomas Jefferson, 1802**

Alexander Hamilton was a prominent figure closely associated with the Rothschild family. Born in the British West Indies, he came to America and married into the wealthy Schuyler family of New York, concealing his age, true name, and birthplace. Payment receipts preserved in the British Museum show that Hamilton received support from the Rothschild family.

In 1789, Hamilton was appointed as the first Secretary of the Treasury by President Washington and remained a key advocate for the central banking system in the United States. In 1790, faced with severe economic hardship and debt crisis after the Revolutionary War, he strongly recommended that Congress to establish a private central bank similar to the Bank of England to fully fulfill the responsibility of issuing currency. His main idea was that: the central bank, owned by private individuals, headquartered in Philadelphia, with branch banks established throughout the country, government currency and taxes must be placed in this banking system, which is responsible for issuing national currency to meet the needs of economic development, lending to the U.S. government and charging interest. The total capital of the bank was \$10 million, with private individuals owning 80% of the shares, and the U.S. government owning the remaining 20%. Of the 25-member board of directors, 20 were elected by shareholders and 5 were appointed by the government.

Hamilton represented the interests of the elite class, once pointing out, "All communities divide themselves into the few and the many. The first are the rich and well-born; the other, the mass of the people. The voice of the people has been said to be the voice of God; and however generally this maxim has been quoted and believed, it is not true in fact. The people are turbulent and changing; they seldom judge or determine right."

Jefferson, on the other hand, represented the interests of the common people, and his response to Hamilton's views was, "We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights, that among these are Life, Liberty and the pursuit of Happiness." Regarding the issue of a private central bank system, the two sides were also diametrically opposed.

Hamilton believed, "If the private interests of wealthy individuals and credit were not concentrated in society, society would not succeed." "The national debt, if not excessive, will be to us a national blessing."

Jefferson countered, "A private central bank issuing the public currency is a greater menace to the freedom of the people than a standing army." "We must not let our rulers load us with perpetual debt."

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p32, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

在私有中央银行制度的问题上，双方也是针锋相对。

汉密尔顿认为，“如果不把社会上有钱的个人的利益和财富信用集中起来，这个社会不可能成功。”^[14]“国家的债务，如果不是过多，应该是我们国家的福祉。”^[15]

杰斐逊反驳道，“一个私有的中央银行发行人民的公共货币，这对人民自由的威胁比敌人的军队更严重。”^[16]“我们不能容忍统治者将永久债务强加在人民的身上。”^[17]

1791年12月，当汉密尔顿的方案被提交国会讨论时，立即引起了空前激烈的争论。最终，参议院以微弱多数通过了这项提案，而在众议院也以39对20票过关。此时，被严重的债务危机压得喘不过气的总统华盛顿陷入了深深的犹豫，他征询了当时的国务卿杰斐逊和麦迪逊的意见，他们明确表示这个提案明显与宪法冲突。宪法授权国会发行货币，但绝没有授权国会转让发币权给任何私人银行。华盛顿显然被深深地触动了，他甚至已决心要否决该法案。

得知这个消息后，汉密尔顿立刻跑来劝说华盛顿，财政部长汉密尔顿的账本似乎更有说服力，那就是如果不成立中央银行以得到外国资金投入，政府将很快垮台。最终，迫在眉睫的危机压倒了对未来长远的顾虑，华盛顿总统于1791年2月25日签署了美国第一个中央银行的授权，有效期20年。^[18]

国际银行家终于取得了第一个重大胜利。到1811年，外国资本占到了1 000万股本中的700万，英格兰银行和内森·罗斯柴尔德成为美国中央银行——美国第一银行（The First Bank of the United States）的主要股东。^[19]

汉密尔顿最终成为巨富。第一银行后来与亚伦·波成立的纽约曼哈顿公司成为了华尔街的第一家银行，它在1955年与洛克菲勒的大通银行合并成为大通曼哈顿银行（Chase Manhattan Bank）。

对金钱极度渴望的政府，与热烈期盼政府债务的私有中央银行一拍即合，从中央银行成立的1791年到1796年短短的五年时间里，美国政府的债务就增加了820万美元。

杰斐逊在1798年懊恼地说：“我真希望我们能增加哪怕一条宪法修正

Fig. 231-9. In December 1791, when Hamilton's plan was submitted to Congress for discussion, it immediately sparked unprecedented controversy. In the end, the proposal narrowly passed the Senate and also cleared the House by a vote of 39 to 20. At this time, President Washington, who was gasping for air under a severe debt crisis, was deeply hesitant. He sought the opinions of then-Secretary of State Jefferson and Madison, who clearly stated that the proposal was in direct conflict with the

Constitution. The Constitution authorized Congress to issue currency, but it did not authorize Congress to delegate the power of currency issuance to any private bank. Washington was evidently deeply moved and even determined to veto the bill.

Upon learning this, Hamilton immediately lobbied Washington. The persuasive argument from Hamilton, the Secretary of the Treasury, was that without establishing a central bank to attract foreign investment, the government would quickly collapse. Ultimately, the pressing crisis outweighed long-term concerns, and President Washington signed the authorization for the first central bank of the United States on February 25, 1791, with a 20-year term.

International bankers finally achieved their first major victory. By 1811, foreign capital accounted for 7 million out of 10 million shares. The Bank of England and Nathan Rothschild became the major shareholders of the First Bank of the United States.

Hamilton ultimately became immensely wealthy. The First Bank later merged with Aaron Burr's Manhattan Company to become the first bank on Wall Street. In 1955, it merged with Rockefeller's Chase Bank to become the Chase Manhattan Bank.

The government, hungry for money, found common cause with privately-owned central banks eager for government debt. In just five years from the establishment of the central bank in 1791 to 1796, the U.S. government's debt increased by \$8.2 million.

In 1798, Jefferson lamented, "I wish we could add just one amendment to the Constitution, canceling the federal government's power to borrow money."

After Jefferson was elected the third president of the United States (1801-1809), he made every effort to abolish the First Bank of the United States. By the time the bank's charter expired in 1811, the struggle between the two sides had reached a boiling point. The House of Representatives narrowly rejected the proposal to extend the bank's charter by a vote of 65 to 64, while the Senate tied at 17 to 17. Vice President George Clinton broke the deadlock by casting the crucial veto vote, and the First Bank of the United States closed its doors on March 3, 1811.

Upon hearing this news, Nathan Rothschild in London was furious, threatening, "Either extend the bank's charter, or America will face the most disastrous war." The U.S. government remained unmoved, to which Nathan immediately responded, "Give these unruly Americans a lesson and beat them back to colonial times."

As a result, a few months later, the War of 1812 broke out between Britain and America. The war lasted for three years, and Rothschild's objective was clear: to bankrupt the U.S. government. Ultimately, the U.S. government surrendered in 1815, and President Madison proposed the establishment of a second central bank on December 5, 1815. The result was the birth of the Second Bank of the United States in 1816.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p33-34, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

欧洲银行的大笔交易化整为零，交给自己在各地的“卫星银行”去办理，“卫星银行”为得到这些高回报的生意自然更加俯首帖耳，而五巨头也拥有这些小银行的股份。当这些“代表各自地区利益”的小银行们和五巨头坐在一处探讨美国货币政策的时候，探讨的结果也就可想而知。

尽管联邦咨询委员会的“建议”对美联储的董事决策没有强制约束力，但是华尔街五巨头每年四次不辞劳苦地跑到华盛顿，不会是仅仅为了和联储的几位董事喝喝咖啡。要知道，像摩根这样身兼63个公司的董事职务的超级大忙人，如果他们的“建议”得不到任何考虑，而他们仍然乐此不疲地来回奔波，那实在是奇怪之极了。

真相何在

绝大多数美国人并不真正理解国际放贷者的运作方式。美联储的账目从来就没有被审计过。它完全在国会控制的范围之外运作，它操纵着美国的信用（供应）。

参议员巴里·戈德华特

为了制造高价格，美联储只需要降低利率，来扩张信用和造就一个繁荣的股市。当工商业已经习惯了这样的利率环境之后，美联储又将通过任意提高利息来中止这种繁荣。

它（美联储和拥有美联储的银行家们）可以通过轻微调息使市场的价格钟摆般温柔地起伏，也可以猛烈调息来使市场价格剧烈波动，无论哪种情况，它将拥有金融状况的内部信息，事先得知即将到来的变化。

这是一种任何政府从未给予的，少数特权阶层所拥有的最怪异和最危险的（市场信息）先知权。

这个系统是私有的，它运作的全部目的就是利用别人的金钱来获得最大限度的利润。

他们事先知道什么时候制造恐慌来创造对他们最有利的情况。他们同样知道什么时候停止恐慌。当他们控制了金融的时候，通货

Fig. 231-10. [Book: Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p82, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007年]

Most Americans don't truly understand how international lenders operate. The Federal Reserve's accounts have never been audited. It operates entirely outside the control of Congress, manipulating America's credit supply.

— Senator Barry Goldwater

To create high prices, the Fed only needs to lower interest rates to expand credit and foster a booming stock market. Once businesses are accustomed to this rate environment, the Fed will halt this prosperity by arbitrarily raising interest rates. It (the Fed and the bankers who own it) can gently sway market prices by slightly

adjusting interest rates, or violently fluctuate them by aggressively adjusting rates. In either case, it possesses insider information about financial conditions, knowing in advance of impending changes. This is the strangest and most dangerous form of insider trading, a privilege not granted by any government but held by a select few. This system is private, operating solely to maximize profits using others' money. They know when to create panic to create the most advantageous situation for themselves and when to stop the panic. When they control finance, both inflation and deflation are equally effective in achieving their goals.

— **Congressman Charles Lindbergh**

Every Federal Reserve Note (US dollar) in circulation represents a debt owed to the Federal Reserve of one dollar. — Monetary Report, House Banking and Currency Committee Federal Reserve Banks are not government agencies but independent, privately owned, and locally controlled corporations.

Case: Lewis v. United States, Ninth Circuit Court, 1982

The Federal Reserve is one of the most corrupt institutions in the world. Everyone who can hear me speak (Congressional speech) knows that our country is actually ruled by international bankers. Some people think that Federal Reserve Banks are government institutions. They are not government institutions. They are private credit monopolists, exploiting the American people for their own and foreign fraudsters' benefit.

— **Congressman Mike Padden**

When you and I write checks, there must be enough money in our accounts to cover the amount of the check. However, when the Federal Reserve writes a check, there is no money in the account to support it. When the Federal Reserve writes a check, it is creating money.

— **Boston Federal Reserve Bank**

From 1913 to 1949, the assets of the Federal Reserve soared from \$ 0.143 billion to \$45 billion, directly lining the pockets of the Fed's bank shareholders.

— **Estes Kefauver**

So many presidents have repeatedly warned against the power of money, and so many congressional records and legal cases unmistakably indicate the private nature of the Federal Reserve, yet how many Americans, Chinese, and people of other countries know this? That's the terrifying aspect of the issue! We assume that the "free and fair" Western authoritative news media will report all truths, but the truth is that a vast amount of facts is deliberately "filtered" out by them. What about American textbooks? The fact is, various foundations named after international bankers are selecting "content-healthy" textbooks for America's next generation.

膨胀和通货紧缩在实现他们的目的方面同样有效率。

众议员查尔斯·林德伯格

每一元流通中的美联储券 (Federal Reserve Note, 美元) 都代表欠着美联储一美元的债务。

货币报告, 众院银行与货币委员会

美联储地区银行不是政府机构, 而是独立的, 私人拥有的和地方控制的公司。

案例: 勒维斯vs美国政府, 第九巡回法庭, 1982年

美联储是世界上最为腐败的机构之一。所有能听见我讲话 (国会演讲) 的人, 没有一个人不知道我们的国家实际上是被国际银行家统治着。

有些人以为美联储银行是美国政府的机构。它们 (美联储银行) 不是政府机构。它们是私有的信贷垄断者, 美联储为了自己和外国骗子的利益盘剥着美国人民。

众议员麦克法登

当你和我写支票的时候, 我们的账户上必须要有足够的钱来支撑支票的金额。但是, 当美联储写支票时, 账户上是没有任何钱做支撑的。当美联储写支票时, 它是在创造货币。

波士顿美联储银行

从1913年到1949年, 美联储的资产由1.43亿美元暴涨到450亿美元, 这些钱直接进了美联储银行股东们的腰包。

埃斯塔克·穆林斯

如此众多的总统对金钱权力的威胁反复发出过警告, 如此大量的国会记录和法律案例明白无误地说明了美联储的私有性质, 可是有多少美

Fig. 231-11. [Book: Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p83, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007年]

国人、中国人和其他国家的人知道这一点呢？这才是问题的可怕之处！我们以为“自由公正”的西方权威新闻媒体会报道一切真相，原来真相是大量的事实被它们有意地“过滤”掉了。那么美国的教科书呢？事实是，各种以国际银行家们的名字命名的基金会，在为美国的下一代挑选着“内容健康”的教科书。

在威尔逊总统去世之前，他承认自己在美联储的问题上是被“欺骗”了，他内疚地表示：“我在无意之中摧毁了我的国家。”

当1914年10月25日美联储正式开始运作时，第一次世界大战爆发了，又一个完美的时间“巧合”，美联储的股东们注定要大发一笔横财了！

注 释

[1] Quoted in "National Economy and the Banking System," Senate Documents Co. 3, No. 23, Seventy-sixth Congress, First session, 1939.

[2] John Moody, *The Seven Men*, McClure's Magazine, August, 1911, p. 418.

[3] William Guy Carr, *Pawns In The Game* (Legion for the Survival of Freedom, 1978).

[4] Eustace Mullins, *The Secrets of the Federal Reserve* (John McLaughlin 1993) Chapter 3.

[5] Paul M Warburg, *Defects and needs of our banking system*, 1907.

[6] Ron Chernow, *The House of Morgan* (Groove Press, 1990), p128.

[7] Antony C. Sutton, *The Federal Reserve Conspiracy* (Tab Books, 1995) p78.

[8] *Ibid.*, p83.

[9] Eustace Mullins, *Secrets of Federal Reserve* (John McLaughlin, 1993) Chapter 3.

[10] Congressman Charles Lindberg Sr. Speech on floor of the Congress, December 23, 1913.

[11] Eustace Mullins, *The Secrets of the Federal Reserve* (John McLaughlin 1993) p178.

[12] Ferdinand Lundberg, *America's 60 families* (Halcyon House, 1939).

[13] Eustace Mullins, *The Secrets of the Federal Reserve* (John McLaughlin 1993) Chapter 3.

Fig. 231-12. Before President Wilson passed away, he admitted being "hoodwinked" on the Federal Reserve issue, remorsefully stating, "I have unwittingly ruined my country."

When the Federal Reserve officially began operations on October 25, 1914, World War I broke out, another perfect "coincidence," ensuring the Fed's shareholders would make a fortune.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p84, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007年]

第四章

一战与大衰退： 国际银行家的“丰收时节”

我们共和国的真正威胁是这个看不见的政府，它就像一只巨大的章鱼，用它无数黏稠的触角紧紧裹挟着我们的城市、州和国家。这只章鱼的头是洛克菲勒的标准石油集团和一小撮被称为国际银行家的具有极大能量的金融寡头，他们实际上操纵着美国政府来满足他们自己的私欲。

通过控制货币供应来控制政府，这样使剥削一个国家的公民和资源变得更加容易。这就是为什么这些大家族从这个国家诞生之初就竭尽全力来使权力（他们将我们的“领导者”玩弄于股掌之间）和财富（他们通过美联储的货币发行来汲取社会财富）高度集中。

这些国际银行家和洛克菲勒标准石油集团控制了个国家大多数的报纸和杂志。他们用这些报纸的专栏评论来钳制政府官员，对于那些不肯就范的人，他们则通过舆论将这些官员赶出政府机构。

他们（银行家）实际上控制着两党（共和党与民主党），草拟（两党的）政治纲领，控制政治领袖，任用私有公司的头头，利用一切手段在政府高层安插顺从于他们腐败的大生意的候选人。^[1]

约翰·海兰，纽约市市长，1927年

Fig. 231-13. Chapter 4 "The Great War" and the Great Depression: The "Harvest Time" of International Bankers

The true threat to our republic is this invisible government, which, like a giant octopus, firmly entwines our cities, states, and nation with its countless sticky tentacles. The head of this octopus is Rockefeller's Standard Oil cartel and a handful of immensely powerful financial oligarchs known as international bankers, who effectively manipulate the United States government to satisfy their own desires. By controlling the supply of money to manipulate the government, it becomes easier to exploit the citizens and resources of a country. This is why these elite families have

spared no effort since the inception of this country to concentrate power (they manipulate our "leaders" at their will) and wealth (they draw social wealth through the issuance of currency by the Federal Reserve) to a high degree.

These international bankers and the Rockefeller Standard Oil cartel control most of the newspapers and magazines in this country. They use the editorial columns of these newspapers to restrain government officials, and for those who refuse to comply, they drive them out of government institutions through public opinion. They (the bankers) actually control both parties (Republican and Democratic), draft (the) political agendas, control political leaders, appoint heads of private companies, and use every means to install candidates obedient to their corrupt big business interests in top government positions.

— John Hylan, Mayor of New York City, 1927

[Book: Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p85, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

[Book: Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p86, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

Introduction to this chapter:

Fighting costs money, and the bigger the war, the more money it costs. This is a well-known fact. The question is, who pays for it? Because the governments of Europe and America do not have the right to issue currency, they can only borrow money from bankers. War consumes resources at a rate akin to burning, it forces belligerent nations to sell everything they have, and it compels governments, at any cost, to finance themselves from bankers without conditions. No wonder war has always been the favorite of bankers. They plan wars, they incite wars, they fund wars. The magnificent buildings of international bankers have always been built on the ruins of deathbeds.

Another way for international bankers to make big money is to create economic recessions. First, they expand credit, inflate bubbles, and when people's wealth is heavily invested in speculative frenzy, they then pull out the roots of the money supply, causing economic downturns and asset crashes. When the prices of high-quality assets plummet to one-tenth or even one-hundredth of their normal prices, they step in to buy at super-low prices. In the terminology of international bankers, this is called "fleecing the sheep." With the establishment of private central banks, the intensity and scope of "fleecing the sheep" or "shearing wool" actions have reached unprecedented levels.

The most recent "fleecing" occurred on the "little dragons" and "little tigers" of Asia in 1997. Whether China, this big fat sheep, can avoid the fate of being "fleeced" depends on whether China seriously studies the horrifying "fleecing" or "shearing wool" tragedies that have occurred in history.

After foreign banks entered China in full force, the fundamental difference from before lies in the fact that while state-owned banks in the past certainly had the incentive to promote asset inflation to make profits, they never had the intention or ability to maliciously create deflation to bleed people's wealth. The reason why China

has never experienced a major economic crisis since its establishment is that no one had the subjective intention or objective ability to maliciously create an economic crisis. When international bankers fully entered China, the situation fundamentally changed.

本章导读

打仗就要花钱，越大的战争花钱越多，这是尽人皆知的道理。问题是，谁花谁的钱？由于欧美政府没有货币发行权，政府必须也只能向银行家借钱。战争使物资消耗达到燃烧般的速度，战争使交战国砸锅卖铁也要坚持，战争使不惜一切代价的政府不计条件地向银行家融资，难怪战争始终是银行家的最爱。他们策划战争，他们挑动战争，他们资助战争，国际银行家们华丽的大厦，从来就是建立在死亡枕藉的废墟之上。

国际银行家另一个赚大钱的手段就是制造经济衰退。首先是扩大信贷，将泡沫吹起来，等人民的财富大量投入投机狂潮后，然后猛抽银根，制造经济衰退与资产暴跌。当优质资产价格暴跌到正常价格的十分之一甚至百分之一时，他们再出手以超级低廉的价格收购，这在国际银行家们的术语中叫做“剪羊毛”。当私有中央银行成立后，“剪羊毛”行动的力度和范围都达到了史无前例的程度。

最近的一次“剪羊毛”行动，发生在1997年的亚洲“小龙”和“小虎”们身上。中国这只大肥羊最终能否避免被“剪羊毛”的厄运，就要看中国是否认真去研究发生在历史上的一幕幕触目惊心的“剪羊毛”惨剧了。

外资银行全面进入中国之后，与以前最根本的不同就在于，从前的国有银行虽然有推动资产通货膨胀来赚取利润的冲动，但绝没有恶意制造通货紧缩来血洗人民财富的意图与能力。中国自建国以来之所以从未出现重大的经济危机，其原因就是没有人有恶意制造经济危机的主观意图和客观能力。当国际银行家全面进入中国之后，情况发生了根本性的变化。

Fig. 231-14. [Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p86, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵，货币战争 中信出版社，北京，2007年]

保罗·沃尔克：世界经济“有控制地解体”

沃尔克当选（美联储主席）是因为他是华尔街的人选。这是他们的开价。为人所知的是他很聪明和保守，不为人所知的是他即将掀起一场巨变。

查尔斯·吉斯特，历史学家

1973年，美国大通曼哈顿银行董事长戴维·洛克菲勒为了加强北美、西欧和日本金融界之间的关系，在布热津斯基的倡议和协助下组建了一个名叫美、欧、日三边委员会的团体。委员会的主要成员均是北美、西欧和日本的一些大银行家、大企业家和著名的政界人物，并在纽约、巴黎、东京分别设了三个总部，由这三个地区各出一人担任主席。纽约总部的主席理所当然的是戴维·洛克菲勒，作为戴维·洛克菲勒的心腹谋士的布热津斯基便成为这个总部主持日常工作的执行主任。布热津斯基有个在哥伦比亚大学当教授的好友，叫迪安·腊斯克，是佐治亚州人，他在肯尼迪、约翰逊掌管白宫时曾担任国务卿。他向布热津斯基建议邀请佐治亚州州长卡特参加三边委员会，并一再赞美卡特的创业魄力和政治远见。

在腊斯克的热情撮合下，布热津斯基同卡特见了两面。布热津斯基一眼就相中了卡特，认定此人日后必成大器，自然很想将他网罗在身边，但以卡特当时的职位和声望，要想成为三边委员会的成员，在执行委员会表决时恐很难通过。于是，布热津斯基便当面向戴维·洛克菲勒先生做了推荐，着力将卡特大大称赞了一番。三边执行委员会主席采纳了他的意见，并亲自提名。就这样，名不见经传的佐治亚州州长吉米·卡特的名字被列入三边委员会美国成员的名单中。这是他为五年后跨上白宫的台阶所迈出的至关重要的一大步。

在卡特1977年入主白宫之后，他的“入党介绍人”布热津斯基顺理成章地成为卡特总统的国家安全助理，实际上是代表国际银行家进行“摄政”，其角色与尼克松时代的基辛格类似。

1978年，美联储主席职位出缺，这可是国际银行家非常看重的一个

Fig. 231-15. Currency War 1 Upgrade - 8.2 Paul Volcker: The World Economy "Controlled Disintegration"

"Volcker's election (as Federal Reserve Chairman) was because he was Wall Street's choice. That was their price. It's known that he's very smart and conservative, but what's not known is that he is about to unleash a huge change."

— Historian Charles Gist

In 1973, David Rockefeller, chairman of Chase Manhattan Bank, initiated and assisted in the formation of a group called the Trilateral Commission to strengthen relations between North America, Western Europe, and Japan. The main members of the commission were prominent bankers, businesspeople, and politicians from North America, Western Europe, and Japan, with headquarters established in New York,

Paris, and Tokyo respectively, each chaired by a representative from one of these regions. Naturally, David Rockefeller chaired the New York headquarters, and his trusted advisor, Brzezinski, became the executive director in charge of daily operations.

Brzezinski had a friend, Dean Rusk, who was a professor at Columbia University. Rusk, from Georgia, served as Secretary of State during the Kennedy and Johnson administrations. He suggested to Brzezinski to invite the Governor of Georgia, Carter, to join the Trilateral Commission, praising Carter's entrepreneurial spirit and political foresight.

Under Rusk's enthusiastic matchmaking, Brzezinski met with Carter twice. Brzezinski was immediately impressed by Carter and believed he had great potential. Naturally, he wanted to recruit him. However, given Carter's position and reputation at the time, it would be difficult for him to become a member of the Trilateral Commission and pass votes in the executive committee. Therefore, Brzezinski directly recommended Carter to Mr. David Rockefeller, who spoke highly of him. The chairmen of the Trilateral Executive Committee accepted his suggestion and personally nominated Carter. In this way, the name of the small Governor of Georgia, Jimmy Carter, was added to the list of American members of the Trilateral Commission. It was a crucial step towards his ascent to the presidency five years later.

After Carter entered the White House in 1977, his "introducer" Brzezinski naturally became Carter's National Security Advisor, effectively acting as a "regent" for international bankers, similar to Kissinger's role during the Nixon era.

In 1978, the position of Chairman of the Federal Reserve Board became vacant. This was a very important role highly valued by international bankers. David Rockefeller strongly recommended his trusted subordinate, Paul Volcker, for the position, and President Carter could not refuse this request.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p190, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

要角，戴维·洛克菲勒向卡特力荐手下名将保罗·沃尔克担当此任，卡特总统无法拒绝这一要求。

《纽约时报》称“沃尔克的任命得到了波恩、法兰克福和瑞士的欧洲银行的认可”，熊市已久的纽约股票市场还少有人地上升了9.73点，美元在国际市场上一下子坚挺起来。

自从1933年尤金·梅耶从美联储辞职以来，国际银行家族的成员已经全部从金融市场的第一线撤到了幕后，他们主要通过严格挑选美联储纽约银行行长的人选来控制美联储的运作。沃尔克非常符合他们的条件。他早年就读于普林斯顿和哈佛大学，后赴伦敦经济学院进一步深造，50年代担任美联储纽约银行的经济学家，后到大通曼哈顿银行任经济学家，60年代在财政部工作，在尼克松时代是废除金本位的主要操盘手之一。1974年开始担任美联储纽约银行行长的重要职位，实际负责美联储的全盘运作。

1978年11月9日，意气风发的沃尔克在英国沃维克大学（Warwick University）发表的一篇演讲中透露：“世界经济中某种程度的‘有控制地解体’是80年代一项合理的目标。”^[5]

问题是，解谁的体？如何解体？

首当其冲的自然严重负债的第三世界国家，其次是苏联与东欧。

沃尔克上任伊始便祭起“打击世界范围的通货膨胀”这面光鲜的大旗，与紧密同盟英国一道使美元借贷变得昂贵无比。美元拆借利息平均值从1979年的11.2%一口气涨到1981年的20%，基本利率更高达21.5%，国债冲上17.3%。

英国首相撒切尔夫人于1979年5月当选，她发誓“要把通货膨胀从经济中驱除出去”，她上任仅一个月就把基准利率在12个星期之内从12%提高到17%，在如此短的时间之内把所有行业的借贷成本猛然提高42%，这在和平时期的工业化国家中可谓史无前例。撒切尔夫人也因此赢得了“铁娘子”的称号。

在“反通货膨胀”的大旗下，经济陷入严重衰退，人民和商业承受着痛苦的代价，美国和英国的银行家却大发利市。

削减政府开支、减税、开放行业管制、打破工会力量等口号响彻云

Fig. 231-16. The New York Times reported, "Volcker's appointment was endorsed by European banks in Bonn, Frankfurt, and Switzerland." The long-depressed New York stock market rose 9.73 points, and the US dollar suddenly strengthened in the international market.

Since Eugene Meyer resigned from the Federal Reserve in 1933, members of the international banking family have all withdrawn from the forefront of financial markets, mainly controlling the operation of the Federal Reserve by carefully selecting the President of the Federal Reserve Bank of New York. Volcker was very much in line with their selection criteria. He studied at Princeton and Harvard, furthered his studies at the London School of Economics, served as an economist at the Federal Reserve Bank of New York in the 1950s, later worked as an economist at Chase Manhattan

Bank, and in the 1960s worked at the Treasury Department, where he was one of the main architects of the abolition of the gold standard during the Nixon era. He began serving in the important position of President of the Federal Reserve Bank of New York in 1974, effectively overseeing the overall operations of the Federal Reserve.

On November 9, 1978, in a speech at the University of Warwick in the UK, the confident Volcker revealed: **"A certain level of 'controlled disintegration' in the world economy is a fair goal for the 1980s."**

The question was, whose bodies would be disintegrated? How would disintegration occur?

Naturally, the most immediate targets were heavily indebted third-world countries, followed by the Soviet Union and Eastern Europe.

At the beginning of Volcker's tenure, he raised the clear banner of combating "worldwide inflation" and, together with close ally Britain, made borrowing in dollars extremely expensive. Average interest rates on dollar loans skyrocketed from 11.2% in 1979 to 20% in 1981, with the prime rate reaching as high as 21.5%, and government bond yields surged to 17.3%.

Margaret Thatcher was elected Prime Minister of Britain in May 1979, vowing to "drive inflation out of the economy." In just one month of taking office, she raised the benchmark interest rate from 12% to 17% in 12 weeks, causing borrowing costs across all sectors to suddenly rise by 42% in such a short period of time, unprecedented among industrialized nations in peacetime. She thus earned the nickname "Iron Lady" for her actions.

Under the banner of "anti-inflation", the economy plunged into a severe recession, and people and trade bore the painful costs, while bankers in the United States and Britain made huge profits.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p191, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

天，沉重债务负担之下的发展中国家，更是哀鸿遍地，死亡枕藉。此时，发展中国家的债务已经由彼尔德伯格1973年5月会议时的1 300亿美元，暴涨了5倍，到1982年时达到了惊人的6 120亿美元。当美国和英国在“反通货膨胀”的口号下，突然将利率提高到20%左右的时候，发展中国家的巨额债务在如此惊人的“高利贷”压榨之下，已经使它们注定成为国际银行家刀板上的鱼肉了。毫无金融战争防范意识的亚非拉国家将为它们的疏忽付出惨痛的代价。

美国国务卿舒尔茨在1982年9月30日的联合国会议上指出，国际货币基金组织应该对发展中国家的还债严加监督，他敦促发展中国家应该使出口产品“更吸引西方”，只有“自由贸易”才能拯救它们，此外，加大出售原材料的力度，能加快它们债务清偿的过程。

墨西哥总统波提略 (Lopez Portillo) 则针锋相对地指出，英美国际银行家的策略就是要用高利率和与之相随的低原材料价格这对“剪刀”的双刃来扼杀一些发展中国家已经取得的建设成就，并泯灭其余国家取得进步的可能”。他进一步威胁要带领发展中国家停止债务支付。他指出：

墨西哥和其他第三世界国家不能按照与现实情况差异巨大的条件来按时偿还债务。我们发展中国家不愿意成为（西方国家的）附庸。我们不能使我们的经济瘫痪或让我们的人民陷入更悲惨的境地来偿还这些债务。在没有我们参与的情况下，这些债务偿还的费用已经涨了三倍，我们对此没有责任。我们旨在消除饥饿、疾病、无知和依赖方面的努力并没有造成国际危机。^[6]

不幸的是，波提罗在联合国发言后仅两个月就被国际银行家看中的人选所取代，国际货币基金组织作为“维护贷款秩序的警察”插手墨西哥债务清偿，恩格这样描述了这段历史：

现代历史上最具规模的有组织抢劫行动开始了，其规模远超过20年代的类似活动。与西欧或美国媒体精心掩饰的情况正相反，债务国偿付了好几遍欠债，他们正是以血和“一磅鲜肉”来偿还现代组

2
Fig. 231-17. Slogans such as cutting government spending, tax cuts, deregulating industries, and breaking the power of unions echoed through the skies. Developing countries, burdened by heavy debt were particularly hard hit, with widespread

suffering and devastation. By this time, the debt of developing countries had ballooned from \$130 billion at the May 1973 meeting of the Bilderberg Group to an astonishing \$612 billion by 1982, a fivefold increase. **When the United States and Britain suddenly raised interest rates to around 20% under the banner of "anti-inflation"**, the massive debts of developing countries, under such staggering pressure from **"usurious loan,"** had already doomed them to be the prey to international bankers. Countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America, with no awareness of financial warfare prevention, would pay a painful price for their negligence.

U.S. Secretary of State Schultz pointed out at a United Nations meeting on September 30, 1982, that the International Monetary Fund should closely monitor debt repayment by developing countries. He urged developing countries to make their export products "more attractive to the West," emphasizing that only "free trade" could save them, and increasing the sale of their raw materials could accelerate the debt repayment process.

Mexican President Porfirio, in a counter-attack, pointed out that the strategy of Anglo-American bankers is to use high interest rates and accompanying low raw material prices, "like a double-edged sword to erase some of the construction achievements already achieved by developing countries and extinguish the possibility of progress for the rest." He further threatened to lead developing countries to stop debt payments. He stated,

"Mexico and other Third World countries cannot repay debts on time under conditions that differ greatly from reality. We developing countries refuse to be (the vassals of Western countries). We cannot paralyze our economy or let our people fall into a more miserable situation to repay these debts. **The cost of repaying these debts has tripled without our involvement.** Our efforts to eliminate hunger, disease, ignorance, and dependence have not caused an international crisis."

Unfortunately, just two months after Porfirio's speech at the United Nations, he was replaced by a candidate favored by international bankers. The IMF, as the "police of loan order maintenance," intervened in Mexico's debt repayment. Eng describes this period of history as follows:

"The most massive organized looting operation in modern history began, far surpassing similar activities in the 1920s. Contrary to what Western European or American media carefully concealed, debtor countries have repaid their debts several times over, with blood and a 'pound of flesh' to modern Sherlocks in New York and London. After August 1982, developing countries no longer defaulted on their debts as portrayed. They were held at gunpoint and, under the threat of the International Monetary Fund, signed agreements called 'debt solutions,' participated by renowned New York Citibank or Chase Manhattan Bank."

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p192, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

约和伦敦的夏洛克们的。1982年8月以后发展中国家不再还债并非实情。他们的头上被顶着枪，在国际货币基金组织的威逼下，签署了银行家们美其名曰“债务解决方案”的协议，参与的都是著名的纽约花旗银行或大通银行。^[7]

国际货币基金组织的贷款只有在债务国签署了一系列“特别条款”之后才能得到，这些条款包括：削减政府开支，提高税收，货币贬值。然后债务被重新延展，发展中国家还需要支付一笔“服务费”给国际银行家，并被记入债务的本金中。

墨西哥被迫削减对医药、食品、燃油和其他生活必需品的政府补贴，同时比索被贬值到令人惨不忍睹的程度。1982年年初，在波提罗总统一系列经济改革措施之下，比索对美元比价为12比1，而到1989年，比索对美元已贬到2 300比1，墨西哥经济已经事实上被国际银行家们“有控制地解体”了。

据世界银行统计，从1980年到1986年，世界100多个债务国仅向国际银行家支付利息一项就高达3 260亿美元，本金偿付又支付了3 320亿美元，总共发展中国家为4 300亿美元（1980年）的债务支付了6 580亿美元的费用。尽管这样，到1987年，109个债务国还欠国际银行家1.3万亿美元。在如此惊人的基础上进行利滚利，只怕发展中国家永远没有还清债务的时候了。于是，国际银行家与国际货币基金组织就开始对债务国实施破产清偿。接受银行家“债务解决方案”的国家被迫以跳楼价出卖大量核心资产，如自来水、电力、天然气、铁路、电话、石油、银行等。

人们终于见识到国际银行家所策划的世界经济“有控制地解体”具有何等的杀伤力！

世界环保银行：要圈地球30%的陆地

在亚非拉发展中国家深陷债务泥潭之际，国际银行家开始策划一个更大的行动，其方式超乎普通人想象力的极限，正常智力的人们无论如

Fig. 231-18. Loans from the International Monetary Fund are only available to debtor countries after they have signed a series of "special clauses", including: reducing government spending, improving taxation, and currency devaluation. The debt is then renegotiated, and developing countries are required to pay another "service fee" to international bankers, which is added to the principal of the debt.

Mexico was forced to cut government subsidies for medicine, food, fuel, and other essential goods, while the peso was devalued to a devastating extent. At the beginning of 1982, under a series of economic reform measures by President Porfirio, the peso was pegged at 12 to 1 against the US dollar. By 1989, the peso had depreciated to 2300 to 1 against the US dollar, effectively leading to the controlled dismantling of the Mexican economy by international bankers.

According to World Bank statistics, from 1980 to 1986, over a hundred debtor

countries paid a staggering \$326 billion in interest alone to international bankers, with an additional \$332 billion in principal payments, totaling \$658 billion in expenditures for developing countries' debts of \$430 billion (in 1980). However, by 1987, 109 debtor countries still owed international bankers \$1.3 trillion. With such a staggering basis for compound interest, it seemed that developing countries would never be able to repay their debts. Consequently, international bankers and the IMF began implementing debt liquidation for debtor countries. Countries accepting the bankers' "debt solutions" were forced to sell off large amounts of core assets at fire-sale prices, such as water utilities, electricity, natural gas, railways, telephones, oil, and banks.

People have finally witnessed the devastating impact of the international bankers' orchestrated "controlled dismantling" of the world economy.

8.3 The World Environmental Bank: Aiming to Enclose 30% of the Earth's Land

At the time when developing countries in Asia, Africa and Latin America are deeply mired in debt, international bankers are planning a larger action, the method of which goes beyond the limits of ordinary imagination. People of normal intelligence could never imagine that 'environmental protection' would be the entry point for a larger conspiracy.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p193, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

何也想不到“环境保护”竟然是一个更大图谋的切入点。

如果不从历史的角度看问题，就不可能明白国际银行家令人眼花缭乱的“组合拳”的巨大威力！

1963年8月初，美国中西部的一个著名大学里，一位化名为“约翰·多伊”（John Doe）的社会学教授，接到华盛顿打来的一个电话，邀请他参加一项秘密研究课题，参与该计划的15名专家都是美国著名大学的顶尖学者。“约翰·多伊”教授带着好奇来到了一个名叫“铁山”（Iron Mountain）的地方报到。

“铁山”靠近纽约州的哈德逊城，这里有当年冷战期间为防御苏联核打击而修建的巨大的地下设施，几百家美国最大公司的总部都在此处设有临时办公地点。这些公司包括：新泽西的标准石油公司、壳牌石油公司和汉诺威制造信托公司等。如果核战争爆发，这里将成为美国最重要的商业运作中心，以确保核战争之后，美国商业体系仍然能够生存下来。平时，这里是这些公司储存机密文件档案的地方。

这个神秘的研究小组要研究的课题是，如果世界进入了“永久和平”阶段，美国将面临什么样的挑战，以及美国的对应策略。这项研究工作持续了两年半的时间。

1967年，这个15人的课题组完成了一份绝密报告，这份报告的作者们被政府要求对该报告严格保密。但是，其中的“约翰·多伊”教授觉得这份报告实在太重要了，不应该向公众隐瞒。他于是找到著名作家里伦纳德·莱文，在莱文的帮助下，这本名叫《来自铁山的报告》（*Report From Iron Mountain*）的书被戴尔出版公司于1967年正式出版。该书一经面世，立刻震惊美国社会各界。大家都在猜到底谁是“约翰·多伊”。该报告被认为是当时的美国国防部长麦克纳马拉（Robert McNamara）策划的，麦克纳马拉是外交协会的成员，后来担任世界银行行长。运作的研究机构被认为就是哈德逊研究所，该机构的创始人赫曼·卡恩（Herman Kahn）也是外交协会会员。

对于这次泄密事件，约翰逊的国家安全特别助理罗斯托立刻站出来进行紧急“消毒”，他指出该报告纯属子虚乌有。同样是外交协会成员的亨利·卢斯（Henry Luce）控制下的《时代》也说该报告是“巧妙的谎

Fig. 231-18-1. Without viewing the topic from a historical perspective, it's impossible to understand the enormous power of the dazzling 'combination punches' of international bankers. In early August 1963, at a famous university in the Midwest of the United States, a sociology professor using the pseudonym 'John Doe' received a call from Washington inviting him to participate in a secret research project. The 15 experts involved in the project were all top scholars from prominent American universities. Professor 'John Doe' arrived with curiosity at a place called 'Iron Mountain.'

Iron Mountain is near the city of Hudson in New York State, where huge

underground facilities were built during the Cold War to defend against Soviet nuclear strikes. The headquarters of hundreds of America's most vital companies have temporary offices here, including Standard Oil Company of New Jersey, Shell Oil Company, and the Hanover Manufacturing Trust Company. In the event of a nuclear war, this would become America's most important trading center, ensuring that the American trade system could survive after a nuclear war. Normally, it's where these companies store their confidential documents and files.

The subject of this mysterious research group was to study what challenges the United States would face and what corresponding strategies it would adopt if the world entered a 'permanent peace' phase. This research lasted two and a half years.

In 1967, the 15-member research team completed a highly classified report, which the government strictly ordered them to keep confidential. However, the professor known as "John Doe" felt the report was too important to be withheld from the public. He approached the renowned writer Leonard Levin, and with Levin's assistance, the book titled "**Report from Iron Mountain**" was officially published by Dell Publishing Company in 1967. Upon its release, the book immediately shocked various sectors of American society, with everyone speculating about the true identity of "John Doe." The report was thought to have been orchestrated by then-Secretary of Defense Robert McNamara, a member of the Council on Foreign Relations who later became the President of the World Bank. The research institution behind the operation was believed to be the Hudson Institute, founded by Herman Kahn, also a member of the Council on Foreign Relations.

In response to the leak, John F. Kennedy's National Security Special Assistant, Ross, immediately stepped forward to urgently "disinfect" the situation, claiming the report was entirely fictitious. Similarly, Henry Luce, under the control of the Council on Foreign Relations, characterized the report in Time magazine as a "clever fiction." The authenticity of the report remains a subject of debate in American society to this day. [**Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p194, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年**]

言”。该报告究竟是真是假，美国社会到今天仍然争论不休。

不过，1967年11月26日，《华盛顿邮报》曾经在《书评》栏目中介绍过这本书。介绍该书的就是哈佛大学著名教授加布雷思（John Kenneth Gbraith），他也是外交协会成员，在文章中他指出他有第一手的信息证明该报告是真实的，因为他本人就在被邀请之列。后来尽管他没能参加这个项目的的工作，但该项目一直在向他咨询各种问题，他也被告知要对外保密。“我愿意用我个人的名誉担保这个文件（“铁山报告”）的真实性，我也愿意证实它的结论的有效性。我有所保留的只是，将它公布给没有准备的公众是否明智。”^[9]后来加布雷思曾在其他媒体上两次重申该报告的真实性。

那么，该报告究竟有什么惊人的结论，让“精英们”如此紧张呢？

原来，该报告详实地透露了“世界精英们”对未来世界的发展规划。报告的基本宗旨就是，不讨论对与错的问题，也不考虑自由与人权之类的空洞概念，一切诸如意识形态、爱国主义和宗教立场都无关紧要，这是一份“纯粹客观”的报告。

报告开宗明义地指出：

持续的和平，尽管从理论上说并非不可能，但是却不具有可持续性。即便（和平的目标）是可以达到的，它也肯定不是一个稳定社会的最佳选择……战争是使社会稳定的一种特殊方式。除非其他替代方式能够被发展出来，否则战争系统应该被保持和强化。^[10]

报告认为，只有在战争时期，或者是在战争的威胁之下，人民才最有可能服从政府而没有怨言。对敌人的仇恨和被征服与劫掠的恐惧，使人民更能够承受过重的税负和牺牲。战争又是人民强烈情绪的催化剂，在爱国、忠诚和胜利的精神状态下，人民可以无条件地服从，任何反对意见都会被认为是背叛行为。相反，在和平情况下，人民会本能地反对高税收政策，讨厌政府过多干预私人生活。

战争系统不仅是一个国家作为独立政治系统存在的必要因素，对于政治稳定也是必不可少的。没有战争，政府统治人民的“合

Fig. 231-18-2. However, on November 26, 1967, The Washington Post briefly introduced the book in its "Book Review" section. The introduction was written by the renowned Harvard professor Gabriel, also a member of the Council on Foreign Relations. In his article, he indicated that he had firsthand information confirming the authenticity of the report, as he himself was among those invited. Although he was

unable to participate in the project's work, he had been consulted on various topics related to the project and was instructed to maintain confidentiality. "I am willing to vouch for the authenticity of this document (' **Report from Iron Mountain** ') with my personal reputation, and I am also willing to confirm the validity of its conclusions. What I have retained is whether it is wise to disclose it to an unprepared public." Later, Gabriel reiterated the authenticity of the report twice in other media.

So, what surprising conclusions did the report draw that made the "elites" so nervous?

It turns out that the report detailed the "world elite's" plan for the future development of the world. The basic premise of the report is to avoid discussing right and wrong issues, as well as hollow concepts like freedom and human rights. It dismisses all ideologies, patriotism, and religious attitudes, presenting itself as a "purely objective" report.

The report states bluntly, "Sustained peace, although theoretically possible, is not conducive to stability. Even if attainable, it is assuredly not the optimal choice for a stable society... War is a special function of our societal stability. Unless alternative forms of replacement can be developed, the war system should be maintained and strengthened."

The report argues that only during wartime or under threat of war are people most likely to comply with the government without complaint. Hatred for enemies and fear of conquest and plunder make people more willing to endure heavy taxation and sacrifices. War serves as a catalyst for strong emotions, where people can unquestioningly obey in a state of patriotism, loyalty, and desire for victory, viewing any dissent as treason. Conversely, in peacetime, people instinctively oppose high taxation policies and resent excessive government intervention in private life.

[Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p195, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

法性”就会出现问题。战争的可能性提供了一个政府能够拥有权力的基础。历史上不胜枚举的例子表明，失去战争威胁的政权，最终导致了权力瓦解，这种破坏作用来源于个人利益膨胀、对社会不公的怨恨，以及其他解体因素。战争的可能成为保持社会组织结构的政治稳定因素。它保持了社会阶层分明，保证了人民对政府的服从。^[11]

但是该报告认为，传统的战争方式也有其历史的局限性，在这种状态之下，世界政府的大业将难以实现，特别是在核战争时代，战争爆发变成了一种难以预测和风险极大的问题。考虑到该研究正是在古巴导弹危机之后不久开始进行的，当时美国和苏联核大战的阴影肯定在一定程度上影响了研究者们的心理。

问题是，一旦世界出现了“永久和平”，美国社会的出路何在呢？这正是这个秘密研究小组要追寻的答案。

换句话说，他们需要为美国找到一个能够替代“战争”的新方案。经过谨慎的研究，专家们提出，替代战争的新方案必须同时具备三大条件：（1）在经济上必须是“浪费”的，最少需要消耗每年GDP的10%；（2）必须是一种和战争危险类似的、大规模的、可信的重大威胁；（3）必须提供人民强迫性服务于政府的合乎逻辑的理由。

要同时满足这三大条件，也不是一项轻松的工作。专家们先是想到“向贫困宣战”。贫困问题虽然足够庞大，但是不具备足够的恐惧感，所以很快被放弃了。另一个选择是外星人入侵，虽然这足够恐怖，但在60年代还缺乏可信度，于是又被放弃了。最后大家想到了“环境污染”，它在相当程度上是一个事实，具备可信度，在对环境污染的宣传上下工夫，足以达到核战争之后世界末日的恐怖程度，不断地污染环境的确是在经济上非常“浪费”的，人民忍受高税收和降低生活质量，接受政府干预私人生活，为的是“拯救地球母亲”，非常符合逻辑。

这实在是一个绝妙的选择！

经过科学地估算，环境污染问题要达到在世界范围内引起强烈危机的时间大约为一代半左右，即20~30年。报告的发表时间是1967年。

Fig. 231-18-3. "The war system is not only a necessary factor for a country's existence as an independent political system but also essential for political stability. Without war, the 'legitimacy' of government ruling over the people will be questioned. The possibility of war provides a basis for the government to hold power. Countless examples throughout history demonstrate that regimes that lose the credibility of the

war threat ultimately lead to the disintegration of power, stemming from inflated personal interests, resentment of social injustice, and other disintegrating factors. War's potential becomes a political stabilizing factor in maintaining the structure of societal organization. It keeps social classes distinct and ensures the people's obedience to the government."

However, the report argues that traditional modes of warfare have their historical limitations. In this context, the grand project of a world government would be difficult to achieve, especially in the era of nuclear warfare, where the outbreak of war becomes an unpredictable and extremely risky proposition. Considering that this research began shortly after the Cuban Missile Crisis, the shadow of a potential nuclear war with the Soviet Union undoubtedly influenced the mindset of the authors to some extent.

The question then arises: if the world were to enter a "permanent peace," what would be the way forward for American society? This is precisely the answer that this secret research group sought to find.

In other words, they needed to find a new solution to replace "war" for America. After careful study, the experts proposed that the new solution to replace war must meet three conditions simultaneously: (1) economically, it must be "wasteful," consuming at least 10% of GDP annually; (2) it must be a major threat similar to the dangers of war, large-scale, and credible; (3) it must provide logically convincing reasons for the people to compulsorily serve the government.

Meeting all three of these conditions simultaneously was no easy task. Initially, experts considered "declaring war on poverty." While poverty is indeed a significant issue, it lacks sufficient fear, so it was quickly abandoned. Another option was an alien invasion, which, while terrifying, lacked credibility in the 1960s, so it too was discarded. Finally, they settled on "environmental pollution." It was factual to a considerable extent, had credibility, and with diligent propaganda efforts on environmental pollution, it could reach the level of terror akin to the apocalypse after a nuclear war. Continuously polluting the environment was indeed economically "wasteful." People enduring high taxes and decreased quality of life, accepting government intervention in private life to "save Mother Earth," made logical sense.

It was truly a masterful choice.

Scientific estimates have suggested that the environmental pollution issue would reach a crisis point globally in approximately a generation and a half, about 20 to 30 years. The report was published in 1967.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p196, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

20年后……

1987年9月，世界野生环境保护委员会（World Wilderness Congress）第四次大会在美国科罗拉多州丹佛市召开，来自60多个国家的2 000名代表参加了这一次会议。参加这次会议的代表惊讶地发现，一份名为《丹佛宣言》的文件已经为他们准备好了。《丹佛宣言》指出：

因为新的资金必须被筹集起来以扩大环境保护的活动范围，我们应该创造出一种新的银行模式，以便将对环境管理的国际援助与受援国的资源管理的需求加以整合。

这种新的银行模式就是“世界环保银行”的方案。

与以前类似会议迥然不同的是，一大批国际银行家出席了这次会议，为首的就是艾德蒙·罗斯柴尔德男爵、戴维·洛克菲勒和美国财政部长詹姆斯·贝克（James Baker）。这些超级大忙人居然在一个环保会议上盘桓了整整六天，向大会介绍和推销世界环保银行的金融方案。

艾德蒙·罗斯柴尔德在大会上发言，将这个世界环保银行称为“第二个马歇尔计划”，它的建立将把发展中国家从债务泥潭中“拯救”出来，同时还能保护生态环境。^[12]

请注意，截至1987年，发展中国家的全部债务高达1.3万亿美元。

世界环保银行的核心概念就是“以债务替换自然资源”（Debt for Nature Swap）。国际银行家们计划将发展中国家的1.3万亿美元的债务进行再贷款，将债务转到世界环保银行账上，债务国用濒临生态危机的土地做抵押，从世界环保银行那里得到债务延长和新的软贷款（Soft Currency Loan）。被国际银行家圈出的发展中国家的“生态土地”遍布拉丁美洲、非洲和亚洲，总面积多达5 000万平方公里，相当于五个中国的面积，占地球陆地面积的30%！

70年代发展中国家向国际货币基金组织和国际银行家的贷款绝大多数没有抵押品，仅以国家信用为凭证，当债务危机爆发后，国际银行家不太容易进行破产清偿。当这些债务转到世界环保银行头上后，国际银行家们账目上原本很难看的呆账一下变成了优质资产。由于世界环保银行拥有着土地作为抵押，一旦发展中国家无法清偿债务，这些被抵押的

Fig. 231-18-4. Twenty years later..

In September 1987, the Fourth Congress of the World Conservation Union was held in Denver, Colorado, USA, with more than 2,000 delegates from more than 60 countries in attendance. Surprisingly, they found a document called the "Denver Declaration" prepared for them.

The Denver Declaration stated: "Due to the need for new funds to expand the scope of environmental protection activities, we should create a new banking model to integrate international aid for environmental governance with the resource management needs of recipient countries."

This new banking model is the proposal for the "World Conservation Bank."

Unlike previous meetings, this one saw the participation of numerous international bankers, including Baron Edmond de Rothschild, David Rockefeller, and U.S. Treasury Secretary James Baker. These influential figures spent six days at the conference promoting the financial scheme of the **"World Conservation Bank."**

Rothschild even likened it to a "second Marshall Plan," suggesting it could rescue developing countries from debt while protecting the environment.

As of 1987, the total debt of developing countries amounted to \$1.3 trillion.

The core concept of the World Conservation Bank was to "swap debt for natural resources." International bankers planned to refinance the \$1.3 trillion debt of developing countries, transferring it to the bank's accounts. These countries would mortgage ecologically threatened land to the bank in exchange for debt rescheduling and new soft loans. The "ecological lands" earmarked by international bankers covered 50 million square kilometers across Latin America, Africa and Asia, equivalent to five times the size of China, representing 30% of the Earth's land area.

In the 1970s, most loans from developing countries to the IMF and international bankers lacked collateral, relying solely on national credit. When the debt crisis erupted, international bankers hesitated to write off those loans. **However, once these debts were transferred to the World Conservation Bank, the embarrassing bad debts on bankers' books turned into high-quality assets. With land as collateral, if developing countries could not repay the debt, the mortgaged land legally belonged to the World Conservation Bank, making the international bankers controlling it the de facto owners of a large number of fertile land. This land-grabbing scale was unprecedented in human history.**

[Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p197, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

大面积土地在法律上就属于世界环保银行了，而控制着世界环保银行的国际银行家们就顺理成章地成为大片肥沃土地的实际拥有者。以人类圈地运动的规模来看，世界环保银行堪称前无古人。

如此巨大的利益，难怪如罗斯柴尔德和洛克菲勒这般人物也要“关心”此次环保大会长达六天之久。

巴西财政部高级官员科斯塔博士 (Jose Pedro de Oliveira Costa) 在听到罗斯柴尔德的世界环保银行提议之后，一夜未眠。他认为，如果环保银行提供软贷款，在短期内可能对巴西的经济有帮助，至少经济发动机可以再度启动，但是从长远来看，巴西无论如何是无法偿还这些贷款的，最终的结果就是，作为贷款抵押品的风水宝地——亚马逊地区将不再为巴西所拥有。

被抵押的资源还不仅限于土地，水源和其他地面和地下的自然资源也在被抵押之列。

世界环保银行的名称比较扎眼，最终以全球环境基金 (Global Environment Facility) 的名义于1991年成立，由世界银行负责管理，而美国财政部是世界银行最大的股东。国际银行家们的长远规划目前正在逐步得以实施。

Fig. 231-18-5. Given the huge profits, it's no wonder that figures like Rothschild and Rockefeller showed prolonged interest in the environmental conference.

Dr. José Pedro de Oliveira Costa, a senior official from the Brazilian Ministry of Finance, couldn't sleep after hearing Rothschild's proposal for the World Conservation Bank. He realized that while soft loans might temporarily boost Brazil's economy, the country would ultimately be unable to repay them, resulting in the loss of the Amazon region, mortgaged as collateral. Resources pledged as collateral extended beyond land to include water sources and other natural resources above and below ground.

The name "World Conservation Bank" caught attention, eventually establishing itself as the **Global Environmental Facility** in 1991, governed by the World Bank, with the U.S. Treasury as its largest shareholder. The long-term plan of the international bankers is gradually being implemented.

[Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p198, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

金融资本势力有一个极为长远的计划，它旨在建立一个金融系统来控制世界，一个被少数人控制的、能够主宰政治体制和世界经济的（机制）。

这个系统是以封建专制的模式被中央银行家们所控制，它们通过频繁的会议所达成的秘密协议来进行协调。

这个系统的核心就是瑞士巴塞尔的国际清算银行，这是一家私有的银行，而控制它的中央银行们本身也同样是私有公司。

每个中央银行都致力于通过控制财政贷款、操纵外汇交易、影响国家经济活动水平、在商业领域对保持合作的政治家提供回报等方式来控制各自的政府。^[1]

卡洛·奎格雷，历史学家，1966年

Fig. 231-19. Currency Wars 1.0 - Chapter 6 The Elite Club That Rules the World

The financial capital forces have an extremely long-term plan, aimed at establishing a financial system to control the world, a mechanism controlled by a few that can dominate the political system and the world economy.

This system is controlled by central bankers in a feudal dictatorship model, coordinated through secret agreements reached at frequent meetings.

The core of this system is the Bank for International Settlements in Basel, Switzerland, a private bank controlled by the central banks themselves, which are also private companies.

Each central bank is committed to controlling its own government through various means such as controlling fiscal loans, manipulating foreign exchange transactions, influencing the level of national economic activity, and providing returns to politicians who maintain cooperation in trade.

— Renowned historian at Georgetown University, Carlo Quigley, 1966

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p131, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007.

本章导读

在我们的生活中,“世界政府”、“世界货币”之类的词汇出现的频率越来越高。如果没有相关的历史背景,你非常可能把这样的提法当成普通的新闻炒作,其实,一个巨大的计划正在启动。令人忧虑的是,大部分中国人对此仍然知之甚少。

1944年7月,当整个欧亚大陆还被满天的战争烽火所笼罩,就在英美在欧洲大陆开辟第二战场后仅一个多月,来自世界各地的44个国家的代表来到美国新罕布什尔州的著名度假胜地布雷顿森林,商讨战后世界经济新秩序的蓝图。国际银行家们开始实施他们策划已久的计划:控制全世界的货币发行!

此时的国际银行家们已经建立起一系列核心的组织机构:英国皇家国际事务协会和美国外交协会。后来,由这两个核心机构又衍生出两个新的分支:经济领域由彼尔德伯格俱乐部执掌大政方针,负责政治挂帅的是三边委员会。

这些组织的最终目的,就是建立一个由极少数英美精英分子所统治的世界政府,建立最终统一的世界货币发行体系,然后是对所有地球公民征收“世界税”,这就是所谓“新世界秩序”!

在这样的体系之下,所有主权国家的货币政策和经济内政决策权都必须被剥夺,所有主权国家及其人民的经济自由和政治自由必须被操纵。被套在现代人民身上的枷锁不再是铁链而是债务。为了使每一个现代“奴隶”产生最大的效益,粗放的经营管理必须向高效的科学“饲养”阶段过渡,无现金社会,电子货币、国际统一的射频卡身份证、人体内植入身份证等技术将成为最终把现代人变成“奴隶”的标志。

依靠射频识别技术,国际银行家最终将可以监控每一个地球人在任何时间的任何位置。当现金从社会中消失之后,只需要轻敲几下计算机键盘,每一个人都有可能被随时剥夺取得自己财富的权力。对于一切珍惜自由权力的人来说,这是一幅超级恐怖的景象。但对于国际银行家来说,这才是“新世界秩序”的最高境界。

精英们认为他们的计划不是“阴谋”,而是“阳谋”,与传统阴谋不同的是,他们没有明确的领导机构,只是“松散”的“志趣相投的社交圈子”。但是,让普通人不安的是,这些“志趣相投”的重量级人士,似乎总是以牺牲普通人的利益来“充实”他们的“理想”。

美国外交协会的创始人,第一次世界大战结束后国际联盟的首倡者豪斯上校就是这一计划在美国的一位重要操盘手。

Fig. 231-20. This chapter's overview

In our lives, terms like "world government" and "world currency" are becoming more

frequent. Without the relevant historical background, you might very well consider such phrasing mere sensationalism in the news. Yet, a grand plan is indeed unfolding. What's worrisome is China remains largely oblivious to it.

In July 1944, when the whole Eurasian continent was engulfed in flames and just over a month after the Anglo-Americans opened a second front in Europe, representatives from 44 countries around the world gathered at the famous retreat of Bretton Woods in New Hampshire, USA, to discuss the blueprint for the post-war economic new order. **International bankers began implementing their long-planned scheme: controlling the issuance of currency worldwide.**

At this point, international bankers had already established a series of core organizations: the Royal Institute of International Affairs in the UK and the Council on Foreign Relations in the US. Later, two new branches emerged from these two core organizations: the Bilderberg Group, which handles major political policies in the economic field, and the Trilateral Commission, responsible for political leadership.

The ultimate goal of these organizations is to establish a world government ruled by a few elite individuals from Britain and the US and establish a unified world currency issuance system, followed by levying a "world tax" on all global citizens, known as the "New World Order."

Under such a system, the currency policies and domestic economic decision-making power of all sovereign countries must be stripped away, and the economic and political freedoms of all sovereign countries and their peoples must be manipulated. The shackles on modern people are no longer iron chains but debt. In order to maximize the benefits of every modern "slave," extensive management must transition to the efficient scientific "rearing" stage. A cashless society, electronic currency, international unified RFID identifiers, and implanted identity cards in the human body will become the ultimate symbols of turning modern people into "slaves."

With RFID technology, international bankers will ultimately be able to monitor every person on the planet at any time and location. When cash disappears from society, a few keystrokes on a computer keyboard could potentially deprive anyone of the power to access their own wealth at any time. For anyone who cherishes freedom and power, this is a super terrifying prospect. But for international bankers, this is the ultimate goal of the "New World Order."

The elites believe their plan is not a "conspiracy" but an "**open conspiracy.**" Unlike traditional conspiracies, they do not have a clear leadership structure, only "loosely knit" "like-minded social circles." However, what unsettles ordinary people is that these "like-minded" heavyweight individuals always seem to "enrich" their "ideals" at the expense of ordinary people's interests.

The founder of the Council on Foreign Relations, Colonel House, who advocated for an international alliance after the end of World War I, was an important player in this plan in the United States.

[**Book:** Song Hongbing, **Currency War**, p132, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. **Chinese name:** 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

当罗斯福向美国议员中学识最渊博的盲人参议员托马斯·戈尔询问对他废除金本位的看法时，戈尔冷冷地回答：“这是明显的偷窃，不是吗？总统先生？”对于戈尔参议员的坦率，罗斯福一直耿耿于怀。这位参议员就是后来的美国副总统戈尔的爷爷。

另一位终其一生都在追求恢复金本位的众议员霍华德·巴菲特在1948年指出：“我警告你们，两党的政治家都将反对恢复金本位，在这里和国外靠美国持续货币贬值而大发其财的那些人，也会反对恢复诚实货币的制度。你们必须准备智慧和机警地面对他们的反对。”^[20]

对黄金作为最终货币有着终生信念的老巴菲特没能看到金本位的恢复，但这种信念深深地烙印在他的儿子，当今鼎鼎有名的股神沃伦·巴菲特的脑海中。当巴菲特瞧破法币制度最终必将走向崩溃的历史必然后，在1997年银价跌到靠近历史最低点时，果断地吃进了世界上1/3的实物白银存量。

要彻底拔除黄金在货币中的地位并不是一件简单而轻松的事，这个过程被分为三个阶段来实施。第一步就是废除金币在美国国内的流通与兑换，第二步则是在世界范围内废除黄金的货币功能。1944年布雷顿体系所建立的美元兑换体系（Dollar Exchange Standard）取代黄金兑换体系（Gold Exchange Standard）实现了第二步，后来尼克松总统在1971年才最终完成了第三步。

凯恩斯摇旗呐喊，银行家推波助澜，罗斯福瞒天过海终于拔掉了金本位这个镇魔瓶盖，赤字财政与廉价债务货币这一对孪生怪兽终于从牢笼的禁锢中挣扎了出来。

只看重眼前的权力，“哪怕死后洪水滔天”的凯恩斯有一句名言：“就长久而言，我们都会死”，但是人们的行为及其后果将永远载入历史。

“风险投资”选中希特勒^[21]

1933年11月24日的《纽约时报》报道了一本名为《西德尼·沃伯格》（Sidney Warburg）的小册子。这本书最早于1933年在荷兰出版，在书架上只摆了几天就被取缔了。几本幸存的书被翻译成英文，该书的英文版

Fig. 231-20-1. [Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p122, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

5.5 "Venture Capital" Chooses Hitler

On November 24, 1933, The New York Times reported on a booklet titled "Sidney Warburg." This book was originally published in the Netherlands in 1933 and was only on shelves for a few days before being banned. Several surviving copies were translated into English, and the English version of the book was once exhibited at the British Museum but later restricted from the public and research personnel access. The author of the book, "Sidney Warburg," is believed to be a member of the Warburg family, one of America's largest banking families. However, the contents of the book were later firmly denied by the Warburg family.

Fig. 231-20-2. This mysterious booklet revealed the secret history of banking families in the United States and Britain supporting and aiding Hitler's rise to power.

According to the book, around 1929, Wall Street helped Germany repay war reparations through the Dawes Plan and the Young Plan. From 1924 to 1931, Wall Street provided Germany with a total of 138 billion marks in loans through these two plans, while Germany only paid a total of 86 billion marks in war reparations during this period. In essence, Germany received significant financial assistance from the United States to rearm and prepare for war. The loans to Germany were actually raised

by selling German bonds on Wall Street to raise public funds, with the Morgans and Warburgs making substantial profits.

During this process, an issue arose regarding the pressure policy of the French government on the German reparations issue. This policy led to a significant portion of US loans being frozen in Germany and Austria, with France receiving the majority of German reparations, ultimately sourced from Wall Street. Observing France's increasing dissatisfaction, Wall Street bankers convened a meeting in June 1929. Bankers from the Morgan and Rockefeller families, along with leaders of the Federal Reserve, gathered to discuss how to "liberate" Germany from French pressure through "revolutionary" means. One potential leader was Hitler. Sidney Warburg, armed with U.S. diplomatic passports and personal letters from President Hoover and the Rockefellers, was tasked with making private contact with Hitler.

Sidney's contact with the Nazis didn't go smoothly. The U.S. consulate in Munich was unhelpful, and it was only with the assistance of the Mayor of Munich that he managed to meet Hitler. At their initial meeting, the Wall Street bankers proposed a condition: advocating an aggressive foreign policy and inciting anti-French sentiment. Hitler's demand was also steep, willing to say anything for 100 million marks. Sidney relayed Hitler's offer back to New York, where the bankers felt it was an exorbitant sum, far too high at 24 million dollars, and countered with a bid of 10 million dollars. Hitler, not yet weathered by success, promptly agreed.

According to Hitler's request, this money was transferred to a Dutch bank (Mendelsohn&Co. Bank) and then divided into several batches of checks to be sent to 10 cities in Germany.

When Sidney returned to New York to report to the bankers, Rockefeller became deeply fascinated by Hitler's Nazi ideas. Shortly after, the New York Times, which had previously shown little interest in Hitler, suddenly began regularly featuring introductions to Nazi doctrines and Hitler's speeches. In December 1929, Harvard University also began researching Germany's National Socialist movement.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p123, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

勒的演讲做定期介绍。1929年12月，哈佛大学也开始研究德国的国家社会主义运动。

当1931年胡佛总统答应法国政府，任何债务解决方案都会首先征求法国的意见时，他立刻在华尔街失宠了，很多历史学家认为胡佛总统后来大选失利与这件事有着直接关系。

1931年10月，希特勒给西德尼发了一封信。于是华尔街的银行家召开了另一次会议，这次与会者还有英格兰银行的董事长诺曼。会上形成了两派意见，以洛克菲勒为首的人倾向希特勒，另一些人则态度不太明确。诺曼认为花在希特勒身上的1 000万美元已经够多了，他怀疑希特勒永远也不会行动。会议最终决定进一步支持希特勒。

1 希特勒

西德尼再一次来到德国，在希特勒的支持者的一次会议上，有人向他提出纳粹冲锋队和党卫队非常缺乏机关枪、卡宾枪和手枪。这时，大量的武器装备都已经屯放在德国边境的比利时、荷兰和奥地利的城市，只要纳粹支付现金，立刻可以提货。希特勒对西德尼说他有二个计划——暴力夺权和合法执政。希特勒问道：“暴力夺权需要5亿马克，合法执政需要2亿马克，你们银行家会怎么决定？”

五天以后，华尔街的回电指出：“这样的金额完全无法接受。我们不想也不能接受。对此人解释说这样规模的资金调动到欧洲，会震动整个金融市场。”

西德尼做了进一步的报告，三天以后，华尔街的回电称：“报告收到。准备支付1 000万，最多1 500万美元。告诉这个人采取进攻性对外政策的必要性。”

1 500万美元的合法执政道路被华尔街银行家们最终敲定下来。付款方式必须隐匿资金来源，其中500万付给荷兰阿姆斯特丹的蒙德松银行 (Mendelsohn & Co. Bank)，500万付给鹿特丹银行 (Rotterdamse Bankvereinigung)，500万付给意大利银行 (Banca Italiana)。

1933年2月27日，德国国会纵火案的当天晚上，西德尼和希特勒进行了第三次会谈，希特勒提出还需要至少1亿马克来完成最后的夺权行动。

Fig. 231-20-3. When President Hoover in 1931 promised that any debt settlement with France would first be consulted with the French government, he immediately fell out of favor on Wall Street. Many historians believe that Hoover's subsequent loss in the election was directly related to this incident.

In October 1931, Hitler sent a letter to Sidney. A meeting was then convened by bankers on Wall Street, including the Chairman of the Bank of England, Norman. Two opinions emerged at the meeting, with those led by Rockefeller leaning towards Hitler

while others were less certain. Norman felt that the \$10 million already spent on Hitler was sufficient and doubted whether Hitler would ever act. The meeting ultimately decided to further support Hitler.

Sidney returned to Germany once again, and at a meeting of Hitler supporters, someone raised the issue of the shortage of machine guns, carbines, and pistols for the Nazi Storm Troopers and SS. At this time, a large amount of weaponry was already stockpiled in cities in Belgium, the Netherlands, and Austria on the German border, ready for delivery upon Nazi payment in cash. Hitler told Sidney he had two plans, one involving violent seizure of power and the other legitimate governance, asking, "The violent seizure of power requires 500 million marks, while legitimate governance requires 200 million marks. How will you bankers decide?"

Five days later, the Wall Street correction said, "Such an amount is completely unacceptable. We do not wish to, nor can we accept it. Explaining to this individual that moving funds of this scale to Europe would rock the entire financial market."

Sidney made further reports, and three days later, the callback from Wall Street stated, "Report received. Prepared to pay \$10 million, up to a maximum of \$15 million. Advising the necessity for this individual to adopt an aggressive foreign policy."

The legitimate path to \$15 million was ultimately confirmed by Wall Street bankers. The payment method must conceal the source of funds, with \$5 million allocated to Mendelsohn Bank in Amsterdam, Netherlands, \$5 million paid to Rotterdam Bank, and \$5 million paid to Banca Italiana in Italy.

On February 27, 1933, the night of the Reichstag fire in Germany, Sidney and Hitler held their third meeting. Hitler proposed that he needed at least 100 million marks to complete the final seizure of power, but Wall Street only agreed to provide a maximum of 7 million dollars. Hitler proposed that 5 million be sent to the Italian Bank of Rome and another 2 million to the Renania Joint Stock Company in Düsseldorf.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p124, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

华尔街只答应最多支付700万美元。希特勒提出500万汇到罗马的意大利银行，另外200万汇到杜塞尔多夫的瑞纳尼亚公司（Renania Joint Stock Company）。

在最终完成使命之后，西德尼不禁感慨道：“我严格执行了我的使命直到最后一个细节。希特勒是欧洲最大的独裁者。这个世界已经观察他有几个月的时间了。他的行为最终会证明他的好坏，我认为他是后者。对德国人民而言，我真心想我是错的。这个世界仍然要屈从于希特勒，可怜的世界，可怜的人类。”

华尔街资助下的纳粹德国

1933年1月30日，希特勒被任命为德国总理，德国不仅完全摆脱了1923年超级通货膨胀的经济灾难，也从席卷全球的严重衰退中快速恢复过来。在承担着巨额战争赔款的巨大经济压力下，以惊人的速度装备起欧洲最强大的武装力量，并在1939年9月1日发动第二次世界大战，这一切德国仅仅用了六年时间！

而当时的世界第一强国美国仍然在1929年大衰退的泥沼中苦苦挣扎，直到1941年美国直接参战，其经济状况才得到根本扭转。

德国以区区六年的时间迅速完成经济复苏和大规模战争准备，如果没有外来强大的金融资助是完全不可想象的。如此庞大的外来资金资助如果不是为了准备发动战争，就难以有合乎逻辑的解释。

实际上，华尔街就是纳粹德国最大的资金来源。

早在1924年德国超级通货膨胀刚刚平息下来的时候，华尔街的银行家就开始筹划如何帮助德国整军备战。1924年开始的道威斯计划和1929年的杨计划都是为了这个目的。

1924年的道威斯计划，完美地符合德国参谋本部军事经济学家的计划。^[22]

摩根系的美国通用电气总裁欧文·杨（Owen Young）还是罗斯福创办的联合欧洲投资公司最主要的金融后盾。也是这个欧文·杨创办了协

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Fig. 231-20-4. After accomplishing the ultimate mission, Sidney could not help but reflect, "I strictly followed my mission to the last detail. Hitler is the greatest dictator in Europe. The world has been watching him for several months now. His actions will ultimately confirm his character, and I believe it is the latter. For the German people, I sincerely hope I am wrong. This world still has to submit to Hitler, poor world, poor humanity." The origin and significance of this, we must start with the ups and downs of silver in America.

5.6 Nazi Germany Sponsored by Wall Street

On January 30, 1933, Hitler was appointed as the Chancellor of Germany. Germany not only recovered completely from the economic catastrophe of hyperinflation in 1923, but also swiftly emerged from the severe global recession. Under the immense economic pressure of bearing colossal war reparations, Germany rapidly equipped itself with the strongest military force in Europe and launched the Second World War on September 1, 1939, just six years later!

Meanwhile, the then-leading global power, the United States, was still struggling in the quagmire of the Great Depression of 1929. It wasn't until 1941, when the United States directly entered the war, that its economic situation fundamentally turned around.

It's unimaginable that Germany could achieve such a rapid economic recovery and massive wartime preparations in just six years without substantial external financial assistance. Such substantial foreign funding support could hardly have a logical explanation other than for preparing for war.

In fact, Wall Street was the primary source of funds for Nazi Germany.

As early as when the hyperinflation in Germany had just subsided in 1924, Wall Street bankers began planning how to assist Germany in rearming for war. Both the 1924 Dawes Plan and the 1929 Young Plan were both aimed at this purpose.

"The Dawes Plan of 1924 perfectly matched the plans of German military economists."

The president of General Electric, Owen D. Young, a member of the Morgan group, was also the primary financial backer of Roosevelt's creation, the United European Investment Corporation. It was Owen Young who established the Bank of International Settlements to coordinate international banker cooperation. As Carroll Quigley, a renowned historian and mentor to Clinton at Georgetown University, pointed out, "It (the Bank of International Settlements) was to create a financial system to control the world, one controlled by a few individuals that could dominate the political system and world economy."

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p125, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

调国际银行家合作关系的国际清算银行。恰如克林顿在乔治城大学的恩师，著名历史学家卡洛·奎格雷所指出的那样：“它（国际清算银行）是在制造一个金融系统来控制世界，一个被少数人控制的、能够主宰政治体制和世界经济的（机制）。”^[23]

从1924年到1931年，华尔街通过这两个计划总共向德国提供了1380亿马克的贷款，而德国在此期间总共仅支付了860亿马克的战争赔款，德国实际上是得到了一笔美国资助的520亿马克的巨额金融资助，整个德国军事工业得以迅猛发展。早在1919年，英国首相劳合·乔治就预见到了《凡尔赛和约》中德国无法承担的巨额赔款，最终必然导致德国人要么赖账，要么发动战争，不幸的是两者最后都发生了。

面对纳粹德国一排排崭新的现代化军事工厂，再看看美国在大衰退中锈迹斑斑的生产车间，难怪美国议员麦克法登痛斥华尔街银行家和美联储拿着美国纳税人的金钱去资助德国的战争机器：

主席先生，如果德国的诺贝尔炸药公司出售炸药给日本军队用在满洲（中国东北）或其他的地方，它可以把售货票据用美元结算，然后送到纽约公开贴现市场，美联储银行将对该票据进行贴现，并以此为抵押发行新的美元纸币，美联储实际上就是在帮助德国的炸药公司把它的库存塞进美国的银行系统。既然是这样，我们为什么还要派代表到日内瓦参加（德国）裁军的会议呢？美联储委员会和美联储银行不正在让我国政府为日本军队偿还德国军火公司的债务吗？^[24]

除了在纽约商业票据贴现市场上对德国和日本军事工业提供低息的短期融资，美联储还将美国的黄金储备直接运往德国。

本属于美国银行储户的数量巨大的金钱被送给了德国，而且没有任何抵押。美联储委员会和美联储银行仅仅是靠德国人的商业票据就发放美国货币。几十亿美元的资金被注入德国的经济体，这个过程到今天仍在继续。德国廉价的商业票据在这里（纽约）被定价和延期，被抵押的是美国政府的信誉，而支付费用的是美国人民。

Fig. 231-20-5. From 1924 to 1931, Wall Street provided a total of 138 billion marks in loans to Germany through these two plans, while Germany only paid a total of 86 billion marks in war reparations during this period. In essence, Germany received a staggering 52 billion marks in financial assistance from the United States. This massive influx of funds facilitated the rapid development of the German military industry. As early as 1919, British Prime Minister Lloyd George foresaw the enormous reparations

that Germany could not afford under the Treaty of Versailles, ultimately leading to either default or war. Unfortunately, both eventually happened.

Faced with rows of brand-new modern military factories in Nazi Germany and looking back at the rusty production workshops of America in the midst of the Great Depression, **it's no wonder that U.S. Senator McFadden vehemently criticized Wall Street bankers and the Federal Reserve for using American taxpayers' money to support Germany's war machine:**

"Mr. Chairman, if the Nobel Dynamite Trust Company of Germany sells dynamite to the Japanese military for use in Manchuria or elsewhere, it can settle its bills in dollars, which are then sent to the New York open discount market, where the Federal Reserve Banks discount the bills, using them as collateral to issue new U.S. currency. In essence, the Federal Reserve is helping the German dynamite company stuff its inventory into the American banking system. If that's the case, why are we sending representatives to disarmament conferences in Geneva? Isn't the Federal Reserve Board and the Federal Reserve Banks making our government pay off debts to German arms companies for the Japanese military?"

In addition to providing low-interest short-term financing to the German and Japanese military industries on the New York commercial paper discount market, the Federal Reserve also directly transported America's gold reserves to Germany.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p126, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

1932年4月27日，美联储运出了价值75万美元的本属于美国人民的黄金给德国。一个星期之后，另外30万美元的黄金以同样的方式运往德国。仅在5月中旬就有高达1 200万美元的黄金被美联储委员会和美联储银行运往德国。几乎每个星期都有驶往德国的黄金运输船。主席先生，我相信美国银行的储蓄者有权知道美联储用他们的钱在干什么。^[25]

除了华尔街的巨额资助，希特勒的金融制度改革也起到了相当大的作用，其中最关键的一点就是从德国私有中央银行手中收回了货币发行权。在摆脱了以国债为抵押才能发行货币的低效率高消耗程序之后，德国的经济如火箭般地蹿升，德国的失业率在1933年时高达30%，到1938年却出现了劳工紧缺。

美国公司对德国在技术和金融方面的巨大扶持早已不是什么秘密，这些扶持被后来的历史学家解释为“意外事件或短视行为”。正是这些“意外的短视”极大地提高了德国军事工业的生产能力。

1934年，德国的石油生产能力为30万吨天然石油和80万吨合成汽油（煤转油），剩余部分完全依靠进口。在美国标准石油公司的氢化石油专利转让给德国之后，到1944年，德国竟能生产550万吨合成汽油和100万吨天然石油。

尽管德国军事计划部门要求工业企业安装现代化的生产设备来进行大规模的生产，但是德国的军事经济专家和工业企业并没有完全理解大规模生产的含义，直到美国两家主要的汽车生产厂为打入欧洲市场在德国建立新式工厂之后，才让他们大开眼界。德国专家被派到底特律去学习模块生产的专业技术和流水线作业。德国工程师不仅参观了飞机制造厂，还被允许观看了其他重要军事设施，他们从中学到了大量的技术，并最终用这些技术来对付美国。^[26]

与德国军事工业生产体系保持密切合作关系的美国公司还有通用汽车、福特汽车、通用电气、杜邦公司等，它们都属于摩根银行、洛克菲勒的大通银行或沃伯格的曼哈顿银行。

Fig. 231-20-6. "The vast sums of money that rightfully belonged to American bank depositors were sent to Germany, without any collateral. The Federal Reserve Board and the Federal Reserve Banks issued U.S. currency solely based on German trade bills. Billions of dollars flowed into the German economy through this process, which continues to this day. German cheap trade bills are priced and deferred here (in New

York), backed by the credit of the United States government, while the expenses are borne by the American people. On April 27, 1932, the Federal Reserve shipped \$750,000 worth of gold, belonging to the American people, to Germany. A week later, another \$300,000 of gold was shipped to Germany in the same manner. By mid-May, as much as \$12 million worth of gold had been shipped to Germany by the Federal Reserve Board and the Federal Reserve Banks. There were shipments of gold to Germany almost every week. Mr. Chairman, I believe the savers of American banks have the right to know what the Federal Reserve is doing with their money."

In addition to massive funding from Wall Street, Hitler's financial reforms also played a significant role, with the most crucial being the retrieval of currency issuance rights from Germany's private central bank. After getting rid of the inefficient and costly process of issuing currency backed by government bonds, Germany's economy soared like a rocket. In 1933, Germany's unemployment rate was as high as 30%, but by 1938, there was a labor shortage.

It's no secret that American companies provided substantial support to Germany in technology and finance, which later historians explained as "accidental or shortsighted actions." It was precisely this "accidental shortsightedness" that greatly improved Germany's military industrial production capacity.

By 1934, Germany's oil production capacity was 300,000 tons of natural oil and 800,000 tons of synthetic gasoline (coal to oil), with the remainder relying entirely on imports. After the transfer of Standard Oil's hydrogenation patents to Germany, by 1944, Germany was able to produce 5.5 million tons of synthetic gasoline and 1 million tons of natural oil.

"Although some of Germany's military plans required industrial enterprises to install modern production equipment for large-scale production, German military economists and industrial enterprises did not fully understand the meaning of mass production until two major American automobile manufacturers established new factories in Germany to penetrate the European market, which opened their eyes. German experts were sent to Detroit to learn professional techniques and assembly line operations for modular production. German engineers not only visited aircraft factories but were also promised access to other important military facilities, from which they learned a lot of technology and ultimately used it to compete with the United States."

American companies that maintained close cooperation with the German military industrial production system included General Motors, Ford Motor Company, General Electric, and DuPont, all of which were owned by Morgan Bank, Rockefeller Chase Bank, or the Manhattan Bank of Warburg.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p127, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

昂贵的战争与廉价的货币

丘吉尔曾有一句名言：“发动战争远比结束战争要困难得多。”乍听起来，此话不合常理，仔细品味才发现确是至理名言。结束一场战争往往只需要交战双方政府的秘密代表坐在一起讨价还价一番，无非是讨论结束冲突的条件而已，或亏一些，或赚一点，没有谈不成的交易。

但是发动战争就困难多了，凝聚社会共识在民主社会是一件极端费神的事，这一点的确愁坏了国际银行家们。

正如默顿所指出的那样，“在他们（国际银行家）的眼里没有战争与和平，没有口号和宣言，也没有牺牲或荣誉，他们忽略了这些迷惑世人眼睛的东西。”

看清了国际银行家本质的拿破仑也曾一针见血地说道：“金钱没有祖国，金融家不知道何为爱国和高尚，他们的唯一目的就是获利。”

饱受华尔街银行家洗劫的美国人民，在经历了第一次世界大战和1929年大萧条之后，也不那么容易上当了，没有人愿意充当银行家的炮灰再把子女送到欧洲去打仗，于是举国上下充满了被银行家痛恨的“孤立主义”气氛。

1935年，参议员奈伊领导的特别委员会发布了厚达1400多页的报告，详细披露了美国参加一战的秘密，历数银行家和军火公司在参战过程中的阴谋和不法行为，再加上不久前摩根听证会对华尔街在1929年股票暴跌中的种种丑闻披露，使得人民的反战情绪极为强烈。此时，米里斯的畅销书《迈向战争之路》更激起了民众对参战问题的激辩。在此民意之下，美国从1935年到1937年先后通过三项中立法案，严禁美国再次被诱骗而卷入战争。

在国内经济方面，罗斯福新政已经开始五年多了，美国经济始终不见起色，失业率仍然高达17%，到1938年美国再次陷入严重的衰退。

银行家们和罗斯福都认为只有凯恩斯所提倡的超级赤字财政、狂发廉价货币才能挽救经济，而只有大规模战争才能达到这样的效果。

在1933年废除金本位之后，所有通往战争之路上的障碍都已被搬开，万事俱备只欠战争借口。

Churchill once said, "It is much easier to start a war than to end it." At first glance, this statement seems illogical, but after careful consideration, it is indeed profound.

Ending a war often requires only secret representatives of the warring parties to sit down and negotiate, merely agreeing on terms to cease the conflict, whether it's at a loss or gain, there is no deal that cannot be made.

However, starting a war is much more difficult. Rallying societal consensus, especially in democratic societies, is an extremely arduous task that has truly vexed international bankers.

As Morton pointed out, "In their eyes (the international bankers), there is no war or peace, no slogans or declarations, no sacrifices or honors. They overlook these things that confuse the public."

Napoleon, who saw through the essence of international bankers, bluntly stated, "Money has no homeland, financiers do not know patriotism or nobility, their only aim is profit."

The American people, who had been plundered by Wall Street bankers, after experiencing World War I and the Great Depression of 1929, were not so easily fooled. No one was willing to be the bankers' cannon fodder again and send their children to Europe to fight. Therefore, the atmosphere of "isolationism," which was hated by bankers, pervaded the entire country.

In 1935, the Special Committee led by Senator Nye released a report of over 1400 pages, revealing in detail the secrets behind America's involvement in World War I, enumerating the conspiracies and illicit activities of bankers and arms manufacturers during the war. Coupled with the recent revelations of various scandals on Wall Street during the 1929 stock market crash hearings, public anti-war sentiment was extremely strong. At this time, Merrill's bestselling book "Road to War" further sparked public debate on the issue of involvement in the war. Under this public sentiment, the United States passed three neutrality acts from 1935 to 1937, strictly prohibiting being deceived into another war.

In terms of the domestic economy, Roosevelt's New Deal had been in place for over five years, yet the American economy showed no signs of improvement, with the unemployment rate still as high as 17%. By 1938, the United States plunged into another severe recession.

Both bankers and Roosevelt believed that only Keynesian deficit financing, coupled with the issuance of cheap currency, could save the economy, and that only large-scale war could achieve such an effect.

After the abolition of the gold standard in 1933, all obstacles on the road to war had been removed, and everything was ready, only lacking a pretext for war.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p128, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

乔治城大学历史教授查尔斯·坦西尔 (Charles C. Tansill) 认为，对日本的作战早在1933年罗斯福上台之前就已经计划好了。1932年，美国海军就已经证实了从珍珠港海域60英里发动袭击可以重创太平洋舰队。美国情报部门于1940年8月破译了日本军方的密码，并可以解码所有早前截获的日本电报记录。美国制造的破译密码机被送到了世界各地，唯独漏掉了珍珠港这个美国在太平洋最大的海军基地。许多历史学家都相信，罗斯福事先就已经知道日本海军将偷袭珍珠港。

1943年1月13日，罗斯福和丘吉尔在卡萨布兰卡发表了德国必须无条件投降的声明，这个声明令德国内部开始反对希特勒，主张与盟国媾和的势力大吃一惊。德国本来早在1942年8月就提出了和盟国媾和的条件，愿意退回1939年9月1日之前的边境，以结束这一场德国必败的战争。^[27]

德国内部主张推翻希特勒和纳粹政权的力量已经在着手策划军事政变，罗斯福的声明严重打击了德国内部反战力量的影响力。基辛格是这样解释罗斯福卡萨布拉卡宣言的动机的：

罗斯福基于若干理由而做出这项声明（德国必须无条件投降）。他担心讨论对德和平条件可能使盟国内部意见出现分歧，他希望盟国先集中力量打赢战争再说，他也急于向陷于斯大林格勒战役僵局的斯大林担保，绝不单独对德议和。但是，最基本的原因是罗斯福力图避免日后德国的修正主义人士起来声称，德国当年是被空口承诺诳骗才停战的。^[28]

基辛格说的当然有道理，但事实是，残酷和代价高昂的战争被延长了两年多，无数生命和财富化为灰烬。其中就包括600万死于纳粹之手的犹太人，如果战争于1943年结束，他们中的相当一部分人非常可能得以幸存，毕竟在德国有条件投降的协议上，盟国可以有很大的发言权。

但是，刚刚才热了热身的国际银行家岂可轻易放过发大财的好机会。当战火在1945年8月最终熄灭时，美国的国债从1930年仅160亿美元涨到1946年的2 690亿美元，凯恩斯的赤字财政和廉价货币的主张终于在第二次世界大战的硝烟中得到“验证”。国际银行家们在第二次世界大战中再次大发了一笔横财。

Fig. 231-20-8.

Georgetown University history professor Charles C. Tansill believed that the plan for war against Japan had been formulated as early as 1933, before Roosevelt took office. In 1932, the U.S. Navy confirmed that an attack launched from 60 miles off the coast of Pearl Harbor could cripple the Pacific Fleet. In August 1940, U.S. intelligence

decrypted Japanese military codes and could decipher all previously intercepted Japanese telegrams. American-made decryption machines were sent all over the world, except for Pearl Harbor, the largest naval base in the Pacific for the United States. Many historians believe that Roosevelt had advanced knowledge of the Japanese naval attack on Pearl Harbor.

On January 13, 1943, Roosevelt and Churchill issued a statement in Casablanca demanding Germany's unconditional surrender, which shocked forces inside Germany opposing Hitler and advocating for peace with the Allies. Germany had already proposed terms for peace with the Allies as early as August 1942, offering to withdraw to the borders before September 1, 1939, to end this war that Germany was bound to lose.

The forces within Germany advocating for the overthrow of Hitler and the Nazi regime had already begun planning a military coup, and Roosevelt's statement dealt a severe blow to the influence of the anti-war forces within Germany. Kissinger explained the motive behind Roosevelt's Casablanca declaration: "Roosevelt made this declaration (Germany must surrender unconditionally) for several reasons. He feared that discussing peace terms with Germany might lead to internal disagreements among the Allies. He hoped that the Allies would concentrate on winning the war first before discussing peace terms. He also wanted to reassure Stalin, who was bogged down in the Stalingrad battle, that there would be no separate negotiations with Germany. However, the most fundamental reason was Roosevelt's attempt to avoid future German revisionists claiming that Germany had been deceived into a ceasefire by empty promises."

Kissinger's explanation makes sense, but the fact remains that the brutal and costly war was prolonged for more than two years, countless lives and wealth turned to ashes. Among them were 6 million Jews who died at the hands of the Nazis. If the war had ended in 1943, a significant portion of them might have survived. Indeed, the Allies could have had a significant say in the conditions for Germany's surrender.

However, the international bankers, who had just warmed up, could not easily pass up the opportunity to make a fortune. When the flames of war finally extinguished in August 1945, America's national debt skyrocketed from a mere \$16 billion in 1930 to \$269 billion in 1946. Keynesian deficit financing and the advocacy of cheap currency were finally "validated" amid the smoke of the Second World War. Once again, international bankers reaped huge profits during World War II.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p129, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

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Fig. 231-20-9. [Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p130, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, *货币战争* 中信出版社, 北京, 2007年]

第七章

诚实货币的最后抗争

历史表明，放贷者会使用包括滥用权力、诡计、欺骗和暴力在内的一切手段来确保他们对货币和货币发行的控制，以便达到控制政府的目的。

詹姆斯·麦迪逊，美国第4届总统

Fig. 231-20-10. "History shows that lenders will use all means, including abuse of power, deceit, trickery, and violence, to ensure their control over currency and its issuance, in order to achieve control over governments."

- James Madison, 4th President of the United States

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p157, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵，货币战争 中信出版社，北京，2007年]

本章导读

在整个世界现代史中，没有一个事件像刺杀肯尼迪总统这样明目张胆、毫无掩饰、无所顾忌地践踏民主政治了。

在肯尼迪被刺杀后的短短三年中，18名关键证人相继死亡，其中6人被枪杀，3人死于车祸，2人自杀，1人被割喉，1人被拧断了脖子，5人“自然”死亡。英国的一名数学家在1967年2月的《伦敦星期日时报》中声称，这种巧合的概率为10万万亿分之一。从1963年到1993年，115名相关证人在各种离奇的事件中自杀或被谋杀。

如此大规模的协调和组织，如此明显的证据和证人封杀，都说明肯尼迪遇刺事件其实已经不是一次秘密谋杀，而更像是公开处决，意在警告今后的美国总统们要搞清楚谁才是这个国家的真正主宰！

一般说来，如果美国总统死于任内，“舆论”必然一致认为是“自然原因死亡”。如果总统是在众目睽睽之下被枪杀，“舆论”就会报道“凶手是个孤僻的疯子”。如果有好几个凶手涉案，“舆论”则会断定“凶手们是互不相识的孤僻的疯子”。谁要是有任何疑问，谁就会被嘲笑为“阴谋论者”。只是刺杀肯尼迪的阴谋太过明显，稍有正常思维能力的人都不会相信官方的结论。在这种情况下，有意误导阴谋论的方向，就成为一种补救措施，于是40多年来，各种阴谋解说泛滥成灾，而真正的阴谋得以“大隐于朝”。

刑侦学讲究的是证据，没有证据就无法得出结论。在40多年的岁月里，肯尼迪遇刺案的各种证据和证人早已灰飞烟灭了，人们将永远无法得到确凿的证据来判断究竟谁是真正的凶手。但是犯罪心理学却可能从另一个角度出发，研究谋杀案件的动机，从而打开通向真相的大门。

本章将从分析肯尼迪遇刺案件的动机入手，揭开20世纪60、70年代国际银行家为了在世界范围内废除黄金和白银这两种“诚实的货币”，所引发的一系列惊心动魄的历史事件。

Fig. 231-20-11. "In the entire modern history of the world, no event has been so openly, unabashedly, and unscrupulously trampled upon democratic politics as the assassination of President Kennedy.

In the mere three years following Kennedy's assassination, 18 key witnesses died successively: 6 were shot, 3 died in car accidents, 2 committed suicide, 1 was throat-

cut, 1 had his neck broken, and 5 died from "natural" causes. A mathematician from Britain claimed in the London Sunday Times in February 1967 that the probability of such coincidences was one in ten million billion. From 1963 to 1993, 115 related witnesses either committed suicide or were murdered in various bizarre incidents.

Such large-scale coordination and organization, along with blatant evidence and witness suppression, all indicate that Kennedy assassination was not merely a secret murder, but more akin to public execution, aimed at warning future U.S. presidents to understand who the true masters of this country are.

Generally speaking, if a U.S. president dies in office, the "consensus" will inevitably attribute it to "natural causes." If the president is assassinated in plain sight, the "consensus" will report that the "assassin is a solitary madman." If there are several perpetrators involved, the "consensus" will conclude that "the perpetrators are solitary madmen who do not know each other." Anyone who has doubts will be ridiculed as a "conspiracy theorist." However, the Kennedy assassination conspiracy was too obvious; anyone with normal reasoning abilities would not believe the official conclusion. In such a scenario, deliberately misleading the direction of conspiracy theories becomes a remedial measure. Thus, for over forty years, various conspiracy theories have proliferated, while the real conspiracy remains 'hidden in broad daylight.'

Forensic science emphasizes evidence; without evidence, no conclusions can be drawn. Over the course of more than forty years, various evidence and witnesses related to the Kennedy assassination have long since vanished into thin air, and people will never be able to obtain conclusive evidence to determine who the real culprit is. However, criminal psychology may approach it from another angle, studying the motives behind murder cases, thereby opening the door to truth.

This chapter will begin by analyzing the motives behind the Kennedy assassination case, unveiling a series of thrilling historical events triggered by international bankers in the 1960s and 1970s, aiming to abolish gold and silver, the two 'honest currencies,' worldwide."

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p158, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

总统令11110号：肯尼迪的死亡证书

对于美国人来说，1963年11月22日是一个不寻常的日子，肯尼迪总统在得克萨斯州的达拉斯市遇刺身亡。噩耗传来，整个美国都陷入了震惊和悲伤之中。

几十年以后，人们在说起这一时刻时，很多人都能清楚地记得当时自己在干什么。究竟是谁、为什么刺杀肯尼迪至今仍众说纷纭。美国官方的沃伦委员会的最终结论是一个名叫奥斯瓦德的凶手单独作案，但是此案的疑点实在太多，几十年来社会上流传着各种阴谋论。

↑ 肯尼迪遇刺前两分钟

最明显的疑点是凶手被警方抓获不到48小时，就在众目睽睽之下被另一名犹太杀手近距离枪杀，上百万人在电视机旁看到了谋杀全过程，而该凶手的动机竟然是“要向全世界的人展示犹太人的胆量”。

另一个巨大的疑点是到底几个人参与了谋杀肯尼迪。沃伦委员会的结论是奥斯瓦德在5.6秒的时间里连发三枪，其中一发子弹打飞，一发击中肯尼迪的颈部，另外一发致命的子弹命中肯尼迪头部。几乎没有人相信奥斯瓦德能在这样短的时间里准确射击三次，更奇怪的是打中肯尼迪颈部的子弹是先击中了肯尼迪后，再射中坐在肯尼迪前方的德州州长的，而这样的概率几乎为零，所以人们称之为“神奇的子弹”。更多的专家相信，不止一人从不同的方向朝肯尼迪开枪，而且不止三发子弹。

据后来护卫肯尼迪车驾的一名巡警回忆：“当肯尼迪在机场忙着和欢迎的人群握手时，约翰逊（副总统）的秘密特勤（secret service）走过来

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Fig. 231-20-12. For Americans, November 22, 1963, was an extraordinary day. President Kennedy was assassinated in Dallas, Texas. When the shocking news spread, the whole country was plunged into shock and sorrow. Decades later, many can still vividly recall what they were doing at that moment. The identity of the assassin and the reasons for Kennedy's assassination remain subjects of debate. The official conclusion from the Warren Commission was that a lone gunman named Oswald committed the act, but there have been many conspiracy theories circulating in society for decades.

The most glaring question is why Oswald, the alleged assassin, was shot dead by another Jewish assassin within 48 hours of his arrest, in full public view. Millions watched the murder unfold on television, and the killer's motive was reportedly to "show the world the courage of the Jewish people."

Another major question is how many people were involved in Kennedy's assassination. The Warren Commission concluded that Oswald fired three shots in 5.6 seconds, one missing, one hitting Kennedy's neck, and another hitting his head, causing fatal injury. Few believe Oswald could have accurately fired three shots in such a short time. In addition, the bullet that hit Kennedy's neck reportedly first hit Texas Governor Connally, who was sitting in front of Kennedy, before hitting Kennedy. The probability of this happening is almost zero, leading to the bullet being called a "magic bullet." Many experts believe that more than one person shot at Kennedy from different directions and that more than three bullets were fired.

[Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p159, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

给我们做安全工作指示。最让我吃惊的是他们说总统在德利广场（刺杀现场）的行车路线临时做了修改。如果保持原来的路线，杀手可能完全

↑ 杰克·卢比枪杀奥斯瓦德
来源：维基百科

没有机会下手。他们还给我们下了一个闻所未闻的命令，通常情况下，我们四个摩托护警应该紧靠总统座车的四周，但是他们这次让我们全部退到车后，任何情况下不得超过总统座车的后轮。他们说这是为了让大家有一个‘没有遮拦的视野’……我的另一位朋友（保护副总统约翰逊）看见他（约翰逊）在第一发子弹飞出前30

或40秒时，开始在车里弯下身来，甚至在车队拐上休斯敦大街之前就这样做。也许他在车里的地毯上找什么东西，但是他看起来就好像预感到会有子弹飞过来一样。”^[1]

当第一夫人杰奎琳随着丈夫的遗体乘空军一号到达华盛顿机场时，她仍然穿着溅满肯尼迪鲜血的大衣，她坚持这样做就是为了“让他们看看自己犯下的罪恶”。此时的凶手奥斯瓦德仍被警方看押，杰奎琳所说的“他们”又是谁？杰奎琳在自己的遗嘱中说道，在她死后50周年（2044年5月19日），如果她最小的孩子已经去世，她授权肯尼迪图书馆公开一份500页的关于肯尼迪的文件。让她没有想到的是，她最小的儿子在1999年的一次飞机失事中丧了命。

肯尼迪的弟弟罗伯特，著名的民权运动推动者，在1968年当选民主党总统候选人之后，几乎肯定可以最终当选总统，但是就在他欢庆胜利的时候，又是在大庭广众之下被乱枪打死。

在肯尼迪被刺杀后的短短三年中，18名关键证人相继死亡，其中6人被枪杀，3人死于车祸，2人自杀，1人被割喉，1人被拧断了脖子，5人“自然”死亡。英国的一名数学家在1967年2月的《伦敦星期日时报》中声称，这种巧合的概率为10万万亿分之一。从1963年到1993年，115名相

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Fig. 231-20-13. According to a later recollection from a police officer who was guarding Kennedy's car, "As Kennedy was busy shaking hands with the welcoming crowd at the airport, Vice President Johnson's Secret Service came over to give us security instructions. What surprised me the most was when they said the president's

motorcade route at Dealey Plaza (the assassination site) had been changed at the last minute. If the original route had been maintained, the assassin might not have had any chance. They also gave us an unheard-of order. Typically, the four motorcycle escorts should be close to the president's car on all sides, but this time they made us all retreat behind the car, never to go beyond the rear wheels of the president's car under any circumstances. They said it was for everyone to have an 'unobstructed view'... My other friend (protecting Vice President Johnson) saw him (Johnson) starting to bend down in the car about 30 or 40 seconds before the first shot, even before the motorcade turned onto Houston Street. Maybe he was looking for something on the car floor, but he seemed to anticipate bullets coming his way."

As First Lady Jacqueline arrived at Washington Airport with her husband's body aboard Air Force One, she was still wearing a coat splattered with Kennedy's blood. She insisted on doing so to let "they see what they did," while Oswald, the perpetrator, was still in police custody. But who were "they"? In her will, Jacqueline stated that on the 50th anniversary of her death (May 19, 2044), if her youngest child had also passed away, she authorized the Kennedy Library to release a 500-page dossier about Kennedy. What she didn't anticipate was her youngest son's death in a plane crash in 1999.

Kennedy's brother Robert, a prominent civil rights advocate who was almost certain to ultimately become president after being elected the Democratic Party's presidential candidate in 1968, was tragically assassinated in public as he celebrated his victory.

After Kennedy's assassination, in just three short years, 18 key witnesses died one after another. Among them, 6 were shot, 3 died in car accidents, 2 committed suicide, 1 was stabbed in the throat, 1 had their neck twisted, and 5 died of "natural" causes. A British mathematician claimed in a February 1967 article in the London Sunday Times that the odds of these coincidences occurring were a 1 in 1,000,000,000,000. From 1963 to 1993, 115 related witnesses died of suicide or murder in various bizarre incidents.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p160, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

关证人在各种离奇的事件中自杀或被谋杀。^[2]

沃伦委员会让人生疑的还有封存所有文件、档案和证据长达75年，直到2039年才解密，这些文件涉及CIA、FBI、总统特警保镖、NSA（国家安全局）、国务院、海军陆战队等机构。另外，FBI和其他政府机构还涉嫌销毁证据。

2003年，肯尼迪遇刺40周年，美国ABC广播公司搞了一次调查，70%的美国人认为刺杀肯尼迪是一个更大规模的阴谋。

如此大规模的协调和组织，如此明显的证据和证人的封杀，都说明肯尼迪遇刺事件其实已经不是一次秘密谋杀，而更像是公开处决，意在警告今后的美国总统们要搞清楚谁才是这个国家的真正主宰。

问题是，肯尼迪家族也是国际银行家集团的“圈里人”，其父约瑟夫·肯尼迪就是在1929年股票崩盘时大发其财，后来被罗斯福总统任命为首届美国证券交易委员会（SEC）主席，早在20世纪40年代就跻身亿万富豪的行列了。如果没有这样显赫的家境，肯尼迪也不可能成为美国历史上第一位信仰天主教的总统。那么肯尼迪何以得罪了整个统治精英阶层，以至于落得杀身之祸呢？

毫无疑问，肯尼迪是一位富有雄心和才干的人物，年纪轻轻的他一坐上总统的宝座，就碰上了古巴导弹危机这样的重大挑战，他的表现坚定沉稳，可圈可点，面对和苏联可能爆发核战争的巨大危险而毫不妥协，最终逼退了赫鲁晓夫。肯尼迪还意气风发地推动了美国航天计划，最终使人类的足迹第一次踏上了月球，尽管他没能亲眼看到这一伟大的时刻，但他的神奇的感召力却伴随着整个计划。在推动民权运动方面，肯尼迪兄弟更是功勋卓著。1962年当第一名黑人大学生试图到密西西比大学注册时，引发了当地白人的强烈反对，全美国的目光都聚焦在了民权运动的这个焦点上。肯尼迪毅然下令出动400名联邦执法人员和3 000名国民警卫队队员护送这名黑人学生上学，此举震惊了美国社会，肯尼迪顿时深得人民爱戴。在他的号召下，美国青年踊跃参加和平队，志愿奔赴第三世界国家去帮助发展当地的教育、卫生和农业。

肯尼迪在主政的短短三年中，能有如此耀眼的政绩，的确堪称一代豪杰。这样雄才大略的抱负，如此果断坚毅的心志，再加上美国人民的

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Fig. 231-20-14. The Warren Commission's actions raised further suspicions by sealing all files, records, and evidence for 75 years until 2039, involving agencies such as the CIA, FBI, Secret Service, NSA, State Department, and Marines. Additionally, the FBI and other government agencies were suspected of destroying evidence.

In 2003, the 40th anniversary of Kennedy's assassination, ABC conducted a survey revealing that 70% of Americans believed Kennedy's killing was part of a larger conspiracy.

The extensive coordination and organization, along with glaring evidence and witnesses, suggest that Kennedy's assassination was not merely a secret murder but more akin to public execution, aimed at warning future U.S. presidents to understand who truly rules the country.

The question remains: Why did the Kennedy family, entrenched in the circles of international bankers—his father Joseph having amassed great wealth during the 1929 stock market crash, later appointed by President Roosevelt as the inaugural chairman of the SEC—offend the entire ruling elite to the point of facing deadly consequences? Without a doubt, Kennedy was an ambitious and talented figure. He ascended to the presidency at a young age and faced significant challenges such as the Cuban Missile Crisis. His performance was steadfast and commendable; he refused to compromise in the face of the immense danger of nuclear war with the Soviet Union, ultimately forcing Khrushchev to retreat. Kennedy also enthusiastically promoted the U.S. space program, which ultimately led humanity to set foot on the moon for the first time. Although he did not live to see this great moment, his charismatic influence accompanied the whole endeavor.

In advancing the civil rights movement, the Kennedy brothers were particularly distinguished. In 1962, when the first black student attempted to register at the University of Mississippi, sparking intense opposition from local whites, the nation's attention focused on this focal point of the civil rights movement. Kennedy decisively ordered 400 federal law enforcement officers and 3,000 National Guardsmen to escort the black student to school, a move that shook American society and instantly endeared Kennedy to the people. Inspired by his call, American youth enthusiastically joined the Peace Corps, volunteering to help develop education, health, and agriculture in third world countries.

In Kennedy's brief three years in office, achieving such remarkable accomplishments truly made him a hero of his time. With such grand ambitions, resolute determination, the love of the American people, and the admiration of countries around the world, Kennedy was certainly not a figure willing to be a "puppet".

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p161, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

热爱和世界各地的敬仰，肯尼迪岂是愿做“傀儡”的人物?!

当肯尼迪越来越强烈地想按照自己良好的意愿来运作这个国家时，他就必然与他背后的强大而无形的统治精英集团产生尖锐的冲突。当冲突的焦点涉及国际银行家最核心、最敏感的问题——货币发行权的时候，肯尼迪也许并不知道自己的大限已经到了。

1963年6月4日，肯尼迪签署了一份鲜为人知的11110号总统令^[3]，着令美国财政部“以财政部所拥有的任何形式的白银，包括银锭、银币和标准白银美元银币（Silver Dollar）作为支撑，发行‘白银券’（Silver Certificate）”，并立刻进入货币流通。

肯尼迪的意图十分明显：从私有的中央银行——美联储手中夺回货币发行权！如果该计划最终得以实施，美国政府将逐步摆脱必须从美联储“借钱”并支付高昂利息的荒谬境地，并且以白银为支撑的货币不是“透支未来”的债务货币，而是基于人们已有劳动成果的“诚实货币”。“白银券”的流通将逐渐降低美联储发行的“美元”（Federal Reserve Note）的流通度，很可能最终迫使美联储银行破产。

如果失去控制货币发行的权力，国际银行家对美国这个最大的财富创造国将失去大部分影响力，这是关乎生死存亡的根本问题。

要搞清楚11110号总统令的由来和意义，我们必须从白银美元在美国的几起几落说起。

白银美元的历史地位

白银在美国成为合法货币始于《1792年铸币法案》（*Coinage Act of 1792*），该法案奠定了美元的法律地位。1美元包含纯银24.1克，金银比为1比15。美元作为美国货币最基准的度量衡是以白银为基础的。此美国长期保持金银货币双轨制。^[4]

到了1873年2月，《1873年铸币法案》^[5]在欧洲罗斯柴尔德家族的努力下，废除了白银的货币地位，实行了单一的金本位。由于罗斯柴尔德家族掌握着世界上大部分的黄金矿产和黄金供应，他们实际上控制了个欧洲的货币供应。白银的产地比黄金更为分散，产量和供应量也大

Fig. 231-20-15. As Kennedy increasingly sought to govern the country according to his own good intentions, he inevitably clashed sharply with the powerful and invisible elite ruling behind him. When the conflict centered on the most sensitive issue of currency

issuance, dominated by international bankers and the ruling elite, Kennedy perhaps did not realize that his time was running out.

On June 4, 1963, Kennedy signed little-known Executive Order 11110, instructing the U.S. Treasury Department of the Treasury to "issue silver certificates against any silver bullion, silver, or standard silver dollar in the Treasury," and to put them into circulation immediately. Kennedy's intent was clear: to wrest control of currency issuance away from the privately owned central bank, the Federal Reserve! If this plan were ultimately implemented, the U.S. government would gradually free itself from the absurdity of having to "borrow" money from the Federal Reserve and pay exorbitant interest, and the currency backed by silver would not be a debt-based currency of "borrowed future," but an "honest currency" based on the existing fruits of people's labor. The circulation of "silver certificates" would gradually diminish the circulation of "Federal Reserve Notes" issued by the Federal Reserve, possibly eventually forcing the Federal Reserve banks into bankruptcy.

If the power to control currency issuance were lost, international bankers would lose much of their influence on the United States, the largest wealth-generating country, which is a fundamental issue of life and death.

To understand the origin and significance of Executive Order 11110, we must begin with the ups and downs of silver in America.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p162, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

Stone & Webster等美国各类公司将在未来几十年赚得盆满钵满。

帕金还想到了更远的前景，保护阿拉伯半岛所产生的巨大产业链：美国军事基地建设，国防工业合同和其他相关的一切活动的合同，还包括更加庞大的管理与服务合同。而这一切又会产生新一波的工程建设合同，诸如军用机场、导弹基地、人员培训中心等所有与之相关的项目。

帕金的目标是，不仅要让石油美元绝大部分流回美国，还要使这笔巨款所产生的利息收益全部花在美国公司身上。

沙特人会对此“现代化”的工业基础设施和城市市容备感骄傲，其他欧佩克国家将艳羡沙特如此迅速地变成了一个“现代国家”，然后这一套计划将被用于其他国家。

帕金的出色计划和游说能力令幕后大老板非常满意，在这样一个大计划之下，基辛格博士于1974年来到沙特，最终敲定了石油美元的大政方针。

脱离了金本位庇护的风雨飘摇中的美元，终于找到了石油这个避难所。

里根遇刺：粉碎金本位的最后希望

尽管在世界范围内，金本位已经被全面废除，除了瑞士等极少数国家，黄金与纸币已经全然没有任何联系，但是最让国际银行家寝食难安的还是黄金的价格在整个70年代的持续上涨，防止金本位复辟乃国际银行家最高优先级的工作。

1975年1月1日，为了向世人展现黄金不过是一种普通金属，增加人们对纯纸币美元的信心，美国政府决定解除对美国人民实行了长达40年的黄金持有禁令。其他国家对黄金则采取课以重税的办法来减少人民对黄金的需求，有的甚至征收高达50%的黄金增值税。美国人在黄金消失了40年后，已经对黄金非常生疏了，再加上购买的烦琐与不便，黄金解禁并没有产生预想的紧张局面，国际银行家终于长长地松了一口气。当后来的美联储主席保罗·沃尔克看到前中央银行家约翰·埃克斯特手中玩弄的金币时，不禁好奇地问道：“约翰，你的金币是从哪里买的？”

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Fig. 231-20-16. **7.8 Reagan's Assassination: The Last Hope of Shattering the Gold Standard**

Although the gold standard has been completely abolished worldwide, except for a few countries like the Swiss franc, where gold still has some connection with paper currency, the skyrocketing price of gold throughout the 1970s remains the biggest concern for international bankers. Preventing the return of the gold standard is their

top priority.

On January 1, 1975, to demonstrate that gold is just a regular metal and to increase confidence in the pure paper currency of the dollar, the U.S. government decided to lift the 40-year ban on owning gold for Americans. Other countries have imposed heavy taxes to reduce the demand for gold, some even imposing up to a 50% value-added tax on gold. After 40 years of gold disappearance, Americans had become unfamiliar with gold, and coupled with the inconvenience of purchasing, the lifting of the gold ban did not create the anticipated tension. International bankers finally breathed a sigh of relief. When later Federal Reserve Chairman Paul Volcker saw the coins played with by former central banker John Exeter, he couldn't help but curiously ask, "John, where did you get your coins?"

[Book: Song Hongbing, *Currency War*, p179, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

On the assassination of President Trump

President Trump, his team members, and their relatives may still be assassinated, regardless of whether Trump is successful in this campaign or not. The media revealed that there were at least three shooters on the scene at that time ready to kill Trump. The hidden hands behind the scenes in the US like to carry out assassinations of presidents and politicians with good ideas of justice. U.S. politicians should re-enact laws to severely punish criminal families and control these crimes.

Any major crime is bound to bring significant benefits to the families of interest groups. Assassination crimes related to family interests must target the families of serious criminals. The crimes of these criminal groups cannot make the criminal evidence disappear by destroying corpses or killing insiders. As long as a crime is committed, there will inevitably be irremovable evidence left on them. Evidence collection should be carried out on all potential targets. As long as the quantum entanglement proves that all members of the families involved in the planning of the assassination and those who have knowledge of it behind the scenes, after a public trial, they must all be sentenced to death and all family property within six generations of the above-mentioned criminals shall be confiscated.

Within the next three thousand years, members of the six generations of the above criminals are prohibited from entering any university for study, from engaging in any government affairs work or civil service work, prohibited from engaging in work in the fields of justice, finance, security, economy, biology, chemistry, nuclear physics and military. Relatives within three generations and within three generations of the above-mentioned offenders must report to the police when leaving any city, and are prohibited from taking any aircraft, high-speed rail or luxury cruise ship within 1,000 years. Only in this way can the world control this kind of vicious crime and save this chaotic world, and can kind and weak people be effectively protected. Since Western missionaries forged almost all the ancient European history and judicial system, in the present era, the media is basically controlled by interest groups, the public is brainwashed, and the guilty are turned into innocent or minor crimes after being defended by lawyers for evil criminals. Global judicial ethics have declined by 2,000 -

4,000 years. Some vicious crimes can only be controlled if they are dealt with in accordance with the methods and laws of ancient China.

Fig. 231-20-17. In his book "Why Gold?", Ernest Wilk pointed out the essence of the international bankers suppressing gold:

"Starting in 1975, the United States, in cooperation with major member countries

of the International Monetary Fund, began the 'suppression' of the world gold market. The purpose of suppressing the price of gold is to convince the people of the major countries that paper currency is better than gold. The successful manipulation (control of gold prices) will ensure that the process of excessive issuance of paper currency can continue indefinitely."

Economists unanimously believed that after losing the government's official purchasing demand, gold would be proven to be almost worthless. Some even thought that \$25 per ounce was the "intrinsic value" of gold. In August 1975, to further eliminate the influence of gold, the United States and Western industrialized countries decided that the gold reserves of each country would no longer increase, and the International Monetary Fund would sell 50 million ounces of gold to suppress the price of gold. However, the price of gold remained strong, reaching \$430 per ounce in September 1979, which was more than ten times higher than the price when the Bretton Woods system collapsed in 1971.

The U.S. Treasury began its first gold auction in January 1975, starting with 300,000 ounces and later increasing to 750,000 ounces, but still unable to resist buying pressure for gold. It wasn't until November 1978, when the Treasury announced an unprecedented 1.5 million ounces for auction, that market prices eased slightly. By October 16, 1979, the U.S. Treasury could no longer sustain this, announcing that regular auctions would shift to "surprise" auctions.

The \$400 gold price was widely seen as a fair reflection of the serious over-issuance of the dollar since 1933 and was thought to be a stable and sustainable level. However, the long-term price trajectory of gold was altered by the "Iranian hostage crisis" that erupted in November 1979. Following the crisis, the Federal Reserve swiftly announced the freezing of Iran's gold reserves in the U.S., a move that sent chills through central banks worldwide— if Iran's gold could be frozen, then no country's gold in the U.S. was secure. Consequently, nations rushed to purchase gold and repatriate it directly to their own reserves. Iran, in particular, frantically bought gold on the international market, joined by Iraq in the buying frenzy, propelling gold prices to \$850 per ounce within weeks.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p180, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007. Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

挽救美国经济。1981年1月，里根上任伊始就要求国会成立“黄金委员会”（Gold Commission）研究恢复金本位的可行性。此举直接触犯了国际银行家的禁区，1981年3月30日，入主白宫仅69天的里根就被一名叫辛克利

的追星族一枪打中，子弹距心脏仅1毫米。据说此人这样做是为了吸引著名影星朱迪·福斯特的注意。当然，和绝大多数刺杀美国总统的凶手一样，此人被认为神经有问题。

这一枪不仅使里根总统“清醒”过来，也打碎了恢复金本位的最后希望。

1982年3月，17人组成的

“黄金委员会”以15比2票的差距，否决了恢复金本位的思路，里根总统赶紧“从善如流”。

从此，再也没有一位美国总统敢动恢复金本位的念头了。

↑ 1981年3月30日，里根遇刺

（来源：维基百科）

注 释

[1] Jean Hill, *JFK: The Last Dissenting Witness* (Pelican Publishing Company 1992) p113-116.

[2] Craig Roberts, *JFK: The Dead Witnesses* (Consolidated Press International 1994) p3.

[3] Executive Order 11110 actual text:

“AMENDMENT OF EXECUTIVE ORDER NO. 10289 AS AMENDED,
RELATING TO THE PERFORMANCE OF CERTAIN FUNCTIONS AFFECTING
THE DEPARTMENT OF THE TREASURY

By virtue of the authority vested in me by section 301 of title 3 of the United States Code, it is ordered as follows:

SECTION 1. Executive Order No. 10289 of September 19, 1951, as amended, is hereby further amended--

Fig. 231-20-18. President Reagan, witnessing these dramatic changes, became convinced that only a return to the gold standard could save the U.S. economy. In January 1981, at the outset of his presidency, Reagan called for the establishment of a "Gold Commission" by Congress to explore the feasibility of restoring the gold standard. This move directly encroached upon the taboo of international bankers. On March 30, 1981, just 69 days into his presidency, Reagan was shot by a stalker named Hinckley, missing his heart by only 1 millimeter. It was said that Hinckley did this to

gain attention from the actress Jodie Foster. Like most assassins of U.S. presidents, Hinckley was considered mentally unstable.

Reagan survived the assassination attempt on March 30, 1981, which not only woke him up but also shattered the last hope of restoring the gold standard. In March 1982, the "Gold Commission," consisting of 17 members, rejected the idea of restoring the gold standard by a 15-2 vote, prompting President Reagan to swiftly acquiesce.

From then on, no U.S. president dared to entertain the idea of returning to the gold standard.

[Book: Song Hongbing, Currency War, p181, CITIC Publishing House, Beijing, 2007.

Chinese name: 宋鸿兵, 货币战争 中信出版社, 北京, 2007 年]

黄巢起义有多恐怖？

黄巢进入长安以后，“天街踏遍公卿骨”，三品以上官员全部处死，四品以下的照常上班，“杀唐宗室在长安者无遗类”。

又因广德公主等人表面归顺，暗中却私藏公卿于地下室、暗门中，黄巢下令大肆诛杀心怀唐朝、暗中抵抗的士子阶级，“纵杀八万人”血流在路上像是小溪，人需要提起裤腿涉水过河，时人称之为“洗城”。

“焚市肆，杀人满街，尤憎官吏，得皆杀之”
他之前每攻克一城，也都是这样到处杀世家大族和宗室，以至于南宋历史学家郑樵说：隋唐时期官员选举、婚姻结合都要看家世渊源，当时家家藏着家谱一类的东西，但是自黄巢大乱以后“取士不问家世，婚姻不问阀阅”，因为“其书散佚，而其学不传”。

Fig. 231-21. The situation during the Huang Chao Uprising when chaebol or financial oligarch and officials of the late Tang Dynasty were slaughtered. 2024-04-26. <https://v.douyin.com/iYK8GUrR/> EUy:/ M@W.MW 07/19

If you don't understand Chinese, please find your friend to translate it.

In the Tang Dynasty capital city of Chang'an alone, apart from all officials ranked third grade or higher who were slaughtered by the Huang Chao Uprising, at least 80,000 people from wealthy families and official clans were also massacred.

Fig. 231-21. **Discovered suspected "Apollo moon landing shooting location** # US moon landing # **US moon landing is fake".** 2024-05-11. <https://v.douyin.com/i2aLHAGD/> 07/27 V@Y.zt Rxs:/

Fig. 231-22-1. Fake Lunar Landing Site, Devon Island, Canada. 2024-05-17.
<https://www.douyin.com/note/7369795884466425126>

加拿大的德文岛
看起来和
美国登月的照片
一模一样！

中国的嫦娥六号总设计师说：我们到处都找遍了，但是没有找到阿波罗曾经踏足过的盆地！

加拿大
德文岛

NASA
火星照

1973年美国带回的月球土壤中没有任何水的痕迹。中国在首次登月时发现了带回来的月球土壤中的水。美国说中国的发现是假的。印度在登月时还在月球土壤中发现了水的痕迹。

然后美国改变了态度，说确实有水。美国还违反自己制定的《狼法案》(Wolf Act)，要求中国分享其月球土地... ..

Fig. 231-22-2. An island in Canada closely resembles the lunar landscape from the 1969 U.S. lunar landing. American netizens have found the filming location of the moon landing hoax from the last century, and have found it to be similar to landing on Mars.

The above image is Devon Island in Canada, and the following image shows a fake Mars landing photo released by NASA in the United States.

Go on a trip to Devon Island in Canada immediately.

2024-05-14. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7368677970904419618>

Fig. 231-22-3. An insider at NASA confessed to the moon landing fraud before his death and left a video.

2024-06-07. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7377472085355924799>

中国2030登记计划 吓坏了美国 登月造假或许要真相了 (下)

Fig. 231-22-4. Episode 371 | Google's AI Determines That U.S. Moon Landing Photos Are Fake.

The vague and evasive responses from the U.S. and NASA regarding the technology and challenges of the moon landing are the best evidence of fabrication. April 29, 2024. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7362975294468181302>

Fig. 231-23. The Yasukuni Shrine, located under Kyodon in Tokyo, is a notorious place. This place is the "holy temple" of today's Japanese militants, as it houses a memorial tablet containing 14 Class A war criminals, including Kenji Tokaihara. [The most detestable Japanese invader of China, who was enshrined as "martyred" by Japan, September 6, 2016. https://www.sohu.com/a/113714618_209689]

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth 4 billion yuan in China, looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion US dollars, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollar.

臭名昭著的“靖国神社”里到底有什么 博主拍视频揭露引热议

Fig. 231-24. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits.

<https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan is the world's largest criminal state, responsible for killing at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people, and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, which began with the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights during the Siege of Port Arthur and resulted in only 36 survivors during the Lushun Massacre, China's population loss reaches 280 million.

Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth at least 4 billion yuan in China, looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least

250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion US dollars, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollar.

Fig. 231-25. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits. <https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

On October 17, 1978, during the regular "Autumn Festival" held at Yasukuni Shrine, the memorial tablets of 14 Class A war criminals were officially enshrined. These 14 Class A war criminals include Hideki Tojo, one of the key decision-makers in the China-Japanese War and the Pacific War; Kenji Doihara, the spy leader who stole military and economic intelligence from allied countries and orchestrated the

establishment of the puppet state of Manchukuo; Matsui Iwane, the prime culprit of the Nanjing Massacre; Hitoshi Imamura, Heitaro Kimura, and Susumu Muto, who were also significant figures in the Pacific War. Furthermore, there were the deceased Class A war criminals who passed away during their imprisonment due to illness, such as Yosuke Matsuoka and Nobuyuki Abe; those sentenced to life imprisonment, including Toshio Shiratori, Kiichiro Hiranuma, Kuniaki Koiso, and Mitsuhiro Umezu; and Tojo's co-conspirator, Shigenori Togo, who was sentenced to 20 years in prison. They were all guilty of crimes against peace, violation of international conventions and laws of war, and crimes against humanity, and their hands were stained with the blood of Asian people as executioners. In addition, the memorial tablets of Prince Kitashirakawa and Prince Kitashirakawa-no-Miya Nagahisa, who died during the Taiwan Campaign after the China-Japanese War and in Inner Mongolia during the Second China-Japanese War, were also enshrined in October 1959. Along with the Class B and Class C war criminals already enshrined at Yasukuni Shrine, the total number exceeds 1,000 individuals. To this day, Yasukuni Shrine enshrines over 2.46 million memorial tablets, out of which 2.32 million are for the casualties of World War II.

The heinous crimes committed by 14 Class A war criminals enshrined in the Yasukuni Shrine (pictured). May 28th, 2005. <http://news.sina.com.cn/c/2005-05-28/07526011294s.shtml>

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people, and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, which began with the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights during the Siege of Port Arthur and resulted in only 36 survivors during the Lushun Massacre, China's population loss reaches 280 million.

臭名昭著的“靖国神社”里到底有什么 博主拍视频揭露引热议

Fig. 231-26. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits.

<https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people, and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, which began with the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights during the Siege of Port Arthur and resulted in only 36 survivors during the Lushun Massacre, China's population loss reaches 280 million.

臭名昭著的“靖国神社”里到底有什么 博主拍视频揭露引热议

视频片段

“... The Chinese soldiers disguised in civilian clothes were severely prosecuted.”

“... 伪装成市民的中国军人被严厉地揭发了。”

Fig. 231-27. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits. <https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth at least 4 billion yuan in China, looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion US dollars, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollar

臭名昭著的“靖国神社”里到底有什么 博主拍视频揭露引热议

视频片段

日露戦争の勝利は、世界特にアジアの人々に独立の夢を与え、多くの先覚者が独立、近代化の模範として日本を訪れた。しかし、第一次世界大戦が終わっても、アジア民族に独立の道は開けなかった。
アジア民族の独立が現実になったのは、大東亜戦争結戦の日本軍による植民地権力打倒の後であった。日本軍の占領下で一度燃え上がった炎は、日本が敗れても消えることなく、独立戦争などを経て民族国家が次々と誕生した。

Postwar Independence Movements
Japan's victory in the Russo-Japanese War inspired other oppressed peoples, particularly Asian peoples, to dream of achieving independence. Many future leaders of independence movements visited Japan as a model for independence and modernization. But even when the turmoil of World War I subsided, the road to independence seemed endless to the peoples of Asia. Not until Japan won a stunning victory in the early stages of the Greater East Asia War, did the idea of independence enter the realm of reality. Once the desire for independence had been kindled under Japanese occupation, it did not fade away, even though Japan was ultimately defeated. Asian nations fought for their independence, and achieved triumph.

“... Once the desire for independence had been **kindled under Japanese occupation**, it did not fade away, even though Japan was ultimately defeated. Asian nations fought for their independence, and **achieved triumph.**”

“各国人民是在日本的占领”

Fig. 231-28. 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

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Japan has issued counterfeit currency worth at least 4 billion yuan in China, looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth 5,289-7,933.5 billion US dollars, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth 50,000 billion US dollars, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth 132.55-280.5 billion US dollars, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about 5,000 billion US dollars, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about 800 billion US dollars, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth 20,000-30,000 billion US dollars, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about 3,535.71 billion US dollars, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth 114.4 billion US dollars, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth 420 billion US dollars, at least 1,233 million tons of food worth about 700 billion US dollars, at least 1,000 tons

of platinum worth about 32.258-37.868 billion US dollars, at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion US dollars, at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about 18-23.4 billion US dollars, as well as 480 million pigs, sheep, chickens, and ducks, and 20 million head of cattle, horses, and donkeys. Additionally, 300 million houses were destroyed. These looted assets have accumulated significant wealth for Japan's development over an average of 85 years and must be compensated with a minimum of 10% compound interest. Otherwise, any country has no reason not to kill the evil Japanese and recover these assets.

From 1957 to 2022, Warren Buffett's return on investment: 38,653,482.5%, annual compounded rate: 21.52%; Partner's actual return on investment from 1957 to 2022: 21,390,125.88%, annual compounded rate: 20.44%.

Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people, and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, which began with the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights during the Siege of Port Arthur and resulted in only 36 survivors during the Lushun Massacre, **China's population loss reaches 280 million.**

臭名昭著的“靖国神社”里到底有什么 博主拍视频揭露引热议

视频片段

总供祀人数
246.6 万人

其中1937-1945年间
侵华战争和太平洋战争
阵亡者总数
232.5 万人

超过了总死鬼的94%

Fig. 231-29.

2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine

Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million people, and raped and gang raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women. If we start counting from the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, which began with the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights during the Siege of Port Arthur and resulted in only 36 survivors during the Lushun Massacre, China's population loss reaches 280 million.

However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits. <https://v.kuaishou.com/3qAzm9>

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Japan may seem like a defeated country in World War II, but in reality, it was a victorious country in World War II.

The Japanese government, Emperor, and conglomerates are very evil, intentionally setting the minimum inheritance tax in Japan at only 30 million yen, causing exhaustion and abandonment of houses among the middle and lower class citizens. The minimum personal threshold for inheritance tax must be increased from 30 million yen to 90 million yen in Japan.

34.6. The unique culture shapes the Chinese people's simplicity, kindness, and public spirit - a set of images or videos.

No country in the world has as many touching stories of mutual assistance and selfless dedication as China, in any era. This is the cultural heritage, this is civilization, this is the religion embedded in the heart. Many Westerners believe that going to church to pray or participate in religious festivals is a religious belief, but no country's kindness reaches the level of the Chinese people, religious belief should not be very narrow formalism of going to church to pray, but kindness and empathy engraved in the heart, and disdain and struggle against evil forces.

Fig. 232. In 1942, the leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong, gave lectures in front of the cave where he lived, wearing clothes with many patches. 2021-03-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwSVUNd/i@c.aajpq:/10/08>

The leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong:

A great philosopher, a great thinker, a great logician,
a great military strategist, a great strategist,
an outstanding calligrapher, and an outstanding poet.

A Chinese leader and pioneer of the new social system who often wears patched

clothes and pants.

The world owes him a Nobel Prize in Literature, a Nobel Prize in Physics and a Nobel Peace Prize, because Mao Zedong's ideology has prevented war in China for the past few decades.

The bold and unrestrained poetry of Su Dongpo, a literary giant in Chinese history during the Song Dynasty, has been unmatched for nearly a thousand years. In modern times, only Mao Zedong's the poem "Spring in the Qin Garden" "Snow" can compare in its boldness. Outstanding poetry like this comes once in a millennium.

Fig. 233. In his later years, Chairman Mao's body grew larger, causing his cotton undershirts to shrink easily. Eventually, these clothes became too small for him to wear.

However, since the Chairman did not want to discard them, the staff would sew two pieces together to make one, or three pieces together to make two, then add extra material to make them larger so that Chairman Mao could continue to wear them.
2024-02-26. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwSquLd/06/04Yzg:/l@p.qr>

Fig. 234. Among the many relics of the great Chinese leader Mao Zedong, there is a pajama that has been worn for over 20 years and has been patched with 73 patches.
[A pajama with 73 patches. Do you know whose it is?2021-06-29.
<https://v.douyin.com/iNwSxJ8y/kPx:/08/26h@O.xF>]

In the past 200 years of world history, which leader's philosophy, logic, literature, and strategic level can surpass Chairman Mao Zedong?

官当大了容易忘记受苦的人 让他们记住饿肚子的滋味

毛主席的护士长吴旭君回忆说：六十年代后期，毛主席主持了一次大区书记会议。快到吃饭的时候还没散会呢。汪东兴就请示毛主席：是不是搞点东西给大家吃？主席说：好啊，但不要搞多了，每人吃一小碗面条就行了。我当时觉得主席很奇怪。等散会后看到主席挺高兴的。就问他：主席，今天来开会的都是些高级领导，为什么你才给他们吃一小碗面条，太小气了。主席笑了，他说：正因为他们都是高级领导干部，平时谁敢让他们饿肚子？到我这里不准吃饱，就是要让他们记住饿肚子的滋味，官当大了，容易忘记还有受苦的人。这就是，为什么老人家离开我们四十多年了，人民还依然那么的热爱他。

Fig. 234-1. When officials rise to high office, they often forget about the suffering of ordinary people.

Chairman Mao Zedong's head nurse, Wu Xujun, recalled: "In the late 1960s, Chairman Mao presided over a national conference of regional secretaries. The meeting was almost over, but it was not time for dinner yet. Wang Dongxing asked Chairman Mao for permission: 'Should we get something for everyone to eat?' The Chairman said: 'Sure, but don't overdo it. Just give each person a small bowl of noodles.' I found it strange at the time. After the meeting, I saw the Chairman looking quite pleased. I asked him: 'Chairman, today's attendees are all senior leaders. Why did you only give them a small bowl of noodles? Isn't that stingy?' The Chairman smiled and said: 'Precisely because they are all senior leaders, who dares to let them go hungry on a regular day? By not allowing them to eat their fill here, I want them to remember the taste of hunger. When officials rise to high positions, they often forget about those who suffer.' That's why, even though the old man has been gone for over forty years, the people still love him so much."

[A person's official position can easily forget those who suffer at the bottom# The sentiment of great men.2024-05-14. <https://v.douyin.com/i2Qyvxs7/> 02/01 UyG:/R@x.FU]

Fig 235. The magical Chongqing Sichuan River Gorge, the uncanny work of nature, the highway hanging on the steep cliffs, how did it form in the end! #The uncanny work of nature #Natural wonders #Cliffs #Mountain roads. 2024-03-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqrtB7q/N@j.Px FhO:/ 10/05>

Fig 236. The magical Chongqing Sichuan River Gorge, the uncanny work of nature, the highway hanging on the steep cliffs, how did it form in the end! #The uncanny work of nature #Natural wonders #Cliffs #Mountain roads. 2024-03-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqrtB7q/N@j.Px FhO:/ 10/05>

Fig 237. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy One shot, watching the cement roads connecting every household in the deep mountains of 100,000 mountains, it's like a heavenly road, shocking #away from the hustle and bustle of the city #100,000 mountains #mountain roads #beautiful countryside #healing scenery. 2024-03-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqyxYN3/> 05/05 m@q.EH oDU:/

Fig 238. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy
One shot, watching the cement roads connecting every household in the deep mountains of 100,000 mountains, it's like a heavenly road, shocking #away from the hustle and bustle of the city #100,000 mountains #mountain roads #beautiful countryside #healing scenery. 2024-03-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqyxYN3/> 05/05 m@q.EH oDU:/

这里就是很多人驱车千里赶来

Fig 238-1. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. [Xiangxi, Hunan Province. 2024-04-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iYUffMCu/xSy:/04/28r@R.kc>]

Fig 238-2. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. North Panjiang Guanxing Highway. [Experience the North Panjiang Highway in Guizhou Province, thrilling and thrilling. 2024-02-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iY9FVjeW/> 04/25 P@K.jc Hll:/]

Fig 238-3. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy. [The winding mountain road built on cliffs in Guizhou Province has scared away many young drivers. Do you dare to challenge it# Thrilling stimulation. 2024-03-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iY9Ff7v6/> /vf:/ 12/28 x@F.U]

Fig 238-4. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. **Zhenfeng North Panjiang Canyon Highway**. [Inventory the stunning self driving highways around Guiyang. These stunning self driving highways around Guiyang. The ordinary path can also be extraordinary. 2023-11-12. <https://v.douyin.com/iY92m3n2/Xzg:/z@G.vS10/21>]

Fig 238-5. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy.

[Guizhou Province Expressway Scenic Video. 2024-04-06.
<https://v.douyin.com/iY92t1Db/08/30K@w.seoqR:/>]

Fig 238-6. A road that has deterred countless veteran drivers from other places! The most thrilling road in China is built on vertical cliffs, and local villagers have to ride it for 3 hours every time they go home# Panshan Highway # Eighteen Bend Mountain Road # thrilling # incredible# Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. 2024-06-14.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7380201340057799975>

The transportation infrastructure projects leading to rural areas in China that can only be completed with national transfer payments. This is a part of political party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economy and rural behavioral economy.

If you have enough courage and technology, perhaps you can choose the right time to experience one of China's most dangerous highways.

Fig 238-7. A road that has deterred countless veteran drivers from other places! The most thrilling road in China is built on vertical cliffs, and local villagers have to ride it for 3 hours every time they go home# Panshan Highway # Eighteen Bend Mountain Road # thrilling # incredible#2024-06-14.
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The transportation infrastructure projects leading to rural areas in China that can only be completed with national transfer payments. This is a part of political party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economy and rural behavioral economy.

“受人之托 忠人之事”

1999年，娶了救命恩人遗孀的战地记者
卢宇光：他托我照顾妻儿

“你愿意嫁给我，让我照顾你吗？”

如今，儿子和女儿均在中国上学
品格坚毅，勤奋好学
战友的儿子也始终尊称卢宇光为爸爸，从未改变

Fig 239. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

In 1999, Chinese war journalist Lu Yuguang, as a correspondent, reported from the battlefield during the Second Chechen War in Russia. During his coverage, he encountered a Russian special forces soldier and the two formed a bond, looking out for each other and enjoying each other's company along the way. However, due to the intense conflict, the vehicle they were traveling in hit a landmine. In order to protect Lu Yuguang, the special forces soldier sacrificed himself by shielding him from the

incoming shrapnel. Before his death, the soldier entrusted Lu Yuguang with taking care of his wife and child, a request to which Lu Yuguang agreed.

After the war ended, Lu Yuguang tirelessly searched for the soldier's family and eventually found them. The special forces soldier left behind a wife and a one-year-old son. It was a heart-wrenching moment for Lu Yuguang and the soldier's family upon learning of his sacrifice. As promised, Lu Yuguang vowed to take care of them for the rest of his life. Over time, a deep bond developed between Lu Yuguang and the soldier's widow, leading to a marriage. They later had a daughter together, whom Lu Yuguang treated as his own. Despite the cultural differences and the inherent risks faced by a war journalist, Lu Yuguang's wife became apprehensive and fearful, ultimately leading to a peaceful divorce.

After the divorce, Lu Yuguang brought the two children back to China and supported their higher education. Despite their separation, Lu Yuguang continued to provide regular financial support to his former wife, honoring his commitment to the fallen Russian special forces soldier.

Today, the son and daughter display strong character, resilience, and a diligent attitude towards learning. The son of the special forces soldier continues to refer to Lu Yuguang as his father, and this has never changed.

[Entrusted with a loyal person's task, one should repay it with a gushing spring for a mere drop of kindness. How many people in this world can truly achieve this? Perhaps that is also why Lu Yuguang is respected both in Russia and abroad. #vision #kindness #emotions. <https://v.douyin.com/iJW9nsnd/>]

Fig 240. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

Lu Yuguang is not only the chief journalist of Phoenix TV in Moscow, but also a war correspondent on the Russian battlefield. Since we cannot prevent war, let us tell the world the truth about war. [Revealing the truth, understanding history, and paying tribute to Lu Yuguang. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWytb8w/>]

俄L斯特种兵为救我国记者

用身体挡住子弹而牺牲

留下遗言：请照顾好我的家人

Fig 241. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

[Russian special forces sacrificed their lives in honor of saving Chinese war correspondent Lu Yuguang! Leave a last word: "Take care of my family." In order to repay the favor and take better care of the benefactor's widow, Lu Yuguang has married and lived a happy life# China Russian Friendship# Touching# Passing Positive Energy# Songs to Others. <https://v.douyin.com/idAeTs16/WmQ:/04/10o@Q.Kw>]

中国战地记者为报恩 娶了俄特种兵遗孀 今和平分手儿女随他回国

Fig 242. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

Lu Yuguan has a deep bond of camaraderie with Lieutenant General Gerasimov, the director of the Russian Defense News Bureau. This is not only because Lu Yuguan possesses abundant experience as a war correspondent, but also because he embodies the Chinese values of loyalty, gratitude, and kindness. His unique professional integrity has earned the respect of the Chinese people in Russia. Lu Yuguan, driven by his passion and belief in journalism, strives to spread the truth to the world because he cannot stop the war. Ignoring personal danger, he navigates fearlessly through gunfire and explosions.

From General Konashenkov (Игорь Конашенков), the author can still feel a strong breath of righteousness, wisdom, bravery, courage, insight, kindness, and gratitude, even on his tired body, which is rare among Western generals. If General Konashenkov has the opportunity to become President of Russia in the future, it may be of great help to the stability of Russia and the continuity of global peace.

[Character Story: Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWaPYkA/>],[Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now

break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. June 27, 2022.
<https://www.163.com/dy/article/HASQN4LV055333WB.html>]

Fig 243 A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

[Character Story: Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWaPYkA/>]

6月7日

北顿涅茨克

Fig 244. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

The son of a seventy-five year old grandmother in North Donetsk was killed and left alone. She doesn't know how to live in the future. [In this short lifetime, we will eventually lose. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWGkFtV/>]

战场遇险， 最自私的就是西方记者

在里面叫 因为什么呢

Fig 245. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

When the battlefield is in danger, the most selfish are Western journalists [Reporter # personally experienced. Sharing Lao Lu's Journalist Experience Here#<https://v.douyin.com/iJ7Lxf5a/>]

Fig. 246. After the snowstorm, the highway was blocked all night, and the nearby villagers came early in the morning... 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdSQ2xG/c@A.gO IIV:/> 07/28

Fig 247. Residents along the highways in various parts of Hubei are providing free hot water and food for stranded drivers on the highway! Three years ago, people from all over the country helped Hubei, and the people of Hubei are not cold! Natural disasters have no mercy, but people do! Let's get through this difficult time together! #Hubei #Human warmth #Positive energy #Going home for the Spring Festival2024-02-05.<https://v.douyin.com/iNdap1d9/> 10/31 s@E.hb Vlp:/

Fig 248. Thank you for the love meal sent by my fellow Jishou people. It's the first time I've eaten bacon this year. #The joy of traffic jam on highway. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdmH5XR/Q@x.sR01/08 Rkc:/>

Fig 249. Only free delivery, not for sale! Villagers near the Macheng section of Hubei Province climb onto the highway to deliver meals #Huanggang #Highway #Seeking Beauty Huanggang. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd9MfNp/03/26OxF:/r@r.rR>

Fig 250. Blizzard can't stop people from returning home for the Spring Festival. The true feelings of the villagers are touching. There is true love everywhere, because we are a family that loves and cares for each other. # Broadcasting video #Human warmth #Touching moments #Positive energy #Heartwarming. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdtDJJW/10/14BtE:/W@M.JV>

Fig 251. Thank you, Hubei. # Original Video #Real Outdoor Life #Have a Seafood Dinner Outdoors. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdnQ2md/goQ:/02/06Q@K.Wz>

Fig 252. Kind-hearted people from Jingmen, Hubei spontaneously sent free food to those stranded on the highway. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdW6Ly8/> 04/05 a@N.jp trR:/

Fig 253. The ice and snow are ruthless, but Huanggang has love. In the year of the great epidemic, the whole country saved Hubei. In the face of the snow disaster, the people of Hubei know how to be grateful! Without a call or command, the people of the old liberated area came together and sent water and food to the people of all ages for free! The people of beautiful Hubei have beautiful hearts of China! Wish peace. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd7AXwq/t@e.OKndN:/03/13>

Fig 254. The ice and snow are ruthless, but Huanggang has love. In the year of the great epidemic, the whole country saved Hubei. In the face of the snow disaster, the people of Hubei know how to be grateful! Without a call or command, the people of the old liberated area came together and sent water and food to the people of all ages for free! The people of beautiful Hubei have beautiful hearts of China! Wish peace. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd7AXwq/t@e.OKndN:/03/13>

Fig 255. The ice and snow are ruthless, but Huanggang has love. In the year of the great epidemic, the whole country saved Hubei. In the face of the snow disaster, the people of Hubei know how to be grateful! Without a call or command, the people of the old liberated area came together and sent water and food to the people of all ages for free! The people of beautiful Hubei have beautiful hearts of China! Wish peace. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd7AXwq/t@e.OKndN:/03/13>

Fig 256. Episode 83 | On February 5th, in the Macheng section of the Daguang Expressway in Hubei Province, villagers delivered hot meals to drivers stuck in traffic for free, knocking on windows one by one and asking, "Do you need food?" #I want to give you a thumbs up #Hubei freezing rain and snow disaster #Hubei Expressway.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdvFjgF/D@h.oQ GvF:/03/14>

村民免费为高速堵车司机送热饭

挨个敲窗询问“需要食物吗？”

被困车主：太温暖了！感动得掉眼泪

Fig 257. Episode 83 | On February 5th, in the Macheng section of the Daguang Expressway in Hubei Province, villagers delivered hot meals to drivers stuck in traffic for free, knocking on windows one by one and asking, "Do you need food?" #I want to give you a thumbs up #Hubei freezing rain and snow disaster #Hubei Expressway.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdvFJgF/D@h.oQ.GvF:/03/14>

Fig 258. Episode 83 | On February 5th, in the Macheng section of the Daguang Expressway in Hubei Province, villagers delivered hot meals to drivers stuck in traffic for free, knocking on windows one by one and asking, "Do you need food?" #I want to give you a thumbs up #Hubei freezing rain and snow disaster #Hubei Expressway.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdvFjgF/D@h.oQ GvF:/03/14>

Fig 259. Peasant friends once again moved people across the country to tears # nostalgia memory # rural life # Tiktok records rural life # my rural life # snow in my hometown. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdcve1R/> 12/31 m@Q.kc Hvf:/

Fig 260. Peasant friends once again moved people across the country to tears # nostalgia memory # rural life # Tiktok records rural life # my rural life # snow in my hometown. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdcve1R/> 12/31 m@Q.kc Hvf:/

Fig 261. High-speed icebound, there is love in the world, ordinary farmers around the area distribute food for free. This is the simple farmers of China. The traditional virtues of the Chinese nation are so great and lovely. Farmers are often our angels. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd3yTVC/06/18fba:/t@R.KW>

网友车子因大雪被困高速

集卡分2亿

大爷走了十几分钟山路 特地送上自己烧的热水

Fig 262. #Highway Traffic Jam during Spring Festival# Grandpa Delivers Hot Water from a Long Distance# Warm Chinese New Year # Macheng, Hubei. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdTL52t/04/20V@y.GV Hli:/>

Fig 263. Do you know what this is about? The people nearby the Hunan Expressway have given their best to warm the heart of the wandering children passing by. The wandering children are still warm in their hearts, but what about our local officials? I would like to give my fellow villagers a big thumbs up. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdKLYGm/rRK:/S@Y.MW> 09/05

湖北孝感一家宴团队 在高速路附近支起7口大锅

免费为旅客煮鸡蛋、蒸包子等

负责人：平时挣点钱
现在花钱做点有意义的事

Fig 264. A catering team in Xiaogan, Hubei set up seven large pots near the highway and cooked eggs, noodles and steamed buns for passengers for free. 2024-02-05. https://v.douyin.com/iNdEfQQN/gbn:/07/29_g@B.go

Fig 265. This year, I went back to my hometown to celebrate the New Year, with many touching scenes, which brought tears to my eyes! Let's remember their faces. This year, although we have encountered a freezing and snowy weather that we haven't encountered in many years. The warm scene on the highway makes the people of the whole country feel even more familiar!

Long live the great unity of the Chinese people! Long live the Chinese peasant uncles.

2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR1T3cN/f@b.aA03/28kca/>

Fig 266.In times of crisis, loyalty is seen. The party member commando team delivered supplies to thousands of stranded vehicles at the west exit of Jishou Expressway. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdehr4/k@p.dN09/14 HVL:/>

Fig 267. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey】 Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 268. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey. Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 269. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey. Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuoyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 270. Passenger: I cannot repay your kindness, but I wish them a happy wedding and a healthy baby. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8MGed/> ipq:/ n@Q.kP 08/22

Fig 271. Passenger: I cannot repay your kindness, but I wish them a happy wedding and a healthy baby. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8MGed/> ipq:/ n@Q.kP 08/22

风雪寒 人心暖

孝洪高速应城段受困乘客得到及时救助

网友：应城豆皮味道好极了

1019

97

2月4日上午9点，孝洪高速上一辆从上海开往重庆已经连续行驶两天的大巴车被大雪困住，车上载有40余名疲惫不堪的乘客。

24

@今日应城 应城市融媒体中心

风雪寒 人心暖 孝洪高速应城段被困乘客得到及时救助 #暴雪 #... 展开

120

Fig 272. Episode 18 | Cold Snow and Warm Hearts: Passengers Trapped in the Yingcheng Section of Xiaohong Expressway Are Rescued in Time #Blizzard #Safety. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8GLoG/HiC:/g@o.qR> 07/30

常德高速因积雪致司机受困

正在家中办喜事的男子带队爬上高速路给受困人送饭菜

Fig 273. Episode 25 | On February 4th, snow caused drivers to be trapped on the Changde Expressway in Hunan Province. A man was celebrating a wedding and led a team to the side of the highway to deliver hot meals to the trapped people. Source: @YiYeZhiQiu. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRLX3pC/> usR:/ E@h.bA 11/14

Fig 274. Ice and snow are merciless, but villagers are the most close. # Villagers' hanging basket sent relief supplies and received warm letters. # Big V said #Big V said hotspot @Jingshi Live.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRLGv9w/> mQx:/ 01/08 j@p.da

Fig 275. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 276. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 277. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 278. But do good deeds and don't ask about the future! I hope everyone on the highway can get home safely! Little things like this really didn't expect to bring so much heat. Thank you very much for all the villagers' efforts, and I am also honored to be a Chinese daughter. #Record True Life. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNHFLu/>

Fig 279. The high-speed stranded people received help and sent a thank-you letter using a "basket" to express their gratitude. The reply said: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" #Blizzard #Heartwarming #Hubei @Villager Su Junjie. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRFXWku/F@u.fbJCU:/06/01>

Fig 280. The snow is merciless, but people are not. # Highway #Love Knows No Boundaries #Returning Home for Spring Festival. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRf3X/w@s.EU>

Fig 281. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRFECnn/06/10m@D.HI.NWZ:/>

Fig 282. Compassion is the highest virtue in all morality. 2023-12-05.
https://v.douyin.com/iNR63XJy/MJi:/01/06_x@s.eb

Fig 283. Episode 1 | Warming the stomach and the heart! More than a dozen citizens in Jishou, Hunan, spontaneously sent hot food to people stranded on the highway (Source: @happy) #The atmosphere of the Spring Festival begins with the Spring Festival transportation home #What is the New Year? # 2024 is a beautiful Chinese New Year.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdwRc6n/lvS/> 10/30 c@N.JI

Fig 284. #On the third day of delivering hot water on the highway, two children who were delivering hot water on the highway ran countless times. The hot water came, friends # Hunan Expressway Positive Energy.2024-02-06. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRweWeH/01/11 mdn:/L@J.II>

Fig 285. #Xinjiang #Gansu #Zhangye City. The city of Zhangye has provided a warm welcome to stranded tourists during the extreme weather in Xinjiang, showing a "charity in time of need" attitude. Source: @Yangtze River News #Extreme Weather #Moment of Touching. 2024-02-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwfY3wD/> 09/21 J@v.SY hBG:/

Fig 286. #This is the best tourism promotional video. The strong winds and heavy snow affected more than 20,000 tourists and stranded them in Guazhou. Only 50,000 people in the small county were receiving them. Before the farewell, the official apologized for the poor hospitality. Please forgive us. 2024-02-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwyQEQq/> ufo://J@v.Sy 11/05

Fig 287. In Guazhou, Gansu Province, there is a history of the Guiyi Army, and today there is a love in the snow. No matter how the times change, the simplicity and kindness of Gansu people will never fade. #Where is Guazhou? # A heart-warming scene in the snowstorm #Guazhou, Gansu Province, is worth seeing.2024-02-25. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwyVcqX/F@H.vF> 04/02 IPK: /

Fig 288 Chinese people #Guazhou #positive energy. 2024-02-20.
<https://v.douyin.com/iNwf3ST1/05/26t@R.KwZmQ:/>

2.5万名旅客因天气恶劣滞留

甘肃瓜州5万人小县倾城接待

送别前官方致歉：招待不周 请包涵

滞留旅客：这里的人都太淳朴了

感动

感谢

酒店爆满后，县城所有学校、体育馆开放
接纳游客，连消防队都开放了
朋友圈里好多人说可以来我们家
瓜州市民开始自发请游客来家里住
有序接纳滞留在风寒中的游客们

@苍穹神鹰 · 02月21日

#甘肃瓜州倾城接待#感谢#

Fig 289. The entire city of Guazhou in Gansu received 25,000 tourists stranded due to the snowstorm, including residents, businesses, and government agencies. I# Thank you.2024-02-21. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwPM2gX/06/11> PKw:/ J@v.Fu

超2万名游客受风雪影响滞留瓜州

5万人小县倾城倾心接待!

Fig 290. Recently, the strong wind and snow affected more than 20,000 tourists stranded in Guazhou, and the small county of 50,000 people warmly received them! #Warm Heart #Passion #Unity (Source @Yuyechengfeng CCTV13, The Paper).2024-02-22.<https://v.douyin.com/iNwyHGDU/v@S.Lw pda:/ 07/06>

因大风暴雪滞留甘肃瓜州的 2万多名群众陆续离开

瓜州发布：有招待不周的地方 向你们表示歉意请多包涵

Fig 291. As the weather improves, more than 20,000 people stranded in Guazhou have left one after another. Guazhou has issued an apology for any inadequate hospitality..2024-02-20.<https://v.douyin.com/iFuuRjnX/N@W.zg07/31Wzt:/>

**开国少将，大军区
司令员问保姆借钱
丝毫无损其高尚**

85年5月张铨秀将军突然对保姆说：

“我答应要送这位烈士的子女大学毕业的，经济上有点缺口，你借点钱我，下个月发工资还给你。”保姆立刻取了钱双手递给首长时，含泪说：

“你家庭经济不宽裕却资助那么多人，能否向组织反映？”将军爽朗地笑着混：“家丑不可外扬啊！”然后认真道：“共产党员只有为人民付出的责任，没有向人民索取的权力。”

Fig 291-1. The founding major general and commander of a large military district borrowed money from a nanny, which in no way diminished his noble character.

In May 1985, General Zhang Zhixiu suddenly said to the nanny, "I promised to send the children of this martyr to college, but I have a little financial shortfall. Can you lend me some money and I will pay you back next month when I receive my salary?" The nanny immediately handed over the money with tears in her eyes and said, "Your family's finances are not abundant, yet you support so many people. Can you report this to the organization?" The general laughed heartily and said, "Family problems should not be made public!" Then he sincerely said, "As a member of the Communist Party, we have the responsibility to give to the people, but no right to ask for anything in return."

2024-03-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iFwWpWwL/Wmq:/01/06 i@P.Kj>

Fig 291-2. Monument: Prototype of the character: Hu Jun (1889-1935), head of the logistics department of a division of the Red Fourth Army. During the Red Army's Long March over the snowy mountains, he sacrificed his life due to the severe cold while marching, and was known as the "logistics head who froze to death."

The text "Monument" revolves around the theme of a monument and narrates the touching story of a logistics chief of the Red Army who, while marching, gave his own cotton coat to a comrade and died of the severe cold. It praises his selfless and altruistic spirit, and his spirit can be regarded as a model.

2023-07-28. <https://v.douyin.com/iFwv7wSa/Y@M.wS 08/14 XMj:/>

Fig 291-3. Kuang Renong, the founding major general. "Red Army generals who fainted from hunger while guarding their own grain bags"

After the start of the Long March, Kuang Renong had been the deputy head of the supply department of the Red 5th Division, and began to follow the troops in their transfer. In August 1935, the main force of the Red Army was preparing to cross the grassland, and Kuang Renong was transferred to the head of the supply department of the Red 13th Regiment. In order to secure provisions for the troops to cross the grassland, Kuang Renong led his supply troops to nearby farms to buy grain.

Unfortunately, due to the sparse population in the area, the procurement of provisions did not go smoothly, and the troops set off without being able to procure enough food. Unable to complete the task of procuring provisions, Kuang Renong took out the

rations allocated to himself and said, "I was unable to procure enough food, so I will give my rations to the larger force to distribute to the comrades."

The comrades all understood that their failure to procure enough provisions was not the fault of the supply department. In order to shake off pursuers, the troops had to take the risk of crossing the grassland and begin a difficult journey. As the head of the supply department, Kuang Renong carried a bag of grain and followed the troops across the grassland.

During the process of passing through the swamp grassland, Kuang Renong did not eat a single grain of food. He dug for wild vegetables, ate tree bark, and grass roots. He even looked carefully through horse dung, to see if there were any leftover grains, and picked them out.

As the grain in Kuang Renong's bag dwindled, he did not eat a single grain, but gave everything to the soldiers. After several days of not eating any provisions, only eating wild vegetables and grass roots, Kuang Renong's face grew pale. As he walked, he suddenly felt dizzy and collapsed to the ground. One of the soldiers in the supply department saw their leader collapse and quickly helped him up, realizing that the leader had passed out of hunger.

The soldier took out a piece of dried beef from Kuang Renong's bag and put it in his mouth, reviving him. When Kuang Renong woke up and saw the dried beef in his mouth, he uncharacteristically became angry. He said to the young soldier, "Comrade, the supplies of our department are meant for the troops, how can I eat them?"

This is the selfless Kuang Renong, responsible for the logistics of the troops, and held himself to extremely high standards. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, Kuang Renong served as the secretary of the logistics department of the East China Military Region, continuing to adhere to the revolutionary tradition of hardship and simplicity. He never bought new clothes, wearing patch upon patch, and took pride in it.

2023-06-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iFw3BRoy/05/22f@o.qeEuf/>

Fig 291-4. A little red army soldier who, while traversing through the swampy meadows, would rather starve than admit to being hungry in extreme difficulty, and also cares for their injured leader.

One late afternoon in late August 1935, on the vast grassland, Red Army soldiers were struggling to march forward. Dark clouds covered the sky, and heavy rain was about to come.

Chen Gong, the leader of the officer team, re-injured his leg and fell behind the troops. He was leading a tired and thin horse, taking slow steps forward. Suddenly, he saw a young Red Army soldier, who was only eleven or twelve years old, also falling behind. He quickly caught up to him.

When he approached the young soldier, Chen Gong noticed that the boy was wearing tattered clothes, had a pale face, and his grass sandals were already worn out, with his small feet frozen and swollen. Chen Gong asked him, "What's your name, kid? Can't walk anymore? Let me give you a ride on the horse for a while."

The young Red Army soldier replied, "My name is Nine-and-a-Half, I have much stronger endurance than you. You go on ahead."

Chen Gong sternly said, "Kid, you must ride for a while!"

The young soldier stubbornly replied, "I can walk. Or else, let's have a race with your horse."

"Then let's walk together."

"No, you go first. I have to wait for my companion, I'll surpass you in a while!"

Chen Gong had no choice but to hand over the last bit of barley flour from his bag of provisions to the young soldier and said, "Eat it!"

The young Red Army soldier patted his own bulging bag of provisions and said, "You see, I have more than you."

Chen Gong looked at the young boy's bag of provisions and indeed, it was full. He felt that the young soldier was not lacking in food and could recover after a little rest, so he relaxed and continued to lead the horse forward.

Chen Gong's mind was never at peace. After a long time, he suddenly realized that Nine-and-a-Half had never caught up.

It was impossible for Nine-and-a-Half, who looked pale and was stumbling, to have so much food in his bag of provisions. Chen Gong realized that something was wrong and shouted, leaping onto his horse and galloping back along the way.

When he found the young soldier, he had collapsed on the grassland.

Comrade Chen Gong struggled to lift the young soldier onto the horse, and his hand touched the young soldier's bag of provisions. The bag was hard, as if it contained something. He took it out and found a piece of charred ox kneecap, with several bite marks on it.

Comrade Chen Gong understood everything. At that moment, the young soldier stopped breathing.

Comrade Chen Gong held the young soldier tightly, full of self-blame. Later, at General Chen Gong's home, there was always an extra pair of chopsticks and a bowl on the table every Chinese New Year, in memory of the young soldier.

2024-01-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKf1gLr/03/15VLw:/d@a.NJ>

2022-05-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKaHXAK/i@P.KjRkp:/10/28>

Fig 291-5. Chairman Mao Zedong's ex-wife, the first female Red Army to go up to the Jinggang Mountains, was bombed by Nationalist planes during the Long March. In order to save the injured soldiers lying on stretchers, she threw herself on top of them and was hit by many shrapnel. In a situation completely without anesthesia, she performed surgery to remove some of the shrapnel, leaving a bowl-deep scar on her back. In the end, seventeen pieces of shrapnel were only found in her ashes. 2022-09-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKHPvMj/05/17> e@b.Nj RXz:/

独腿走完长征路的开国将军:钟赤兵
二渡赤水后,经三次无麻药截肢失去右腿
多次拒绝主席准备的担架,坚持独腿走路
以惊人的毅力爬雪山过草地,到达陕北

Fig 291-6. Chizhi Bing, a one-legged soldier who had undergone amputation three times, was lying on a stretcher with 17 shrapnel wounds on his body. He was protected from the bombing of Nationalist planes by He Zizhen, the wife of Chairman Mao Zedong.

In 1935, the then political commissar of the Red Army, Zhong Chibing, was seriously injured at the Lou Mountain Pass. His injuries were so severe that the doctors recommended amputation. Due to continuing to fight after being injured, the bone that was hit by the bullet shattered. With limited medical supplies, the surgery had to be conducted under extremely difficult conditions, using only a knife and a broken carpenter's saw. The surgery had to be performed three times, each time under excruciating circumstances. Zhong Chibing endured immense pain during the surgeries, but his strong will allowed him to remain silent. Even when the doctors suggested he call out if the pain was unbearable, he chose to silently endure. The first amputation only removed part of his leg below the knee, but later the doctors had to perform another surgery to remove the rest of his right leg below the knee to prevent infection. Unfortunately, due to extremely poor medical conditions, the wound became infected for a second time, contrary to their hopes.

In a situation where there was no other choice, the doctor was forced to perform a third amputation, this time cutting off the entire right leg from the root. Enduring three amputation surgeries in half a month caused Zhong Chibing to experience repeated pain, and although he ultimately saved his life, he lost his right leg forever.

After the three amputation surgeries, Zhong Chibing became a wounded person with half a leg missing. However, even after the surgery, Zhong Chibing's wound remained severely infected, leading to persistent high fever and unconsciousness. In difficult conditions, doctors performed multiple surgeries and ultimately pulled Zhong Chibing back from the brink of death.

Although Zhong Chibing managed to save his life, the wound on his right leg was difficult to heal. Faced with the daunting task of the Long March, both the commander of the Red 12th Regiment and the Red First Army, Peng Dehuai, hesitated about whether to let Zhong Chibing continue with the army. However, Zhong Chibing expressed a strong willingness to follow the Red Army, regardless of his weakness and disability. In August 1935, Zhong Chibing set out from Luhua, northwest of Sichuan, and began the arduous Long March of climbing snow-capped mountains and crossing grasslands. When he encountered cliffs that were impassable by litter, he would prop himself up with a crutch and push forward. With every step, the wound on his leg would cause intense pain. His guards later recalled, "Commissar Zhong never let anyone carry him over the snow-capped mountains. He crawled bit by bit, often falling from high places. Later, when his injuries slightly improved, he let his comrades tie him to a horse for the march." After crossing countless mountains and rivers, Zhong Chibing arrived in northern Shaanxi with the army in October 1936, bringing an end to the Long March.

After the establishment of New China, in 1954, during the Spring Festival tea party, Guizhou warlord Wang Jialie, as a democratic person, attended the symposium with Zhong Chibing. At that time, Wang Jialie did not know that General Zhong Chibing had been disabled in battle with his own troops. He walked up to Zhong Chibing and bowed deeply, asking, "May I ask, General, what is your surname? How did you lose your right leg?"

Zhong Chibing smiled and said, "I am surnamed Zhong, named Chibing. My legs were borrowed by your honorable army's double gun soldier at Loushan Pass. I don't know when sir will return them?"

The words made Wang Jialie feel deeply ashamed, and he clasped his hands together, saying, "I have long heard of your great name, General, please forgive my past mistakes and continue to guide me."

Years later, Zhong Chibing did not dwell on past mistakes, saying, "Mr. Wang, this is all in the past. History has turned a new page. In the future, we will work together and contribute to the development of Guizhou."

Moved by this, Wang Jialie tightly grasped Zhong Chibing's hand and said, "General Zhong, you truly have the bearing of a great leader. I greatly admire you."

On September 27, 1955, Zhong Chibing was promoted to the rank of major general and was honored with the First-Class 81 Medal, the Second-Class Independent

Freedom Medal, and the first-class Liberation Medal.

[In 1935, Zhong Chibing sawed his leg three times, and He Zizhen blocked the gun for him. Mao Zedong: "Carry the Long March together." 2023-03-16.

https://www.360kuai.com/pc/9a9f67d9d3429972a?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1];

[2023-09-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iFK9fwpM/07/28e@o.qr iPx:/>]

Fig 291-7. **The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."**

Eight young women sacrificed themselves by jumping into the river after fiercely battling the Japanese invaders to cover the breakout of the anti-Japanese alliance army.

Cold Cloud (1915-1938), from Huachuan County, Heilongjiang Province, after the Japanese invaded China, she joined the 5th Army of the Northeast Anti-Japanese Allied Forces in 1937. Leading female soldiers, she bravely faced the powerful and cruel Japanese invaders, enduring the harsh tests of nature. Relying on her loyalty to the country and faith in victory, she fought to drive the savage Japanese invaders out of China, engaging in long-term battles between mountains and rivers.

In October of the same year, on the banks of the Wusihun River, a tributary of the Mudanjiang River, she deliberately exposed her position to engage in fierce combat with the Japanese puppet army, in order to cover the breakout of the majority of the anti-Japanese Allied forces. After firing her last bullet and throwing her last grenade, she and 7 female warriors from her unit sacrificed themselves by jumping into the river, known as **the "Eight Females Jumping into the River."**

At the time of the sacrifice, the oldest, Cold Cloud, and An Shunfu, were 23 years old, while the youngest, Wang Huimin, was 13 years old. Their average age was less than 20, the same age as students in the sixth grade of elementary school to just graduating from university. At the height of their youth, like fresh flowers, they withered in the flames of the evil Japanese invasion of China, submerged in the rushing waters of the Wusihun River. However, their lives are forever immortalized in their heroic sacrifice, their young and beautiful faces forever remembered in history, their unyielding spirits immortalized in a timeless monument.

[The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."2023-11-03. <https://v.douyin.com/iFEj4CYL/SIC:/m@q.Eu 08/30>];

[The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."2018-10-21. https://www.sohu.com/a/270275737_425345]

Table 33-1."The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" creates ten world records.

1	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in Chinese history.
2	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in world history.
3	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in World War II history.
4	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by women in world history.
5	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by female warriors in World War II history.
6	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by women in world history.
7	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by women in World War II history.
8	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by the youngest women's team in World War II history.
9	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by the youngest girls' warrior team in World War II history.
10	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by the youngest girls' warrior team in modern history.

缅怀先烈 英雄不朽

第九个烈士纪念日

1941年，新四军重建后不久便遭到日军进攻，鲁迅艺术学院华中分院的400多名师生向盐城西乡楼王庄一带水网地区转移。“九女投河”的悲壮故事，就发生在鲁艺华中分院二队转移途中。

Fig 291-8. Nine brave and tenacious women, each with their own unique characteristics. In the midst of this battle, one of China's most talented and hardworking writers sacrificed her life to rescue these girls, and a renowned musician also perished.

If Hollywood directors are preparing to make a unique, justice-driven, vibrant and youthful film idolizing those who fearlessly fight against evil forces, in order to promote everlasting peace in the world, they should carefully consider this subject matter. Not only is it an unparalleled theme in Chinese history, but also an extraordinary and profoundly moving story in the annals of world history. The

unique plot in this film will help at least achieve high attendance in China.

2022-09-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iYc47Sh6/> ztr:/ 12/18 b@n.qE

What qualifications do we have to forgive the evil Japan for our ancestors?

Table 33-2."The Nine Women Drowning in the River" creates 18 world records.

1	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance by female warriors during World War II.
2	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of brave women resisting Japanese aggression in world history.
3	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous women fighting back against Japanese invaders in World War II.
4	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of a group of brave women resisting Japanese aggression in World War II.
5	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most evil beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
6	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most brutal beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
7	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most savage beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
8	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most shameless beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
9	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most hypocritical beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
10	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most despicable beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
11	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most inhumane beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
12	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for pretending to be polite in World War II.
13	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for pretending to be civilized in World War II.
14	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for hiding their true intentions in World War II.
15	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the most inhumane and beastly nature of the Japanese people.
16	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the Japanese people's penchant for torturing and abusing prisoners of war.
17	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the Japanese people's penchant for torturing and abusing women.
18	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most evil, brutal, savage, shameless, hypocritical, despicable, anti-human,

pretending to be polite, pretending to be civilized, adept at hiding true intentions, and inhuman nature of Japan in World War II.

中国远征军7姐妹宁死不屈

七名译电员女战士
战斗到弹尽粮绝，为防止机密泄

在被日军围困险被玷辱
拉响了手雷，天涯殉国

向女英雄们致敬

Fig 291-9. "Seven sisters" who jumped off cliffs and died for their country.

Seven women soldiers of the Chinese Expeditionary Force fought until they ran out of ammunition and food. They would rather die than surrender, jumping off cliffs and dying for their country.

Salute to the female heroes. Salute to the female heroes.

2023-02-28.<https://v.douyin.com/iYcVmu9R/> |@P.KW CUI:/ 11/26

中国远征军7姐妹宁死不屈
七名译电员女战士
战斗到弹尽粮绝，为防止机密泄露
在被日军围困险被玷辱
拉响了手雷，天涯殉国

向女英雄们致敬

Fig 291-10. "Seven sisters" who jumped off cliffs and died for their country.

Seven women soldiers of the Chinese Expeditionary Force fought until they ran out of ammunition and food. They would rather die than surrender, jumping off cliffs and dying for their country.

Salute to the female heroes! Salute to the female heroes!

In 1942, seven female interpreters were surrounded by the Japanese army during their retreat. Radio is crucial for war. Seven female soldiers, in order to prevent the leakage of confidential information, collectively sounded the hand grenade and died in the end of the world# Passing Positive Energy # Paying tribute to women and not letting men down # Remembering History # Paying tribute to heroes # Like our heroes

2023-02-28.<https://v.douyin.com/iYcVmu9R/> |@P.KW CUI:/ 11/26

唯一的湖南隆回（司门前镇）籍开国少将白天，逝后十年，家乡人才知：我们隆回县也有一位开国少将！

他战功卓越，却婉拒毛主席、朱总司令说服领中将衔。彭德怀元帅追着他打，骂道：“我是你的入党介绍人，原是国军少将，跟共产党干了近三十年，授中将怎不行？连主席的话都敢不听！”到56年才勉强领少将衔。但白将军对家人一直秘而不宣。73年逝世前对家人说：“司门前人是我的乡亲，全国人民都是我的乡亲。”

Fig 291-11. In 1956, General Wei Wei was promoted to the rank of Major General, but he never told his family about the promotion. It wasn't until ten years after his death that his hometown of Longhui County discovered that there was a founding major general from their county.

Wei Wei, who repeatedly refused the rank of Lieutenant General, finally agreed to be appointed as a Major General, showing his indifference to fame and fortune and his noble character, which is rare in other countries around the world.

Originally named Wei Wei, he was appointed as the Chief of Staff and Deputy Commander of the 93rd Army of the Nationalist Army in 1939.

In 1940, he joined the Eighth Route Army and changed his name to Bai Tian.

In 1955, at the ceremony of conferring ranks in the new China, it was decided to appoint Bai Tian as Major General. However, Bai Tian refused directly without even thinking about it. He believed that after joining the Communist Party, he had mostly worked in administrative positions, and that his achievements did not "deserve" the rank of Major General.

In order to persuade Bai Tian to accept the rank of Major General, many leaders, including Chairman Mao, personally visited him. However, Bai Tian simply said, "In any case, I will not accept the rank of Major General!"

Marshal Peng Dehuai had a good personal relationship with him and scolded him loudly, "You were already a Major in the Nationalist Army, and now they want to give you the rank of Major General, isn't that excessive? Why are you so stubborn?!"

However, Bai Tian still refused. This made Marshal Peng angry, and he immediately picked up his riding crop and waved it towards Bai Tian, saying, "You dare not listen to me and Chairman Mao? Are you trying to make me angry?!"

Seeing Marshal Peng become angry, Bai Tian quickly hid behind a table, and the two of them ended up circling the table. After a while, they both stood panting, staring at each other, neither willing to concede.

After a while, Bai Tian sighed and knew that if he didn't agree to Marshal Peng's request, he wouldn't let him off. So he reluctantly said, "I will accept the appointment, but I will only accept the rank of Major General."

2024-03-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iYef4gTR/Hli:/w@s.Rk> 04/26

抗日女英雄
被用11颗钢钉 钉在
这棵树上折磨致死
后来竟奇异的长出了
人形

Fig 291-12. In 1919, **Xu Rumei** was born into an intellectual family in Wenchang County, Hainan. Her father was a well-known lawyer in the area, and the family was well-off. Xu Rumei was the only daughter in the family and received a good education from an early age. **Her father named her "Rumei," hoping that she would be as proud and**

resilient as the plum blossom.

After the evil Japanese invasion of China, Xu Rumei joined the resistance against Japan. Following the Japanese invasion of Hainan Island, they began to sweep through and commit mass killings. Wherever the Japanese army went, buildings were burned down and the property of the people was looted. Countless civilians fell under the swords and guns of the Japanese army. During a mission, 24-year-old Xu Rumei was betrayed by a traitor who informed the Japanese army, leading to her and several comrades being surrounded by the enemy. While trying to break out of the encirclement, her comrades sacrificed themselves one by one, and Xu Rumei was also seriously injured. Because of her injuries, she left a trail of blood, which allowed the Japanese army to track her down, and she tragically fell into their hands.

The evil Japanese soldiers took Xu Rumei back to a nearby village and subjected her to intense interrogation, trying to force her to reveal the whereabouts of the guerrilla group and the injured. Xu Rumei refused to confess, but was tortured by the enemy. Later, the Japanese army tied Xu Rumei to a tree and tortured her to force her to disclose hiding place of the guerrilla group and the organization's deployment. When **Xu Rumei still refused to confess, the inhumane Japanese soldiers resorted to a cruel method - they brought 11 long iron nails and pierced Xu Rumei's body, nailing her to the tree, causing blood to flow profusely.**

Xu Rumei could no longer speak, but in order to vent their anger, the Japanese soldiers released dogs to attack her body, creating a scene so bloody that it made the villagers present covered their faces and wept.

After Xu Rumei's sacrifice, a miraculous human-shaped tree emerged at the site later.

[She is a female hero in the war against Japanese aggression. She was tortured to death by being nailed to a tree with 11 steel nails. Later, the tree miraculously grew in the shape of a human, and people called it the Hero Tree, paying tribute to the hero. #SaluteToTheHero.2021-09-23. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdjTtWP/02/20TL:/Z@Z.md>];
[How tragic was her sacrifice? She was nailed to a tree by the Japanese army with 11 long nails and was also torn apart by a wolf dog. 2024-01-07. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1787406044218231916&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

网友提问：

为什么解放军那么受欢迎爱戴？

关于朝鲜战争，美国记录了各参战国对平民的暴行，但最后一句是：只有中国没有伤害无辜平民。美军有被俘后反审讯的训练，讲课时第一句就是：“不要认为你会幸运的被中国军队捕获”

一位美军战俘躲在山洞里，惊讶的看见了志愿军战士比比划划的用手语向朝鲜老百姓买白菜，在美军的印象里，这玩意儿还用买？拿过来吃就是了，于是美军十分顺滑的向志愿军投降了。（美军士兵詹姆斯·乔治·温纳瑞斯自己回忆的）他们是真的想投降，只是不敢投朝鲜人民军。人民军都不虐待战俘的，直接当场毙了。

抗战结束后，阎锡山留了一部分投降的日军当自己的王牌，解放战争里这支日本雇佣军被解放军包围，走投无路，派人试探性地问解放军这边：“我们这边还有妇孺，能不能保证所有人的生命安全？”我军回答：你什么时候听说过八路军虐待俘虏？日军一想确实是这个道理，马上投降了。

Fig 291-13. One netizen asked: **Why does the PLA receive so much love and respect?**

Regarding the Korean War, the US documented atrocities committed by various warring countries against civilians, but the last sentence was: Only China did not harm innocent civilians. The U.S. military has training for resisting interrogation after being captured, and the first thing taught in the class is: "Don't think you will be lucky to be captured by the Chinese army."

A U.S. soldier who was a prisoner of war hid in a cave and was surprised to see a volunteer soldier of the Chinese army using sign language to buy cabbage from North Korean villagers. In the impression of the US military, would this cabbage still need to be bought? The U.S. military usually just takes it and eats it, so the U.S. soldiers very smoothly surrendered to the volunteer army. (Recollection of US soldier James George Wrennery)

They really wanted to surrender, but they dared not surrender to the Korean People's Army. The People's Army does not mistreat prisoners of war, they just kill them on the spot.

After the war, Yan Xishan left a portion of surrendering Japanese soldiers as his ace

card. During the War of Liberation, this Japanese mercenary force was surrounded by the People's Liberation Army, with nowhere to go. They sent someone to tentatively ask the PLA: "We still have women and children on our side, can you guarantee everyone's safety?" Our army replied: When have you heard of the Eighth Route Army mistreating prisoners of war? The Japanese soldiers realized this was true, and immediately surrendered.

2024-03-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iYe5yXNB/XMj:/g@o.Qk> 04/26

Fig 291-14. Anti-Japanese hero Zhao Yiman

Evil Japanese invaders tortured Zhao Yiman for nine months before her execution, breaking her ribs and causing at least 24 fractures throughout her body, with some bones even piercing her skin.

But Zhao Yiman remained silent throughout, refusing to give the Japanese any information about the Northeast Anti-Japanese Alliance forces. Her resilience left the Japanese invaders stunned.

At the time, even the Japanese army doctor said that her body's ability to endure pain

had exceeded the limits of human physiology, something that medical science could not explain.

[Anti-Japanese female hero Zhao Yiman. Do not forget the past painful history. Today's peaceful and prosperous era is exchanged by countless ancestors with blood and life. We should strive to be strong and pay tribute to the heroes. #Do not forget national humiliation #Zhao Yiman #remembering history.2024-02-17. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdr4yPu/N@j.Pk dan:/ 08/29>]

Fig 291-15. The most beautiful female teacher in the Wenchuan earthquake
Yuan Wenting (September 6, 1982 - May 12, 2008), from Shifang City, Sichuan Province, was at the Democratic Center Elementary School in Shifang Shigu Town when the Wenchuan earthquake occurred. The school building was severely damaged and collapsed instantly. In order to minimize casualties among the children, she repeatedly

rushed into the classrooms and carried out one child after another with her delicate hands. After her last attempt, the teaching building collapsed, and her youth was forever frozen at the age of 26. She saved a total of 13 children's lives.

2024-03-06. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdUPNdd/N@W.zt 08/29 QxS:/>

山西“铁娘子”王光

1943年，日军对我岳南根据地进行残酷的“钳形合围”“铁滚扫荡”，扬言要变根据地为“无人区”。王光担任一区反“扫荡”总指挥。10月一天，她率上寨民兵掩护群众转移，不幸被敌人抓获，受尽酷刑，仍坚贞不屈，最后被灭绝人性的日军开膛破肚挖去心脏，壮烈牺牲，年仅23岁。

Fig 291-16. Wang Guang, the "Iron Lady" of Shanxi, in 1943, the Japanese army carried out a brutal "pincer encirclement" and "iron sweep" against the Yuennan base of our guerrilla region, threatening to turn the base into a "no man's land." Wang Guang served as the overall commander of the first area to resist the "sweep." One day in October, she led the militia to protect the people and transfer them, but unfortunately she was captured by the enemy, subjected to cruel torture, and still remained unwavering.

In the end, she was brutally killed by the inhumane Japanese army, who carved out her heart. She sacrificed herself at the young age of 23.

[Wang Guang, an anti-Japanese heroine, was born in 1920 in Shanxi# Salute to Heroes # Remember History # Never Forget National Shame # Character Stories # Love China 2023-12-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdUTqSB/> BGI:/s@e.BT02/21]

Fig 291-17. The blind soldier from Shangganling carried his broken leg comrade on his back and launched the final charge towards the US military # Salute to the hero . 2023-10-19.<https://v.douyin.com/i2Bj7oW/> 11/11 trE:/J@i.cn

中国军人的高素质

Fig 291-17-1. The video clearly shows **the poor moral quality of Western soldiers** and the excellent qualities of Chinese soldiers, arousing the love of the Chinese people for high-quality Chinese soldiers. 2024-03-12. <https://v.douyin.com/i2SL8GCf/> 11/10 O@X.ZZ qEh:/

Fig 291-17-2. Video of disaster relief. In April 2024, PLA soldiers rushed to aid the flood-hit areas in northern Guangdong. These are the sons and daughters of the Chinese people in uniform. Where there is disaster, there they are. Salute to the frontline rescuers. May everyone return safely. Disasters are ruthless, but there is love on earth. When one place is in trouble, support comes from all sides. 2024-04-24. <https://v.douyin.com/i2S2byBH/Qkp:/K@w.fB.10/05>

Fig 291-17-3. 2024 Flood Control and Disaster Relief in Northern Guangdong# The most beautiful Chinese soldiers# 2024-04-30. <https://v.douyin.com/i2SjJHfu/> 04/17 vfO:/ Q@x.sR

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